

Investigating the Impact of Agile Transformation on Sustainability: The Case of Indian IT Startups

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ABSTRACT

The synergy between 'agile' and 'sustainability' has become crucial for Indian Information Technology (IT) Multinational Corporations (MNCs) and startups, given India's status as the third-largest global startup ecosystem. Despite this, a concerning 67% of Indian IT startups face failure within five years, prompting a strategic shift toward sustainable practices. The research problem revolves around the inherent business unsustainability, accentuated by ineffective risk management, unproductive performance management and inefficient strategic management. While project success is linked to the chosen transformation method, this connection is often overlooked and under scoped within the context of holistic startup sustainability.

Investigating the impact of agile transformation on the sustainability of Indian IT startups, this research aims to identify contributing factors, review existing literature, analyze managers' perspectives on agile transformation, and assess the current landscape of agile sustainability frameworks. Motivated by fragmented literature and a lack of practical investigations, this research seeks to establish a correlation between agile methodologies and sustainability in the context of Indian startups, contributing valuable insights to bridge existing gaps.

Employing a multiple method approach, grounded in interpretivism philosophy and an inductive approach, this study conducted qualitative semi-structured interviews and focus groups with 34 IT startup founders, co-founders, managers, agile coaches, practitioners, and project managers. The purposeful sampling technique was employed, and the data was thematically analyzed to derive meaningful results while maintaining credibility, ethical standards, and validity.

The research unveils that 70% of startup failures stem from non-financial process-oriented factors highlighting the often-misunderstood nature of agile philosophy. Insights on positive influence of successful agile transformation on the overall startup sustainability, seek to guide founders, entrepreneurs, and managers, emphasizing the need to transform culture, mindset, and stakeholder participation. The agile startup sustainability framework as a research contribution, unravels the intricate relationship between agile methodologies and startup sustainability, paving the way for practical applications and further exploration in diverse industries and global regions. Future recommendations include broader demographic inclusion in studies, offering guidance for Indian IT startups, and contributing to their success and India's economic growth.

DECLARATION

I declare that this research titled “Investigating the Impact of Agile Transformation on Sustainability: The Case of Indian IT Startups” is my unique and original work and follows all the necessary regulations of the University of the West of Scotland. This research has not been submitted for any other purpose or any other academic establishment in any part of the world except to achieve this Doctorate in Business Administration.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BML	-	Build Measure Learn
CAGR	-	Compound Annual Growth Rate
DPIIT	-	Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade
FDI	-	Foreign Direct Investment
GDP	-	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	-	Green Data Protection Regulation
GEM	-	Global Entrepreneurship Monitor
IBEF	-	India Brand Equity Foundation
IT	-	Information Technology
ITeS	-	Information Technology Enabled Services
KPMG	-	Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler
MEITY	-	Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology
MGI	-	McKinsey Global Institute
MNC	-	Multi-National Corporation
MVP	-	Minimum Viable Product
NASSCOM	-	National Association of Software and Services Companies
PWC	-	Price Waterhouse Coopers
ROI	-	Return On Investment
SDLC	-	Software Development Life Cycle
SME	-	Small and Medium Enterprises
TAM	-	Technology Acceptance Model

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION

Sustainability, a crucial global concern, extends beyond environmental considerations to encompass social and economic aspects. In the business context, sustainable practices promote long-term viability by addressing more than just environmental impact, social responsibility, and ethical governance, with respect to the specific industry (Axel and Lars, 2016; Denning, 2019). Indian IT startups have played a pivotal role in driving innovation and economic growth. With a surge in entrepreneurship, these startups often embrace innovative methodologies to enhance flexibility and responsiveness. Indian IT startups face sustainability challenges in the recent years due to intense competition, limited access to funding, evolving regulatory environments, market saturation, high operational costs, the need for continuous innovation, etc., which pose hurdles. Many startups grapple with achieving profitability, leading to struggles in sustaining their presence in the dynamic business landscape, which accounts for 67% failure rate (Dutta *et al*, 2020). Agile transformation, a paradigm shift in project management and product development, on the other hand, emphasizes adaptability, collaboration, and customer feedback which emerged in response to the limitations of traditional, linear methodologies, promoting iterative development and continuous improvement (Collier, 2012; Dikert *et al*, 2016).

The impact of agile transformation on sustainability of Indian IT startups is investigated in this research, to comprehend how agile tackles the difficulties encountered by these startups by exploring the viewpoints of IT project managers, entrepreneurs, co-founders, and startup founders. In the Indian context, this research helps agile coaches, agile consultants, and industry practitioners while also adding to the body of scholarly knowledge. This research bolsters the competitive edge, organizational agility, and sustainability of Indian IT startups by highlighting intangible themes and agile concepts, broadening agile's influence beyond just a project management tool.

The importance of agile transformation for startups has increased since the pandemic, which supports this research's applicability to both industry and academia. Unlike previous research, it attempts to create a conceptual framework that addresses sustainability issues and presents opportunities. This approach investigates performance, strategy, and risk-related issues, providing a foundation for future research in the dynamic landscape of Indian IT startups.

1.2 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Even the most globally successful businesses have once been startups with humble beginnings. Global Entrepreneurship Monitor claims that almost 100 million startups and entrepreneurs emerge with innovative business models and ideas with a broader vision of solving an existing business problem or bringing a new product to contribute to a country's Gross Domestic Profit (GDP) (GEM, 2018). In the 21st century, IT services have become the integrator and facilitator for most business startups regardless of the industry to perform, manage and solve critical business problems (John, 2017). In accordance with Singh *et al* (2019) and India Brand Equity Foundation IBEF (2019), almost worth the USD 4 trillion globally in the year 2017, the IT industry has contributed immensely to India's economy and GDP.

NASSCOM (2019) accounts for an average share of 7.7% ranging from 1.2% in 1998 to a peak of 9.3% in 2014 wherein nearly 19,000 startups have enumerated within the year 2018. It is clear that with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 10.45%, India's IT industry can contribute 156.5 US billion in 2021 as shown in Figure 1.1 (IBEF, 2019).

Figure 1. 1 Forecast: Indian IT Industry net worth

Source: Adopted from IBEF (2019)

McKinsey Global Institute forecast a strong increase from 7% to 10% contribution from the IT industry towards India's GDP by the year 2025 given the digital transformation efforts taken by the Indian government towards promising 835 million subscribers and multiple business SMEs and startups to be connected through digitization (Noshir *et al*, 2019; Dutta *et al*, 2020).

In agreement with Dutta *et al* (2020) and Mathur and Khurana (2013), with worldwide recognized capabilities, ability to provide cost-cutting services, and extensive spending on skill development and technological advancements, India has emerged to be “The topmost offshoring destination for IT companies across the world” in recent years contributing to exports 62% the US and UK 17%. Yet as inspiring as this resounds for entrepreneurs and founders to establish more IT startups, there is an utmost urgency to leverage the efficiency of business management and adaptability towards risk and change, shifting focus to adopting the best transformation method for Indian IT startups ensuring ‘Sustainability’, a vaguely and ill-treated business concept in India (Micic, 2017; Geyi *et al*, 2020). IT startups face extensive barriers to growth in terms of innovation, problem-solving and scalability and many researchers have linked this to the management method that they employ (Oliva and Kotabe, 2019).

Transformational methodologies such as the traditional Waterfall, Spiral, Parallel, V-shaped, etc., although have benefitted them, have been time consuming, change resistive and failed to deliver sustainability (Mahalaksmi and Sundararajan, 2013). Following linear and sequential methodologies have bypassed the presence of unprecedented risks and uncertainty and have failed to feedback unpredictable changes in IT start-ups ultimately leading to their collapse (Danijela *et al*, 2019). This has affected the Indian IT start-ups to be rigid and non-robust, allowing chaos and in worst cases collapse in less than 5 years of establishment (Stephen, 2016; Stephen, 2018).

According to Blome *et al* (2013) and Marshall *et al* (2015), the term ‘agile startup’ has been booming recently, although the concepts of agile, organization agility and sustainability are not new to the academic literature yet there exists a scarcity of studies relating agility and sustainability in particular to startups (Geyi *et al*, 2020). Although researchers like Ciccullo *et al* (2018) and Chen *et al* (2017) have addressed the relationship between agile and sustainability, they have failed to empirically investigate the impact that the agile transformation method has on business sustainability and practices (Geyi *et al*, 2020). IT businesses globally have always been challenged with being ‘agile’ to change and transform business strategies, risk management and performance, focusing on people rather than the process and collaborating customer experience with production (Serrador and Pinto, 2015; Yusuf *et al*, 2020) The viability of agile transformation in guaranteeing the long-term sustainability of IT start-ups in India is a subject of uncertainty, necessitating a comprehensive examination of the existing research gap.

1.3 INDUSTRY BACKGROUND

The Target industry for this research is the IT industry, further narrowed down to the startup sector, focusing only on Indian demography. The further sections review the definition, importance, size and growth rate, trends, and current scenario of IT start-ups in India. As per David *et al* (2021) startup is a new and impermanent company that has a business model based on novelty and expertise with a high prospective for rapid progression and scalability. As per Cho and McLean (2009), IT startups can be tech-based entities or companies that temporarily creates innovative products and IT services for customers in India or overseas, involving high volume of risk and uncertainty within the startup ecosystem leading to high transience rate (Preisendorfer *et al.*, 2012). Indian government defines a startup to be under 7 years of establishment with an annual turnover less than INR 100crore equivalent to USD 14million and headquartered or primarily operating within India (IBEF, 2019). These definitions clearly outline the target sample for this research.

As per Jose and David (2017), startups have four stages of life cycle: 1) Seed: preparation for a startup (Korreck, 2019); emergence (Pirolo and Presutti, 2010) and start-up (Mueller *et al.*, 2012), no business plan 100% defined, self-managed smaller teams (Mueller *et al.*, 2012; Bocken, 2015). 2) Early: young (Bocken, 2015), product/service active on market, establish client-base, product innovation (Ng *et al.*, 2014). 3) Growth: growing (Bocken, 2015; Santisteban and Mauricio, 2017); early growth (Pirolo and Presutii, 2010) and growth and development (Ng *et al.*, 2014), perfecting business model, being competitive, market share (Mueller *et al.*, 2012). 4) Expansion: mature (Santisteban and Mauricio, 2017; Bocken, 2015), external financing, alliances, and mergers, increase profitability, enhance business management (Ng *et al.*, 2014).

1.3.1 IMPORTANCE IN THE RESEARCH

IT startups in different countries have been highly influential in contributing towards the economic growth, talent and skill development, and increased job creation which proves its relevance in the constantly changing and dynamic markets such as India. (Olawale and Garwe, 2010; Sulayman *et al.*, 2014). According to Kelley and Nakosteen (2005) and Spiegel *et al.* (2016), startups, through their initial stages of development, prove significant for the contribution to the economic growth of the developing countries. India; accounts for 55% market share of the USD 185-190 billion international services outsourcing in the year 2017 and 2018. With proven digital capabilities in providing services to worldwide customers and investment in new skill-learning and technology,

Indian IT start-ups contribute to 79% export revenue of the IT industry. The US; accounts for 62% and the United Kingdom accounts for 17% of exports from India (Forbes, 2019; KPMG, 2019). The tech-driven industries that utilize IT services account for 40% of India's GDP and 30% of earnings (Sharma *et al*, 2012). From the year 2010 to 2017, the employability of graduates in the IT start-up sector rose to a CAGR of 7.15%, where almost 6 million graduates were added to talent acquisition and 2% of IT revenue was spent on their training skills and communication, making IT industry attractable, which clearly show the impact that this research has (IBEF, 2019).

1.3.2 MARKET SIZE AND GROWTH RATE

India's IT-Business Process Management sector accounts for USD177billion in 2019 whereby the annual growth rate records as 6.1 per cent projecting a USD 350 billion growth estimation by 2025 and USD 181billion estimation by the year 2020 for IT-Enabled services (CompTIA, 2020).

CompTIA (2020) records an increase of exports from the Indian IT startup industry estimating USD 137billion and USD 44billion from domestic hardware revenues in the year 2019, which has further accelerated the industry's employment to 4.1 million as of the fiscal year 2019. IT exports account for 79% of the industry's total revenue with 9% growth every year, estimated to be USD 137billion in 2019, further expected to grow after 2020. With USD167billion in 2017-2018, NASSCOM's future forecast predicts 13% growth rate worth USD 225billion for India's IT revenue contribution estimation by 2020 (NASSCOM, 2019). Indian IT industry spending expects to reach USD 90 billion with the digital segment revenue to account for 38 per cent of the USD 350 billion forecast for the year 2025. The prominent cities in India where a strong network of IT startups is concentrated, where Bengaluru records 27%, followed by Delhi at 25% (KPMG, 2019).

1.3.3 KEY TRENDS

The Information Technology (IT) industry, soaring to an impressive worth of USD 5.2 trillion in the 1st quarter of 2020, faces a global growth rate projection of less than 4%, as depicted in Figure 1.2. Notably, the software development sector commands a substantial 40% share of the entire IT and enabled services landscape. Delving into the pinnacle achievements and key trends within the Indian IT and ITeS sector, Table 1.1 meticulously categorizes these groundbreaking advancements some of which are Artificial Intelligence, Cloud computing, Big Data Analytics, Blockchain, etc.

Table 1. 1 Key trends in Indian IT startup sector

COMPONENT	TREND	
Total Export revenue	8.3% growth rate	USD \$136 billion in FY19
Acquisition & Mergers	Cognizant acquires Contino Infosys acquires ABN AMRO Bank L&T acquires Mindtree	
Employment	Online Platforms for Skill upliftment	2million tech professionals, employees & students benefited
Investment	Q4 of 2018	USD \$2,400 million
Revenue growth	July-September 2018	6.8% Year on Year
Government Initiatives	Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY) launch MeitY Startup Hub (MSH) portal National Policy on Software Products 2019 to develop India as a software product nation Information Technology identified as one of 12 champion service sectors, setting up Rs 5,000 crore (US\$ 745.82 million)	
Technology	Artificial Intelligence	Union Budget 2018-19: leveraging AI technology; National AI* portal; Software product nation
	Cloud Computing; Mobile Computing and Applications Big Data Analytics; Automation; Virtual Reality Augmented Reality; Blockchain Data	

Source: Adaptation of IBEF (2019)

Figure 1. 2 CompTIA Global IT Industry growth forecast

Source: Adaptation of CompTIA (2020)

1.3.4 SITUATION ANALYSIS

As shown in Table 1.2, the global presence of India’s IT software and hardware sector has attracted Foreign Direct Investment inflow of USD 39.4billion between 2000-2019 as released by the Department for Promotion of Industry Trade (Noshir *et al*, 2019). In accordance with KPMG (2019), expanding economy, increasing demand for exports, availability of skill pool, low-cost services and advances in technology can be considered as competences for this industry. Yet the huge competition, cultural division, undeveloped ecosystem, etc., can be threats for scaling.

Table 1. 2 SWOT Analysis of Indian IT startups

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESS
Worldwide delivery centers & vertical diversification IT and ITeS sector have low-cost advantage Skilled workforce & graduates	Lack of funding unless promising Undeveloped ecosystems for startups Large demographic & cultural division
OPPORTUNITIES	THREAT
Expanding economy Demands for exports from new verticals Contribution of Artificial Intelligence & Machine learning to 2035	Government policies and taxation Huge competition & survival of niche market Constantly changing market environment Uncertainty in consumer behavior & loyalty

Source: Adaptation of IBEF (2019)

Government initiatives such as ‘The Start-up India’, Phased Manufacturing Program (PMP) and software technology parks have aided positive culture and platforms for new startups in India. Demonetization Policy operational from 2016 has been a major hiccup for start-ups, restricting money transactions and investments for business ventures across the globe (IBEF, 2019). Despite the government’s instability, Indian IT SMEs’ investment portfolio projects growth a rate of 17.2%. Only 8 unicorns since 2012-18 reached venture capitalists, which alarmed the industry’s sustainability. Softbank, a Japanese funding giant has invested over INR 580billion in startups since 2014. A glaring absence of innovation, an overreliance on imitation of Western ideas, a dearth of uniqueness, and stifling constraints imposed by venture capitalists and angel investors collectively contribute to the staggering 67% failure rate reported by IBM within the first five years of establishment for Indian IT startups. As attested by the comprehensive research conducted by Noshir *et al* (2019), this alarming trend is further underscored by a drastic decline in startup numbers, plummeting from 6000 in 2017 to a mere 800 in 2018. These findings unequivocally highlight the severe and pervasive crisis plaguing the sustainability of startups in the Indian IT landscape.

1.3.5 COMPETITOR ANALYSIS

Table 1. 3 IT Industry: Competitor Analysis for Indian IT startups

| |
|---|---|---|---|--|
| Stock price:
TCS (NSE)
₹2,003.90 -6.95 (-0.35%) | Stock price: INFY
(NSE) ₹682.05 -3.20 (-0.47%) | Stock price:
HCLTECH (NSE)
₹1,046.05 +9.80 (+0.95%) | Stock price:
WIPRO (NSE)
₹336.25 +1.30 (+0.39%) | Stock price:
TECHM (NSE)
₹728.00 +4.45 (+0.62%) |
| Revenue:
19.08 billion USD (2018) | Revenue:
10.94 billion USD (2018) | Revenue:
9 billion USD (2018) | Revenue:
8.4 billion USD (2018) | Revenue:
4.77 billion USD (2018) |
| Headquarters:
Mumbai, India | Headquarters:
Bengaluru, India | Headquarters:
Noida, India | Headquarters:
Bengaluru, India | Headquarters:
Pune, India |
| Number of employees: 371,519 | Number of employees: 200,364 (2017) | Number of employees: 117,781(2018) | Number of employees: 164,659 (2018) | Number of employees: 113,550 |
| CEO:
Rajesh G
(Feb 2017–) | CEO:
Salil Parekh
(Jan 2018–) | CEO:
C Vijayakumar (Oct 2016–) | CEO:
Abidali N (Feb 2016–) | CEO:
C. P. Gurnani (24 May 2012–) |

Source: Adaptation of CompTIA (2020)

Table 1.3 meticulously outlines the key players dominating the Indian IT sector, showcasing their revenue, stock prices, and workforce numbers. It is imperative to recognize that each of these IT giants once grappled as startups to secure their position in the market. In recent times, these industry giants have undergone a transformative journey, embracing agile methodologies as a strategic imperative in response to the dynamic demands of the ever-evolving IT industry. This strategic shift towards agile practices has not only fortified their positions but has also enabled them to deliver top-notch solutions, ensuring sustained competitiveness in the global IT arena.

The agile paradigm shift has been influential in aligning these industry leaders with the critical needs of flexibility, collaboration, continuous improvement, accelerated time-to-market, heightened customer satisfaction, improved team dynamics, and heightened adaptability. By debunking the myth that agile methodologies are an unattainable pinnacle for startups, this research aims to pave the way for IT startups to not only survive but thrive in the fiercely competitive IT landscape.

1.4 RESEARCH PROBLEM: BUSINESS UNSUSTAINABILITY

Sustainability is a major issue for Indian IT startups due to a combination of internal and external factors. Firstly, intense competition within the Indian IT sector creates challenges for startups to differentiate themselves and gain a foothold in the market, affecting their ability to sustain operations (Mishra and Dash, 2017). Limited access to funding, a common hurdle for startups, hampers their scalability and innovation efforts (GEM, 2019). The dynamic regulatory environment in India introduces uncertainties, and startups must continuously adapt to changing policies, adding complexity to their sustainability efforts (PWC, 2020). Operational costs, including infrastructure, talent acquisition, and marketing, can strain resources, particularly for startups with limited capital. The rapid evolution of technology requires startups to stay current, demanding ongoing investments in skill development and technology adoption (NASSCOM, 2020). Furthermore, the scarcity of experienced leadership and industry-specific knowledge among startup founders can impact strategic decision-making and hinder long-term sustainability. Balancing growth aspirations with financial stability and navigating these multifaceted challenges is crucial for Indian IT startups aiming to establish and maintain sustainability in a competitive business landscape (Biloslavo *et al*, 2018). Business unsustainability, the primary problem being addressed in this research, has been argued to be an integral part of any business rather than a value addition and therefore requires in-depth exploration.

Researchers like Sushil (2017) and Dinesh and Sushil (2019) have recognized the failure to empower a flexible and innovative transformation method as the reason for decelerating growth and sustainability of Indian IT startups. However, according to Subbarao and Rani (2015) and Lonkar and Gupte (2017), there is a clear relationship between the management of performance, risk and strategy and the transformation method employed, that researchers have failed to attribute to startup sustainability. Identifying and mitigating risks, developing and executing a clear and effective strategy and setting measurable performance goals and improving them is integral to sustainable development. While the management of performance, risk, and strategy is linked to the chosen transformation method, this connection is often overlooked in the context of overall startup sustainability. The following subsections highlight the sustainability issues in the Indian IT startups in the context of risk, strategy and performance.

1.4.1 PROBLEM 1: INEFFECTIVE RISK MANAGEMENT

In the landscape of Indian IT startups, ineffective risk management practices represent a critical impediment to sustained success. The dearth of comprehensive risk awareness within startups, as well as resource constraints and the rapid scaling pressures inherent in the industry, contribute to a scenario where risk assessments are often reactive rather than proactive. Critics have globally raised concerns about the impact of Indian Government policies and tax regulations, including Goods and Services Tax (GST), Make in India, Demonetization, and the Phased Manufacturing Program (PMP), on the growth trajectory of businesses in India, especially impacting the initial phases and creating uncertainty for startups (Niazi *et al.*, 2016; Satar and John, 2016). The constantly shifting client requirements and the escalating demand for technological advancements, such as Big Data science, Artificial Intelligence, and automation, underscore the pressing need for change management in Indian IT startups (IBEF, 2019; Dutta *et al.*, 2020). The dependence on specific clients or projects without adequate diversification, coupled with inadequate contingency planning, further amplifies vulnerability. This multifaceted challenge calls for a proactive commitment to developing a comprehensive risk management framework, instilling a risk-aware culture, and allocating sufficient resources to navigate the dynamic and uncertain landscape of the IT startup sector in India.

Figure 1. 3 Forecast: volume of startup exits worldwide

Source: Adaptation of Statista (2019)

As shown in Figure 1.3, the global startup landscape has witnessed a significant increase in exit volumes, with forecasts suggesting a fourfold rise within four years, reaching around 5600 exits by 2021 (Statista, 2019). However, the stark reality is a substantial failure rate, with only 30% of Indian startups attracting venture capitalists and investors, and merely a 10% probability of achieving further success (Niazi *et al.*, 2016; Dutta *et al.*, 2020).

Despite India being recognized as one of the largest global hubs for startups since 2012, a high exit rate of 67% within five years, leading to over 800 startups declining, highlights the challenges faced, resulting in only eight profitable unicorns achieving success (Satar and John, 2016; Govardhan and Jeyakumaran, 2018). The COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated these challenges, negatively impacting the economy and disrupting daily business activities for startups (Andreas *et al*, 2020; PWC, 2020).

1.4.2 PROBLEM 2: UNPRODUCTIVE PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT

Golicic and Smith (2013) and Paulraj *et al* (2017) have established a direct relationship between performance and sustainability. According to Paulraj *et al* (2017), the emergence of more digital startups in this era has disrupted the delivery models and mindset of major IT companies putting them under pressure based on 3 dimensions of performance namely cost, quality and time. According to authoritative research by Towey *et al* (2019) and the insightful findings of Govardhan and Jeyakumaran (2018), a staggering 64% of the financial budget within the realm of software development is allocated towards the creation of features that ultimately prove to be irrelevant and alien to the final product envisioned by clients. This revelation aligns seamlessly with the conclusions drawn by Ahimbisibwe *et al* (2017), who assert that the predominant hurdle to sustainability lies in the traditional methodologies still adhered to by Indian IT startups. These outdated practices, incapable of adapting to the swiftly changing dynamics, not only hinder the timely delivery of projects but also compromise client satisfaction and service quality, posing a critical challenge to the viability of these startups in the competitive landscape.

Szekely and Strebel (2013), used the term sustainable innovation to empower changes and improvement in the process, operation, business model and thought process which in turn lead to the richer performance of a business. Lopez-Valeiras *et al* (2015) and Adams *et al* (2016), furthered this ideology to bring more than just economic profits and returns, enriching cultural and organizational values. Klewitz and Hansen (2014) and Dyck and Silvestre (2018), suggested sustainable innovation for SMEs and entrepreneurs who aim to bring long term values to the business. As this research focuses on the Indian IT startups and their performance not being able to par with global businesses, the concept of sustainability and its innovations concerning agile transformation, needs to be scrutinized for maximized performance levels (Adams *et al*, 2016).

However, conflicting reports from Esfahbodi *et al* (2017) and Malik *et al* (2021) acknowledge the negative influence of sustainability on business profit, signifying alternatives to maximize business performance and practices. Researchers Ciccullo *et al* (2018) and Chen *et al* (2017) have outlined the challenges businesses face towards the integration of sustainability and transformation methods. According to McKinsey reports, culture and performance account for 59% while measuring agility within transformational methods, to overcome challenges (McKinsey, 2019).

1.4.3 PROBLEM 3: INEFFICIENT STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT

As per Backlander (2019), the traditional transformation methods have been static in terms of strategic management and thereby stagnating the scaling of the IT companies. Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI), a framework developed by Carnegie Mellon University has become a standard for organizations including project management and systems engineering IT companies to improve processes, achieve maturity levels and enhance product/service quality systematically. Most IT MNCs and companies aim to achieve the highest maturity level which shows their position within the competition (Benmoussa *et al*, 2015). Reports from NASSCOM (2017) depict that, startups, confined to this maturity ideology, often fail to align their strategies with long-term goals, lacking effective planning of finances, human capital, knowledge, and other tangible and intangible resources (Sweetman and Conboy, 2018; Stephen, 2018). As per Silva *et al* (2019), startups from time to time have ignored the thought of continuous integration and sustainability. Indian startups have failed to have effective alignment and planning of finances, human capital, knowledge, and other tangible and intangibles leading to ineffective strategic management (Stephen, 2018).

As Daniel and Fabio (2018) and Antonella *et al* (2018) argue, startups also evolve over years and attract more competition from senior players in the same industry therefore without continuous integration and forward-thinking, they may end up being immature startups without any growth potential, which stand as an ideal attraction for angel investors and shareholders (Bianchi *et al*, 2016). Constellation Research's CEO argues that traditional methods manage and produce output too slow and unwelcome change at the later stage of development creating uncertainty over the result (Ahimbisibwe *et al*, 2017). The compelling assertion made by Zwikael *et al* (2014) regarding the connection between planning and project success finds vivid confirmation in the transformative journey of Tata Consultancy Services (TCS).

TCS, a global leader in the IT industry, strategically reaped dividends of \$19 billion by pivoting towards agile planning and practices. This monumental shift wasn't merely theoretical; it was a tangible commitment reflected in the internal training of a staggering 10,000 agile scrum masters. The visionary initiative outlined by Shanmugasundaram (2019) positions TCS on a trajectory to deliver differentiated and collaborative services, setting a bold target to fully realize these advancements by the year 2020. This exemplifies not only the power of strategic planning but also the tangible impact it can have on the success and future positioning of a global industry leader.

As per Shrivastava *et al* (2017) Infosys has over the years identified 'fast delivery' as of much significance wherein the company follows the pattern of "failing easy to succeed fast". In concordance to all these problems is the lack of organizational agility as identified by 500 C-level executives and mid-line managers that degrade the performance of even top companies which by no means can be alien to startups (Chen *et al*, 2017; Geyi *et al*, 2020).

1.4.4 LACK OF UNDERSTANDING OF AGILE TRANSFORMATION AND ITS INFLUENCE ON IT STARTUP SUSTAINABILITY

The previous sections highlighted the key problems in the light of sustainability within the context of Indian IT startups. For years, IT industry has practiced various Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) methods to instigate processes that involve developing a new software, building a new website, add features onto existing platforms, etc., and have tried to improve efficiency and productivity (Collier, 2011; Measey, 2015). Nevertheless, the change in demands, constantly evolving customer requirements, challenges within the demography and globalization, etc., and to add, the sustainability issues as highlighted in the previous sections, has created a pressure in choosing the right methodology for the IT projects (Lonkar and Gupte, 2017; Dean and Marc, 2020). MNCs and global IT companies with larger infrastructure and sufficient funds have updated their transformation methodologies time after time (Sabrina, 2019). Although the scope of these transformation methods has only remained within the light of project management, the impact of choosing the right methodology can mean an entirely different spectrum of opportunities for startups, where project success rapidly increases their growth. This research aims to explore the scope of agile methods for the overall sustainability of Indian IT startups taking a turn from the conventional project management perspective to a broader big picture of steering business operations towards sustainability.

Figure 1. 4 Agile methodology and business sustainability

Most researchers have studied the traditional and agile methodologies, compared and contrasted them but only a few have analyzed them in the light of sustainability (Diego *et al*, 2020; Geyi *et al*, 2020). Figure 1.4 brings out some key issues such as changing priorities, visibility with clients, early innovations, etc., that can affect strategic management, change in government policies, large volume of exits, etc., that can affect risk management; decline in productivity, demand of fast delivery and cost effectiveness, etc., that can affect performance management (Pedro and Jeffrey, 2015; Dikert *et al*, 2016). Can agile transformation yield to these issues in these key areas is the primary problem statement. It is necessary to study the impact of agile transformation on the three highlighted sustainability management disciplines and this research aims to address this.

Moreover, these traditional and agile methods which have been largely applied in MNCs and global IT companies, can be a threat due to its complexity, cause ambiguity, pose adoptability challenges, misuse of concepts without understanding the real benefits, etc., which greatly and urgently requires an agile startup sustainability framework to be developed for Indian IT startups, which breaks down the complexity of these methods for achieving holistic sustainability (Fabio and Masaakik, 2019; Noshir *et al*, 2019; Ghezzi and Cavallo, 2020). The development and adoption of this sustainable agile framework is crucial for Indian IT startups to thereby address the multifaceted challenges, ensuring a holistic approach to innovation, organizational values, and long-term success.

1.5 RESEARCH JUSTIFICATION

As per Colombo and Grilli (2005), Cowling *et al* (2006) and McAdam and McAdam (2008) the soaring failure rate of IT startups all over the world have always alarmed the startup ecosystem. Ejermo & Xiao (2014) claims that within a span of 10 years from 1990 to 2000, Sweden noticed that 21% startups failed within 5 years of establishment. Hyder and Lussier (2016) also claims that 80% and more of IT startups worldwide have failed to survive and perform over a year forecasting the same for future. Many researchers like Santisteban and Mauricio (2017), Niazi *et al* (2016) and Oliva and Kotabe (2019) through decades have critically reviewed literatures on factors that influence startup success and survival means. However, Sulayman *et al* (2014) and Lonkar and Gupte (2017) criticize that there has always been a lack and want to identify such factors as they are evolving over time. With respect to IT startups worldwide and particularly India in this research, it is necessary to identify critical factors that affect sustainability of startups to mitigate risks Dutta *et al* (2020). Balboni *et al* (2014), Almakenzi *et al* (2015) and Banda and Lussier (2015) further prolong the research of Van de ven and his colleagues in the year 1984 to identify such critical factors influencing startup sustainability and success.

As per Bocken (2015) and Lonkar and Gupte (2017), early researchers have neglected to categorize and distinguish these factors according to their type, for example, internal and external. Despite researchers like Jose and David (2017) and Pugliese *et al* (2022) attempting to target respective factors that affect each stage of startup development, there exists a necessity to obtain a detailed understanding of importance of factor categorization with respect to sustainability. As several researchers like Geyi *et al* (2020), Noshir *et al* (2019), Dinesh and Sushil (2019), amidst the success of Indian IT startups, the ever-present uncertainty cannot be overlooked and therefore a forethought strategy and vision towards sustainability needs to be implanted at the very beginning stages of startup development (Denning, 2019). Therefore, there exists a literature gap in the systematic determination, categorization and management of such factors that influence sustainability of IT startups and those that are specific to Indian demography. Chapter 2, Section 2.2.3 identifies and categorizes such sustainability factors.

The scope of existing SDLC methods has only been confined to project and process management. MNCs and global IT companies adhere to these SDLC methods as part of their process but don't view them beyond the scope of project management. Choosing the right SDLC method can not

only ensure effective project management but can prove critical for a startup that is struggling to succeed in getting new project and achieve customer satisfaction, which in the hindsight can improve startup sustainability. International Project Management Association (IPMA) presentation on 2008 World Congress stressed the significance of sustainability as an integral part of project management method, wherein, during those period sustainability principles were still considered to be in its early days (Cobb, 2011). Labuschagne and Brent (2007), Labuschagne and Brent (2008) and Pade *et al* (2008) were a few of the earliest researchers that related project management to environmental, social and economic aspects of sustainability. Gareis *et al* (2009) criticizes that less importance has been given to IT startup sustainability, particularly software development startups, where the projects are small scaled and short-lived. Eid (2009) claims that failure to address sustainability as an issue has lowered the standards of the projects and has cost the business model of the startup.

Since 2013, several researchers like Silvius and Tharp (2013), Yvonne (2014) and Maria *et al* (2018) have accounted for an increase in momentum towards this ideology of relationship between projects and its sustainability. Jose and David (2017) and Yazici (2020) consider this growing significance has encouraged project managers and startup entrepreneurs to focus on challenges of sustainability with respect to the project undertaken. As researchers like Briassoulis (2001) and Van (2003) exclaim, there is no concrete definition of sustainability, and the term has been vaguely used in different contexts. Therefore, there exists a need for sustainability to be defined with respect to IT startups that can give a clear sense to project management (Silvius and Tharp, 2013). As per Sahil *et al* (2017) project management in IT startups have always overlooked the choice of an ideal software development method as a potential to transform the organization. Chapter 2, Section 2.2.1 and Section 2.3 conceptualizes sustainability for the context of Indian IT startups and links the SDLC methods to the holistic transformation and sustainability.

Many researchers like Lonkar and Gupte (2017), Ahimbisibwe *et al* (2017) and Denning (2019) criticize existing software development methodologies such as waterfall, spiral, parallel, iterative and V-shaped for their failure to provide clarity of the initial requirements, cost and development time estimation, adaptation of changes in requirements, delivery time, customer experience and satisfaction. As per Sahil *et al* (2017), Berglund *et al* (2018) and Gerster *et al* (2020), sustainability prevails as the major issue for Indian startups demanding the best transformation method and an

appropriate practice framework designed exclusively for Indian startups. Therefore, there's a need for such traditional and agile software development methods to be analyzed in the light of sustainability and potential transformation. Chapter 2, Section 2.4 and 2.5, scrutinizes existing literature on transformation methods for sustainability.

Figure 1. 5 Research justification: 5S Framework

The Science-Sensibility-Situation framework of this research, as shown in Figure 1.5, captures the entire research in terms of the issue, focus and methods. This figure highlights the situational issues that exists in the Indian IT startup landscape as shown in Section 1.3.4, wherein the startup failure rate has increased to an alarming 67% in the last four years leading to the question of what could be the potential reasons, and the ever-growing necessity of sustainability as integral part of businesses. The decline in economic contribution of IT startups towards India's growth, gaps in the literatures of agile and sustainability and lack of a sophisticated agile startup sustainability framework that effectively captures agile elements for the sustainability of Indian IT startups in its simplicity forms the science of this research. Moreover, this research primarily focuses on filling the knowledge gap in agile sustainability theories within the context of Indian startups, developing superior knowledge in sustainability and competitive advantage in Indian IT startups, and finally developing a framework that addresses the current state of larger volume of exits and sustainability, by further investigating the work of Santiago and Emre (2017) and Geyi *et al* (2020). The sensibility of this research as shown in the figure, highlights the scientific methods and research designs that best captures the analytical sensibility and creates an impact in the field of

sustainability by providing practical implications for startup stakeholders, and improve the application of agile transformation in the scope of holistic sustainability of Indian IT startups. This research aims to utilize systematic literature review method to overcome the failures of existing literature where there is a lack of balance between academic and practical application. Researchers across various management disciplines have extensively analyzed sustainability factors, yet limited research has delved into the transformation methods within India's IT startup sector.

Although leading IT companies have shifted towards agile way of transforming businesses, crucial barriers namely the lack of funds, human resources, project and client database etc., has obligated Indian startups to disregard or not completely move towards agile, creating a hurdle for sustainability, a literature gap yet to be filled (Noshir *et al*, 2019; Dutta *et al*, 2020). As per John (2017), multiple records of autonomous literatures and reports on agile transformation method have flooded the research public but its understanding and comparison in theory and practice in the context of Indian IT sector is yet to be tapped in and investigated. There seems to be an ambiguity with agile as preached as a theory and agile as practiced by startups. This research further investigates agile transformation and how effective it can be in practice as opposed to the theory. Chapter 2, Section 2.5.6 and Chapter 4, Section 4.3.4 further analyzes this literature gap.

Moreover, frameworks developed by Micic (2017), Oliva and Kotabe (2019), Geyi *et al* (2020) and Dutta *et al* (2020), and few others have attempted to widen the scope of agile, mostly to a specific company, but still there exists a primary literature gap for a lightweight and simple agile sustainability framework that links startup management disciplines and promotes overall sustainability of Indian IT startups to be developed. The lack of a well-established hypothesis or framework, poor alignment of problems, neglecting cultural impacts, etc., targeted for Indian IT startups, prove that there is a gap in literature linking agile and sustainability of Indian IT startups. The ultimate contribution of this research is to address this literature gap by developing an agile startup sustainability framework that identifies the immediate sustainability factors, encapsulates the benefits of agile philosophy and practices, links agile elements with the key pillars or management disciplines of IT startups and finally promotes holistic sustainability, competitive advantage and organizational agility. Chapter 2, Section 2.7.6 and Chapter 5, Section 5.5, Figure 5.8 show the development of a new framework by addressing the identified literature gaps.

1.6 RESEARCH MOTIVATION

Over the past few decades, the Indian IT startups have witnessed an unprecedented surge in the interest and urgency surrounding sustainability and practices. While there have been remarkable strides in the development and adoption of sustainability, significant challenges persist in the relevant conceptualization and customizable adoption of these sustainability practices in the context of Indian IT startups, a significant gap which exists in the understanding of agile transformation for the sustainability of Indian IT startups.

Despite advancements in the IT industry, sustainability challenges like cultural misalignment, reliance on traditional methodologies ill-suited for dynamic environments, and inadequate readiness for effective agile transformation, hinder the seamless integration of agile transformation into existing IT startup landscape. Addressing such often overlooked demographic and non-financial factors is paramount for fostering transition towards a more sustainable Indian IT startup space. The motivation behind this research lies in the recognition of the critical role that agile transformation plays in overcoming such challenges by evaluating its benefits and developing a holistic framework to potentially use it.

Motivated by a sincere passion for business strategy consulting and a deep aspiration to contribute to the IT domain, the researcher is driven to address startup challenges through agile methodologies. Having witnessed the transformative impact of agile on IT sustainability in MNCs, the researcher questions why Indian startups struggle to thrive, and displays extensive interest and passion for the research topic. With a strong IT background and a commitment to scrutinize factors influencing sustainability, the researcher aims to scale agile concepts for Indian startups, ensuring sustainable profitability. This motivation is fueled by a compelling desire to contribute to India's growing economy, analytical curiosity, a dedication to acquiring relevant knowledge, and a calm commitment to completing research within self-set deadlines.

This research seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by investigating innovative strategies to overcome barriers to sustainable agile adoption, promoting a more customer collaborative and flexible transformation methodology paradigm for the benefit of current and future Indian IT startups. The overarching goal is to inform startup founders, co-founders, project managers, agile coaches, agile practitioners, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the public, ultimately accelerating the transition to a more agile driven sustainable business environment.

1.7 RESEARCH AIM

The aim of this research is to investigate agile transformation, sustainability of IT Startups, and develop an agile transformation sustainability framework for Indian IT start-ups, supported with implementational guidance to help startups achieve sustainability.

1.8 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

As this research aims to investigate the impact of agile transformation on the sustainability of Indian IT startups, it is necessary to address the research problems stated in Chapter 1, Section 1.4 and thereby derive objectives that adhere to them. The following research objectives collectively contribute to the research topic:

RO1: Identify factors that foster sustainability in Indian IT start-ups

Sustainability was illuminated as the primary concern of this research in Section 1.4 and also the ambiguity and lack of clarity around the conceptualization of sustainability for Indian IT startups in specific was established in Section 1.5. To address this, it is necessary to conceptualize sustainability, identify specific sustainability factors and categorize them under risk, strategy and performance management to foster overall sustainability of Indian IT start-ups. Further to the descriptive analysis of Indian IT startup landscape in Section 1.3, Chapter 2, Section 2.2 and findings in Chapter 4, Section 4.3.1 will address this objective.

RO2: Evaluate literature on impacts of traditional transformation methodologies on Indian IT start-up sustainability

Adhering to the scarcity of researchers who have examined traditional transformation methodologies in the light of holistic sustainability, this research objective aims to evaluate literature on the impacts of traditional transformation methodology on the sustainability of Indian IT start-ups in the lens of risk, strategy and performance management. This requires prior understanding of transformation methods and how they link to the overall sustainability of Indian IT startups, which will be addressed in Chapter 2, Section 2.3 - Section 2.4, and through findings in Chapter 4, Section 4.3.2.

RO3: Analyze managers’ perception of agile transformation and its impact on Indian IT startup sustainability in theory and practice

In response to understudy of agile transformation in the light of holistic sustainability and implementation challenges, this research objective aims to analyze managers’ perception of agile transformation methodology in theory and practice and compare its impact on the sustainability of Indian IT startup with that of traditional methodologies in the lens of risk, strategy and performance management through literature in Chapter 2, Section 2.5 - Section 2.6 and findings in Chapter 4, Section 4.3.3 - Section 4.4.

RO4: Assess current agile frameworks for Indian IT startup sustainability and develop a new framework

Addressing the inefficiency of how agile is currently applied in the Indian IT startup landscape, raised in Section 1.4 and Section 1.5, this objective aims to assess current agile sustainability frameworks, identify framework gaps, establish the rationale for a new framework and develop a new framework to ensure successful adoption of agile transformation in Indian IT startups, that achieves sustainability in risk, strategy and performance management. Further to the literature review of current frameworks in Chapter 2, Section 2.7, the findings as discussed in Chapter 5, Sections 5.2 and 5.4, will address this objective.

1.9 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The Indian IT startup industry has been facing sustainability challenges in the recent years as identified in Section 1.4 and 1.5, and therefore there’s a need to analyze innovative strategies to overcome such barriers. Based on research rationale and significance, and the foremost correlation drawn between the transformation methodologies that startup employ and the holistic startup sustainability, it is critical for this research to analyze the impact of agile transformation on the sustainability of Indian IT startups. The following research questions adhere to the objectives given in Section 1.8. The research topic leading to the primary research question “How can agile transformation contribute to the sustainability of Indian IT start-ups?” has been further sub-divided into specific research questions as follows:

RQ1: What are the factors that influence sustainability in Indian IT start-ups?

RQ2: Are existing management frameworks effective enough to support the sustainability of Indian start-ups? If yes, how? If not, why?

RQ3: How Indian IT startups adapt to agile transformation in both theory and practice?

RQ4: How effective are current agile transformation frameworks in managing sustainability of Indian IT start-ups?

The research topic can be broken down into research problem, which is sustainability, target industry, which is Indian IT startup landscape, and the potential resolution or phenomenon to be studied in subject with the research problem, which is agile transformation. RQ1, aims to achieve RO1 by identifying specific sustainability factors that influence Indian IT startups. RQ2 and RQ3, aims to achieve RO2 and RO3 by analyzing traditional non-agile and agile transformation methodologies in the light of holistic startup sustainability by addressing practical implementation challenges in addition to the comparison between theory and practice. Finally, RQ4 achieves RO4 by closing the literature scarcity of an agile startup sustainability framework that effectively addresses the holistic sustainability of Indian IT startups.

1.10 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION

The major contributions of this research on resolving the aims, objectives and questions have been condensed in this section and in Chapter 6, Section 6.6. Table 1.4 correlates the objectives of this research with the associated contributions underpinned within each chapter and section of this research. This research, characterized by an in-depth exploration and critical analysis of literature and practices concerning agile transformation, makes a substantial contribution to both academic knowledge and practical guidance.

Chapter 1's descriptive analysis of Indian IT startup industry and Chapter 2's conceptualization, significance and identification of sustainability factors serves as a valuable resource for startup founders, entrepreneurs and CEOs offering insights into the external and internal challenges that should be addressed early in their startup journey. Notably, this research distinguishes itself within the specific context of Indian IT startups.

Table 1. 4 Relating research objectives and research contributions

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES	CONTRIBUTIONS	CHAPTER/SECTIONS
Identify factors that foster sustainability in Indian IT start-ups	Descriptive analysis of Indian IT startup industry, key trends and challenges, situational and competitive analysis	Chapter 1, Section 1.3
	Conceptualization, significance and categorization of sustainability factors in the light of risk, strategy and performance	Chapter 2, Section 2.2 Chapter 4, Section 4.3.1
Evaluate literature on impacts of traditional transformation methodologies on Indian IT start-up sustainability	Linking transformation methodology to startup sustainability	Chapter 2, Section 2.3 Chapter 4, Section 4.3.2
	Evaluating traditional transformation methodologies in the light of risk, strategy and performance management	Chapter 2, Section 2.4 Chapter 4, Section 4.3.2
Analyze managers' perception of agile transformation and its impact on Indian IT startup sustainability in theory and practice	Evaluation of Agile transformation methodology	Chapter 2, Section 2.5.1 - Section 2.5.5 Chapter 4, Section 4.3.3
	Implementational challenges: Theory vs practice	Chapter 2, Section 2.5.6 Chapter 4, Section 4.3.4
	Evaluation of literature gaps	Chapter 2, Section 2.6 Chapter 4, Section 4.4 Chapter 5, Section 5.2 - Section 5.4
Assess current agile frameworks for Indian IT startup sustainability and develop a new framework	Evaluation of current frameworks in the light of relevant theories	Chapter 2, Section 2.7.1 - Section 2.7.2
	Evaluation of framework gaps	Chapter 2, Section 2.7.3
	Development of the new framework	Chapter 2, Section 2.7.4 - Section 2.7.6 Chapter 5, Section 5.2 - Section 5.5
	Validation of the new framework	Chapter 5, Section 5.5
	Implementation guidance for the new framework	Chapter 5, Section 5.6

The examination of changes in processes over the decade, a unique aspect not explored in other research papers, is highlighted in Chapter 2, Section 2.6, which identifies literature gaps. The creation of a groundbreaking agile startup sustainability framework in Chapter 5, Section 5.5, stands out as a distinctive contribution tailored for Indian IT startups. This framework not only emphasizes the implementation of agile with the right mindset, culture, and stakeholder participation but also integrates risk, strategy, and performance agility to impact competitive edge and organizational agility for overall organizational sustainability.

Table 1.4 and 6.1 succinctly summarizes the research's contributions to literature and agile theories, showcasing select sections from each chapter. The inclusion of target interviewees with substantial knowledge and experience in the IT industry adds depth to the research. Findings from these interviews, validated through two focus groups, provide a diverse array of opinions on agile, presenting both pros and cons that enrich the research. The research goes further to analyze the behavioral and cultural perspectives collected from interviewees, enhancing its relevance and reliability for IT startups. The methodological approach, combining recent literature with practical evidence, represents a significant contribution to the success of this research.

A major practical contribution emerges in the form of the agile startup sustainability framework introduced in Chapter 5, Section 5.5, Figure 5.8. This framework, accompanied by guidelines and an action plan in Chapter 5, Section 5.6, Figure 5.9, addresses the sustainability crisis faced by Indian IT startups. Despite financial support efforts for startups in India, the rising number of exits necessitates new models for sustainability. This research becomes the first to explore the relationship between agile transformation and startup sustainability in the Indian context.

The research's primary beneficiaries include young startup entrepreneurs, founders with experience in larger MNCs, project managers, agile scrum masters, coaches, and practitioners. It offers practical guidance by identifying key factors affecting sustainability through a combination of literature and data analysis. Notably, the focus on process-oriented factors over financial ones underscores the need for startup founders to prioritize product/service/software quality.

This research challenges traditional non-agile and agile methodologies in Indian IT startups, highlighting key strategies, such as transparency with customers and resource allocation for MVPs, form a roadmap for sustainability. Emphasizing the concept of "agile done right," the research underscores the frequent misapplication of agile principles by startup managers. It advocates for customized agile practices to sustain competition and internal agility, offering consultants insights for guiding startups toward sustainable success.

This research will be a significant commitment to theoretical information through the top to bottom survey of different ideas and subjects of agile transformation and sustainability. This is accomplished through an intensive survey of the scholastic, the business-based writing, and the analyst's acknowledgment of the effect of outside and interior drivers on adoption and execution of agile technique in Indian startups.

Moreover, this research applies multiple methods to collect data and utilizes manual thematic data analysis as the most appropriate and feasible methodological approach for such exceptionally vast and diverse literature of agile transformation. In opposition to previous researchers using quantitative techniques, the selection of multiple qualitative methods can bring out in-depth understanding of agile transformation and sustainability for Indian IT startups in this research, yielding to methodological contribution.

1.11 RELEVANT RESEARCH REVIEWED IN THE LITERATURE

A wide range of research has been conducted under the concept of sustainability but nevertheless, only few researchers have identified the potential relationship between the sustainability of Indian IT startups with agile transformation and its benefits.

1. Bolis *et al* (2014), Mensah and Enu-Kwesi (2018), proposed the significance of a holistic and project perspective of sustainability or sustainability development, proposing collective interests to be valued while defining sustainability.
2. Dyllick and Muff (2016), identified the importance of sustainability for businesses and startups to impact profitability, growth strategies, skilled workforce, effective business practices, productivity and strategic alignment of goals and vision.
3. Industrial publications such as the IBEF (2019), KPMG (2019), NASSCOM (2019), Statista (2019), Forbes (2019), CB Insights (2019) and Failory (2020), collectively proposed various sustainability challenges that Indian IT startups are facing. The factors include ignored customers, product unwelcomed, lack of innovation, failed business models, lack of visibility with customers, strategic misalignment, unproductive culture, silo-traditional mindset, high competition, untimely deliverables, ineffective planning, etc. Shockingly, a theme where 63% of the reasons were process oriented was recorded aiming to understand the transformational methodologies that decide the process.
4. Immelt (2017), Stephen (2018), Tarhini *et al* (2018), Denning (2019) and Khalifeh *et al* (2020), have researched on the linkage of transformational methodologies and sustainability for IT enabled process but not explicitly leaving a literature gap for this research to tap in.
5. Traditional transformational methodologies such as the Waterfall, Spiral and Iterative methods were compared for their appraisals and criticism to support the support the

sustainability of businesses (Naumann *et al*, 2011; Munassar and Govardhan, 2011; Bassil, 2012; Balaji and Sundararajan, 2012; Vaishnavi *et al*, 2014; Adel and Abdullah, 2015).

6. Collier (2012), Measey (2015), Ghani and Bello (2015), Marshal *et al* (2015), Dikert *et al* (2016), Lappi *et al* (2018) have contributed immensely towards the literature of agile transformation and its benefits although leaving the literature gap of what specific elements impact the sustainability of Indian IT startups.
7. As significant part of this research focuses on implementation challenges of agile transformation for startups in India, there was a need to consider literature on agile transformation theory vs practice and there were lot of literature gaps highlighted in this section (Paternoster, 2014; Ghani *et al*, 2015; Kamei *et al*, 2017; Alsahli *et al*, 2017).
8. Pantiuchina *et al* (2020), Geyi *et al* (2020), Dean and Marc (2020), Diego *et al* (2020) and Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020) were few of the predominant researchers who tapped into the relevant research of agile transformation and sustainability. This research identified scarcity of literature in the fourth quadrant of literature evaluation to relate the terms agility and sustainability. Although few researchers have attempted to close this literature gap by focusing on either performance agility and sustainability, operational agility and sustainability but never collectively addressing them as a holistic approach.
9. The existing agile frameworks developed by El-Khalil and Mezher (2020), Geyi *et al* (2020), Dean and Marc (2020) and Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020) fail to address communication lags, a lack of rigidity in requirement gathering, unclear customer collaboration, low tolerance for changing demands, absence of an agile culture, and benefits favoring managers over teams. Furthermore, existing frameworks lack risk agility and fail to incorporate sustainability metrics. The proposed framework aims to address these gaps, emphasizing the need for sustainable evaluation in agile transformation, providing a distinctive contribution to the field.

As per the findings of several research including Gandomani *et al*, 2013; Santiago and Emre, 2017; Geyi *et al* (2020); Dean and Marc (2020), there remains limited literature corresponding to the relationship between agile transformation and sustainability, especially within the context of Indian IT startups. None of the research has been conducted in the Indian startup ecosystem and therefore proves the uniqueness and importance of this research to domain of agile sustainability.

1.12 SUMMARY OF RESEARCH METHOD

As per Baker and Thomas (2007), modern day management issues have become more complex, and it has increased the difficulty to identify the appropriate paradigm for the given research method. This section highlights key points from Chapter 3 which discusses philosophy, approach and methodologies adopted. Walliman (2005) stresses upon the importance of presenting tools and techniques used for the research design and development and therefore this section discusses them.

Table 1. 5 Summary of Research methodology

Data Research	Field Research
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To perform critical evaluation of the academic and industry-based Agile Transformation literature • To define and discuss the literature gap between Agile Transformation and Sustainability • To develop a theoretical framework that addresses the literature gap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To collect and analyze the qualitative semi-structured research interviews and focus groups • To validate the Sustainable Agile Framework for its benefits and limitation as part of field study • To provide implementation guidelines to academics and practitioners
To develop Sustainable Agile Transformation Framework and to provide implementation guidance to academics and practitioners	

Table 1.5 compiles the research focus based on desk and field. Publications of books, press conferences, reports, journals and articles have been categorized into academic and industrial desk research, to establish an in-depth critical literature review for developing an agile startup sustainability framework. Qualitative semi-structured interviews and focus groups form the field research which comprises the verbal and non-verbal empirical investigation. As per Baker and Thomas (2007), both desk and field research decide a research method to be selected.

(I) Research Philosophy: Given the framework of research questions, interpretivism philosophy would be appropriate, wherein the approach of positivism or interpretivism really depends on the need of the research questions (Thomas, 2013). This research applies qualitative methods concerning with the spurs of human conduct and the motives for it – asking “what”, “how” and “why” questions about human behaviors and taking a realistic approach to the sustainability phenomena (Creswell, 2013; Robson and McCartan, 2015). However, as this research adopts multiple methods, it uses semi-structured interviews to gather information, as outlined and uses Qualitative focus groups to validate or reassess the research objectives and therefore inductive approach will be appropriate.

(ii) Research Strategy: A case study strategy was considered suitable and appropriate considering the proposed aim which was to understand managers' perceptions and understandings of agile transformation and sustainability. To ensure generalizability of research findings beyond homogenous businesses for the broader applicability and impact of this research, purposeful sampling, grounding the case study in a robust theoretical framework, transferability within similar contexts, replicability and providing in-depth insights into Agile as a phenomenon were considered. Moreover, to construct meanings from mixed-method qualitative semi-structured interviews and focus groups, a case strategy sequences each interpreting and validating the other, can be useful to explore new phenomenon based on sustainability of Indian IT startups (Saunders *et al* 2012).

(iii) Sampling: IBEF (2019), registers 19,000 IT startups within the year 2018, serving as the sample population to be selected from. This research considers purposeful sampling method to be appropriate for sampling information. The sample frame includes both startup delegates and agile community consulting startups who can provide relevant information. 20 semi-structured interviews with IT startup founders and co-founders, entrepreneurs and project managers in India will be sampled and transcript decoded which will further be validated through the 2 focus group discussions with 7 participants each comprising agile practitioners, senior agile consultants, agile coaches and senior project managers.

(iv) Data Collection: The nature of articles collected as data served as the deciding factor: 'conceptual' versus 'empirical'. Science direct journals, IEEE journals, PMI articles, conference papers, and government sources such as newspaper articles, press releases, tech start-ups report, government statistics websites. Qualitative approach will utilize interviewing method to effectively collect data, wherein different means such as computer aided telephonic interviewing, interactive voice recording, practical observation, direct face-to-face interviewing will compliment data collection (Manuel, 2012).

(v) Data Analysis: Sustainability (S) as the primary outcome will be regarded as dependent variable and factors contributing to sustainability such as strategic agility, risk agility and operational agility will be considered as independent variables. As qualitative approach has been decided appropriate for research objective of finding and assessing factors that affect sustainability, thematic analysis to find the emergent themes and codes that could possibly

arrive from data collection. (Verma, 2012; Krishnan and Prashantham, 2019). As part of qualitative approach, research objective is achieved through the determination of perception of managers about agile transformation on sustainability, recording patterns within this theme, in other words, find repeated information that carry significance within multiple interviews. This gives this research a holistic picture of the Indian IT startup ecosystem for future researchers and practitioners.

1.13 RESEARCH OUTLINE

This section outlines the entire structure of this thesis to provide quick guidance on what to expect from each chapter and to present how the aim of this research will be established.

Chapter 1 is an introduction to the thesis, research background, Indian IT startup industry, its importance, growth rate and industry trends, current research problem of sustainability, research aim, objectives, and contributions and furthermore, includes research motivation and justification, brief of literature review and research methodology and an outline of research structure.

Chapter 2 conceptualizes sustainability with respect to IT startups, scrutinizes sustainability factors through academic and industrial resources and provides the evaluation of literatures on non-agile and agile transformation methods over sustainability, bringing out the literature gaps. Furthermore, this chapter evaluates existing agile frameworks and its gaps to develop a conceptual framework in achieving sustainability of Indian IT startups.

Chapter 3 presents the research methodology predominantly justifying the need and suitability of each parameter of research onion that has been adopted in this research. This chapter further outlines the research design, considers data access, and explains the collection, sampling techniques and strategy and data analysis procedures. Moreover, the ethical considerations, validity and reliability through trustworthiness evaluating the quality of this research have been addressed and justified in this chapter.

Chapter 4 documents the qualitative data, reporting the collection and analysis of data from research interviews conducted wherein the overview of themes, keywords and codes developed through manual thematic analysis of qualitative analysis and the in-depth data collected from semi-

structured interviews and focus groups have been formulated. The adopted and emerged themes have been differentiated from previous research contributions.

Chapter 5 discusses on the findings from Chapter 4 backed by the secondary qualitative data collected and documented in Chapter 2 using appropriate tables and tools to explain the emergent themes arrived from the data analysis which contributes to the larger success of this research. Further, this chapter validates the agile startup sustainability framework, based on the findings and provides an implementational guidance for managers incorporating this framework.

Chapter 6 summarizes the key research findings, draws conclusions, explains how the research objectives and questions have been met and answered, discusses both the theoretical and practical contributions of this research along with the managerial implications and practical recommendations through a strategic roadmap developed in this chapter. Also, the research limitations and recommendations for future research have been addressed towards the end.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter briefly introduced the research problem with its significance towards IT startup industry in India. This chapter presents an extensive exploration of relevant and recent academic and industry-based literature on sustainability and transformation methodologies, with a particular focus on the IT startup sector in India. Sections 2.2, 2.4, and 2.5 delves into the key elements of sustainability, failures of transformation methodologies, and the contrasting dynamics of agile and traditional methodologies. The synthesis of these insights aims to uncover reasons why Indian IT startups grapple with new business challenges, linking this to the methodology employed and scrutinizes the significance of sustainability as a central research concern. Section 2.6 elucidates the literature gaps, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive agile startup sustainability framework.

This chapter fills a significant void by bridging academic theories with industry practices, addressing the implementation challenges overlooked by academics. It conducts a thorough review of agile transformation and sustainability literature over the last two decades, answering initial research questions and laying the foundation for the development of a new agile startup sustainability framework. The subsequent sections, 2.7.4 and 2.7.5, proposes the rationale for this framework, underscoring its importance in impacting the sustainability of Indian IT startups and instilling organizational agility. This chapter will ultimately contribute to identifying the literature gaps and framework to be developed in Chapter 5 and for future opportunities.

2.2 SUSTAINABILITY

As discussed in Chapter 1, Section 1.4, the current scenario of IT startups in India, sustainability was identified as a predominant threat that has cost numerous start-ups to fail and exit in large volumes which makes it a prominent research area to be explored and delved into. This section will further scrutinize the conceptualization, significance, identification of factors, and measurement metrics of sustainability, addressing Research Question 1 and Research Objective 1, Chapter 1, Section 1.9. This section serves as the foundation for the sections to follow.

2.2.1 CONCEPTUALIZATION OF SUSTAINABILITY

The term "sustainability" has ascended to paramount importance in recent times across corporate, political, and academic realms, emerging as a focal point for comprehensive, long-term planning. Brundtland report first coined the term sustainable development which emphasizes “the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland, 1987). Over the years, the term sustainability has been linked to the Triple Bottom Line (TBL), seeking to balance economy, society and environment as shown in Figure 2.1 (Elkington, 1998). Lindsey (2011) and Bolis *et al.* (2014) assert a resolute stance on decision-making, emphasizing values intricately linked to collective interests in sustainability; Ceasar and Page (2013) argue that sustainability, marked by challenges and opportunities, can align with future environmental needs, while Stoddart (2011) relates it to resource allocation for present and future societal, economic, and environmental growth, and Basiago (1999) connects sustainability to perpetuating specific outcomes and associated processes over the long term.

Figure 2. 1 Sustainability Conceptualization

Source: Adapted from Brundtland (1987) and Elkington (1998)

Despite this, scholarly attention has predominantly been fixed on sustainability within the triad of economy, society, and environment (Gray & Milne, 2013; Thomas, 2015). Sustainability, a holistic concept, applies across industries, domains, context and stakeholders involved and analyzing more than just the environment, economy and social pillars can be integral for achieving the research aim. Concepts such as corporate social responsibility or environmental management have gained momentum in the context of businesses in recent years. Notably, to inject greater significance into the discourse, a cultural perspective has been integrally incorporated into the sustainability definition as shown in Figure 2.1 (Tjarve and Zemīte, 2016; Mensah and Enu-Kwesi, 2018).

Sustainable development as an idea guarantees numerous things to numerous individuals shaping various aspects around the idea yet there's vagueness encompassing the subject and the significance of the words themselves. In attempts to apply and adapt sustainability to the Information Technology (IT) industry, recent studies have created both tensions and complements where IT services have been viewed as part of innovative measures and growth across industries but there is no clear or specific definition with respect to the IT industry. Gareis *et al* (2009) criticizes that less importance has been given to IT startup sustainability, particularly software development startups, where the projects are small scaled and short-lived. Eid (2009) claims that failure to address sustainability as an issue has lowered the standards of the projects and has cost the business model of the startup.

Table 2. 1 Various definitions of sustainability development

S.NO	VARIOUS ANGLES OF SUSTAINABILITY DEVELOPMENT	LITERATURE
1	Ability to continue existing practices for future periods	Dernbach, 1998, 2003; Lele, 1991; Stoddart, 2011
2	Ability to meet future needs without depleting current resources	Brundtland Commission Report (Schaefer & Crane, 2005); World Commission on Environment and Development; Goodland & Daly, 1996; Cerin (2006); Abubakar (2017)
3	Sustainability can be achieved through social, economic and environmental sustainability (3 pillars)	Gossling-Goidsmiths, 2018; Zhai and Chang, 2019; Ukaga et al (2011); According to the United Nation Communications Group (UNCG) and the Civil Society Organization (CSO) [2017]
4	Current decision making should involve consideration of pillars of sustainability	Gray (2010); Kolk (2016); Wanamaker (2018); Yang (2019); Taylor (2016)
5	Addition of culture into the pillars of sustainability	Agenda 21 for culture and the United Cities and Local Governments (UCLG); Saiyed and Zahraa (2017); Necefer et al (2015);
6	Usage of Information technology to ensure project success and sustainability	Khan (2011); Farnaz (2003); Hilty (2011); Dyllick and Muff (2016); Chen et al (2017); Geyi et al (2020)

Since 2013, several researchers like Silvius and Tharp (2013), Yvonne (2014) and Maria *et al* (2018) have accounted for an increase in momentum towards this ideology of relationship between projects and its sustainability. Jose and David (2017) and Yazici (2020) consider this growing significance has encouraged project managers and startup entrepreneurs to focus on challenges of sustainability with respect to the project undertaken. Table 2.1 overall captures the shift of conceptualization of sustainability development literatures from Dernback (1998), Brundtland Report, which focuses more on the TBL pillars, to the recent literatures from Chen *et al* (2017) and Geyi *et al* (2020) which highlights other aspects to be considered. This table moreover depicts that the concept of sustainability can yield numerous benefits when seen under different contexts and lenses.

On the other hand, the organizational sustainability of Indian IT startups, as compared to MNCs and global IT companies can be different to the project sustainability. In the volatile landscape that Indian IT startups navigate, effective risk management is imperative for identifying and mitigating potential challenges, safeguarding the organization against unforeseen disruptions. Strategic planning provides a cohesive roadmap, guiding startups in setting goals, defining target markets, and positioning themselves competitively (Venters *et al*, 2014). This strategic clarity not only informs decision-making but also contributes to the efficient allocation of resources.

Concurrently, performance optimization, achieved through the establishment and monitoring of key performance indicators, enables startups to continually refine processes, enhance operational efficiency, and align activities with overarching strategic objectives (Henderson, 2011; Lonkar and Gupte, 2019; Enders and Remig, 2015). The integration of these pillars can ensure a holistic approach to organizational sustainability, fostering resilience, adaptability, and the ability to seize growth opportunities in a dynamic business environment (Fatemi and Fooladi, 2013; Lopez *et al*, 2015; Gregory *et al*, 2015).

As established before, startups rely on the project frequency and their success rate. In this regard where project success has been linked to sustainability, the scope of project success needs to be expanded from mere project management to the holistic organizational sustainability of the startups (Santiago and Emre, 2017; Yang, 2019). This requires the management disciplines such as risk, strategy and performance to be linked to the project management, wherein, the success of projects complements the success of risk, strategy and performance management.

Moreover, Sub-Section 2.3.2 will further identify the relationship between project success and overall sustainability of IT startups. Based on these above definitions, it can be clearly seen that there are multiple conceptualizations of sustainability yet with respect to software and IT startups, the project success has greater impact on the sustainability of Indian IT startups and that has been included in the Figure 2.1. This direct relationship between project success and sustainability of startups has been approved by various literature in software engineering and management (Axel and Lars, 2016; Denning, 2019). Having scrutinized the concept of sustainability and linked it to the target sector of this research, the next section will bring out its importance in the IT startups industry in India.

2.2.2 THE NEXUS BETWEEN SUSTAINABILITY AND BUSINESS START-UPS IN THE IT SECTOR

Sustainability as an outcome has been credited and valued for business industries, government sectors, charitable organizations and society (Hörisch, Freedman, & Schaltegger, 2014). As this research focuses primarily on the sustainability of Indian IT startups, it is necessary to understand why startups struggle over a period of establishment to be profitable and sustainable. According to Wang *et al* (2014), sustainability measures and practices within businesses, can lead to accelerated profitability and increased growth rate as opposed to alarming failure rate. From being an addition, sustainability has become a necessity for IT MNCs and startups, to address current practices and process to align them towards achieving increased sales profits, skill development, improved employee and company productivity to meet customer demands, create new opportunities and have a positive impact over the community (Dyllick and Muff, 2016).

With sustainability practices in place, businesses can take undue advantage of technological advancements, reduce overhead costs, attract more talent rather than losing employees, drive innovation, instill ethical considerations and motivate team and management (Wilshusen and MacDonald, 2017). Figure 2.2 correlates these factors to achieving competitive advantage in Indian IT startups. Startups, although in their seed and growth stages, can give more attention to aligning management practices to sustainability in their business model to achieve competitive advantage for the longer run (Lahti *et al.* 2018). The idea of competitive advantage represents a private segment that hopes to amplify benefits by beating contenders, rather than the undeveloped area where non-benefit destinations are the more regularly the objective (Henderson, 2011). This shows the strong relationship between sustainability and competitive advantage.

Modern economies demonstrate how sustainable competitive advantage depends on the company's strategic position inside an industry (Lahti *et al.* 2018). Studies prove that factors affect competitive advantage also affect the sustainability of a business and its benefits. In Table 2.2, the Key Performance Indicators (KPI), argued to be an integral tool for leaders and managers to monitor the performance of the company in each management discipline is shown (Wilshusen and MacDonald, 2017). For example, Lahti *et al* (2018) claims that competitive advantage and product innovation can be potential indicators of strategic management. Considering these factors and indicators can be integral when correlating sustainability to management disciplines.

Table 2. 2 Benefits of sustainability

S.NO	MANAGEMNT DISCIPLINE	INDICATORS	LITERATURE
1	Risk management	Effectiveness Efficiency	Dyllick & Muff, 2016; Wilshusen & MacDonald, 2017; Hörisch, Freedman, & Schaltegger, 2014;
2	Performance management	Enhanced stakeholder returns Service innovation	Wang, Hawkins, & Berman, 2014;
3	Human resource management	Employee retention Employee satisfaction	Lahti et al. 2018;
4	Strategy management	Competitive advantage Product innovation	Reim et al, 2015
5	Finance management	Cost savings Passive cash flows	
6	Marketing management	Brand image Market innovation	

Source: Adapted from Wilshusen and MacDonald (2017)

According to Rodriguez *et al* (2009), IT businesses must constantly advance their resources, competencies and day-to-day activities to yield a competitive advantage for a sustainable business involving both the individual and the company's responsibility to maintain it. According to a survey conducted by Henderson (2011), 62 per cent of the senior executives emphasize the need for sustainability strategy for corporate companies and 22 per cent believe that sustainability can be inevitable for future concerns. Reim *et al* (2015), argue that sustainability influences resource allocation and competitiveness in the areas of sustainability pillar as shown in Sub-Section 2.2.1, Figure 2.1. From being merely an environmental concern for management in manufacturing companies, the scope of sustainability has been elevated to entrepreneurship studies, IT strategic management and project sustainability to influence continuous innovation (Schaltegger 2002; Cohen and Winn 2007; Dean and McMullen 2007; Hess and Warren, 2008).

Numerous researchers have explored the scope of sustainability practices towards corporate strategy and the relationship between financial and non-financial Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and sustainability (Mill, 2006; Porter and Kramer, 2011; Gupta *et al*, 2019). Yet the magnitude of research has always been restricted to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) or environmental measures rather than the relationship between IT practices and sustainability. Melo *et al* (2011) argue that businesses need to focus on improving business processes as part of sustainability measures. With respect to stock market and financial performance, businesses focusing on sustainability can perform better than competitors (Melo *et al*, 2011).

Figure 2. 2 Relationship between sustainability and competitive advantage

Source: Adaptation of Melo *et al* (2011)

Nidumolu *et al* (2009), during a major IT recession in the year 2009, claimed that sustainability measures cannot be overlooked given their significance in the dynamic market to be innovative and sustainable among competition. According to the survey conducted by Krishna *et al* (2017), the pressure of globalization, complex stakeholder needs, scandals of corporate strategies, global crisis, etc., has furthermore emphasized the urgency of sustainability measures in IT and non-IT companies where 90 per cent of Chief Executive Officers (CEO) consider sustainability as top priority. As discussed in Chapter 1, Section 1.4, business sustainability has been the major problem amidst Indian IT startups and having learnt its significance both internal and external to the startup, the next section scrutinizes factors that affect this sustainability.

2.2.3 FACTORS AFFECTING SUSTAINABILITY (ACADEMIC LITERATURE)

As identified in the previous section, sustainability can lead to startup wellness (Rodriguez *et al.*, 2009; Flint, and Golicic, 2009). As justified in Section 1.5 and Section 2.2.1, the key dimensions for the sustainability of Indian IT startups namely, risk, strategy and performance have often been overlooked and understudied. Subbarao and Rani (2015) and Lonkar and Gupte (2017), reveal the clear relationship between the management of performance, risk and strategy and the transformation method employed, that researchers have failed to attribute to startup sustainability. It can be strongly argued that risk, strategy and performance are key pillars and dimensions of sustainability, and this research further aims to explore how agile transformation can influence these dimensions in Section 2.5.

Identifying and mitigating risks, developing and executing a clear and effective strategy and setting measurable performance goals and improving them is integral to sustainable development. Therefore, the factors affecting sustainability of startups, scrutinized in the following sections views them under the lenses of risk, strategy, and performance.

2.2.3.1 STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY

As per Savitz and Weber (2007) and Crittenden *et al* (2011), sustainability can only be achieved when sustainable practices align with business strategies and thereby potentiate competitive advantage both in terms of the market and competition. Researchers like Boons and Lüdeke-Freund (2013) and Bocken *et al* (2014) claim the significance of incorporation of sustainability and its values into strategic management and link it to business model innovation.

Jiménez and Lorente (2001) and Maria *et al* (2018) criticize that there are more to just economy, society and environmental aspects of sustainability that can contribute to the knowledge management of strategic operations and development and claim that it proves relevance throughout the business life cycle. In accordance and conclusion drawn from Schaltegger *et al* (2013), Hahn and Kühnen (2013), Orsato *et al* (2015) and Dutta *et al* (2020), and other governmental reports from IBEF (2019), KPMG (2019) and NASSCOM (2019) this research identifies five prominent strategic risks as tabulated in Table 2.3, that affect sustainability of startups. The relevance of these factors with respect to Indian IT startups will be scrutinized further in Chapter 4, Section 1.3.

Table 2. 3 Strategic factors that affect sustainability

STRATEGIC FACTORS	DEFINTION	LITERATURE
Ineffective Planning	Plans fail to incorporate incremental learning culture but rather impose set of numerous procedure and rules	Crittenden et al., 2011; Porter & Linde, 1995; Savitz & Weber, 2007; Bocken et al., 2014; Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Jiménez & Lorente, 2001; Lozano, 2012; Schaltegger et al., 2013; Hahn & Kühnen, 2013; Consolandi et al., 2009; Orsato et al., 2015
Poor Requirement Management	Management's focus on deadlines rather prioritizing user requirements	
Misaligned road maps	Deviated focus of strategic plans from the organizational vision and goals, thereby deviating from roadmap	
Pre-mature Scaling	Failure to identify the actual need of the moment and that which can benefit both customers and the company before transforming	
Failed Business Model	Lack of a unique, profitable, and sustainable business model that welcomes change	

As depicted in Table 2.3, ineffective planning which is predominant in IT startups can pose serious threats to the sustainability of startups, wherein the priority of numerous procedures and rules over incremental planning has led to startups being rigid and unresponsive to change (Orsato *et al*, 2015; Dutta *et al*, 2020). IBEF (2019) also claims that the management’s focus on deadlines rather than prioritizing user requirements has led to poor requirement management in IT startups which is also shown in Table 2.3. Other factors such as misaligned roadmaps, pre-mature scaling and failed business models have been identified as strategic factors that affect sustainability of IT startups.

2.2.3.2 PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY

As per Morioka and Carvalho (2016), there exists a fragmentation and dispersion of literatures that link sustainability and performance yet direct relationship between them has always been approved (Paulraj *et al*, 2017). As Bos-Brouwers (2010), Govardhan and Jeyakumaran (2018) and Towey *et al* (2019) claim, sustainability can target an efficient and effective performance of the business by considering all the performance risks that are associated with it. Although Esfahbodi *et al* (2017) and Malik *et al* (2021) claim that considering sustainability can negatively influence businesses, overlooking such performance risk factors as in Table 2.4, can disrupt business performance (Ahimbisibwe *et al*, 2017). Pivotal contributions from literature, highlighted by Ciccullo *et al*. (2018), Chen *et al*. (2017), and Paulraj *et al*. (2017), illuminate crucial factors. These insights serve as compelling motivators for businesses to conscientiously address transformation risks and issues, paving the way for the integration of sustainable practices (McKinsey, 2019).

Table 2. 4 Performance factors that affect sustainability

PERFORMANCE FACTORS	DEFINITION	LITERATURE
Poor Financials	Excessive operational cost; low turnover; bureaucracy; ROI; low profitability; burn rate;	Morioka & Carvalho, 2016 Bos-Brouwers, 2010
Team Inefficiency	Closed mindset; distrust within employees; deliverables; organizational culture;	Garnåsjordet, Aslaksen, Giampietro, Funtowicz, & Ericson, 2012; Bansal & Roth, 2000; Warner & Zheng, 2013; Parsa, Van der Rest, Smith, Parsa, & Bujisic, 2015; Sandvik, Duhan, & Sandvik, 2014
Stagnant Learning	Lack of continuous learning and innovation; failure to feedback customer needs into production; implementation innovation;	
Unsatisfied Customers	Customer attraction & retention; traffic; customer satisfaction; lack of visibility; feeble transparency;	

As per Warner and Zheng (2013) startups fail in performance due to productivity lack which can be accounted to financial and non-financial factors such as team skill set and lack of visibility. Warner and Zheng (2013), Silvius and Tharp (2013) and Jain *et al* (2018) add to the list of factors highlighting issues in leadership, lack of innovation and failing plans of strategy to satisfy customers and continuously grow in terms of performance. Ciccullo *et al* (2018), Chen *et al* (2017) and Paulraj *et al* (2017) highlight financial challenges such as business expenses, annual turnover and tax regulations as controlling factors for startup performance. Business entrepreneurs and experts have different dimensions to startup sustainability, but this research focuses on performance risks in terms of method performance and thereby formulates factors in Table 2.4.

Most notable of the performance factors as established in Table 2.4, is the unsatisfied customers, which poses serious threat to customer satisfaction and retention. Duhan and Sandvik (2014) and Paulraj *et al* (2017), further claim that lack of visibility and feeble transparency with customers have led to startup processes and results being isolated from the customer. This factor will be further scrutinized in Chapter 4, Section 1.3 in the context of Indian IT startups.

2.2.3.3 RISK MANAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY

Table 2.5 comprehensively illuminates pivotal risk factors impacting the sustainability of Indian IT startups, as corroborated by existing literature. Winnall (2013) contends that risk mitigation is indispensable in the transformative landscape of software development startups. Silvius *et al.* (2012) establishes a direct correlation between risk and the uncertainty of events influencing the achievement of strategic goals. Niazi *et al.* (2016) and Satar and John (2016) underscore the universal challenges faced by startups, emphasizing competition, meeting customer demands, sustaining market presence, fostering brand loyalty, attracting skilled talent, and navigating legislative landscapes.

Dutta *et al.* (2020) assert the profound linkage of these factors to sustainability, underscoring their paramount importance. Aligning with IBEF (2019) and Govardhan and Jeyakumaran (2018), three critical dimensions of sustainability, sub-standard governance and compliance, lack of innovation, and mismanagement of resources coupled with communication gaps with customers, are identified as focal points necessitating urgent attention in the startup ecosystem. This can also be applied to the startup landscape in India.

Table 2. 5 Risk factors that affect sustainability

RISK FACTORS	DEFINTION	LITERATURE
High Uncertainty	Failure to identify global risks such as pandemics, fluctuation rates, recession, potential growth periods;	Office of Government Commerce, 2010; Winnall, 2013;
Sub-standard Governance & Compliance	Meeting government legislations and regulations; maintaining management standards; governance of employees & needs; brand value; CSR;	Silvius et al., 2012; Project Management Institute, 2013; Sanjai et al 2016;
Lack of Innovation	Failure to identify and capitalize trending technologies reflected in limited patents recorded; lacking agility;	Satar and John, 2016; Hill, 2016; Evers et al., 2014;
Poor Resource Management	Ignorance of resource and capability building leading to limited core competences that can deprive sustainable competitive advantage	IBEF, 2019; Govardhan and Jeyakumar, 2018; Noshir et al, 2019;
Miscommunication	What customer wants and what startup companies offer can be entirely different leading to high operational cost, time wasted on building unproductive software, compromised quality and less scope towards customer retention	Dutta et al, 2020;

As shown in Table 2.5, Hijazi *et al.*, 2012 and Purvis *et al* (2019) claim that startups aimed to disrupt market innovation through faster dynamics lack innovation. Silvius *et al* (2013) and Purvis *et al* (2019) have tried to correlate these risk factors with sustainability, implying that viewing businesses through sustainability lens can improve the practices adopted for addressing challenges in risk management. Although Silvius *et al* (2013) critiques that these factors can vary according to startup sector, demography, diverse interests of stakeholders involved, etc., there are few that prove common to Indian startups (Noshir *et al*, 2019; Dutta *et al*, 2020). This requires entrepreneurs and employees to be fully committed to understanding the importance of assessing and addressing these factors that affect the sustainability of Indian IT startups.

2.2.4 FACTORS AFFECTING SUSTAINABILITY (INDUSTRIAL LITERATURE)

The following chart Figure 2.3 compares various industrial reports from online resources such as Statista (2019), Forbes (2019), CB Insights (2019) and Failory (2020) to collectively identify factors that in general affect sustainability of startups. Statista (2019), Forbes (2019) and CB Insight (2019) report similar ranking for market fitness 42%, lack of funds 29%, team inefficiencies 23%, Competition 19%, lack of innovation 17%, failed business model 17%, poor marketing 14%, customer experience 14%, early scaling 13% and legal compliance 14% as prominent factors that affect sustainability of startups as compared to Failory (2020).

Figure 2. 3 Comparative charts of Industry reports for sustainability factors

Source: Adapted from Statista (2019), Forbes (2019), CB Insights (2019) and Failory (2020)

Industrial researchers such as Radha and Ilankumaran (2018), Kaur (2017), Panditta (2017), and Ciric *et al.* (2019) assert that critical factors, including poor resource management, lack of awareness and mentorship, failure to exceed customer expectations for retention, and decelerating growth strategies, augment those previously identified. Failory (2020) and Dutta *et al.* (2020) further elevate the discourse by incorporating entrepreneur experience and education into the realm of considerations for business sustainability. Esfahbodi *et al.* (2017) explore sustainability factors for Indonesian startups across finance, organization, product, market, and external dimensions, providing insights applicable to Indian startups as well. Daniel and Fabio (2018) contribute to the discourse by studying the startup ecosystem and formulating a maturity model based on industrial reports, considering societal, cultural, methodological, and technological factors as crucial sustainability elements.

Noshir *et al.* (2019) and Singh *et al.* (2019) posit that Digital India, as an initiative toward digitization, can serve as a catalyst for Indian IT startups to forge global connections with businesses and entrepreneurs, presenting substantial contributions. Krishnan and Prashantham (2019) shed light on axial disparities in opportunities for startups across various demographics and regions in India, emphasizing the competitive advantage some startups possess in attracting angel investors and venture capitalists.

While most sustainability factors are externally oriented, internal factors also play a pivotal role in their resolution, as noted by Chen *et al.* (2017). Consequently, linking the practical transformation method to the sustainability challenges within the ecosystem becomes imperative, as addressing them in isolation would yield limited benefits. The ensuing section will encapsulate a synthesis of both academic and industrial factors explored in the preceding sections.

2.2.5 SUMMARY OF FACTOR (ACADEMIC-INDUSTRIAL)

The below Table 2.6 summarizes the factors identified from academic and industrial resources in Table 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5, that address the sustainability of Indian IT startups, and categorizes under three major components of sustainability, risk, strategy, and performance. Table 2.6 effectively addresses Research Objective 1, by categorizing the sustainability factors under the management disciplines of risk, strategy and performance, closing the literature gap.

Table 2. 6 Categorizing factors that affect sustainability

RISK	STRATEGY	PERFORMANCE
Product Unwelcomed	Failed Business model	Team inefficiency
No market needs	Strategic misalignment	Ignored Customers
Lack of funds	Early Scaling	Unproductive culture
Lack of innovation	Client Management	Customer satisfaction
Legal compliance	High Competition	Deliverables
Resource Management	Ineffective planning	Health of financial operation

Moreover, these factors identified in Table 2.6 can be of utmost importance for future researchers aiming to address sustainability issues in any startup as these factors highlight literature from across disciplines. According to Chen *et al* (2017) and Noshir *et al* (2019), addressing these collective factors can help startups be cost-effective, create more opportunities for innovative strategies, improve the company’s reputation, add new customers, get more projects through trust, attract more skilled workforce and meet customer demands effectively. As these factors have been identified as more targeted towards Indian IT startups, the Agile transformation as proposed as the solution needs to address these issues. Further these factors need to be validated and verified with data collected from the sample population nominated for this research to be interviewed.

2.3 TRANSFORMATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

The previous Section 2.2 discussed the factors affecting sustainability of Indian IT startups and that these factors lead to transformation of these startups. This section discusses holistic and IT-enabled transformation, linking IT method to transformation and further sustainability, bridging Research Question 1 and 2, Chapter 1, Section 1.9.

2.3.1 DEFINITION OF TRANSFORMATION

According to Axel and Lars (2016), meta-transformation is a holistic process that encompasses both guiding and enabling the business. Consequently, it is imperative to establish a concise relationship among the key components of IT management before embarking on any transformation, as illustrated in Figure 2.4.

Rajagopalan and Mathew (2014) emphasize the critical role of digital and IT-enabled transformations in any business. A plethora of literature has extensively examined factors influencing or driving such transformations, as evidenced by studies conducted by Yoo *et al.* (2010) and Fuchs and Hess (2018). However, Denning (2019) and Immelt (2017) provide a valuable critique, suggesting that an exclusive focus on the transformation journey is essential for achieving the desired change and gaining a profound understanding of the failure factors and challenges faced by startups.

Figure 2. 4 Meta transformation: A holistic approach

Source: Adapted from Axel and Lars (2016)

Although Oliva and Kotabe (2019) and Axel and Lars (2016) address issues and barriers that business faces during transformation, limited research has been accounted for startup transformation and that which triggers it, thereby creating a literature gap. Transformation, regardless of scale, possesses the potential to propel or guide any business towards the sought-after change. The intricate interplay of IT management components and a comprehensive understanding of the transformation journey are paramount in this pursuit.

2.3.2 LINKING TRANSFORMATION AND IT METHOD

As per Lucas *et al* (2013) and Immelt (2017), IT enabled transformation has increasingly impacted businesses in recent years by bringing excellence towards process, customer relations and experience, market capitalization and innovation. As Stephen (2018) and Geyi *et al* (2020) argue, any software development method that disrupts traditional practices and their fundamental business resources and capabilities, process, and customer relations, can be transformational.

Figure 2. 5 Dimensions of IT-enabled transformation

Source: Adapted from Axel and Lars (2016)

Researchers like Axel and Lars (2016), Daniel and Fabio (2018) and Denning (2019) vehemently underscore the significance of achieving IT excellence for overall transformation. Their collective insights provide the foundation for this research, driving a focused examination not merely into conventional aspects but specifically delving into the intricate realm of software development methods capable of catalyzing transformative shifts within startup ecosystems. Leveraging their research, this research aims to unearth novel perspectives and innovative approaches that can catalyze holistic transformations within the dynamic domain of Indian IT startup enterprises.

Furthermore, Immelt (2017) emphatically underscores that, irrespective of a business's scale, be it a startup or a multinational corporation (MNC), achieving IT excellence is not just advantageous but pivotal for survival. Figure 2.6, as elucidated by McKeown and Philip (2003), delineates IT transformation as the very bedrock upon which more extensive transformations rest, necessitating a comprehensive reevaluation of business processes. This involves fostering avenues to augment performance through astute risk management and strategic foresight. Aligning with Ahimbisibwe *et al.* (2015), the strategic selection of a transformation method that seamlessly aligns with and advances the overarching goal of sustainability has the potential to transform IT startups in India. Morgan and Page (2008) along with Denning (2019) propound a visionary framework, delineating four dimensions of IT-enabled transformation as crucial milestones toward broader transformations. Figure 2.5 visually encapsulates these dimensions, portraying a roadmap that is not only applicable to established enterprises but can also be judiciously applied to startups, charting a course towards enduring success.

2.3.3 TRANSFORMATION METHOD PROCESS

As established in Chapter 1, Section 1.3, this research unequivocally focuses on the realm of software startups dedicated to the development and construction of web applications, software, and apps. Crowne (2002), Taylor *et al.* (2008), and Ahimbisibwe *et al.* (2015) firmly establish a critical nexus between transformation and the judicious selection of the software development method. Building on this foundation, Taylor *et al.* (2008), Eloranta (2014), and Paternoster *et al.* (2014) forcefully contend that both product-based and project-based software startups confront a dearth of innovative and sustainable business models. These startups grapple with challenges in developing, marketing, and selling their proprietary products, signaling a compelling need for a paradigm shift in their strategic approach. Sahil *et al.* (2017), Daniel and Fabio (2018) and Maria *et al.* (2018), refer software development method as “code and fix”, being chaotic given the nature of the process involving mere planning and designing of the software based on quick decisions. Although Awad (2005) and Qureshi (2012) critique this process as strenuous given the inability to enhance features or add-ons and fix issues once the product develops to its later stages. Misra *et al.* (2012) and Denning (2019) highlight the concept of ‘Method’, wherein random Software Development (SD) processes were alternated with a disciplined and controlled processing, with an approach towards effective and predictable SD.

Chapman (2004) accounts to the definition of SD methods as collected document of 3P's namely policy, process and procedure, that constitute the software business engineering and management. However, Sanchez and Connor (2016) and Abrahamsson *et al* (2017), claim that software development method or 'methods' involves activities and process that includes development and maintenance of software and accompanying projects. Tarhini *et al.* (2018) intricately links crucial elements such as planning, design documentation, sets of codes, and test manuals to the artifacts inherent in any software development method. According to their perspective, these components collectively serve as the foundation for a spectrum of activities and measures, all of which are visually elucidated in the comprehensive depiction presented in Figure 2.6. This figure serves as an illuminating roadmap, showcasing how these foundational elements seamlessly interconnect to guide and shape the trajectory of software development.

Figure 2. 6 Process of transformational software development method

Source: Adapted from Tarhini *et al* (2018)

Chandr *et al* (2010) argue that software development methods should be entirely disciplined and follow a set of instructions covering the entirety of the development and maintenance process. However, researchers like Misra *et al* (2012), Ahimbisibwe *et al* (2015) and Sanchez and Connor (2016), critique that the process of developing a software cannot be rigid but rather flexible given the complexity and uncertainty of the environment. Denning (2019) claims this flexible approach to be enabling and empowering teams and giving businesses the freedom to choose the appropriate and suitable development method for their nature or type. Clarke and O'Connor (2012) also appraise this flexible approach to be effective in delivery time and quality of the end product, claiming that there exists the gap between the methods and demands of the context and situation. Stephen (2018) attests this to the difficulty of generalizing software development methods.

Giardino *et al.* (2014) and Geyi *et al.* (2020) assert that startups' primary preoccupation has never revolved around establishing work procedures or defining processes; rather, their paramount focus is survival. This critical perspective prompts a compelling inquiry into the efficiency of existing transformation methods, demanding scrutiny of their flexibility and adaptability in the uncertain startup landscape. The inherent scarcity of knowledge and research on software methods tailored for startups accentuates a significant gap within the existing literature, emphasizing the urgent need for a more robust exploration of this critical domain.

2.3.4 LINKING TRANSFORMATION METHODS AND SUSTAINABILITY

According to Denning (2019), there has been a discernible shift in scholarly attention towards sustainability literature. Notable researchers such as Budsaratagoon and Jitmaneeroj (2019), Pantiuchinal *et al* (2020), and Dean and Marc (2020) underscore the critical importance of sustainable practices in IT software startups, urging further exploration in this emerging field. Budsaratagoon and Jitmaneeroj (2019) caution against generalizing sustainability principles for IT startups. Dean and Marc (2020) contend that the interplay between IT elements and their sustainability impact significantly shapes business focus. Several researchers, including El-Khalil and Mezher (2020) and Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020), posit that sustainable IT transformation aligns with future innovation without compromising current business needs. However, as pointed out by Denning (2019) and Mensah and Enu-Kwesi (2018), focusing solely on economic, human, and environmental factors has not sufficiently sustained existing systems or methods, necessitating advanced perspectives on sustainability.

Although early researchers like Immelt (2017), Stephen (2018) and Tarhini *et al* (2018) identified the shift in startup management and the need for more innovative solutions, they fail to relate the results to sustainability issues. Khalifeh *et al* (2020), proposes the value of incorporating sustainability into software projects, highlighting the importance of project sustainability in the context of project management. These fragments of intersection of sustainability and project success has all the more lead to functional and non-functional requirements for sustainable software development methods to be standardized and key performance indicators be developed to assess software sustainability.

The previous section depicted the stages of software development methods and how significant they are for any IT software project to be successful (Sahil *et al*, 2017; Daniel and Fabio, 2018; Maria *et al*, 2018). Sustainable software development integrates principles of environmental responsibility, social ethics, and economic viability into the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), to provide a more holistic management for startups, which extends the scope of a software development method to transform an entire startup (Denning, 2019). Wigger and Shepher (2019) assert quality as the paramount element of sustainability that should never be compromised. Khalifeh *et al* (2020) further propose a conceptual framework guiding software development methods and products based on sustainability principles. Yazici (2020) advocate for a green strategic framework offering business strategies rooted in a comprehensive understanding of sustainability, which further presented a model for setting goals to achieve effective sustainability. Mahaux *et al* (2011), initiated the paradigm for the transformation process in software engineering, which was furthered by Budsaratragoon and Jitmaneeroj (2019), who emphasized the attainment of sustainability alongside the final product. Tam *et al* (2020) argue that an appropriate requirements approach can contribute to sustainable ICT systems by integrating knowledge. Yazici (2020), propose detailed guidelines for social sustainability in requirements engineering.

The choice of the right Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) can have a transformative impact on an IT startup, influencing risk management, resource utilization, customer satisfaction, process innovation, and overall sustainability (Abirami *et al*, 2021). While many studies focus on the expansion and administration of software sustainability, only a few addresses the evaluation of software sustainability, neglecting metric evaluation of factors against sustainability standards. Consequently, investigating the necessity and justification for the foundation of software sustainability evaluation represents a crucial literature gap.

2.3.5 TRANSFORMATION METHOD AND CHALLENGES

Esubalew's (2018) comprehensive study unveils 95 pivotal work practices derived from nearly 30 primary studies, meticulously classified into development practices, process management practices, and organizational practices. This wealth of empirical data underscores the operational landscape of IT startups. In a business context, the heightened responsiveness of IT startups to global customer concerns, stakeholder dynamics, technological shifts, and market dynamism mirrors the strategic solutions exercised by their multinational counterparts (Denning, 2019).

Recognizing the pivotal role of software development as the source shaping the fundamental structure of the company, a holistic examination of software engineering in startups becomes imperative, considering its dependencies and influence across various facets of the business ecosystem (Ahimbisibwe *et al*, 2015; Sanchez and Connor, 2016).

Figure 2. 7 Transformation method challenges relating to sustainability

The challenges encapsulated in Figure 2.7's depiction of transformation methods represent a convergence of sustainability challenges from Section 2.2, Tables 2.3 - 2.6 and the transformation method challenges elucidated in this section. In the realm of business transformation, the ultimate objective of any method is to achieve high-quality requirement gathering, streamlined data code efficiency, accelerated time-to-market, cost-effectiveness, and waste minimization—all critical elements for effective software development (Bhatti and Tabassum, 2017). These challenges, pertinent to business success, span a spectrum, including the ability to reuse codes, effective capture and fulfillment of customer expectations, time constraints, changing priorities, emerging technologies, and dynamic team interactions (Jain *et al.*, 2018). The upcoming section will meticulously scrutinize existing transformation methods through the strategic lens provided by Figure 2.7, evaluating their efficacy in navigating these multifaceted challenges and contributing to business growth.

2.4 EXISTING TRANSFORMATION METHODOLOGIES ON SUSTAINABILITY

In Section 2.3, we delved into the intricate interplay between transformation, methodology, and sustainability. Building upon that foundation, this section rigorously assesses the efficacy of established/traditional waterfall, iterative, and spiral transformation methodologies in fostering sustainability. This evaluation aims to provide robust insights and address Research Question 2, as articulated in Chapter 1, Section 1.9, thereby offering a nuanced perspective on the synergic relationship between transformation methods and the sustainability of business operations.

2.4.1 DEFINITION OF EXISTING METHODS

As extensively explored in Section 2.3.4, the nexus between transformational methods and sustainability has been established. Consequently, this section undertakes a meticulous examination to unravel the nuanced impacts of existing/traditional transformation methods, including Waterfall, Iterative, and Spiral approaches, on the holistic sustainability. Advocates of traditional methodologies, often deemed as heavyweight, argue for their rigorous definition and documentation phases (Reifer, 2002). Echoing this sentiment, Fowler (2004) and Qumer and Henderson-Sellers (2008) align traditional transformation methods with plan-centric activities, a predictable sequence of results, a highly process-oriented approach, predetermined methods, and fewer opportunities for re-engineering. These characteristics may find greater suitability in larger projects within IT MNCs rather than in the context of smaller to medium-sized projects within the dynamic landscape of IT startups. The traditional methods further carry the imprint of fixed requirements and budget constraints, delineating a structured approach to project management.

2.4.2 WATERFALL METHOD

The waterfall method epitomizes a more rigid, sequential, and linear approach to software development, where each stage is pursued in a methodical progression. In alignment with this perspective, Fowler (2004) contends that the waterfall method compartmentalizes IT projects based on distinct phases, including requirement gathering, design, coding, and software testing. Figure 2.8 encapsulates the sequential waterfall method, where the process unfolds in a step-by-step fashion, starting with client communication for requirement gathering before delving into project planning. This planning phase encompasses forecasting the project budget, setting deadlines, and establishing key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor progress.

Following this, the development method is meticulously analyzed, leading to the actual coding and thorough testing of the developed software. The final phase involves the deployment of the end product, as highlighted by Pressman (2005) and Vaishnavi *et al.* (2014). This systematic breakdown underscores the method's structured nature, wherein each phase follows the preceding one in a cascading fashion, contributing to a disciplined yet potentially inflexible development process. The waterfall method usually has discrete goals for each activity wherein, there is less opportunity to review or correct the earlier stage, making the method more suitable for approach that is structured, and process centered (Pfleeger and Atlee, 2006). Handoffs and backflows between phases restrict waterfall method to achieve goals that have high dependency on each other, further weakening them of re-engineering and re-construction of code and software in the later stages of development (Bassil, 2012; Vaishnavi *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 2. 8 Waterfall method

Source: Bassil (2012)

Waterfall accommodates iteration of stages in a minimalistic manner where the stages never overlap between them (Pressman, 2005). Since the customer dynamism in requirement gathering might require managers to revisit stages iteratively to identify bugs and alter software codes, the waterfall method cannot comply with this aspect. Software coupling which unifies codes and data in waterfall methods restricts any change in the process and requirement data. As shown in Sub-Section 2.3.3, software reusability, one of the major transformation challenges, cannot be done through the waterfall method as re-engineering can be cumbersome and expensive (Bassil, 2012). In recent times software engineers and developers have modified the waterfall method aiming to address the problems intrinsic in the waterfall method, allowing flexibility, overlapping of phases creating dependence, validation of each phase and reducing overhead costs making changes to an IT project before the deployment phase.

Nevertheless, even with modifications, the waterfall method remains susceptible to significant delays in deploying end products due to the inherent challenge of adapting the entire process to accommodate a single change within a specific phase (Munassar and Govardhan, 2011). This vulnerability underscores the limitations of the modified waterfall approach, emphasizing the potential for prolonged project timelines and hindered adaptability in response to evolving requirements.

2.4.3 ITERATIVE METHOD

Deviating from the conventional approach of commencing with a complete set of requirement specifications, as depicted in Figure 2.9, the Iterative method adopts a more dynamic strategy. This methodology focuses on developing a prototype initially, allowing for ongoing modifications to specifications based on client feedback. This iterative process continues in cycles until each updated version is developed, progressively satisfying client requirements.

Figure 2. 9 Iterative method

Source: Adapted from Nabil *et al* (2010)

As articulated by Nabil *et al.* (2010), this iterative approach transforms the development process into a step-by-step process, ensuring that deliverables align with evolving client expectations at every stage. According to Munassar and Govardhan (2011), the factors that demotivated waterfall methods, paved the way for a faster delivery, less requirement gathering and flexible coding and testing to be developed, leading to the concept of iteration or iterative methods. In comparison with the waterfall method, iterative method approaches the entirety of projects into smaller portions which allows room for the developers and coders to visualize progress and gain feedback from customers (Vaishnavi *et al.*, 2014).

Although different from the waterfall method, iteration method still follows a mini-waterfall process with feedback from one stage and providing necessary information for the next stage (Munassar and Govardhan, 2011). The step-by-step incremental method of developing a design application or prototype before the development of actual product or service, has been appraised to make planning effective at the design stage and avoiding heavy documentations (Ahimbisibwe *et al*, 2015). Tracking bugs/ rectifying at initial stages gives customers opportunities for feedback and changes at any stages, making product more relevant and aligned to client specifications (Cavana, 2017; Budi *et al*, 2016).

Although client requirements are met, working without requirements at initial stages can be cost ineffective with more resource requirements claiming iterative method to fail during changing specifications (Soeken and Wille, 2012). Progress of projects depends highly on risk analysis and therefore a clear definition of increment cannot be provided, and risk management gets unattended making it suitable only for larger projects. Despite attempts to address ambiguous or changing requirements through the iterative method, the substantial escalation in costs and consistent failure to meet deadlines can significantly impact coding and deployment, leading to unforeseen challenges in the design phase. The emphasis on repetitive methodologies in iterative methods can impose considerable strain on customers, demanding their active involvement throughout the development process (Adel and Abdullah, 2015). Amidst these challenges, iterative methods have necessitated the establishment of iterative testing and feedback as integral components of software development practices.

2.4.4 SPIRAL METHOD

Integrating elements from both the waterfall and prototype methodologies, the Spiral method stands out by implementing iterative development cycles, particularly well-suited for highly risky projects, strategically organized in spirals. This innovative approach posits that development stages and prototypes of deliverables can occur simultaneously, thus significantly enhancing the risk management capabilities of the traditional waterfall method (Richard *et al.*, 2014). Illustrated in Figure 2.10, the Spiral method places a premium on the meticulous identification of objectives and goals within a pre-defined set of documented projects. Each phase is executed multiple times, fostering iterative refinement and thorough evaluation until the final deployment.

Originating from the pioneering work of Boehm (1988) and expounded upon by Khan *et al.* (2013), the Spiral method presents a dynamic and robust model that concurrently mitigates risks and ensures the attainment of project objectives in a highly iterative manner. The Spiral method emphasizes risk analysis and mitigation as one of its core principles to evaluate multiple options to implement a software product.

Figure 2. 10 Spiral method

Source: Adapted from Khan *et al.* (2013)

While incorporating elements from the waterfall stages, the Spiral method has garnered acclaim for its exceptional flexibility, allowing for the dynamic determination of stages based on the project's inherent complexity. The assessment of projects within this methodology has witnessed heightened transparency, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the project's dynamics. One of the key strengths attributed to the Spiral method is its effective risk management capabilities (Khan *et al.*, 2013). This intrinsic feature enables change management feasibility and facilitates customization according to evolving project requirements.

A significant drawback frequently leveled against the Spiral method is the elevated costs attributed to its intricate approach and design complexity, coupled with the requirement for high-level skill expertise. This complexity often leads to challenges in adhering to budget constraints, making effective implementation demanding and the prospect of replicability seemingly impossible. The criticisms that have historically been directed at waterfall methods persistently apply to spiral methods, especially concerning the intensive documentation process, as highlighted by Leasu *et al.* (2012), Mahalakshmi and Sundararajan (2013), and Richard *et al.* (2014).

2.4.5 IMPACT OF EXISTING METHODS ON SUSTAINABILITY

IT startups as compared to MNCs have been forced to adapt themselves to the high complexity of the business environment under constant changes and transformations of the engineering practices (Stocia *et al*, 2013). According to Chronis and Gren (2016), organizational agility can be the key to achieve strategic advantages and ultimately market sustainability. Holvitie *et al* (2018), argue that with traditional transformational methodologies, it can be highly impossible or mostly difficult to adapt to such changes with the approach of existing tools, methods and architectures. According to Standish Group (2009), traditional methods for years have not benefited or addressed the increase in project failure rate. Deadlines for project have been ambiguous and the value gets delivered right at the end of the project cycle, allowing no flexibility for changes to be accommodated (Olszewska *et al.*, 2016). Table 2.7 meticulously dissects Sections 2.4.2 - 2.4.5 to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the appraisals and criticisms associated with Waterfall, Iterative, and Spiral methods. This thorough examination serves as a foundation for a nuanced comparison of these traditional approaches and establishes a meaningful linkage to Table 2.8.

Table 2. 7 Comparison of traditional methodologies: Appraisals and criticisms

METHOD -OLOGY	APPRAISALS	CRITICISMS	LITERATURE
WATERFALL METHOD	Simple to use and understand	The software is ready only after the last stage is over	Fowler (2004) Pressman (2005)
	Management simplicity thanks to its rigidity: every phase has a defined result and process review	High risks and uncertainty	Pfleeger and Atlee (2006)
	Development stages go one by one	Not the best option for complex and object oriented projects	(Vaishnavi et al, 2014)
	Perfect for the small or mid-sized projects where requirements are clear and not equivocal	Inappropriate for the long-term projects	Bassil, 2012; (Munassar and Govardhan, 2010)
	Easy to determine the key points in the development cycle	The progress of the stage is hard to measure while it is still in the development	(Munassar and Govardhan, 2011).
	Easy to classify and prioritize tasks	Integration is done at the very end, which does not give the option of identifying the problem in advance	Bennett et al. (2002)
ITERATIVE METHOD	Some functions can be quickly developed at the beginning of the development lifecycle	Iterative method requires more resources than the waterfall method	(Nabil et al, 2010) Munassar and Govardhan (2011)
	The paralleled development can be applied	Constant management is required	(Vaishnavi et al, 2014)
	The progress is easy measurable	Issues with architecture or design may occur because not all the requirements are foreseen during the short planning stage	(Sanjana and Shaveta, 2011)
	The shorter iteration is - the easier testing and debugging stages are	Bad choice for the small projects	(Ron, 2013)

	It is easier to control the risks as high-risk tasks are completed first	The process is difficult to manage	Budi et al (2016) (Soeken and Wille, 2012) Adel and Abdullah, 2015)
	Problems and risks defined within one iteration can be prevented in the next sprints	The risks may not be completely determined even at the final stage of the project	
	Flexibility and readiness to the changes in the requirements	Risks analysis requires involvement of the highly-qualified specialists	
SPIRAL METHOD	Lifecycle is divided into small parts, and if the risk concentration is higher, the phase can be finished earlier to address the treats	Can be quite expensive	(Richard, 2014) (Khan et al, 2013). (Leasu et al, 2012; Mahalakshmi and Sundararajan, 2013;)
	The development process is precisely documented yet scalable to the changes	The risk control demands involvement of the highly-skilled professionals	
	The scalability allows to make changes and add new functionality even at the relatively late stages	Can be ineffective for the small projects	
	The earlier working prototype is done - sooner users can point out the flaws	Big number of the intermediate stages requires excessive documentation	
	Project is divided by short and transparent iterations	The team should be highly professional and client-oriented	
	Risks are minimized thanks to the flexible change process	New requirements may conflict with the existing architecture	
	Fast release of the first product version	With all the corrections and changes there is possibility that the project will exceed expected time	

Within the scope of Table 2.7, critical elements for comparison, including clarity in requirement analysis, precise budget and time estimation, adaptability to changes, software criticality, development costs, complexity of projects, communication between clients and the development team, and the size of the company, are meticulously identified. The synthesis of insights from Berglund *et al.* (2018) and Gerster *et al.* (2020) reinforces the robustness of this comparative framework, providing a comprehensive understanding of the strengths and weaknesses inherent in each methodology.

Table 2.8 establishes a strategic linkage that bridges theoretical frameworks and practical considerations, fostering a deeper understanding of how the traditional Waterfall method addresses or exacerbates the sustainability challenges outlined in Figure 2.7 and Table 2.7. As depicted in Table 2.8, the waterfall method adheres strictly to a linear-sequential life cycle, offering simplicity in understanding and implementation. However, a notable drawback lies in its dependency on the successful completion of each preceding step to proceed to the subsequent stage.

Table 2. 8 Impact of Waterfall method on sustainability

TRANSFORMATION METHODOLOGY	IMPACT ON SUSTAINABILITY		LITERATURES	
WATERFALL	RISK	VISIBILITY	Long term visibility; Not transparent	Royce (2006); Farrell (2007); Hughes, Cotterell and Mall (2011); Mahadevan, Kettinger and Meservy (2015); Mostafa (2015); Hobbs and Petit (2017); Karthikeyan and Madhuchhanda (2021); Geyi et al (2020); Chen et al,(2017)
		UNCERTAINTY	Can be handled only by Change requests	
		CONTINUOUS INNOVATION	Cannot be done by Waterfall	
		COMMUNICATION	Formal communication and more process centric	
		BUDGETING ESTIMATION	Any change may involve additional cost and time	
		RESOURCES	Any uncertainty can involve additional resources; Proper management	
	STRATEGY	PLANNING	Pre-defined planning unwelcoming change during course of the project; systems are fully specifiable, predictable, and built through meticulous and extensive planning	
		REQUIREMENT GATHERING	Documentation takes more than 3 months and business sign-off requires approval	
		ROADMAPPING	Strategic roadmap is designed for long term	
		SECURITY MANAGEMENT	Properly defined security management and plan	
		SCALING UP	Cannot be done internally within a project and difficult to adapt	
		CONTINUOUS INNOVATION	Only at early stages of project implementation and therefore no learning	
	PERFORMANCE	DELIVERABLES	Deadlines set	
		CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE	Based only on customer satisfaction and not experience; Customers are important	
		CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT	Continuous improvement ex., service cannot be achieved	
		IMPLEMENTATION	Structured and rigid	
		TEAM SKILL SET	High dependency on skilled resources Command and control (Not self-organized)	
		CROSS FUNCTIONAL	Explicit knowledge management Not flexible with organizational changes	

The culmination of each step serves as a critical juncture where thorough reviewing and compliance checks take place. This emphasis on sequential progression, while providing clarity, introduces a potential bottleneck at each stage's conclusion, necessitating meticulous scrutiny before advancing to the next phase. According to Satar and John (2016), the dynamic environment predominant in the Indian startup ecosystem has impacted immensely over the processes and tools, allowing customers to directly view the output and results. Startups that have failed to accommodate this change of requirements during the process have had the hardship of selling their products successfully as the customer needs have been ignored. Moreover, the high dependency of each stage over the previous one makes it completely difficult when some issues can only be solved during later stages or need immediate attention.

In terms of resource allocation, the cost estimation is fixed and therefore, addition of any change can ultimately threaten startups that follow waterfall methods (Noshir *et al*, 2019; Singh *et al*, 2019). The development of Minimum Viable Product (MVP) has been completely ignored by the waterfall method which not only gives less visibility to the customers but also affects the risk management of allocating the best resources. Estimating the time and budget for every stage can be extremely complicated and therefore misalignment with the strategic direction can possibly occur. As waterfall methods were initially built for object-oriented projects, IT startups in India that build new software cannot work on waterfall to continuously monitor and learn through feedback. The waterfall method does not support sustainability for startups in terms of strategic sensitivity where processes and tools are prioritized rather than the interaction and communication with people (Krishnan and Prashantham, 2019). Failure to include or collaborate with the team with every stage of the process has not only demotivated team members to work but also instilled fear psychology and pressure to perform rather than learn. Given the rigidity of the waterfall method to accommodate changes, the culture and mindset of the team has been predominantly fixed and biased (Sabrina, 2019).

According to Julio and Rosaria (2018), the idea of less documentation was captured by the iterative method which starts off with minimum requirements where the complete process of building a software breaks down to iterative steps. Although the iteration of stages was considered, the rigidity of each stage was still the same which led to no overlapping of the stages which insisted on all the requirements to be known beforehand (Gerard *et al*, 2018; Philipp *et al*, 2018). As this research focuses predominantly on the Indian IT startups, their dynamism in terms of requirement gathering needs more convenient methods that could adapt to this change to ensure sustainability. The need for more skilled resources can be highly pressurizing and failing to support optimum risk management (Abdullah, 2018). Visibility with the customers has not been raised as a concern in this approach which has alienated the process from the customers (Diego *et al*, 2020). The iterative method still follows the existing principle of waterfall where focus remains within the management following a top-down approach of hierarchy which does not develop team building, learning and growth. These literatures moreover, highlight the limitations of the iterative method to support project sustainability and therefore can prove of less significance in the scope of holistic sustainability of Indian IT startups.

Spiral model can be seen as one of the major developments in the transformation literature which brought the idea of working software for the visibility of the customers which impacted the risk management where documentations and approval were controlled yet the cost remained high for smaller changes to be introduced (Dikert *et al*, 2016; Eriks *et al*, 2018). The requirement of expert resources, and extensive documentation made the approach more complicated, taking too much time to identify and evaluate risks. A larger emphasis on risk management burns out the IT companies adapting the spiral method costing them excessive time for planning, resetting and prototyping (Pedro and Jeffrey, 2015; Circullo *et al*, 2018). Despite attempts to rectify the shortcomings of previous methods like Waterfall and Spiral, other traditional approaches such as the V-shaped and parallel methods fall short in fully addressing critical concerns. These concerns include rigidity in project execution, cost-ineffectiveness, limited visibility for customers in terms of Minimum Viable Product (MVP) building, high dependency on sub-projects, integration challenges, and the inherent complexities associated with adapting to changing project dynamics (Munassar and Govardhan, 2011; Balaji and Sundararajan, 2012; Ajah and Ugah, 2013; Budi *et al.*, 2016). Consequently, it is evident that traditional methods are ill-suited for ensuring the sustainability of Indian IT startups, given the highlighted factors. The subsequent section will undertake a comprehensive examination of the agile transformation method, aiming to overcome these challenges and foster the sustainability of Indian IT startups.

2.5 AGILE TRANSFORMATION METHOD ON SUSTAINABILITY

In Section 2.4, an extensive evaluation was conducted on established/traditional transformational methodologies, encompassing the waterfall, iterative and spiral transformation methods, with a primary focus on sustainability considerations. Building upon this foundation, the current section delves into the realm of agile transformation. It not only provides a comprehensive definition of agile transformation but also conducts a meticulous assessment of agile in comparison to traditional methodologies concerning sustainability. Furthermore, this section explores the implementational challenges inherent in theoretical and practical contexts. The overarching goal is to address Research Question 3, as articulated in Chapter 1, Section 1.9, thereby contributing valuable insights into the efficacy and challenges of agile transformation in the pursuit of sustainability.

2.5.1 DEFINITION OF AGILE

Agility, as defined by Collier (2012), signifies the "ability of fast and easy movement" in the realms of rationality, performance, and decoding. Recognizing the limitations and pitfalls inherent in traditional methodologies, a groundbreaking solution emerged in the form of the agile method. This approach served as a strategic alternative to the documentation-focused and rigid nature of traditional transformational methods, as proposed by Cohen *et al.* (2004). Figure 2.11 serves as a vivid visual representation of the agile methodology, encapsulating the essence of the process where input undergoes translation into output through the software development process. The distinctive feature highlighted in the visual is the continuous feedback loop, characterized by meticulous inspection and adaptation. This iterative process ensures that each stage undergoes repeated iteration and incremental refinement, contributing to the dynamic and adaptive nature that defines agile methods.

Figure 2. 11 Agile transformation model

Source: Collier (2012)

Agile software development does not necessarily introduce new practices but recognizes people as key contributors for the success of a project, whereby the focus lies on the effectiveness and maneuverability (Reis, 2011). The development process in agile starts with the most basic set of deliverables, iterative and incremental approach performed through highly collaborative and cross-functional self-organizing teams to produce high quality, cost effectiveness and timely deliverables to meet the varying requirements of its shareholders increasing the agility of the development team (Collier, 2012; Waardenburg and Vliet, 2013; Measey, 2015). The following Sub-Section 2.5.2 will discuss the agile manifesto which lies in the heart of an agile transformation.

2.5.2 MANIFESTO: VALUES

As per Campanelli and Parreiras, (2015), notable characteristics of a business being agile are adaptive planning, timely delivery, iterative improvements, high flexibility in responding to change, willingness to learn, being lean, etc. As shown in Figure 2.12 the manifesto consists of 4 primary values suitable and appropriate for any industry wanting to be part of the agile movement emphasizing on individuals and interactions over processes and tools, working software more than comprehensive documentation, customer collaboration over contract negotiation and responding to change more than following a rigid plan (Cho, 2008; Measey, 2015).

Figure 2. 12 Agile manifesto values

Source: Adapted from Ajah and Ugah (2013)

As per Hohl *et al* (2018), agile does not completely eliminate the need for the values on the right but emphasizes that the values on the left hold much significance and relevance to producing the end product that meets customer expectations and demands (Cobb, 2011).

2.5.3 BENEFITS OF AGILE METHOD

Agile method has gained much popularity in software development companies aiming to improve their end products through a flexible and customer friendly process, resulting in higher customer satisfaction (Hussain *et al*, 2009; Lindvall *et al.*, 2002; Rodriguex *et al.*, 2009; Schlauderer and Overhage, 2013; Olszewska *et al.*, 2016). Agile transformation often gets confused with agile adoption methods as the former focuses on the wider management perspective of the company whereas the latter focuses on the processes involved. For agile to be adopted successfully, companies need to understand how agile works and the benefits it can bring to their software development process to make it reliable and relevant (Moravcová and Legeny, 2016).

Demonstrated in Figure 2.13, the advantages of agile transformation for IT companies are manifold and impactful. Industry giants like Microsoft serve as compelling examples, having embraced agile transformation to reap substantial benefits and significantly enhance their operational efficiency and outcomes. Ghani and Bello (2015), claim that agile methodologies can incorporate reliable engineering and management practices to ensure high quality and successful end products. Agile methods have proven beneficial towards addressing the need to fast track the delivery of IT products and ensuring that customers are satisfied with the quicker deliverables (Fowler and Highsmith, 2001; Williams and Cockburn, 2003). Agile methods promote team collaborations, minimize documentation, and provide early software releases while being able to respond to the rapid changes in customer requirements (Cockburn and Highsmith, 2001). Incremental management coupled with high flexibility in processes makes delivery of software easier and quicker in agile methods (Campanelli and Parreiras, 2015; Hoda and Murugesan, 2016). Dikert *et al* (2016), claims agile method to be an extremely attractive option for refining the company's performance, improving quality, productivity and increased customer satisfaction (Campanelli and Parreiras, 2015).

Figure 2. 13 Elements of Agile transformation

Source: Adapted from Ghani and Bello (2015) and Campanelli and Parreiras (2015)

Gandomani and Nafchi (2016) and Dikert *et al* (2016), propose how better team collaboration, accelerated delivery, increased Return on Investment (ROI), etc., has elevated the scope of agile methods for effective management. Customers feel more involved and valued throughout the agile process. The need for a dynamic method to respond to changing customer requirements, with less documentation and delivery products early distinguish agile methods from others (Nerur *et al*, 2005; Williams and Cockburn, 2003).

Agile projects have consistently demonstrated superior success rates compared to traditional methods, as substantiated by the compelling evidence provided by Ghani and Bello (2015) and Kamei *et al.* (2017). The subsequent section will robustly differentiate agile from non-agile methods, leveraging the critical factors delineated in Sub-Section 2.4.5, thereby shedding further light on the unparalleled effectiveness of agile methodologies in project execution.

2.5.4 DIFFERENCE BETWEEN EXISTING AND AGILE TRANSFORMATION

There are strengths and weaknesses for both traditional (non-agile) and agile methodologies, each customized for the nature of a specific project that adopts it. Balaji and Sundararajan (2012), given the feasibility and clear set of requirements prior planning, criticize non-agile traditional methodologies to be highly rigid and heavy with respect to documentation and change accommodation during the software development process. Table 2.9 effectively compares Sections 2.4.3 and 2.5.4 to bring out the differences between traditional and agile methods, wherein the methods are compared based on the notable aspects of fundamental belief, management styles, organizational structure, re-engineering cost, requirement gathering, team size, etc.

Table 2. 9 Comparison between traditional and Agile transformation

ASPECT	TRADITIONAL TRANSFORMATION	AGILE TRANSFORMATION
Fundamental belief	Systems are fully specifiable, predictable and are developed through extended and detailed planning	High quality adaptive software is developed by small teams that use the principle of continuous improvement of design and testing based on fast feedback and change
Management styles	Command and control	Leadership and collaboration
Knowledge management	Explicit	Tacit
Communication	Formal	Informal
Development model	Life cycle model (waterfall, spiral or modified models)	Evolutionary-delivery model
Organizational structure	Mechanic (bureaucratic, high formalization), targeting large organization	Organic (flexible and participative, encourages social cooperation), targeting small and medium organizations
Quality control	Difficult planning and strict control. Difficult and late testing	Permanent control or requirements, design, and solutions. Permanent testing
User requirements	Detailed and defined before coding/implementation	Interactive input
Re-engineering cost	High	Low
Development direction	Fixed	Easily changeable
Testing	After coding is completed	Every iteration

Client involvement	Low	High
Additional abilities required from developers	Nothing in particular	Interpersonal abilities and basic knowledge of the business
Scaling of the project	Large scale	Low and medium scale
Developers	Oriented on plan, with adequate abilities, access to external knowledge	Agile, with advanced knowledge, co-located and cooperative
Clients	With access to knowledge, cooperative, representative, and empowered	Dedicated, knowledgeable, cooperative, representative, and empowered
Requirement gathering	Very stable, known in advance	Emergent, with rapid changes
Architecture	Design for current and predictable requirements	Design for current requirements
Remodeling	Expensive	Not expensive
Team size	Large teams and projects	Small teams and projects
Primary objective	High safety	Quick value

Source: Adapted from Balaji and Sundararajan (2012) Stoica *et al* (2013) and Dikert *et al* (2016)

As shown in Table 2.9, traditional methods with substantial risk and uncertainty deprive them of their suitability for complicated or object-oriented projects but prove best for small sized projects. Agile method proves its ability to adapt through face-to-face communication yet agile demands technical skilled and cross-functional employees (Balaji and Sundararajan, 2012; Stoica *et al*, 2013; Dikert *et al*, 2016). As briefed in Sub-Section 2.2.5, multiple factors have been accumulated to reason out the high failure rate of startups within 5 years, significant of which can be the failure to anticipate change and immediate response, although inadequate funds, lack of resources, etc., are common to all. Implementing agile can aid in strategic planning, ideal software development and timely delivery of end products, also boosting the performance of the management and the team for long-term growth (Ahimbisibwe *et al*, 2017). Gopaldas (2018), through a survey explains how 6 projects out of 30 require more agile based methods and implementation. Most researchers and authors have kept agile principles and values as the basis to build tailored agile models such as, distributed scrum (Duc and Abrahamsson, 2016), XP (Coleman and Connor, 2006; Sverrisdottir *et al*, 2014), hyper-agility (Marion *et al*, 2012), iterative and incremental (Sánchez *et al*, 2015), and tailored agile (Duc and Abrahamsson, 2016) which have become operational within MNCs. Primary studies mentioned that startups adopt agile development method as in a general category (Björk *et al*, 2019; Kuhrmann *et al*, 2017; Hijazi *et al*, 2012; Sánchez and Connor, 2016; Taylor *et al*, 2008).

Agile methods can be highly suitable for IT startups given the shorter life cycle, smaller team size, easy management, minimal hierarchies and organizational structure, etc., as discussed in Sub-Section 1.3.1 (Hijazi *et al*, 2012; Sánchez-Gordón and O'Connor, 2016; Kuhrmann *et al*, 2017). With prompt delivery through MVPs and continuous improvement through collaboration, agile promises better customer relationships and higher satisfaction levels (Taylor *et al*, 2008). According to Yazici (2020), agile allows flexibility within the requirement gathering process by building self-organized and cross-functional teams, working closely with the customers. Adaptive planning, as one of the key factors of agile transformation enables positive response to change management by continuously improving the development process (Björk *et al*, 2019). Kuhrmann *et al* (2017), argues that startups have gradually been attracted by agile methods with the short delivery cycles, internal flexibility and strategic alignment with business goals to promote process management. According to Taylor *et al* (2008), startups can moreover build efficient teams by constantly measuring and learning modern technologies and skills through agile methods, satisfying both the team and the customers, committing to flexibility and faster delivery.

Traditional methods fail to embrace change during the process which proves unsuitable for IT startups in India. The iterative development and incremental management distinguish agile from traditional methods, allowing development to follow the startups' business strategy. As opposed to command control style of management in traditional methods, the agile method inculcates leadership and collaboration (Giardino *et al*, 2014; Duc and Abrahamsson, 2016). Encouraging self-organization, alignment of short-term goals with the big picture and cross-functional team communication proves agile as a great collaborative transformation method which has been completely overlooked by traditional methods (Moran, 2015). Agile teams can approach a new project through stages adopting continuous iteration and improvement rather than negotiations and contracts (Pedro and Jeffrey, 2015). The organic organizational structure of agile method proves highly suitable for small and medium companies (Nomi, 2015). The agile method, when employed in startup environments, has demonstrated a remarkable capacity to significantly reduce re-engineering costs. Unlike traditional methods, as emphasized by Marion *et al*. (2012) and Vinay and Saleeshya (2019), agile incorporates testing in every iteration, enabling early and continuous testing of deliverables. This approach facilitates the provision of a working software to customers for swift feedback.

Furthermore, the inherent suitability of the agile method for smaller teams and projects, in contrast to traditional methodologies, underscores its potential to offer substantial benefits for Indian IT startups. This assertion is supported by insights from Santiago and Emre (2017) and Tam *et al.* (2020), highlighting the immense advantages that Indian IT startups can harness through the adoption of agile methodologies.

2.5.5 AGILE TRANSFORMATION METHOD ON SUSTAINABILITY

2.5.5.1 ENHANCED STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT

Rand and Eckfeldt (2004), claimed that projects fail to effectively contribute to overall company success because the strategic planning process does not align with the vision and mission of the company to take complete advantage of flexibility and adaptability. Defining client requirements has been the major challenge for any method, given changes, time, cost, quality, etc., and agile arguably provides higher adaptability and flexibility to cope with today's dynamic projects through effective collaboration with stakeholders (Leasu *et al.*, 2012). According to PwC (2017) reports, 60-80% in 2018 from just 1% in 2000 of businesses employ agile method.

Figure 2. 14 Agile enhanced strategic planning

Source: Adapted from John (2017)

Figure 2.14 compellingly illustrates that agile transformation, as opposed to the waterfall method, markedly elevates regression analysis. The effort vs time graph for documentation phase in software development accounts to the distinctive advantage that lies in the agile framework's exceptional flexibility, enabling a robust capacity to retrospectively examine and analyze previous stages. This heightened adaptability, as outlined by Balaji and Sundararajan (2012), positions agile transformation as a more dynamic and insightful approach compared to the rigid waterfall method.

Waterfall method's failure to adapt and iterate to changes has been considered the key for agile transformation and ensure smooth transition from traditional practices (Marian *et al*, 2016). Carsten *et al* (2020), argues that there exists a strong relationship between agile capabilities and emerging strategies within the company where the more agility, the more enhanced the strategic planning becomes. Agile takes a different approach towards quality and testing wherein it overcomes the segregation of stages as in waterfall by doing testing in parallel iteration, which makes working deliverable at each stage feasible (Rajesh, 2015). Retrospection and re-planning are arguable characteristics of agile which aims to deliver high value to clients. Rather fixing requirements through set of processes, agile bases on iterative evolvment of product more than development (Balaji and Sundararajan, 2012; Daneva *et al*, 2013).

2.5.5.2 IMPROVED OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY

Adopting agile methods can increase productivity by simplifying the development process, whereby speed and time of delivery are enhanced without compromise in quality (Stare, 2014). As per Fagerholm *et al* (2015), agile across industries has facilitated productivity by emphasizing process innovation. While agile and iterative methodologies arose in response to the shortcomings of sequential approaches, it's crucial to highlight the distinctiveness between them. Agile, in distinct contrast to iterative methods, advocates for the incremental delivery of portions of the project at each stage, thereby reducing costs akin to the efficiency seen in lean methodologies (Santos *et al.*, 2013; Kate and Robin, 2018).

Figure 2. 15 Agile transformation and operational efficiency

Source: Adapted from Pedro and Jeffrey (2015)

In complete contrast to traditional methodologies, the agile method places a robust emphasis on active communication with both clients and the development team, involving them right from the inception of the development process. This approach, featuring requirement analysis through stories instead of extensive documentation, aligns clients' objectives with the company's overarching goals. Illustrated in Figure 2.15, while adhering to fixed time and cost constraints, agile methodology ensures a steadfast commitment to quality, thereby creating space for the incorporation of additional features or functionalities in the deliverables. This commitment to quality and flexibility, as underscored by Pedro and Jeffrey (2015), exemplifies the distinct advantages offered by agile methodologies in comparison to traditional methods.

Agile transformation provides flexibility of hybrid methodologies where one or more agile methods can be employed. As per John (2017), Kanban ensures effectiveness, Lean defines development principles, Scrum improves planning, and XP the operations. According to Winter (2015), agile performance improvement measures can leverage methods and practices to ensure that the customer value gets optimized, and a collaborative learning environment gets developed. Malik *et al* (2021), argues that team autonomy, team capability, psychological empowerment, innovative behavior, agile communication, etc., can be critical factors in determining the success of agile transformation and its impact over performance.

2.5.5.3 EFFECTIVE RISK MANAGEMENT

Agile method combining concepts of appraised and criticized methodologies open wider perspectives to modern literatures for risk management where many practitioners and successful companies have admitted agile to be suitable for most environments and addressing uncertainties. Figure 2.16, as adapted from Standish Group (2016), strongly illustrates the contrast in graphs, emphasizing the tangible benefits of agile methodologies. This visual representation highlights the increased visibility, exponential growth in business value, and heightened adaptability, collectively contributing to a substantial reduction in overall project risk, serving as a compelling visual testament to the transformative impact that agile methodologies can have on project outcomes. By focusing on result rather than process, agile often eliminates mismatches between expected deliverable and that developed, which largely reduces time wastage and improves risk mitigation (Giannakis and Papadopoulos, 2016).

Figure 2. 16 Agile value proposition

Source: Adaptation of Standish Group (2016)

According to Mamaghani and Medini (2021), resilience, agility and risk management have strong relationships with each other and directly increase the ability of companies to handle changes effectively. In contradiction to traditional methodologies, agile allows room for unstable requirements, and unknown risks, which makes agile scrum masters or project managers as facilitators of risk management rather relying on external sources (Iosif *et al*, 2016). As per Standish Group (2016) Reports, the chaos resolution of failure rate of waterfall vs agile from year 2011-2015 shows that agile has 39% more success rate for all size projects. As shown in Table 2.10, complexity of projects, keeping testing to the very end, inability to accommodate change in requirements, considering time and cost as variables, conflicting goals or unresponsive clients can be considered as risks which have been the major cause for downfall of traditional methodologies and agile overcomes these issues (Gaurav and Pradeep, 2012). Mamaghani and Medini (2021), propose the correlation between the environment, resilience, risk and agility and exclaims the need to address the complexity and uncertainty underlying it holistically.

Table 2.8 meticulously outlined the influence of the traditional waterfall method on the sustainability of IT startups. In tandem with this, Table 2.10, correlated with Figure 2.7, comprehensively delineates the impact of the agile method on the sustainability of IT startups. A comparative analysis of these two tables serves as a potent tool for gaining in-depth understanding of the efficacy of these methods in addressing the identified sustainability factors outlined in Section 2.3. This comparative insight forms a crucial foundation for making informed decisions regarding the adoption of transformational methodologies in the context of Indian IT startup sustainability.

As presented in Table 2.10, the dynamic development of startup ecosystem has stimulated startup founders and managers to get software delivered on time, set clear objectives that change during project implementation and therefore managing risk, strategy and performance can be crucial for a startup sustainability to be developed, and the need for agile methods (Kaufmann *et al*, 2020).

Table 2. 10 Impacts of Agile transformation on sustainability

TRANSFORMATION METHOD-LOGY	IMPACT ON SUSTAINABILITY			LITERATURES
AGILE	RISK	VISIBILITY	High visibility; High transparency	Sven and Sebastian (2012); Mali and Ananth (2012); Jeff and Matt (2013); Mario (2014); Georgios (2015); Pedro and Jeffrey (2015); Nomi (2015); Henry et al (2016); Dag et al (2016); Marcio (2018); Philipp et al (2018); Abdullah (2018); Linda (2019); Sabrina (2019); Woogan and Seok-Won (2019); Mairon (2019); Martin et al (2019); Tom (2019); Fabio and Masaaki (2019); Victor and Joakim (2019); Dean and Marc (2020); Diego et al (2020); KMPG (2020); CIO (2020)
		UNCERTAINTY	Can be handled and adopted at any sprint;	
		CONTINUOUS INNOVATION	Mandated in Agile	
		COMMUNICATION	Informal communication and more people oriented	
		BUDGETTING ESTIMATION	Cost and time are not constraints as they can be backlogged	
		RESOURCES	No need of additional resources	
	STRATEGY	PLANNING	Continuous planning welcoming change during course of the project; systems are high quality; Adaptive software; Continuous design improvement; Feedback change	
		REQUIREMENT GATHERING	Very minimal documentation needed saving time	
		ROADMAPPING	Strategic roadmap is designed for short term	
		SECURITY MANAGEMENT	Security plan needs to be built in parallel with project; Unstable at early stages	
		SCALING UP	Can be done internally within a project and easily adapted	
		CONTINUOUS INNOVATION	At every stage of project implementation and therefore continuous learning	
	PERFORMANCE	DELIVERABLES	Continuous working deliverable at regular intervals; No timeline	
		CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE	Based on customer experience and not satisfaction; Customers are crucial	
		CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT	Continuous improvement ex., change in attributes or functionality can be achieved	
		IMPLEMENTATION	Semi-structured; Not process oriented; Highly flexible	
		TEAM SKILLSET	Encouraging learning and development; Leadership and Collaboration (Self-organized); Minimum dependency	
		CROSS FUNCTIONAL	Tacit knowledge management Highly flexible with organizational changes	

2.5.6 IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES: THEORY VS PRACTICE

The challenges inherent in the agile method become particularly pronounced when there is undue emphasis on the timely delivery of the end product at the expense of thorough requirement gathering and information acquisition. Furthermore, a shift towards a predominant focus on agile ceremonies and tools over and above customer expectations and satisfaction, as stipulated in the agile manifesto (Ghani *et al.*, 2015), can further exacerbate the complexities associated with agile methodologies. According to Hoda *et al* (2010) and Sharma *et al* (2012), the high dependency on customers can also negatively result in unprecedented development of product features, out-of-track progress and unaccomplished goals if the customers are not clear with their expectations. Agile methods advocating limited documentation of requirements pose a threat to future developers and management, when losing track of changes implemented within the software development, because of continuous increments of changes (Kamei *et al*, 2017).

Table 2. 11 Implementation challenges of Agile transformation

AGILE SUCCESS FACTORS	THEORETICAL FACTORS	PRACTICAL FACTORS	ACADEMIC LITERATURE
Quality Scope Time Cost	Organizational	Management commitment Organizational Environment Team Environment	Chow and Cao, 2008; Sharma and Sarkar, 2012; Olszewska <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Kamei <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Alsahli <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Paternoster, 2014; Ghani <i>et al.</i> , 2015
	People	Team Capacity Customer Improvement Customer Involvement	
	Process	Project Management Process Project Definition Process	
	Technical	Agile Software Techniques Delivery Strategy	
	Project	Project Nature Project Type Project Schedule	

Source: Adaptation of Chow and Cao (2008) and Sharma *et al* (2012)

Chow and Cao (2008), along with Sharma *et al.* (2012), have proposed a comprehensive measure of agile success, encompassing organizational, employee, process, technology, and project success. Table 2.11 strategically adapts these success factors to gauge agile performance in terms of quality, scope, time management, and cost efficiency, and highlights some notable practical success factors such as management commitment, organization environment, team capacity, customer involvement, project management process, agile software techniques, nature of the project, etc. (Paternoster, 2014; Kamei *et al.*, 2017).

The significance of this table lies in its pivotal role in the critical evaluation of existing agile frameworks and the formulation of new framework in this research. The emphasis on practical factors within this table addresses crucial concerns, underscoring its importance in refining and advancing agile methodologies for optimal project outcomes and overall sustainability. Despite the success, agile methods can be highly time consuming on the developer end given the accommodation of every change to align with customer expectations which eventually can burn them out (Olszewska *et al.*, 2016; Kamei *et al.*, 2017). The first sprint or cycle can always be a challenge given the minimum planning and inability to deliver early and on top of this, accepting numerable iterations can eventually waste resources (Alsahli *et al.*, 2017). The ability of the management and development team to understand customer expectations and develop purposeful software can directly impact success of agile methods (Olszewska *et al.*, 2016; Alsahli *et al.*, 2017).

Research on the customer's perspective of agile transformation remains scarce which can be influential in determining the need for agile in the first place (Schlauderer and Overhage, 2013). Hyder and Lussier (2016), that collaborative agile environment that brings customers and the developers together can impact effective requirement gathering and accommodation of changes, yet the difficulties of actual collaborative practices and tasks can be strenuous and therefore result in ineffective engineering processes (Benmoussa *et al.*, 2015). Another concern is that companies focus more on delivering working software to merely satisfy customers and meet expectations just-in-time yet fail to achieve competitive advantage for customers with respect to usability where agile by itself cannot address usability of software (Jurca *et al.*, 2014). The sole purpose of delivering user-friendly and customer-oriented products has been often neglected by agile companies, failing to assist them to be effective in process (Alsahli *et al.*, 2017).

Multiple literature has researched on the benefits of agile transformation yet very few have focused on the adoption challenges and reality of agile implementation. According to Hussain *et al.* (2009) and Moravcová and Legény (2016), an agile company struggles drastically during the implementation phase where agile knowledge and tools gets poorly communicated within the team and friction between agile practitioners and developers focus more on ceremonies rather than perceiving what practically works for them. Although agile methods have improved product usability and customer satisfactory designs, less focus has been given to continuous learning and adaptation where the management accomplishes a project and leaves abruptly (Alsahli *et al.*, 2017).

Another challenge can be the transition from traditional methodologies to agile methods, whereby agile gets treated as an alternative to waterfall rather than understanding the actual necessity for agile practices and ceremonies (Ghani *et al*, 2015; Kuhrmann *et al*, 2017).

However, agile methods cannot be the ultimate solution for all customer problems but allow flexibility to managers and developers to tailor their practices and agility levels to fit into the scenario of startup context. Paternoster (2014), Olszewska *et al* (2016) and Malik *et al* (2021), argue that although agile compared to traditional methods addresses uncertainty and faster delivery time to a larger extent, there could be certain agile practices that can waste time and resources, and moreover, prove to be meaningless.

Table 2. 12 Common misconceptions of agile methods

MYTHS/MISCONCEPTIONS/CHALLENGES	LITERATURE
Agile means Scrum	Linda (2019); Sabrina (2019); Woogan and Seok-Won (2019); Mairon (2019); Martin et al (2019); Tom (2019); Fabio and Masaaki (2019); Victor and Joakim (2019); Dean and Marc (2020); Diego et al (2020); KMPG (2020); CIO (2020)
Agile means to not have a plan and documentation	
Claiming to be Agile while merely following Agile practices	
Agile is a silver bullet	
Only for developers and software engineers not managers	
Agile as an alternate to Waterfall rather finding the actual need	
Agile is a project management/software development method	
Agile as operational and tactical, rather than strategic (Not sustainable)	
Agile is transformation of tools and practices rather culture and mindset	
Agile projects fail to give budget estimates	
No re-planning needed for product backlogs	
Management in Waterfall and process in Agile	
Agile projects do not scale	

In recent studies, researchers such as Linda (2019), Sabrina (2019), Fabio and Masaaki (2019), and Diego *et al*. (2020) have diligently identified the misconceptions and myths surrounding agile philosophy and concepts, for example, “agile means scrum”, “agile means to not have a plan and documentation”, etc. Table 2.12 serves as a comprehensive compilation of these misconceptions from diverse literature sources. This table emerges as a valuable resource for addressing agile implementation challenges and gaining insights into the perspectives of Indian IT startup managers, aligning with the research objective articulated in Chapter 1. The common misconceptions highlighted in this table will undergo further scrutiny through the findings discussed in Chapter 4, Section 4.5. The subsequent Section 2.6 is designed to highlight literature gaps within the research scope.

2.6 LITERATURE GAP EVALUATION

The literature review encapsulated in Chapter 2, spanning Sections 2.2 to 2.5, unveils five crucial themes that collectively form the foundation of understanding the intricacies within the realm of Indian IT startup sustainability. Firstly, a profound exploration remains in the conceptualization of sustainability tailored to the specific context of Indian IT startups, dissecting the influential factors shaping this paradigm. Secondly, the evaluation of traditional or non-agile transformation methods delves into their efficacy and impact on the sustainability of startups. Thirdly, the examination of agile transformation methods offers a discerning analysis of both advantages and challenges in fostering startup sustainability. Concurrently, the scrutiny of implementation challenges surrounding agile methodologies unfolds a comprehensive view of agile in theory versus agile in practice. Finally, a compelling rationale emerges for the development of a new framework, shedding light on identified gaps in existing methodologies and paving the way for a groundbreaking contribution to the literature on Indian IT startup sustainability.

Conceptualizing sustainability for a specific context and industry has been the debate of recent years where businesses are aligning their strategic vision and goals towards sustainability and sustainable development. To achieve this research's objectives, a deeper insight and relevant conceptualization of sustainability in the context of Indian IT startups is integral. Ensuring long-term profitability and gaining a competitive edge through sustainability practices has been a focal point for over a decade, particularly in the context of IT multinational corporations. However, existing research predominantly conducted outside of India, excluding startups, limits its applicability to a developing country like India. Acknowledging the distinct cultural, mindset, and skilled workforce differences, this research takes a contrasting approach. Unlike Geyi *et al* (2020) and Dean and Marc (2020), it focuses on the established agile transformation for sustainability tailored specifically for Indian IT startups. Aligning with the insights of Bolis *et al* (2014), Dyllick and Muff (2016), and Enu-Kwesi (2018), this research underscores the importance of sustainability, emphasizing factors such as profitability, long-term growth, skilled workforce development, strategic alignment, competitive advantage, and a safe environment. Noteworthy is the lack of similar studies exploring sustainability factors with a focus on the opinions and perspectives of Indian startup founders and managers. Contrary to Western-centric researchers, this research addresses this gap.

Section 2.2.1 identified a strong correlation between project sustainability and overall startup sustainability and further Section 2.3.4 depicted risk, strategy and performance management disciplines of startups to be inter-linked to the choice of transformation SDLC method. Industry reports from IBEF (2019), KPMG (2019), NASSCOM (2019), Statista (2019), Forbes (2019), CB Insights (2019), and Failory (2020) as reviewed in Section 2.2.4, collectively identify sustainability challenges ranging from neglected customers, unwelcomed products, and lack of innovation to failed business models, inadequate customer visibility, strategic misalignment, unproductive culture, traditional mindsets, intense competition, untimely deliverables, and ineffective planning. These challenges, contributing to a 63% failure rate, underscore the critical need for a nuanced and context-specific approach to sustainability for Indian IT startups. This contributes to the identification and categorization of factors that affect the sustainability of Indian IT startups.

The divergence in attitudes and interpretations of the same concept across different parts of the world is evident, emphasizing the need to recognize regional nuances in research findings. Extensive exploration of the agile transformation phenomenon in comparison to traditional methodologies such as waterfall, iterative, and spiral methods has been undertaken in various literature sources (Naumann *et al*, 2011; Munassar and Govardhan, 2011; Bassil, 2012; Balaji and Sundararajan, 2012; Vaishnavi *et al*, 2014; Adel and Abdullah, 2015). However, a critical literature gap remains unaddressed which is the correlation between project success and overall sustainability, as underscored in Section 2.3.

Despite substantial contributions from Collier (2012), Measey (2015), Ghani and Bello (2015), Marshal *et al* (2015), Dikert *et al* (2016), and Lappi *et al* (2018) towards agile transformation literature, existing gaps persist in understanding the practical application of agile principles and specific elements impacting sustainability. This further raises questions about the persistently high failure rate of Indian IT startups, a concern explored by Paternoster (2014), Ghani *et al* (2015), Kamei *et al* (2017), and Alsahli *et al* (2017). Addressing these gaps is imperative for a more comprehensive understanding of the intricate dynamics influencing the sustainability of Indian IT startups in the context of agile transformation.

As highlighted by Althonayan (2003), the application of the Four-Quadrant framework as shown in Table 2.13 provides a systematic categorization of literature based on their source (academic or industry), purpose (visionary or implementation), and results (descriptive or prescriptive).

This framework has been instrumental in conducting a meticulous evaluation of all preceding literature within the realm of agile transformation and sustainability, spanning Sections 2.2 to 2.5. Visionary-centered literature offers detailed descriptions of phenomena, while implementation-focused literature provides practical suggestions and guidelines, often with a prescriptive nature. Table 2.13 effectively captures the combinations of visionary or implementation with descriptive or prescriptive writing across each quadrant, laying the groundwork for identifying literature gaps in this research.

Table 2. 13 Literature evaluation framework

		RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY	
		VISIONARY	IMPLEMENTATIONAL
RESEARCH QUESTIONS	DESCRIPTIVE	QUADRANT 1	QUADRANT 2
		<p>Describes Agile definitions and discusses the links to sustainability factors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theoretical alignment of transformation methodology with key sustainability areas may be discussed Some form of conceptual framework developed Agile startups implementation process unlikely to be discussed Research based on theoretical assumptions supported by literatures 	<p>Describes the Agile implementation process providing practical guidelines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation issues of transformational methodologies described and literatures may be discussed and reviewed Theoretical Agile framework may be defined and discussed General Agile implementation guidelines and discussions may be considered Research describes empirical examples of Agile implementation based on existing literature
	PRESCRIPTIVE	QUADRANT 3	QUADRANT 4
		<p>Provides prescriptive Agile approach and discusses the links to organizational factors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Factors affecting sustainability of startups with prescriptive guidance Theoretical Agile adoption and challenges discussed prescriptively Theoretical Agile sustainability framework exploring nature of Agile Present a basic vision towards Agile sustainability implementation process 	<p>Provides prescriptive Agile approach and discusses the implementation process</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Factors affecting sustainability of startups with implementation guidance Agile adoption and challenges may be discussed as part of implementation Agile implementation steps, challenges and practical recommendations may be discussed Benefits of Agile implementation discussed on empirical data (risk, strategy & performance)

Source: Adapted from Althonayan (2003)

The ability to highlight literature gaps and shortcomings by categorizing them into the mentioned themes can be seen as the core benefit of this four-quadrant framework. Upon critical evaluation, it becomes evident that previous literatures predominantly concentrated on exploring the enablers and influencers of agile transformation, neglecting the crucial aspect of pre-requisites and its actual implementation and the ensuing positive and negative impacts on startups in India. This oversight is addressed by researchers such as Gandomani *et al* (2013) and Khalil and Khalil (2016), who assert that agile transformation in the IT startup industry demands a startup-specific approach.

This necessitates a tailored focus on training, team-centered goals, and iterative methodologies that align with the dynamic nature of startups. In emphasizing the significance of agile transformation, Fry and Greene (2007) underscore core factors including objectives, scope, prerequisites, resources, infrastructure, and scale. They caution against adopting agile methodologies solely for cost reduction and time savings, urging a more strategic and contextual consideration of agile transformation within the startup ecosystem. This critical perspective challenges conventional notions and emphasizes the need for a nuanced and customized approach to agile implementation, recognizing its inherent complexities and potential impact on the multifaceted landscape of startups in India. This research aims to address this literature gap by developing a conceptual framework that overcomes these limitations, emphasizing on room for startup-specific customization, linking management disciplines with organization agility, recognizing key pre-requisites for successful agile transformation and engraving intangible aspects of agile startup transformation. This contributes immensely to the literature of agile transformation and startup sustainability.

One of the main literature findings of this research centers on the pivotal roles played by organizational culture and adoption practices in shaping the dynamics of agile transformation within the context of Indian IT startups. Change resistance, misalignment between goals and strategy, adoption mismatches and failures, inappropriate methods can be deciding factors for evaluation of transformation methodologies (Santiago and Emre, 2017; Sabrina, 2019; Geyi *et al*, 2020). The research literature grouped in the fourth quadrant as shown in Table 2.13 tends to be scarce and more evolving in nature which compiles the work of Tam *et al* (2020), John (2017), Geyi *et al* (2020) and Raeh and Mohamad (2020). The former two researchers focus on the Indian IT startup industry and the cultural barrier that decelerates the growth of startups and the latter two focus on the study of the relationship between agility and sustainability to overcome these barriers. Yet the scarcity of prescriptive and implementational literature is one of the major literature gaps. The ultimate contribution of this research is the creation of a groundbreaking agile startup sustainability framework, pushing the boundaries beyond conventional project sustainability to encompass the holistic startup sustainability. Diverging from the norm observed in most Quadrant 4 research papers, this research not only conceptualizes but also delivers tangible implementation guidance, guaranteeing the effective application of the developed framework.

This distinctive approach sets a new standard, promising an extraordinary impact on the literature of agile transformation and startup sustainability, marking a monumental leap forward in advancing the discourse within the field.

Further, the focus on agile adoption practices amidst elevated level of uncertainty, viable solutions and recommendations for overcoming cultural barriers, optimum performance through agile transformation by reducing delivery time, multiple iterations to deliver a working model, etc., have been the core findings of these literatures in the fourth quadrant (Geyi *et al*, 2020). The scarcity of literatures in this fourth quadrant reveals the scope and impact this research can have in the academic field of agile transformation and sustainability as this prolongs to be the untapped relationships for the Indian IT startups as shown in Appendix 4.

While some researchers have started exploring the intersection of agility and sustainability, a critical examination reveals a scarcity of studies delving deeper into their nuanced impacts or developing frameworks tailored specifically for startups in India. This conspicuous literature gap serves as a fertile ground for deriving a conceptual framework, poised to make substantial contributions to both the academic community and industrial practitioners. Table 2.14 systematically delineates these literature gaps by scrutinizing academic and industrial research conducted over the last decade (2010-present). It illuminates key trends related to sustainability, framework components, and adoption challenges in the context of agile transformation. This comprehensive analysis sets the stage for addressing unexplored areas and advancing the understanding of agility and sustainability in the specific context of Indian startups.

The Indian IT startups have still not successfully captured the idea of agile transformation and sustainability, as startup founder, entrepreneurs and managers have no clear understanding of it or have misconceptions about it (Ghani *et al.*, 2015; Kamei *et al*, 2017; Alsahli *et al*, 2017). As this research proposes the scope of agility to improve sustainability in three management disciplines, targeted sustainability elements will be included in the framework to be developed. As this research is first of its kind in India, the researcher therefore implements constructive approach to explore and deeply understand the perception of startups. Moreover, the use of quantitative or mixed approached from previous researchers have not provided the holistic picture of agility and sustainability and therefore qualitative approach has been considered to identify implementation and adoption challenges of agile transformation, all within the context of Indian IT startups.

Table 2. 14 Research literature gaps (2012 - Present)

RESEARCH LITERATURE GAP (2012 - Present)			
AREA	LITERATURE GAP	RESEARCHER (YEAR) – ACADEMIC	RESEARCHER (YEAR) – INDUSTRY
Evolution & Significance of Sustainability	Silo sustainability management mentality and maturity practices	Lindsey (2011) Gray and Milne (2013) Bolis et al (2014) Thomas (2015) Ilka (2016) Sania et al (2016) Santisteban and David (2017) Marcio (2018) Mensah and Enu-Kwesi (2018) Victor (2019) Vinit and Joakim (2019)	GEM (2018) IBEF (2019) NASSCOM (2018) Autopsy (2019) Failory (2020) Forbes (2019) Statista (2019)
	Weak understanding of how to custom-define sustainability for an Indian IT startup		
	Management's failure to foresee future risks		
	Pursuing sustainability as just another management segment rather an embedment to the startup management		
	Lack of good understanding of key factors contributing to sustainability and its importance in Indian startups		
Risk & Sustainability	Failure to identify potential and relevant risks to sustainability	Silvius et al (2012) Winnall (2013) Evers et al (2014) Serrador and Pinto (2015) Hill (2016)	Office of Government Commerce (2010) Project Management Institute (2013) Office of Government commerce (2010) Project Management Institute (2013) IBEF (2019) KPMG (2019)
	Lack of compliance governance leading to risks	Dyer et al (2018) Govardhan and Jeyakumaran (2018) Martijn et al (2019) Tom (2019)	
	Failure to identify and capitalize resources available		
	Ignorance of resource and capability building		
	Wasting time building unproductive software leading to compromised quality & low customer retention		
Strategy & Sustainability	Lack of empirical planning & incorporation of internal & external risks in strategies	Crittenden et al (2011) Bocken et al (2014) Boons and Lüdeke-Freund (2013) Lozano (2012) Schaltegger et al (2013) Hahn and Kühnen (2013) Orsato et al (2015) Sushil (2017) Biloslavo et al (2018) Dinesh and Sushil (2019)	Capasso et al (2015) Iwasiuk (2016) Kaur (2017) Panditta (2017) Yurum et al (2018) IBEF (2019) KPMG (2019) Abirami et al (2021)
	Lack of effective requirement		
	Poor understanding of significance of aligning Agile processes with strategic objectives & vision		
	Failure to identify the actual need of the moment before scaling		
	Lack of continuous learning from every project to develop unique & profitable business model		
Performance & Sustainability	Ineffective management to identify and minimize excessive costs	Bansal and Roth (2000) Bos-Brouwers (2010) Garnåsjordet et al (2012) Warner and Zheng (2013) Sandvik et al (2014) Parsa et al (2015) Yngve et al (2016) Morioka and Carvalho (2016) Paulraj et al (2017) Ahimbisibwe et al (2017) Due and Abrahamson (2018) El-Khalil and Mezher (2020)	Standish group (2016) NASSCOM (2018) Daniel and Fabio (2018) Autopsy (2019) Forbes (2019) CB Insights (2019) Endrik et al (2019)
	Closed mindset and distrust within employees leading to unproductive culture		
	Lack of continuous learning and innovation		
	Lack of customer experience & retention		
	Inadequate cross functional skill-set in the boardroom		
	Lack of awareness of sustainability		

	Lack of a robust corporate governance aligned with the sustainability		
Transformation method (process & frameworks)	Lack of understanding of factors influencing the choice of any method	Collier (2011) Cocco et al (2011) Waardenburg and Vliet (2013)	Capodiecici et al (2014) Standish Group (2009) Misra et al (2012)
	Lack of a fully dynamic and holistic sustainable transformation method framework for startup	Measey (2015) Olszewska et al (2016) Oktay et al (2016)	Sahil et al (2017) Eriks et al (2018) Cesa et al (2019)
	Opportunities in effective software development practices	Micic (2017); Esubalew (2018)	Abrahamsson et al (2017)
	Overlooking the change of internal and external environment	Antonio and Angelo (2018) Linda (2019)	
	Inconsistent method standards, controls, and procedures	Subbarao (2014) Lonkar and Gupte (2017) Berglund et al (2018)	
	Inability to aggregate risk, strategy, and performance into method	Dean (2020)	
Transformation method (existing) & sustainability	Lack of visibility & transparency within & outside organization	Mahaux et al (2011) Stefan et al (2011); Gu et al (2012)	Chronis and Gren (2016) Senapathi and Drury-Grogan (2017)
	Ignorance of startup instabilities while developing framework	Coral et al (2011); Lacy (2012) Penzenstadler et al (2013)	Holvitie et al (2018) Noshir et al (2019)
	Confusion as to the need & degree of a new transformation to solve problems	Calcro et al (2013) Mario (2014); Georgios (2015) Nomi (2015)	Singh et al (2019) Krishnan and Prashantham (2019)
	Dismissing the importance of agility rather than focusing on rigidity	Santiago and Emre (2017) Parita et al (2018) Esubalew (2018); Mairon (2019)	
	Lack of focus on people management & skill development		
Agile transformation & sustainability	Lack of understanding of relationship between agility & sustainability	Sven and Sebastian (2012) Blome et al (2013) Marshall et al (2015)	Bhatti and Tabassum (2017) Paez et al (2018) Martin and Alon (2019)
	Lack of understanding of how to integrate Agile into existing organizational sustainability practices	Pedro and Jeffrey (2015) Dikert et al (2016) Chen et al (2017) Ciccullo et al (2018)	Gaida and Miler (2019) Forbes (2019) Statista (2019) Pantiuchina et al (2020)
	Lack of sustainability mitigation & measurement during Agile startup transformation	Philipp et al (2018) Gerard et al (2018) Lappi et al (2018) Abdullah (2018)	Jonas et al (2021) 15 th state of Agile report (2021)
	Lack of commitment from top management towards flexible organization	Julio and Rosaria (2018) Ochoa-Zambrano (2021)	
	Insufficient knowledge on how to avoid common Agile misconceptions		
Agile adoption & challenges	Lack of Agile mindset	Mali and Ananth (2012) Jeff and Matt (2013)	Doyle et al (2014) Noshir et al (2019)
	Failure to relate Agile implementation & sustainability	Xiaofeng et al (2016) Kim et al (2016) Antonio and Angelo (2018)	Dutta et al (2020) Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020) El-Khalil and Mezher (2020)
	Resistance to change – lack of willingness	Sabrina (2019) Fabio and Masaakik (2019)	
	Agile -scrum bias limiting value-driven startup	Dean and Marc (2020) Diego et al (2020)	
	Division between academics & practitioners adoption methods	Geyi et al (2020)	

An agile framework developed in 2015 by Iamandi (2015) brings out the iterative stages of agile adoption with the idea of scrum and lean management principles for startup management, which inspired El-Khalil and Mezher (2020), Geyi *et al* (2020), Dean and Marc (2020) and Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020) to develop new frameworks which will be reviewed in Section 2.7.

The identification of pivotal literature gaps has illuminated key areas where the current understanding of agile startup sustainability falls short. Firstly, the absence of robust risk management and change practices within the literature underscores a critical need for the integration of risk agility in startups. Secondly, the gap in effective strategic management aligned with agile methods necessitates the development of strategic management principles tailored explicitly for startups. The third gap, pertaining to the lack of metrics for measuring operational efficiency and performance, calls for the creation of a standardized set of key performance indicators specific to agile startup contexts that accurately reflect performance agility and sustainability. Additionally, the fourth gap, which highlights a lack of clarity regarding the relationship between agile transformation and sustainability, necessitates focused research efforts to unveil the nuanced interplay between these elements. Lastly, the absence of clear startup framework with implementation guidelines to infuse sustainability into agile transformation processes calls for a meticulous approach, involving the amalgamation of sustainable practices within agile frameworks and the creation of a step-by-step roadmap for organizations. Addressing these gaps through targeted research efforts in this chapter and proposing practical solutions in Chapter 5 will not only contribute to the literature of agile startup sustainability but also actively contribute to the development of a more comprehensive and applicable conceptual framework. This research objectives and research questions are framed to address these literature gaps and the development of a conceptual framework in Chapter 5 will constructively fill these gaps.

2.7 FRAMEWORK EVALUATION

This section addresses the second part of the aim of the research to develop an agile startup sustainability framework for Indian IT startups that addresses the previously mentioned drawbacks of traditional methodologies and current startup frameworks to support sustainability and ensure competitive advantage and organizational agility. With the evaluation and identification of literature gaps in Section 2.6 in this chapter, the proposed components in the conceptual framework and their derivations will be discussed.

The literature gaps in coherence with the shortcomings of the existing agile frameworks will form the basis for achieving the Research Objective 4, answering Research Question 4, Chapter 1, of building an agile sustainability implementation guide for the IT startup industry and the research community. This section brings out the difference between the existing theory and newly emerged theories based on agile transformation and proposes the rationale for a new framework to be developed. Additional findings from the data analysis and how it has been included in the framework will be presented in detail in Chapter 5.

2.7.1 RELEVANT THEORIES

Lan and Unhelkar (2005), proposes the idea of agile transformation for businesses wherein there is a need for business process to be executed faster than normal, changing customer needs to be met, the operational costs to be reduced, quality of the final product to be improved and therefore performance, risk and strategic management to be accountable and regulated. The theories scrutinized in this section can bring both practical and theoretical aspects of agile transformation towards startup sustainability, evaluating the recent technology and its acceptance and impacts in context with India to validate agile frameworks for the proposed IT startups.

2.7.1.1 TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE THEORY

Venkatesh and Davis (2000), claim that businesses have failed in terms of economic growth predominantly due to the lack of utilizing information technology and software to their maximum potential for the benefit of the business. This has resulted in more acceptance models to be developed for businesses aiming to employ recent technologies and transformational methodologies for the benefit of the business (Wixom *et al*, 2005). The way businesses perceive a new transformation or technology based on its ease of usage and its benefits can determine its acceptance level within the business (Braun, 2013).

Moreover, an in-depth understanding of employees' and managers' perception of any technology can help identify its positive and negative impacts over the holistic business (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), although criticized for its limited power to predict employee behaviors and learning outcomes, proves to be critical for the study of impacts of agile transformation for sustainability of IT startups in India (Braun, 2013; Chen *et al*, 2017).

2.7.1.2 LEAN THEORY

As Blank (2007), ideally explains that startups considered as temporary businesses, pose a need for a steady and scalable business model to be developed over the years of its existence to help sustain the business for achieving long term goals. In addition to this, there also remains a great uncertainty of what profits the startup and what strategic roadmap the startup should follow for its sustainable growth through the years of existence (Middleton and Sutton, 2005). Felin *et al* (2019) and Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010), insist on the constant need for startups to quickly learn and evolve over failures and successes, to conduct practical experiments and build prototypes to identify products and services that profit them and invest on research and development in initial stages for a startup to have a sustainable business model.

Paternoster *et al* (2014), proposed simple and effective methods that help startups evolve by attaining constant customer feedback for even the smallest of prototypes built which eliminates processes that prove unprofitable. Ries (2011), suggested an iterative lean process for experiential learning that proves significant for building sustainable business models for startups. Moreover, the Build-Measure-Learn (BML) process of the lean model aims to promote early learning by building and measuring smaller units of the final product and service referred to as Minimum Viable Product (MVP) and to eliminate hypotheses and assumptions that decelerate the initial growth of the startup (Mueller and Thoring, 2012; Blank and Euchner, 2018).

2.7.1.3 SCRUM MODEL

The Scrum model as shown in Figure 2.17, claimed to be the most used agile model in both startups and large-scaled IT businesses breaks the transformational methodology into iterative sprints which adopts the learn thinking of building MVPs in the lean theory and iterative cycles to help business re-plan product development (Lei *et al*, 2017). The usage of scrum model has outgrown in recent years leading to agile being misinterpreted for scrum.

The higher flexibility and the emphasis on dynamic teams differentiates scrum model from other agile theories by building stability in the process through self-organized teams by overlapping the phases of product/service development training teams for cross-functional learning and development (Abrahamsson *et al*, 2017)

Figure 2. 17 Scrum model

Source: Lei *et al* (2017)

As opposed to traditional transformational methodologies, scrum-agile theory emphasizes on the customer interactive and iterative process of product/service development which brings rapid modifications in response to the greater uncertainties in requirement gathering, time and cost constraints and technological needs (Marcal *et al*, 2007; Lee and Yong, 2010; Sverrisdottir *et al*, 2014; Cocco *et al*, 2011). Cervone (2011) and Rigby *et al* (2016), highlight the application of Kanban board in addition to lean theories by the scrum master who replaces project manager to motivate teams, inculcates agile values and culture, subject life cycle to sprints of 14-20 days (about 3 weeks), etc., to significantly increment changes and quickly learn from early customer feedback. Retrospective in terms of daily standups and end of sprint reviews can be seen as a highly influential theme of scrum theory to help optimize efforts, communicate priorities, involve all stakeholders throughout the development cycle and maintain a visible workflow (Anderson *et al*, 2012; Ahmad *et al*, 2013; Abrahamsson *et al*, 2017; Friess, 2018).

2.7.2 CURRENT AGILE FRAMEWORKS FOR SUSTAINABILITY

Having scrutinized three foundational theories anchoring any agile adoption model in the preceding section, this section undertakes a more rigorous examination and evaluation of the currently posited or implemented frameworks in the wider scope of startup sustainability. Herein, we meticulously scrutinize the strengths and weaknesses inherent in these frameworks concerning project sustainability and startup sustainability. Noteworthy is that the models expounded upon in this section have been put forth by diverse researchers as comprehensive guides for agile management within the IT startup landscape.

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2.7.2.1 EXISTING MODEL 1

El-Khalil and Mezher (2020) developed a conceptual model as shown in Figure 2.18 that links agility and operational performance in the context of sustainability. They claim that agile practices have a positive impact on operational performance, sustainability and that sustainability works as the mediating factor that links agility and operational performance (El-Khalil and Mezher, 2020). Although the context of this study revolves around the US automotive manufacturing industry, the impact of agility over sustainability and performance can be translated for the IT industry (Kalenda *et al.*, 2018; Conboy and Carroll, 2019).

Figure 2. 18 El-Khalil and Mohamad Ali Mezher: Conceptual model

Source: El-Khalil and Mezher (2020)

The hindrances to business agility and sustainability include a dearth of stakeholder collaboration, leadership disengagement, misalignment between agile and sustainability goals, inadequate team skills, weak commitment to sustainability, and an excessive focus on short-term flexibility at the expense of long-term objectives (Lin *et al.*, 2006; Gunasekaran *et al.*, 2019; El-Khalil and Mezher, 2020). Notably, the viewpoint that sustainability is crucial for survival in a highly competitive environment can significantly shape future research and conceptual models in the context of agile transformation. Adeleye and Yusuf (2006) and El-Khalil (2020) propose agile transformation, combining lean theories and scrum models, as a response to ongoing business uncertainty, aiming for higher flexibility, lower costs, innovation, and faster deliveries. A noteworthy limitation of this research is its insufficient consideration of the startup landscape in India, a primary concern, of this research. Nevertheless, the findings can be applied to this research.

2.7.2.2 EXISTING MODEL 2

Geyi *et al* (2020), developed a conceptual model as shown in Figure 2.19 that explored the interaction between agility, sustainability and performance by carrying out a qualitative survey over 311 supply chains in the UK. A strong relationship between agile transformation and sustainability factors has been claimed and further, agile practices have been proposed as enablers of sustainability in terms of performance (Ahimbisibwe *et al*, 2015; Chen *et al*, 2017; Carvalho *et al*, 2017; Aslam *et al*, 2018). This research, focused on five sustainability elements encompassing social, environmental, and economic factors, narrows its scope to supply chain management. While its exploration is confined to this domain, crucial insights, including key performance metrics and agile practices, can still be gleaned, as highlighted by Ciccullo *et al*. (2018), Ciric *et al*. (2019), and Yusuf *et al*. (2020).

Figure 2. 19 Agile capabilities for performance management

Source: Geyi *et al* (2020)

A close collaboration between the stakeholders, although argued to be the crucial factor for sustainability, its intensity and safe levels have not been discussed (Yusuf *et al*, 2014). Waste management as part of the lean manufacturing process to effectively manage resources can be used in the IT industry to eliminate waste in terms of products and services (Yusuf *et al*, 2020; Armanious and Padgett, 2021). Geyi *et al*.'s 2020 research, focused on the UK supply chain sector, cautions against blind generalization. While limited to the UK, the insights gained are valuable for potential application in developing countries and the IT startup industry. The research serves as a foundational reference for future research beyond its specific demographic and industry scope.

2.7.2.3 EXISTING MODEL 3

Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020) have devised a conceptual model, depicted in Figure 2.20, bridging the literature gap concerning Business Model Innovation (BMI), Lean Startup Approaches (LSA), and agile transformation within the realm of strategic agility in dynamic digital startups. This study suggests that integrating lean and agile theories can enhance business model innovation, thereby impacting the sustainability of startups by establishing connections between strategy, performance, and agility, as asserted by Foss and Saebi (2018) and Yang *et al.* (2018).

Figure 2. 20 Agile startup framework for operational and strategic agility

Source: Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020)

This integrated framework underscores innovation as a pivotal element, contributing to both new product/service developments through agile practices and sustainable business models via lean startup approaches. Scholars such as Schneider and Spieth (2013), Weill and Vitale (2013), and Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020) assert that leagile methods, blending agile and lean theories, enhance resource and capability management, thereby influencing strategic startup management. This research elevates agile transformation beyond operational/performance aspects to a strategic level, leveraging MVP, SCRUM, and BMI theories to their fullest and incorporating culture as a critical element, as advocated by Baker and Thomas (2007), Doz and Kosonen (2010), Reis (2011), Damanpour and Aravind (2012), Rosario *et al.* (2016), Cooper and Sommer (2016), and Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020).

2.7.2.4 EXISTING MODEL 4

Dean and Marc (2020) developed a conceptual framework illustrated in Figure 2.21, comprising five essential blocks: prioritizing opportunities, developing business models, validating learning, building Minimum Viable Products (MVPs), and pivoting innovation. This framework is designed to facilitate business sustainability within a lean startup context, aligning with principles advocated by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010), Ries (2011), Gruber and Tal (2017), and Blank and Euchner (2018).

Figure 2. 21 The lean startup framework building blocks

Source: Dean and Marc (2020)

Gruber *et al.* (2008) and Gandomani *et al.* (2013) assert that the first stride toward sustainability involves applying lean and agile principles to eliminate non-profitable products or services. Agile's notable contributions to startups include an emphasis on continuous learning, early implementation of sustainability practices from the inception stage, and the testing of contingency frameworks tailored to specific conditions like fund availability or product/market fitness (Rosario *et al.*, 2016; John, 2017; Blank and Euchner, 2018). External factors such as the inquiry community, nature, society and environment as shown in the Figure 3.8 have been identified as potential threats or influence over startup practices and strategic goals (Signoretti *et al.*, 2019; Oliva and Kotabe, 2019; Wigger and Shepherd, 2019; Wry and Zhao, 2018). This research also highlights dynamism, complexity, communication, etc., as factors of sustainability (Dean and Marc, 2020).

2.7.3 EVALUATION OF FRAMEWORK GAPS

Following the sections that meticulously outlined the advantages and critiques of existing conceptual frameworks, the subsequent analysis in this section will scrutinize these frameworks within the unique context of sustainability for IT startups in India. This comprehensive evaluation will categorize these frameworks under the dimensions of individual, team, technology, and organizational factors. The findings will be succinctly organized and presented in Table 2.15, corresponding to Table 2.11, encapsulating their adoption challenges, common misconceptions, strengths, and weaknesses. This strategic evaluation aims to distill valuable insights that can inform the development of a robust and contextually relevant conceptual framework for the sustainability of IT startups in India.

2.7.3.1 COMMUNICATION LAGS

Mali and Ananth (2012), Jeff and Matt (2013) and Satar and John (2016) claim that face-to-face interaction between the stakeholders can be a critical success factor for agile transformation to be highly productive and profitable. Yet, the pandemic has posed serious threats for all stakeholders to be collocated, making daily stand-ups and reviews to be time consuming and cost in-effective (Kim *et al*, 2016; Geyi *et al*, 2020). This communication lag between stakeholders can be evident in these frameworks which demand new business operations.

2.7.3.2 LACK OF RIGIDITY IN REQUIREMENT GATHERING

The lack of more systematic, disciplined and well documented agile practices has been unsuccessful for IT businesses where there exist uncertainties about the required final product or service (Satar and John, 2016; Kim *et al*, 2016). While agile methodologies champion flexibility and rapid learning, the significance of a structured requirement gathering process in the initial stages cannot be overstated. Chen *et al*. (2017) assert that the apprehension of the unknown or uncertainty may drive managers to make ill-informed decisions and implement ambiguous practices, culminating in unprofitable endeavors. Adding to this perspective, Circullo *et al*. (2018) contend that startups, especially those with newly assembled talents and teams, may face challenges without a well-defined set of documentation. This deficiency can lead to disparities between customer needs and the developed products, subsequently intensifying workload burdens.

2.7.3.3 LACK OF CLARITY WITH CUSTOMER COLLABORATION

Agile theories demand closer collaboration with stakeholders and customers, and these agile frameworks overlook the greater commitment levels and pressure that employees undergo to achieve sprint success (Kim *et al*, 2016; Geyi *et al*, 2020). Marshal *et al* (2015), demands training to be necessary for effective collaboration to influence product quality and project success. This clearly depicts the lack of clarity with levels of collaboration between customers and businesses.

2.7.3.4 TOLERANCE LEVELS OF CHANGE IN DEMANDS

Ahimbisibwe *et al* (2017), criticizes agile method for the lack of investment of time and cost in planning phase where uncertainty drives the business. Signoretti *et al* (2019) and Oliva and Kotabe (2019), claim that customers unclear with their own needs can threaten startups aiming to satisfy them. This limits these agile frameworks which solely depend on customer feedback for all their iterations. This brings business back to the planning phase and revises the whole SDLC which again kills time and slashes money (Pedro and Jeffrey, 2015; Diego *et al*, 2020).

2.7.3.5 LACK OF AGILE CULTURE AND MINDSET

There exists a need for startup adoption and post-implementation model that evaluates the sustainability of the agile startup (Fangmann *et al*, 2020; Nath *et al*, 2021). Isomursu *et al* (2012), claim that agility can only be achieved through a series of incremental improvements that happen every day. This demands that the management team communicates agile values and supports agile culture within the startup. Miler and Gaida (2019) claim that these can be as critical as agile practices to determine sustainability of startups which these current frameworks have overlooked.

2.7.3.6 BENEFITING MANAGERS MORE THAN TEAM

Geyi *et al* (2020) and Mikhieieva and Stephan (2020), claim that lean theory and agile frameworks demands developers to be working with just-in-time attitude. MNCs with a team of developers working in multiple projects possess a serve-to-demand attitude whereas in startups, one or two developers work on one project burning their energy and time off (Philipp *et al*, 2018; Lappi *et al*, 2018). This has been a major drawback for these agile frameworks which have benefited the managers more than the developers and team.

2.7.3.7 LACK OF RISK AGILITY AS A COMPONENT

All the conceptual frameworks and models that have been discussed in this chapter indicate a strong connection between strategy, performance, agility and sustainability yet lack the risk management or risk agility as a component (Ghezzeo and Cavallo, 2020; El-Khalil and Mezher 2020; Geyi *et al*, 2020; Dean and Marc, 2020). Risk management can be crucial for sustainability as discussed in Section 2.4 and therefore the inclusion of risk can be influential and highly impactful for an Indian IT startup sustainability.

Table 2. 15 Evaluation of existing frameworks

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESS	CHALLENGES & MISCONCEPTION	LITERATURE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Working on real products rather on diagrams/drawing - Daily scrum meetings improve micromanagement - Clear assignment of roles/tasks - Shared problems - Low dependencies on team members - Active participation - Effective for tracking progress. - Flexible for all business projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of documentation - Budget and schedule constraint - Work specialization cannot be achieved through cross functional generalist teams - Too many meetings can rather degrade work efficiency - Sprint backlog does not match with customer priority - High transparency demands - High accountability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of knowledge / training / skills - Organizational culture / mindset - Teamwork/communication issues - Escalating commitment - Hard to scale - High management overhead - Increase stress and workload - Lack of quality - Lack of top management support - Long time to market - Low user satisfaction - Over engineered solutions - Over optimistic task estimates - Project team size - Requirements creep - Retrospective inadequacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aliisy-Roberts et al (2017) - Srivastava et al (2017) - Przybyłek and Zakrzewski (2018) - Gaida and Miler (2019) - Al-Ali and Phaal (2019) - Paulmani (2020) - Mikhieieva and Stephan (2020) - Frangmann et al (2020) - Geyi et al (2020) - Nath et al (2021)

2.7.3.8 NEED FOR SUSTAINABILITY FOR EVALUTING AGILE

The imperative for clearly defined metrics in agile transformation, as advocated by Sutherland and Tabaka (2007), Gandomani *et al.* (2014), and Prochazka (2011), has resonated profoundly in recent agile frameworks. In response, key indicators delineating the success of agile methodologies have been incorporated. This research goes a step further by introducing a groundbreaking framework that centers around the sustainability metric of agile transformation, an aspect overlooked by existing frameworks. This distinctive focus on sustainability emerges as the crucial differentiator, setting this research apart in the landscape of agile transformation methodologies.

2.7.4 RATIONALE FOR A NEW FRAMEWORK

According to Nath *et al* (2021) and Fangmann *et al* (2020), the need for in-depth understanding of the phenomena of agile transformation and its sustainability seems to be growing over recent years with complex and ever-changing customer needs that demands businesses to be vigilant, flexible and robust towards uncertainties. Various management consultancies and researchers have tried to address the adoption challenges yet have failed to include certain key metrics that can benefit Indian IT startups and its sustainability (Geyi *et al*, 2020; Diego *et al*, 2020; Dutta *et al*, 2020). Nath *et al* (2021), a recent researcher in this field has revealed that startups still suffer this constant struggle of evolving a business model that works and sustains them over the years.

Silo-sustainability management seems to be lacking the strategic roadmap to direct and drive startup change management. Although the acceptance of management and leadership for agile transformation for the benefit of their business has increased in recent years, the implementation challenges and cultural barriers are also constantly evolving, which inculcates disagreement and chaos of agile adoption models for startups (Kim *et al*, 2016; Srivastava *et al*, 2017; Ebert and Paasivaara, 2017). Therefore, failure of existing models and frameworks in certain scenarios and demography always creates room for more innovative agile frameworks to replace or reinvestigate the process and outcomes (Gandomani *et al*, 2014; Kim *et al*, 2016). As more top IT businesses increasingly invest in transformation and transition from existing SDLC transformational methods to agile, it can be crucial for startups to consider those feasible and effective practices into their culture as they groom their business models (Dean and Marc, 2020; Diego *et al*, 2020). The need for business sustainability beyond environment, social and economic sustainability has been integral for Indian IT startups (Fangmann *et al*, 2020; Geyi *et al*, 2020; Nath *et al*, 2021).

The role of sustainability has evolved over the years and so has its definition. Business sustainability, the major concern of this research, has become a key factor of competitive advantage for IT businesses involving risk, strategy and performance. Mathiyazhagan *et al* (2021), claims that during recent times, being worst hit by the pandemic, IT startups have identified agile transformation to be critical for survival in the market where the competition remains high. The agile culture and mindset as discussed in Sub-Section 2.5.4, has often been overlooked by management and leadership who decide to adopt agile transformation (Beske-Janssen *et al*, 2015; Govindan *et al*, 2016).

The value proposition and alignment with its strategic goals remains unclear before investing in agile, identified as potential threat for its success (Ghezzi and Cavallo, 2020; Nath *et al*, 2021). Failure of existing frameworks to include risk management as a component of agility adds chaos to the process (Dean and Marc, 2020; Mathiyazhagan *et al*, 2021).

Although many literatures have focused on the transformation process, there exists a literature gap where the potential impacts of this transformation over business sustainability is still unidentified. Although financial performance, cost-effectiveness and economic growth must be evaluated for any agile transformation, they cannot be the only factors of measurement of transformation success. Factors such as culture, employee satisfaction, quality, delivery time, customer collaboration, effective requirement gathering, etc., need to be considered for evaluation.

Startups need to embrace challenges and barriers through adoption of agile practices, even though it may financially seem like a burden. Indian startups in specific, need to invest in lean practices from the preliminary stages to avoid future chaos, wherein a more sustainable business model gets developed. Moreover, the importance of sustainability needs to be communicated within the workforce while implementing agile practices and methods. In the perspective of the gaps presented in this Chapter, a need for a more sustainable agile startup framework is evident, which can aid Indian IT startups to tackle sustainability challenges and barriers in a dynamic manner. To address this, this research proposes the development of a new agile startup sustainability framework that can impact key areas of agile transformation and gives implementation guidance towards achieving sustainability and competitive advantage.

2.7.5 DERIVATION OF THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Sub-Section 2.7.3 highlighted key drawbacks of existing agile transformational frameworks which form the literature gap that serves as the baseline for the development of the proposed framework. The derivation of essential components in the proposed framework and its theories will be discussed in this section which combines both the literature gaps from Section 2.6 and framework gaps from Sub-Section 2.7.3. The agile startup sustainability framework was inspired by recent developments, interests and continuing awareness of sustainability and agile transformation literatures. Instead of a specific theory, this framework collaborates the best insights from the literature evaluated and categorized under the four-quadrant framework earlier this chapter.

From the academic perspective, agile literatures have failed to accommodate sustainability into investigation for startup success. From the practitioners or industry perspective, agile practices face many cultural, strategic, risk and performance challenges and barriers that startups fail to address. As literature review highlighted the deficiencies in certain areas of sustainability that agile transformation fails to address, there is still a need for a more holistic approach that includes risk aspects of agility to ultimately bring business sustainability. The proposed framework will therefore aim to address key issues raised in the recent years (2012-present) to align them for the sustainability of Indian IT startups. The components of the proposed framework can be seen as necessary steps towards achieving business sustainability and therefore the initial step would be to identify the challenges and barriers that affect sustainability of startups. This can help align the strategic goals and objectives to overcome these challenges.

To identify these sustainability factors, they need to be categorized under risk, strategy and performance. Most of the frameworks previously discussed have adopted performance and strategy as the major components leaving out risk, which is the highlight of this proposed framework. Any agile framework adopted by a startup should be designed to reveal potential barriers that need to be overcome by agile methodologies. As compared to top IT businesses in India, there can be a major disadvantage in terms of resistance to change and implementation challenges such as the lack of funds, traditional mindset, unclear strategic goals, etc.

Moreover, the need for a methodology in a startup environment needs to be established prior to the actual framework development. Given the unestablished methods of processes and business models, startups may suffer initially with trial-and-error methods to identify best fit practices and agility goals. Therefore, the next step would be to assess various methods and practices for its fitness within the context of sustainability, wherein the outcomes are well communicated and established from top to bottom of hierarchy. The inclusion of risk tolerance can distinguish the proposed framework from the previous frameworks thereby combining best techniques and assessment metrics from risk theories. Understanding both the positive and negative impacts of agile transformation on management disciplines such as strategy, risk and performance proves essential for effective evaluation of any agile framework. There exists a void in the literature where agile transformation never gets evaluated for its ability to sustain the business, which has left agile a mere project management tool instead of using it as the ultimate solution for an IT startup.

An ideal agile startup framework should have a positive impact on business sustainability and that is where the proposed framework will best prove its effectiveness. Sustainability challenges and barriers as discussed in Section 2.2 project a wide array of factors affecting IT startups in India. The key highlights from the literature gaps as tabulated earlier this Chapter under four quadrants and the framework gaps later derived from assessing the current frameworks are as follows.

- Lack of understanding of the key factors that affect sustainability of Indian IT startups.
- Unexploited scope of transformation methodology for achieving Indian IT project sustainability and holistic startup sustainability;
- Failure to consider implementation and adoption challenges of transformation methods;
- Negligence of intangible elements and aspects of transformation methods;
- Failure to include risk, strategic and performance agility as an element of transformation methods linking transformation methods to management disciplines fostering holistic Indian IT startup sustainability;
- Scarcity of frameworks that focus on Indian IT startup sustainability as the ultimate focus that elucidates competitive advantage and organizational agility.

Based on these research gaps summarized above, the proposed agile startup framework would illustrate the importance of each element added into the framework along with its sub elements.

- External Inputs (factors that influence sustainability of Indian IT startups)
- Process Inputs (choice of transformation methodology and implementation challenges)
- Management disciplines (risk, strategic and performance agility)
- Outputs (sustainability; indicators – competitive advantage and organizational agility)

Recent researchers and practitioners in agile transformation who have understood the trends and environment within the industry have raised these issues to be addressed in future research. Appendix 1 provides the summary of all the literature that has contributed towards each element of the proposed framework. Agile literature's growth extends beyond IT to manufacturing, supply chain, and agriculture, highlighting its versatile benefits across industries. In India, an increasing focus on lean and agile transformations in startup literature reflects alignment with current research trends. Addressing the critical challenge of business sustainability in IT startups, this research has the potential to significantly enhance their industry resilience. The proposal for a new framework emerges as a rational response to ensure IT startup sustainability in India.

2.7.6 PROPOSED AGILE STARTUP SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

The primary focus of this sustainable agile startup sustainability framework is to address the literature and framework gaps in Sections 2.6 and Sub-Section 2.7.3. As the sole purpose of this framework is to achieve business sustainability of IT startups, it is necessary that the framework appears simple yet dynamic, user friendly yet strategic with straightforward metrics and provides implementation guidance. One of the top priorities of this proposed framework is to establish and fill the literature gaps within the agile and sustainability literature which demands a straightforward approach towards identifying and addressing sustainability factors. A holistic and unified startup framework can capture all the major components of sustainability and overcome threats and challenges both internal and external to the startup. The primary reason for linking risk to sustainability and agile transformation is to ensure that any agile practice implemented must comply with the overall vision and goals of the business to promote sustainability.

When agile transformation links to the major disciplines of management, it can also have a major impact on sustainability. To fill the literature gaps of strategic misalignment between day-to-day activities and sustainability goals, the framework accommodates the elements of strategic agility.

Figure 2. 22 Conceptual agile startup sustainability framework

The framework, depicted in Figure 2.22, addresses sustainability, a central concern established in Chapter 1, Section 1.4. Within the internal startup environment, it encompasses process inputs (methodology choices, implementation challenges, and startup processes), management disciplines (risk, strategy, and performance management), and the ultimate goal, achieving sustainability. As highlighted in Section 2.2.1, the strong connection between project and startup sustainability is notable, extending beyond project success to encompass effective risk, strategy, and performance management for overall startup sustainability in the context of Indian IT startups (Axel and Lars, 2016; Santiago and Emre, 2017; Denning, 2019). Section 2.3.4 emphasizes the integral link between the choice of transformation methodology and holistic sustainability, highlighting the dependency of management disciplines on process inputs (Tarhini *et al.*, 2018; Wigger and Shepher, 2019; Khalifeh *et al.*, 2020; Yazici, 2020). The framework illustrates this connection between process inputs, including methodology choices, and management disciplines. In assessing the benefits of sustainability, it becomes evident that achieving sustainability equates to gaining a competitive advantage over competitors and ensuring organizational agility, both included in the outputs as indicators of sustainability. Sections 2.2.3 to 2.2.5 identify universal sustainability factors affecting most startups, applicable to the target industry of this research as external inputs influencing startups (Chen *et al.*, 2017; Statista, 2019; Forbes, 2019; Noshir *et al.*, 2019). This aligns with Research Objective 1.

The comparison of traditional and agile methods, explored in the literature by Collier (2012), Mahalakshmi and Sundararajan (2013), Khan *et al.* (2013), Adel and Abdullah (2015), and Measey (2015), raises the question of which approach best suits the sustainability of Indian IT startups. This inquiry will be addressed through findings from semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions in Chapter 4, contributing to the construction of the framework. This aspect revolves around the choice of transformation methodology, evaluating both agile and non-agile methods. Furthermore, Section 2.5.6 delves into the implementation challenges of both methodologies, shedding light on practical barriers and the scope of applicability for the sustainability of Indian IT startups (Ghani *et al.*, 2015, Alsahli *et al.*, 2017, Kuhrmann *et al.*, 2017; Malik *et al.*, 2021). The framework recognizes implementation challenges as part of the process inputs, aligning with Research Objective 3, which will be further addressed in the research findings of Chapter 4.

In pursuit of Research Objective 4, the development of a new and robust framework aims to overcome limitations in existing agile frameworks by El-Khalil and Mezher (2020), Geyi *et al.* (2020), Dean and Marc (2020), and Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020). This new framework incorporates risk agility, strategic agility, and performance or operational agility as crucial elements for achieving sustainability, reinforcing its development. The qualitative themes' findings will intricately shape and fortify the framework, infusing it with depth and meaning as they are seamlessly integrated.

A complete literature review of the sustainability factors affecting a startup both internally and externally has helped derive this framework to address these challenges in advance. Collaboration levels with customers have been clearly defined so that effective communication between all stakeholders can be achieved. The feedback loop added from sustainability to agile transformation can help re-evaluate and retrospect the ever-changing sustainability needs, which shows the dynamic nature and ability to quickly learn from failures. As reviewed earlier in this chapter, there are multiple sustainability challenges and barriers that businesses face and even more so, they are customized for a certain startup which may not be the case for the other. Therefore, a clear categorization into risk, strategy and performance as elements in the framework can help achieve sustainability through agile transformation. According to Dean and Marc (2020) and Geyi *et al.* (2020), integrating sustainability practices into agile transformation has been identified as necessary and hence has been retained with this framework.

This framework not only accomplishes the comprehensive examination of the impact of agile and non-agile transformation methods across all facets of a startup but also successfully dismantles silo management disciplines by orchestrating collaboration among three key functionalities. Its inherent design facilitates transparent communication of transformation methodology philosophies, principles and sustainability goals, establishing crucial connections between external and internal factors and the transformation implementation methods. Figure 2.22 represents a potent tool, capable of delivering substantial value to any IT startup in India aspiring to attain sustainability through agile transformation, thereby yielding competitive advantage and organizational agility as tangible outputs.

2.8 CHAPTER CONCLUSION

This chapter discussed both academic literatures of sustainability and transformation methodologies *yet also* focuses on industry-based literatures for target sector, literatures on IT startups in India, key elements of sustainability in Section 2.2, key failures of transformation methodologies in terms of sustainability in Section 2.4 and agile in contradiction to traditional methodologies in Section 2.5, and challenges to implementation of agile in reality in Sub-Section 2.5.4. To conclude, most startups in India, have either followed traditional methodologies to solve new business problems which can be unprecedented or have practiced agile in just the wrong way, both neglecting sustainability as key research problem to be addressed in this research as explained in Section 2.6 which brought out the literature gaps.

Most of Section 2.2 can be descriptive with strong empirical proof and further sections can be prescriptive focusing on critical review of literature. Academics have overlooked the practical implementation challenges and therefore this research has considered practical experience of practitioners or industry researchers who have considered implementation of agile sustainability and challenges. This chapter presented the literature review on agile transformation and sustainability in the last two decades, examining the existing agile approaches both from the academic and industry perspectives, and finally investigated the literature gaps in more detail. This chapter answered the first 3 research questions and provided the rationale for a new agile startup sustainability framework to be developed in Sub-Section 2.7.4 and Sub-Section 2.7.5. The proposed framework must be validated with the research findings from data collection which will be done in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5. This research targets to provide a complete implementation guideline for agile transformation framework that aids to impact sustainability in the Indian IT startups by building a competitive edge amongst competitors and creating organizational agility within the startup.

Very few researchers have tapped into this relationship between agile transformation and IT startup sustainability and adding the context of India makes it even more worthwhile of research as IT business accounts for a larger percentage of GDP growth. This research incorporated the findings of Geyi *et al* (2020) and Dean and Marc (2020), largely to develop a sustainability model for Indian IT startups. The suggested models and theories were tested in the context of Indian IT startups to evaluate their effectiveness.

However, on complete analysis of the dynamic nature of the startup ecosystem in India, the research found out there were still gaps in the understanding of agile transformation and how it can impact sustainability in terms of management disciplines.

The Indian economy is one that is emerging, where a lot of startups either IT or other sectors with IT processes have evolved. This has shifted the attention to the increasing volume of IT startup exits and therefore sustainability is at stake. Where IT startups have tried to copy western practices, they have failed to adapt to the culture where the employees belong. The mindset with which the entrepreneurs' approach agile transformation has questioned the credibility of agile practices. Therefore, this research not only contradicted a few theoretical findings but also emerged with new contributions that can yield maximum profitability for a startup on the following criteria:

- Sustainability factors can be demographic and culture specific. Within the context of India, non-financial factors account to startup failures more than the financial factors. This shows the potential of an ideal process that can overcome these factors;
- The traditional methodologies such as the waterfall, spiral, V-shaped, parallel and iterative are not effective enough to enhance the sustainability of Indian IT startups where startups are more dynamic and the customer needs are getting more complex;
- The readiness of Indian IT startups to incorporate agile transformation is still not effectively targeted towards achieving sustainability where the need for agile and its impacts within the startup has not been clearly established prior to the transformation;
- The current agile frameworks from Dean and Marc (2020), Geyi *et al* (2020), Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020) and El-Khalil and Mezher (2020), do not work for Indian IT startups where culture plays a key role and achieving agility in management disciplines is neglected.

Every research follows a methodology for approaching research and data collection and the next chapter will discuss the details of methodological approaches and chosen method for this research and provides the justification for using the same.

CHAPTER 3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION

In the previous chapter, we have established the literature gaps, the framework gaps and the development of a conceptual framework. This chapter presents the methodological assumptions and justifications that further steer the methods in which this research is carried out. It presents the elements of research methodology such as the research paradigm, design, approach, purpose and strategy and provides carefully considered judgements based on the research objectives, the nature of research questions and the primary aim of this research. Sample population, size, inclusion criteria and strategy, data collection and analysis methods with profound justification is provided in this chapter. Finally, this chapter exposes research quality, ethical issues and limitations.

3.2 RESEARCH PARADIGM

Thomas Kuhn (1962) claims that paradigm refers to the perspective or philosophical thinking of a researcher's view of the world which in turn gives meaning to the data collected as a set of shared beliefs. Lather (1986) further correlated paradigm to research paradigm whereby the data collected can be viewed as the researcher's perspective of the world. According to Davcik *et al* (2015), careful consideration of this research paradigm can contribute immensely to the success of addressing a research problem. Most scholars believe the research paradigm to direct the next set of actions to be undertaken (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Healy and Perry, 200; Schwandt, 2001). Guba and Lincoln (1994) and Saunders (2011) have been phenomenal with their contribution towards identifying the various classifications of the research paradigm namely, 1) positivism; 2) interpretivism; and 3) pragmatism, whose comparison has been tabulated in Table 3.1.

3.2.1 POSITIVISM

Auguste Comte (1978), coined positivism and stated it to be the measurable reality or a natural phenomenon which research needs knowledge of. Positivism adopts scientific investigation methods to correlate with worldviews. According to Zukauskas *et al* (2018), positivists believe being stable which therefore makes its observation as the natural perspective to help understand it, more than considering it. This leads to a major drawback of the phenomenon being isolated and not observed repeatedly.

Positivists then, tend to manipulate reality with independent variables and their relationships which they believe can best assess reality (Hughes and Sharrock, 2016). As the approach is more scientific, positivists further believe that facts, figures, charts, quantifiable observations, statistical analysis and effective measurements of variables and their interactions can truly address the research problems raised in this research.

Table 3. 1 Comparison of research philosophies/paradigms

PARADIGM	ONTOLOGY	EPISTEMOLOGY	METHODOLOGY
Worldview	Form and nature of reality and gaining knowledge about it	Nature of relationship between research and the researcher	Researcher's ways to address knowledge that can be gained
Positivism	Reality exists and can be perceived	Dualism / Objectivism	Experimentative / Manipulation: Verifying hypothesis created by the researcher Predominantly Quantitative methods
Interpretivism	Reality is multiple and relative; Critical realism	Subjectivism Mutually interactive and interdependent	Active participation from the researcher towards arriving at collective reality/ hypothesis Predominantly Qualitative methods
Pragmatism	Adopting positivism and or interpretivism to best address the research problem; allowing freedom of choice	Both objectivism and subjectivism can provide best answer research questions by integrating multiple perspectives for data interpretation	Action research/ Mixed method design that employ both Quantitative and Qualitative research methods

Source: Adapted from Guba and Lincoln (1994) and Saunders (2011)

Hussey and Hussey (1997), relate positivism to quantitative research and data collection which deducts logic out of reality. Larger sample size, statistical analysis, testing hypothesis to answer research questions can be a few characteristics that define positivism paradigm. As positivists consider themselves independent from the research phenomena, they are external to it, which allows them to observe objectively but limits data interpretation to one's own view of the phenomenon and not collective or pluralistic. Positivists, as stated earlier, rely solely on scientific observations and relate this to natural science and occurrences.

Positivists tend to overlook feelings and intangible factors by exploring factors in complete isolation yet claim their results to be highly justifiable based on empirical/logical dependencies between the variables. Knowledge as positivist view can be acceptable only if there's validation to it (Fadhel, 2002). According to Hughes and Sharrock (1997), positivists adopt questionnaires, surveys, etc. as their predominant tools to collect data from samples.

The reasons why positivism wasn't considered suitable for this research is as follows: 1) Gathering new and unique insights into research problem requires active human interaction and participation between the phenomena and the researcher, which rules out positivism; 2) The exploratory nature of this research considers non-quantifiable objects, real-world experiences and social behaviors as factors as opposed to numbers, variable and facts, which rules out positivist perspectives (Zikmund, 2003). 3) Limited samples size in order to support the depth of case-oriented analysis deviates this research from positivist approach; 4) This research requires more in-depth interviews and focus groups to address the research problem, not to validate but to provide more perspectives of the phenomena and therefore, positivism cannot be suitable 5) Impacts of agile transformation can be subject to the specific startup founders, managers and team members and cannot be observed or manipulated as a hypothesis.

3.2.2 PRAGMATISM

As most scholars took sides with positivism and interpretivism, William James and John Dewey stated that there can be multiple approaches to interpret reality which can include both positivism (objectivism) and interpretivism (subjectivism). Patton (1990), Tashakkori and Teddlie (2003), Alise and Teddlie (2010) and Biesta (2010) claim that singular scientific approaches proved unreliable to arrive at a conclusion about the reality and that when combined with inductive approaches can provide the human behavior and intangibles, making it more complete. Mixed methods as scholars' claim adopt both quantitative and qualitative approaches to arrive at outcomes. According to Saunders (2011), the freedom to choose research methods and data collection techniques makes pragmatism the best approach to answer specific research questions. Pragmatists consider themselves to be in multiple positions of philosophical worldview and therefore prove relevant only when it supports the outcome (Hair *et al*, 2014).

The reasons why pragmatism was not considered suitable for this research is as follows: 1) Use of both quantitative and qualitative methods was not necessary because the research only needs interpretivism that involves human interaction and multiple views and not positivism. 2) In-depth interviews prove more suitable than surveys because of the need for more insights into the phenomena rather than validating any hypothesis. 3) The need to quantify and find relationships between the intangible variables can be highly time consuming and practically unnecessary for a phenomenon such as agile transformation, therefore strongly justifying a qualitative approach.

3.2.3 INTERPRETIVISM

Jean Piaget (1967), coined 'interpretivism' stating that knowledge can be constructed through human interaction and learning from each other. Kim (2001) suggested interpretivism as a paradigm, correlating it to research methodology, constructing reality through active interaction with the phenomena. According to Onwuegbuzie *et al* (2009), interpretivism provides in-depth understanding of the phenomena. Strauss and Corbin (1990) and Young and Collin (2004) argue that the hypothesis follows the research rather than being formulated in the beginning and knowledge can be gained through experience. Shwandt (2001), claims that every other individual is interpretivists as self-perspective can be influenced by others. Berger and Luckman (1966), Young and Collin (2004) and Cunliffe (2008) argue that continuous interaction with research phenomena can highly influence a researcher's perspective and view of reality. As most research questions addressed by interpretivists tend to be broad and vague, the perspectives of participants can highly influence the researcher. According to Creswell (2003), an interpretivists' intention is to interpret other's perspectives of reality and thereby gain knowledge.

Creswell (2012) claims an interpretive framework to be formative and constructive because interpretivists gain understanding and correlate that to their own experience. The results can be unique and completely different take on the phenomena. According to Andrews (2012), a research phenomenon most specific to a certain demography can be understood in-depth using the same language as a tool for direct interaction. Kim (2001), states that interpretivism is based on following; 1) Reality can only be derived through interactions rather than believing it exists prior; 2) Knowledge can be highly influence by society and culture and therefore their meanings may differ with different individuals; 3) Learning can only be meaningful when active participation leads to an inherent passion for more understanding rather than being forced by external pressures.

Vygotsky (1978) claims that understanding of reality can be collectively developed by multiple participants. Factors related to human behavior, culture and society can only be commemorated through direct interaction with humans. Rational experience of an individual and closeness through language can be two attributes of interpretivism. This research primarily adopts interpretivism for several compelling reasons: 1) Interpretivism, characterized by open-ended research questions, permits participants to express views without constraints such as biases, time, and cost (Creswell, 2013). 2) In comprehending the sustainability factors impacting Indian startups, providing participants the freedom to share views and opinions based on industry experience is crucial, allowing for meaningful interpretation of the research. 3) Direct interaction with participants enables the accumulation of unique insights specific to the demographic, contributing to the distinctiveness of the research. 4) The factors identified in this research are highly beneficial for participants as they directly reflect their own experiences.

3.2.4 JUSTIFICATION FOR THE CHOSEN PARADIGM

The justification for this research to choose interpretivism over others is as follows; 1) The social complexity of the phenomena in this research, which is agile transformation and sustainability, requires a philosophy that involves multiple human perspectives, meanings, and interpretations and therefore, interpretivism would be the appropriate philosophy delve into the richness and nuances of human experiences. 2) This research focuses on the sustainability of Indian IT startups, and it is therefore necessary to emphasize the importance of understanding the phenomena only within the Indian contexts. Choosing interpretivism helps align with research objectives in Chapter 1, which seeks to explore and interpret the social and cultural aspects of Indian IT startups. 3) The nature of research questions in Chapter 1, recognizes the subjectivity of reality, wherein each individual participant (For example: startup founders, agile coaches and project managers) can construct their own realities based on their assumptions and perceptions, which further justifies the choice of interpretivism philosophy for this research. 4) There is a necessity for this research to provide a holistic approach of sustainability of Indian IT startups and how agile transformation can be applied to achieve this. This interconnectedness of various factors helps to give a holistic understanding of the phenomena and interpretivism philosophy is considered apt. 5) The use of qualitative tools such as semi-structured interviews and focus groups closely associates with an interpretivist approach.

This research aims to collect data not just to define the phenomena but to derive in-depth meanings, perceptions and experiences in context with the chosen demography, and therefore, qualitative methods embedded in interpretivism are suitable. 6) One of the main contributions of this research is the development of agile startup sustainability framework which requires new theories to be generated or existing frameworks/theories get refined. Using interpretivism, sustainability can be interpreted in novel ways within the context of Indian IT startups.

According to Williams (2007), unique perspectives and understandings emerge from existing knowledge if applied interpretivism yet it can only make sense if in context to the demography. Furthermore, there can be no alternative to understand the sustainability factors and develop a new model for agile startups than to directly interact with managers who have been influenced by the phenomena. Ghauri (2004) and Bryman and Bell (2015) claim that engaging the participants and constructing knowledge can be necessary. Hair *et al* (2015), argue that social constructivism can generate more information about the phenomenon. Zikmund *et al* (2013), further this by adding real time experience to collecting data which can elevate the scope of the research. This belief of epistemology can be associated with sustainability, the phenomena of research which represents perspectives of various startup founders and managers (Saunders, 2011). In consideration of all these factors, interpretivism can be justified as the appropriate paradigm for this research to exploit the sustainability factors that can revive startups failing over time. The researcher's inherent passion towards business consulting for IT startups can categorize the researcher as an active participant (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). On applying interpretivism, the researcher was able to gain in-depth understanding of the way startups work in India and the dirty truths as to why they fail miserably within years of establishment from direct experiences of managers.

Collective views and opinions of these managers, if interpreted, can provide useful information to be developed as a model of future startups to address the ongoing issue of unsustainability. This research paradigm can also help add valuable research into the academic study of agile transformation and its scope for IT startups. An additional reason for justifying this paradigm would be the use of semi-structured interviews as a tool. Although time consuming and non-structured to a certain extent, interpretivism proves to be appreciated within the circle of participants and provides extensive knowledge for their startup development and sustainability, further justifying this as the ideal philosophy for this research.

3.3 RESEARCH APPROACH

Research approach forms an integral part of the research following the choice of research philosophy or the nature of the research. According to Saunders (2011), the adoption of techniques, interpretation and results form the basis of a research approach which further depends on the nature and the research problem. Creswell (2003) claims that further data collection and analysis can only be aligned on the choice of the right research approach. The three divisions of research approaches most used are inductive, deductive and abductive approaches (Ritchies *et al*, 2013).

3.3.1 DEDUCTIVE APPROACH

The most common presumption of deductive approaches can be the use of quantitative tools and methods. Positivists employing scientific approaches and statistical analysis, use different variables and their interaction to understand a phenomenon (Thornhill *et al*, 2009). A deductive approach suits researchers who work with numbers and figures, collectively quantitative data, to derive a generic concept towards a more specific area. Saunders (2011) elaborates methods to arrive at conclusions and develops a framework for testing hypotheses. Creating hypotheses and testing them over existent strategies and academic knowledge can be the prominent attributes that deductive approach deals with. This approach starts with investigating existing theories, developing hypotheses, interpreting the data collected through statistical analysis methods and arriving at conclusions based on them. According to Hair *et al* (2015), deductive approach best suits researchers dealing with cause and effect of different variables and their interaction. According to Zikmund *et al* (2013), deductive approach proves efficient when the conclusions need to be generalized, wherein a theory/hypothesis may be tested for a specific scenario.

3.3.2 INDUCTIVE APPROACH

In contradiction to deductive approach, inductive approach proves useful for qualitative researchers to collect in-depth information and unique insights into a phenomenon. Inductive approach aids researchers to collect multiple views and opinions and finally interpret them to obtain useful information (Colis and Hussey, 2003). The inductive approach deals with primary and secondary data collection wherein a theme gets built to further approach the research questions. According to Saunders (2011), the inductive approach strongly associates itself with the qualitative nature of the research.

This approach works in reverse where the theory or hypothesis gets built in the later part of the research as compared to being formed in the beginning of a deductive approach. This approach results in new theories being proposed in contrast to existing theories being validated. Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004), argue for an inductive approach to employ observations to arrive at conclusions and then interpret through data analysis techniques as compared to statistical and systematic analysis. The flow of information from more generic to specific can be associated with deductive approach whereas a more specific information to a generic view can be associated with inductive approach. Hair *et al* (2015), claims that different research studies may adopt different approaches based on the information being obtained, solely depending on the nature of the research, which makes the choice of the approach incredibly significant to the research, wherein one approach may not be ideal for all types of research.

3.3.3 ABDUCTIVE APPROACH

Abductive approaches address the cons of both deductive and inductive approaches. Bryman and Bell (2015), highlights the lack of clarity in deductive approaches to choose theories and then create hypotheses. Saunders *et al* (2012), highlights the lack of empirical evidence in inductive approaches to back the generic conclusions. Both these disadvantages can overcome these limitations by having a more pragmatist view. Although theories and hypotheses can be part of abductive approaches, they emerge from observations where there is a lack of information about the phenomena in existing theories. According to Saunders *et al* (2012), the use of both quantitative and qualitative data and techniques involving numbers and human interactions can differentiate abductive approaches from the other two. Abductive approach has been claimed to be more complex and time consuming when the researcher is relatively new to academic publishing.

3.3.4 JUSTIFICATION FOR THE CHOSEN APPROACH

Table 3.2 meticulously examines the disparities among the three approaches concerning logic, information flow, data, and theory application. Recognizing the nuances in research nature and judiciously selecting the appropriate approach becomes pivotal, as emphasized by Lincoln and Guba (1985). This table serves as a strategic tool, not merely illuminating distinctions but providing a comprehensive guide for researchers to align their chosen approach with the intrinsic demands of their study, thereby enhancing the rigor and relevance of their research endeavors.

Table 3. 2 Comparison of research approaches

ATTRIBUTE	DEDUCTIVE	INDUCTIVE	ABDUCTIVE
Logic	The conclusion are true because the hypothesis is true	Generating untested conclusion from known theories	Generating a testable conclusion from incomplete observation
Flow of information	Generic to specific	Specific to generic	Interaction between specific and generic
Application of data	Data collected validates an hypothesis	Data collected explores themes to create conceptual frameworks	Data collected explores and validates themes, frameworks and results
Theory	Validating an existing theory	Building new theories	Modify or generate existing/new theories

Source: Adopted from Dudovskiy (2016)

The reasons why an inductive approach has been chosen for this research; 1) The concept of sustainability as identified as a literature gap has not been conceptualized or categorized in the Indian context. Also, Agile transformation and its impact over the holistic sustainability of IT startups is a relatively new and understudied concept. Choosing an inductive approach for this research allows new theories or concepts based on the data to be generated rather than testing pre-existing hypotheses, making it especially useful when little is known about the subject. 2) The nature of research questions as stated in Chapter 1 are open-ended and do not have predetermined hypotheses, which makes an inductive approach the most appropriate. A more organic exploration of the data, or themes and patterns emerged from data collected is what inductive approach allows in research. 3) A comprehensive understanding of sustainability and Agile transformation is a pre-requisite for achieving the research objectives. The inductive approach proves more advantageous because this research deals with diverse data sets, agile experts and IT startup industry professionals and enables the exploration of the data's intricacies and variations. 4) Applying an inductive approach aids the dynamic nature of the research process which allows iterative cycles of data collection and analysis, which further enables the researcher to refine focus and theories as the subject or phenomenon is studied in-depth. 5) Working with qualitative data in comparison to quantitative data qualifies an inductive approach to be more suitable for this research.

6) The research problem sustainability is more specific to the IT startup industry and therefore the data collected will arrive at more generic reasons as to why they fail, directing from specific to more generic information. 7) The aim of this research is to gain perspectives in contrast to validating theories and therefore needs a thematic approach to deal with research problems. Although having chosen an inductive approach to be most suitable, it can be necessary to consider advantages and disadvantages in both approaches to be cautious (Patton, 1990).

The reasons for not choosing deductive approach for this research; 1) This research predominantly deals with qualitative data and not numbers/figures/facts. 2) A hypothesis has not been created prior to actual data observation or collection. 3) Semi-structured interviews and focus groups have been chosen as tools for data collection and therefore deductive approaches must be ruled out. 4) The research area which is agile transformation for the sustainability of Indian IT startups, lacks established theories and moreover, the research questions are exploratory and open-ended, the deductive approach might not be the most suitable. 5) Additionally, deductive research requires clearly defined variables and a well-established relationship between them. The intended aim of this research is complex, and multifaceted, which does not lend itself to clear hypotheses. There is a need for new patterns and relationships during the data collection to be discovered. These points strongly support the justification of inductive approach for this research.

The unsuitability of an abductive approach for this research is underscored by several compelling reasons: 1) The research is purely qualitative, precluding the need for a hybrid approach. 2) While abductive reasoning can address empirical gaps, the complexity, time constraints, and deadlines of this study necessitate a more efficient and streamlined approach for optimal quality. 3) Given the research's focus on human interaction rather than scientific data, an abductive approach would unnecessarily complicate the exploration of perspectives. Moreover, the imperative for a conclusive framework demands avoidance of incomplete and ambiguous information, further rendering the abductive approach less fitting for the research's objectives.

This emphatically advocates for the inductive approach as the most fitting and pertinent method for this research. The selection of this research method is not only more aligned to the interpretivism philosophy but also simplifies the investigative process, underlining its suitability for the research's objectives.

3.4 RESEARCH DESIGN

Zikmund *et al.* (2013) assert that the research design serves as the compass, charting the course of research by linking philosophies and approaches to data collection methods. To effectively address the research problem and answer the research questions, researchers must adopt a research design that differentiates in terms of philosophical assumption, scientific method, nature and form of data collected, conclusions drawn, data analysis techniques and adoption advantages. Creswell (2003) categorizes research designs into three, namely quantitative, qualitative, and mixed. These categories, as depicted in Table 3.3, offer a comprehensive overview of their distinctions, guiding researchers in the strategic selection of an approach that aligns with their specific research objectives. Table 3.3 Comparison of research designs

ATTRIBUTE	QUANTITATIVE	QUALITATIVE	MIXED METHOD
Philosophical assumption	Positivism	Interpretivism	Pragmatism
Scientific method	Confirmatory	Exploratory	Confirmatory and exploratory
Strategies	Experimental Non-experimental	Phenomenology Ethnography Narrative inquiry Case Study Grounded theory	Concurrent Sequential Transformative
Nature and Form of Data collected	Variables Structured and proven data measurements Close-ended questions Numeric values	Words, themes, categories In-depth interviews Field notes Observations Open-ended questions	Mixture of variable, words, themes and categories Collect various forms of data Both qualitative and quantitative approaches
Conclusions	Generalizable findings	Specific findings / unique insights	Both objective and subjective viewpoints
Data analysis	Identifies relationships between variables	Identifies patterns within themes and articulates framework	In separate and combined use of both analysis techniques
Pros	Higher accuracy because of empirical evidence Larger sample can be accommodated Fast and easy	Encourages ambiguity for more research to be done Works real time and allows flexibility to create a generic framework	Hypotheses generated through qualitative approach can be validated and tested through quantitative approach New theories and modification of existing theories

Source: Adopted from Creswell (2003)

3.4.1 QUANTITATIVE METHOD

When a situation can be analyzed structurally and the required data can be quantified using statistical analysis, quantitative methods can prove most effective and suitable (Bell *et al*, 2018). Collecting data from relatively easy to access participants using distributed surveys and questionnaires form the main characteristics of quantitative methods. Eyisi (2016), argues that the numeric characteristics of the data collected in quantitative research can have predictable and arguably most reliable results.

Sekaran and Bougie (2016), claim that the study of science mostly uses this research method given the high dependency upon numbers and facts to propose a hypothesis or a theory. Wider samples and larger sizes can be accommodated through quantitative research methods. Marschan-Piekkari and Welch (2004), propose tables, charts and graphs are amongst the predominantly used tools for representing the collected data and results, which in turn evaluate relationships between variables. Bryman and Bell (2015), furthers the use of tools and techniques to investigate and test hypotheses for larger samples. Sarandakos (1998) and Denzin and Lincoln (2011), correlate quantitative methods to positivist approaches given the alignment between beliefs, approach and tools being used. Cresswell (2003), adds triangulation to the list of purposes that quantitative methods can be suitable, making questionnaires and surveys as the initial source of data collection for any paradigm. Having the sole purpose of quantifying results, quantitative method works with numbers, Figures, etc., in contrast to the qualitative method. The emphasizes on precise measurements, higher accuracy, empirical evidence, etc., can best characterize quantitative methods which can further explain the relationship between variables through tables and graphs (Jackson and Ruderman, 1995).

According to Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004), the empirical nature of quantitative methods can help researchers that work with larger groups of participants. Allan (1991) classifies quantitative methods to be primary and secondary research based on the nature of data being collected. Sukamolson (2007), further adds factorial designs, regression analysis, structural equations, complex experiments, etc., as few other tools used in the quantitative methods. Ticehurst and Veal (2000) and Sukamolson (2007), highlight the inability of quantitative tools to quantify human behavior and emotions, which further suppress their scope towards addressing detailed research of a specific phenomenon.

3.4.2 QUALITATIVE METHOD

Most scholars argue qualitative methods to be the process of interpreting any form of non-numerical data, referred to as language, which perceives reality through themes and then analyses them. The observational nature of qualitative methods associates this with interpretivism, wherein words through experience of participants have more value towards the research (Welman *et al*, 2005). Researchers aiming to explore phenomena to result in new and evolving theories find qualitative methods to best suit them. According to Saunders (2011), qualitative methods best capture cultural values, human behavior, unbiased opinions, etc., through in-depth interviews, focus groups, observations, etc. William (2007) and Sekaran and Bougie (2016), emphasize the active participation between the researcher and the observant to bring out the theoretical nature of the research. The in-depth analysis of a phenomena involves choosing the right participants and ruling out larger, irrelevant samples to a smaller and more meaningful sample size.

In this method, a more specific problem gets scrutinized to get a more general result than wider scopes (Babbie and Mouton, 2004). Wider positions of epistemologies, theoretical frameworks and distinctive research methods can best associate qualitative methods to interpretivism. Nagy Hesse-Biber and Leavy (2004), claim qualitative approaches as a threat to quantitative researchers, where there's freedom of more open-ended questions. Pekrun *et al* (2002) and Leedy and Ormrod (2001), have attributed qualitative as a research method that focuses on bringing complexities associated with a specific real-world phenomenon through varied perspectives. Silverman (1998) and Dooley (2007), appraise qualitative methods to capture real world business practices which cannot be quantified or measured using statistical methods as in quantitative methods.

Moreover, Donalek (2005), reinstated the qualitative method to its broader perspective of understanding human experience, reinforcing the power of verbal descriptions to carry more value and relevance to real-world problems. Jackson and Ruderman (1995) and Denzin and Lincoln (2011), explain that certain emotions and behaviors cannot be measured for traits such as quantity, intensity, etc., whereas understood and interpreted in a meaningful manner. The tools used for qualitative research methods bring out information that cannot be obtained from statistics and figures. As opposed to gathering limited information from wider participants to merely validate a hypothesis as in quantitative methods, qualitative methods identify a potential smaller group to gain complex or large information that can lead to a new theory or another area of research.

Table 3. 4 Difference between quantitative and qualitative researcher

QUANTITATIVE RESEARCHER	QUALITATIVE RESEARCHER
Has deductive worldview	Has inductive worldview
Studies a known phenomenon	Studies a relatively unknown phenomenon
Tests hypothesis and theories	Develops hypothesis and theories
Conducts research in controlled settings	Conducts research in natural or real settings
Highly sensitive to self-interest and benefits from the research	Highly emergent and willing to learn/take risks
Uses more complex reasoning	Usually, interpretative

Source: Adapted from Rossman and Rallis (1998)

The differences in the characteristics of quantitative and qualitative researchers are tabulated in Table 3.4. The laboratory approach of deductive philosophies or quantitative methods has been criticized for business studies, given its failure to function and benefit in the real world, rather than just a theory. In contrast, the highly interactive and social values inclusive nature of qualitative methods prove that researchers who adapt this method would ideally bridge the gap between theories and practical problems. Patton (2002) and Creswell (1999), identify these traits as the fundamental reasons as to why interviews, observations and focus groups can typically bring out in-depth information from the participants, considering their experience, viewpoints and emotions while collecting data from them.

As qualitative methods work with qualitative or non-numeric data, the evaluation or data analysis approaches use traditional procedures such as grounded theory, ethnography, phenomenology historical, case study and action research (Patton, 2002; Strauss and Corbin, 1998; Potter and Wetherell, 1994; Leiblich, 1998). Researchers in contrast employ straightforward procedures to analyze qualitative data, regardless of traditional approaches. Dey (1993), Bryman and Burgess (1994) and Ezzy (2013), have been contributing towards the literature of non-traditional qualitative data analysis, deriving a more generic and less complicated approach to handling qualitative data. According to Saunders (2011), any qualitative analysis or approach must lead to the summary of findings from the real-time data, identifying links between themes and research objectives and finally developing a framework that works for real time research problems.

3.4.3 JUSTIFICATION FOR THE CHOSEN RESEARCH DESIGN

The reasons that justify the choice of qualitative method are as follows; 1) As this research aims towards contributing to the sustainability and process innovation of Indian IT startups, there is an inherent interest in observing and comprehending everyday experiences of startup processes and focus on the quality of the activities rather than the frequency of its occurrence. This demands exploratory research where activities, situations, materials, and quality of relationships associated with research participants are explored. This justifies the reason for choosing qualitative method. 2) Qualitative methods address the research questions in Chapter 1 concerning ‘how’ and ‘why’ and provide room to understand the context, phenomena, and experiences. It is not an easy task to arrive at answers for this nature of questions in terms of numbers as they are human experiences and perceptions. However, getting answers to these questions is essential to contribute to the existing knowledge and literature in sustainability and agile transformation, further developing our understanding. In this regard, the qualitative method seems more suitable and appropriate for this research. 3) The basic philosophy or worldview behind this research is predominantly interpretivism. Hair *et al* (2015) and Bryman and Bell (2015), claim interpretivism to benefit ethnographers who interpret a specific phenomenon in context with a specific ethnic group. Copper *et al* (2006) and Cavana *et al* (2001), bring out critical ethnography as the cross-cultural research approach that covers wider, broader and diverse views to best address the research problem. Most researchers appraise this method to add greater insights to academic literature and add value to the business world (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013; Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). 4) By adopting qualitative methods, this research can accommodate literary and flexible data collection that creates themes and patterns to outline transcribed interview data. 5) As identified in Chapter 2, there are gaps in the existing literature of sustainability and agile transformation in the context of Indian IT startups, and consequently, there is a need to develop new theories, strengthen current theories, or even apply existing theories in new settings. Applying qualitative methods can enhance and enrich the rationale for a new framework to be developed. This will allow future researchers to build on something new and probably find viable solutions.

India, predominantly Tier 1 cities have been chosen as the target ethnic group of this research and the focus is mainly on IT startups and the managers who are strongly associated with its operation, consultation and coaches to identify the factors that impact sustainability in an agile environment.

As Creswell (2013), claims triangulation methods that interlink focus groups and interviews to be highly beneficial for ethnographic research, it has been incorporated into this research. According to Saunders (2011) and Sekaran and Bougie (2016), interactive and diverse data collection methods have been utilized to largely avoid validity issues of this research. Denzin and Lincoln (2011), describe a qualitative method to be observational and that can be highly associated with this research given the perceptions and opinions of managers, agile coaches and project managers in IT startups. This research highlights individual experience, views and opinions over the wider area of agile transformation in context with IT startups. As this research needs more than just mere numbers to effectively address the research problem, language will be used as the effective communication tool to collect qualitative data.

The quantitative methods cannot capture feelings, perceptions and human behaviors through numbers, charts and figures and therefore has been ruled out for this research. Yvonne (2010) and Lewis (2015), include the interpretation of qualitative data into relevant information as an integral part of understanding phenomena. This research aims to capture the phenomena through the perspective of startup founders, co-founders and entrepreneurs and agile coaches, agile practitioners and project managers who have worked for years in the industry. Viewing the major crisis of lack of sustainability through their views and perceptions can bring best results that can help other startups align right from the seed stage. By adopting a case study approach, this research can logically approach the phenomena by comparing literature with data collected. As Saunders (2011) and Hair *et al* (2015) claim, analytical approach, logical reasoning and easy access to target customers can be the prominent traits to select a case study approach for this research. An integration of conceptual frameworks and the developed theories can happen by using case study methods (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). The responses from semi-structured interviews and focus groups used in this research will be integrated to create a new conceptual framework that will benefit emerging or established startups in India.

The clear gap within earlier literatures has been the fact that the manager's perspectives and opinions have not been considered as inputs into an agile startup framework, which has kept it theoretically attractive but practically useless. Patton (2002) compares statistical with qualitative generalization to conclude that qualitative researchers understand the phenomena in depth and rely on the perceptions of managers and coaches for validity and reliability of data collected.

Critical ethnography in addition to the case study approach enhances the scope of this research. The active participation from both ends can explore rich ideas and theories, proving qualitative research more suitable for this research than quantitative methods (Zikmund *et al*, 2013; Patton, 2002; Bryman and Bell, 2015). Cultural and industrial relevance of the researcher with the participants can additionally create pathways for easy interpretation of data, closeness to the research, better engagement level and value for the researcher. The researcher having personally collected data through active participation in interviews, carries richness over small sized samples (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Robson (2007) criticizes qualitative research to be failing if the selection process tends to be flawed and biased. Yet Creswell (1999), has claimed that even 10 interviews can best satisfy the data collection if it meets the point of data saturation. This research considers both these views and therefore selects participants based only on their relevance to the phenomena and nothing else, which can avoid biases and criticism over validity.

A highly populated country like India, where there are hundreds of startups emerging, mere 34 samples cannot summarize the actual phenomena, yet this research will be the beginning of something new that can inspire more researchers to carry it forward. As qualitative methods impose data to be collected in their natural settings, the researcher will personally be present in the IT startups, observe the operations and then interview the managers and agile coaches in their respective environments.

3.5 RESEARCH CHOICE: TRIANGULATION

Patton (1999) proposed using multiple methods in qualitative research to obtain in-depth understanding of the phenomena, which has largely impacted researchers with validation and reliability tests. Patton (1999) and Denzin and Lincoln (2011), collectively identified four categories of triangulation combining methods, observers, theories and data sources. Most researchers credit triangulation to overcome biases such as single method, observer or theory, providing a more balanced view of the phenomena (Heale and Forbes, 2013). Moreover, triangulation adds dimensions to the phenomena by combining these four traits. Combining different data sources, referred to as data triangulation, such as participants, in this case managers and coaches, can increase validity. Combining more observers or researchers, referred to as observer triangulation, can include peer perspectives on the same phenomena being dealt with, using the same qualitative method.

Combining collective theories, referred to as theory triangulation, can provide different perspectives on the interpretation of the same data, bringing cross-disciplined views into account for the same phenomena. Combining both quantitative and qualitative or two different tools in the same methods, referred to as methodological triangulation, can be useful to compare results from different methods, predominantly to establish validity and credibility of data. Thurmond (2001), explains how triangulation can build confidence in researchers and peers in the academic circle to publish data regarding the phenomena, elevating the scope of the phenomena by integrating more theories and exploring innovative ideas to best explain it.

This research utilizes data triangulation by combining participants from both industrial IT startups in India and agile expertise. This research also utilizes methodological triangulation wherein semi-structured interviews and focus groups have been used to add more validity and reliability to the research. Previous research has failed to use triangulation in the context of Indian IT startups, which makes this research exceptionally reliable for the data collected.

One significant limitation lies in the increased complexity and resource demands associated with employing multiple data collection methods which may escalate costs, extend timelines, necessitate a higher level of expertise, contradictory findings from different sources that introduces interpretive challenges, possibility of common biases affecting all data sources, etc. Triangulation can enhance the robustness of this research, when its advantages are judiciously weighed against the practical challenges and interpretive complexities. Justification for choosing triangulation for this research are: 1) Credibility and reliability is integral and concerning for qualitative methods. This research deals with agile transformation as a management concept and unites this with the sustainability of Indian IT startups. There are two different perspectives or data sets that need to converge to get similar results to enhance the overall trustworthiness of the study. To accommodate this, triangulation needs to be employees. 2) Qualitative data is often questioned for individual biases and subjectivity. By cross-verifying findings from both qualitative methods, the researcher can reduce the impact of personal perspectives and provide a more objective and well-rounded analysis. 3) Consistent findings from both sources can strengthen the validity of conclusions, increasing confidence in research outcomes. 4) There are strengths and weaknesses in individual qualitative methods. Using two methods can help one's strength compensate for the other's weakness. This overall strengthens the choice of triangulation for this research.

3.6 RESEARCH STRATEGY: CASE STUDY

This research adopts a case study approach as the predominant research strategy. Saunders (2011) and Hair *et al* (2015), claim the case study strategy to be most effective for the integration or bridging between business and academic scopes through opinions and experiences, thereby adhering to the research objectives. Although agile is a vast literature with years of academic research and developments, relatively few researchers have attempted to tap into agile for startups. Sustainability, although being the major crisis for larger IT companies and often associated with their maturity projects, tends to demotivate startups to adopt them in their initial stages. This academic gap has never been addressed and bridged through a definite conceptual framework that can guide startup practitioners and managers, explaining the phenomena in detail. Therefore, this research requires an in-depth understanding of the field of study and comprehends the phenomena into frameworks that can guide other startups in the industry.

There exists convincing evidence for the impacts that case study strategy can have when research requires a concrete and contextual depth of understanding about a specific phenomenon of interest (Yvonne Felizer, 2010; Zikmund *et al*, 2013). Keeping the research focused and relatively manageable, given the time and cost constraints, case study design can definitely help this research be most effective for a smaller sample size (Lewis, 2015). Multiple case studies or only one case can be chosen to highlight the research problem in depth. Sekaran and Bougie (2016), appraise case study design for its ability to capture the perceptions of the observant, providing a collective report of experiences and further interpreting it to provide context to the research problem. Guest *et al* (2006) and Hair *et al* (2015), also highlight the benefits of case study design in providing new or unexpected results that can challenge assumptions or theories by proposing a more practical solution to the business world and opening new academic study areas for future research.

This research aims to collaborate different viewpoints of actual startup managers and agile expertise to collect necessary information about the sustainability of Indian IT startups. Ozuem *et al* (2008), claims that presenting the case study through research questions could be the very first integral step towards data collection. This research also adopts Yin's approach towards research by addressing the research questions to then understand what needs to be done. In Chapter 1, we see that the main focus or case of the research questions and objectives remain on sustainability of IT startups in India.

This research therefore presents deeper insights into this phenomenon, capturing experiences and viewpoints of various participants. The final research questions demand a new theoretical or conceptual framework to be built based on the research problem, aiming to bridge business and academic worlds. Explanatory design has been implemented given the need to document existing theories based on sustainability, agile transformation and startups. As Eisenhardt (2007), clearly states, this research would not include any data outside the context of Indian IT startups because it would not serve the purpose of this research. The interviews and focus groups used in this research aim to provide the basis for the development of a new theory or framework (Marschan-Piekkari and Welch, 2004). The IT startup industry cannot be overlooked in India for its prolonged contribution towards the country's GDP and global growth. Many government policies and regulations have been targeted to benefit such startups, which proves the failure of these startups in their early stage as a serious threat and a definite case study for research.

3.6.1 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING CASE STUDY

The justifications for choosing a case study strategy are: 1) The flexibility of case study strategy to be integrated with other research methods provides a comprehensive approach. In Section 3.4.3, the choice of qualitative methods was justified. Nevertheless, if future researchers build on this research, it'd be easier for them to combine these qualitative data with surveys or experiments to triangulate findings and enhance the validity of the results; 2) Case study strategy also allows the flexibility of research to be conducted longitudinally, allowing researchers to track changes and understand how the phenomena evolves; 3) This research focuses directly on influencing and impacting Indian IT startups by addressing a real world phenomenon which is the startup sustainability. This requires real-world relevance, to make informed decision-making, develop a conceptual framework and formulate a practical road map for startups, which can be best achieved through case study; 4) It was established as a literature gap in Chapter 2, Section 2.6, that a holistic perspective of startup sustainability which incorporates project sustainability has not been tapped into by previous researchers. Case study strategy enables the examination of entire startups, and this holistic perspective is useful to understand interdependencies and how various elements influence each other; 5) Case study strategy for this research, moreover, allows for an in-depth understanding of sustainability within its real-life Indian IT startup context which highlights complexities and nuances that may be missed in more quantitative approaches.

3.7 PILOT STUDY

Welman *et al* (2005), claims pilot study to be the prototype of the actual research to be conducted to see whether the proposed methodology works for effective data collection. Pilot study consists of a miniature visualization of the full-scale research and primarily evaluates cost structure, risk associated, time required and feasibility in prior to intensive research (Daniel and Sam, 2011). 5 detailed interviews where factors such as current practices, adoption of agile methods in various environments, strategies to maximize efficiency, etc., were considered as protocols that facilities. A few limitations such as availability of managers and unfamiliarity of agile methods may require additional attention to access issues and pre-education of research significance. Conducted over a smaller scale as compared to larger scale provides straightforward feedback and areas for improvement for research quality. Pilot studies can also enrich the Researcher with adequate areas that need to be researched even before asking questions to actual respondents. Zikmund *et al* (2013), argues that pilot study must consider ethical issues and sample randomization.

3.7.1 FEEDBACK FROM THE PILOT STUDY

This research needed clarification on the right and suitable research questions that can bring out the actual phenomena in much rawness and richness. Therefore, pilot study was the inevitable option to ask the respondents chosen through inclusion and exclusion strategy, to contemplate if the research questions were clear, well directed towards achieving the goals of the research and enough to extract necessary information (Guest *et al*, 2006; Lewis, 2015). The experience of worked/working in a startup, knowledge about agile transformation, operating/consulting in India, were few of the criteria's that were included in the pilot study of this research. The criteria used in the pilot study conducted over the period of two months from July-August 2021 were also the integral criteria for actual participants for the main research that happened months later.

The interview process used for the pilot study mimicked the actual research interview process, which led to a few suggestions and issues raised within the interviews. A few startup founders and managers responded plainly explaining their unavailability to attend this interview, claiming this to be a waste of time and cost for their daily operation. Few agile coaches and practitioners have been in the industry for years and do not believe in agile being the actual solution for the startup problems. Few entrepreneurs who have just established their startup, were unaware of agile transformation but were welcoming towards the concept if it provides a practical solution.

Few project managers who have worked for top IT companies criticize agile to be methodologically possible but practically impossible to solve all the problems. As in Chapter 2, these misconceptions about agile and people being unaware about it were expected but the struggle of actual data collection from startup founders was evident from these interviews. Taking this feedback from the pilot study into consideration, the researcher then rephrased some questions in the interview that were too agile focused for the startup founders to avoid reluctance and resistance from them. A new incentive such as free consultation through contacts already accumulated was seen as an attraction to bring in more respondents. The interview process incorporates an introduction to the long-term impact of the phenomena to enhance participant awareness. Certain interviews with individuals deemed irrelevant for the study may be excluded, yet they could provide access to key interviewees supporting the research.

3.8 RESEARCH SAMPLING

3.8.1 POPULATION

According to Elfil and Negida (2017) and Omair (2014), the population refers to the set of people or objects who share the same characteristics or express the same qualities that a researcher is interested in. As of this research, the population would be the startup managers or agile expertise, directly or indirectly involved with agile methodologies of SDLC in general.

3.8.2 SAMPLING

The process of sampling involves a sub-group of people from the population being chosen by the researcher to measure, test or validate the relevance of a research (Shorten and Moorley, 2014). The sample chosen can represent the entire population, ensuring the generalizability of research findings, keeping in mind the difficulty of accommodate everyone to be interviewed and asked for their opinion, given the time and cost constraints. Also, the lack of access to certain demography, destructive nature of observant and inaccuracy in choosing the wrong sampling technique can be threats for the selection of sampling techniques (Tyrer and Heyman, 2016). Researchers argue that although the right sampling technique can help generalize findings, every research suffers from sampling error wherein the findings deviate from the actual reality. Most researchers claim sampling bias to be the predominant cause for the sampling error where the data collected favors one group over the other, accused to be the result of poor choice of sampling methods.

3.8.3 SAMPLING METHODS

According to Omair (2014) and Tyrer and Heyman (2016), sampling methods can be broadly classified into probability and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling methods further divided into random, cluster, systematic and stratified sampling involves random selection wherein all the participants have the equal probability of being chosen for specific research (Shorten and Moorley, 2014). Non-Probability sampling methods further divided into quota, purposive, self-selection and snowball sampling involve a judgement or reason for a specific choice of participant for research (Elfil and Negida, 2017). The comparison of these two sampling methods has been tabulated in Table 3.5.

Table 3. 5 Difference between probability and non-probability sampling

COMPARISON ATTRIBUTES	PROBABILITY	NON-PROBABILITY
Definition	All participants of the population have equal probability/opportunity to be selected as sample	Only selected participants from the population are judged to be appropriate selection of sample
Selection process	Random	Subjective judgement
Nature of selection	Fixed and predetermined	Not specified
Nature of method	Fair/non-discriminatory	Instinctive/prejudiced
Sampling Bias	Comparatively low	Comparatively high
Hypothesis	Tested	Generated
Inference type	Statistical	Analytical
Research type	Confirmatory	Exploratory/descriptive

Source: Adaption of Elfil and Negida (2017)

The set of research questions, the chosen methodology, knowledge and access to the population of interest, sample size, deviations between findings, time and cost constraints can be considered the significant factors that decide the sampling method to be appropriate for research (Shorten and Moorley, 2014). As this research tends to be more inductive and qualitative in nature, the non-probability sampling proves to extract rich data from participants. According to Young and Casey (2019), researchers who approach non-probability sampling select samples based on subjective judgement instead of random sampling. Although there exists criticism of non-probability sampling for being biased and researcher focused, this research sampling method has theoretical evidence and strong practical reasons to be applied in research.

3.8.4 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING NON-PROBABILITY SAMPLING

Non-probability sampling, while departing from the strict randomness of probability sampling, offers several robust advantages that make it a deliberate and strategic choice for this research. One compelling reason is the flexibility it provides in the selection of participants, allowing the researcher to target specific individuals or groups with unique and specialized knowledge pertinent to the research objectives. Qualitative researchers who use non-probability sampling methods can furnish convincing evidence for their samples to be included in their research rather than just feel forced to use this sampling method because of the lack of access, time and cost-constraints. As the main focus of this research is not to generalize theories but to generate new theories that can give an in-depth understanding of the phenomena, non-probability sampling proves to best anchor this research in the right direction. The researcher must keep in mind the bias and validity of data being collected as this can pose a serious threat for the research if overlooked. Practical reasons for this research to adopt non-probability sampling is the cost-effective, time-efficient and quicker selection process compared to random sampling. The limited research in the area of agile transformation in Indian IT startups, demands an exploratory research method where the research brings out the phenomena in much detail. Non-probability sampling can help avoid time consuming or expensive research and directly focus on the participants that are completely relevant for this research.

3.8.5 SAMPLING STRATEGY: PURPOSIVE SAMPLING STRATEGY

According to Omair (2014), purposive sampling uses the judgement of the researcher to select samples for the research wherein the sample size can be relatively smaller or larger than random sampling methods. Elfil and Negida (2017), claims that making generalization of theories cannot be the ultimate intention for choosing sampling methods during a qualitative research and therefore non-probability sampling focuses on particular traits or interests within the population to best understand the phenomena or research problem, in this case the understanding of agile methods. Although some researchers claim purposive sampling to be inaccurate with the representation of the entire population, qualitative researchers use this sampling technique to determine extremes, existence and explore different views of the phenomena of interest (Shorten and Moorley, 2014).

3.8.6 APPRAISALS AND CRITICISM OF PURPOSIVE SAMPLING

The wider range of purposive sampling techniques from homogeneous to expert sampling and mixed techniques gives more options for the researcher to achieve the best data collection (Omair, 2014; Shorten and Moorley, 2014). Although generalizations can be drawn out of purposive sampling strategies, researchers can be prone to high probability of research bias where an ill-constructed framework or poorly conceived judgements can produce inaccurate results and findings (Elfil and Negida, 2017).

3.8.7 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING PURPOSIVE SAMPLING

According to Patton (1990), the best samples produce rich information that can help the research with its quality and accuracy. This research adopts a purposive sampling strategy that combines the following techniques to gather in-depth and rich data for this research. Homogenous sampling helps determine samples based on common traits or characteristics that can separate them from the population. This research uses homogeneous sampling strategy with the focus of grouping samples who share the traits of entrepreneurs of IT startups, agile consultants and coaches, project managers of larger companies and IT employees. Snowball sampling allows participants to contribute towards the selection of samples where there exists difficulty finding participants. As this research focuses on IT startups, each startup founder has a pool of connections who they can suggest as valuable interviews for this research. This helps the researcher to also broaden connections for future research and therefore snowball technique can increase the accessibility of participants.

Criterion sampling poses various relevant and significant criteria for pre-selecting samples from the population. This research needs to filter out irrelevant and unnecessary samples, keeping in mind the research bias solely to achieve the objectives of this research. The inclusion and exclusion criteria have been tabulated in Table 3.6. The first criterion determines whether the sample selected from the population has their startup established solely in India or have worked for an Indian startup demography. As this research addressed the issues specific to Indian IT startups, it can be irrelevant to include startups outside India, although they share some common interests. Therefore, startups established in Tier 1 cities namely, Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata, Bangalore, Hyderabad, Ahmedabad and Pune are of best interest for this research.

As this research completely focuses on IT startups, the sample selected must qualify the basic requirement of being established for less than 7 years. This results in IT startups with more than 7 years of establishment being excluded from the sampling because of irrelevance to this research.

Table 3. 6 Purposive sampling: Inclusion and exclusion

CRITERIA	INCLUSION	EXCLUSION
Country of establishment	Tier 1 cities in India	Outside India
Established years of IT Startup	1 to 7 years	More than 7 years means the startups are well established
Experience in SDLC	Aware of traditional or non-traditional software methodologies of product life cycle	Not aware of methodologies of any sort related to traditional or non-traditional methodologies
Agile transformation	Having some knowledge of Agile transformation and it's positive or negative impact	Having no knowledge of Agile transformation and its impacts over IT startups

Experience in SDLC can be considered as a significant criterion for sampling given the fact that in Chapter 2, the researcher has discussed multiple divisions within the IT industry. Therefore, the ideal sampling would include IT startups that develop software as product/service centered, following any methodology or process for its development. As this research compares traditional and agile transformation methodologies, it would be a necessity for the interviewee to understand basic terms related to the methodologies. The final criteria include samples with at least minimum awareness of agile transformation and its positive or negative impacts as it forms the basis of this research. Samples with no awareness of agile transformation cannot contribute towards the scope of this research. A few participants addressed through pilot study made it clear that they are unaware of agile or methodologies of any sort and therefore proved irrelevance to this research.

3.8.8 SAMPLE SIZE

Bartlett *et al* (2001), claims that determining the sample size can be crucial for any research to evaluate its value and relevance in a theory generation. Quantitative researchers have statistical methods to determine the number of participants and therefore have less complexity as compared to qualitative researchers, because of the exclusion of researcher and participant biases.

Moreover, the ability to accommodate a larger number of participants gives qualitative researchers an upper hand when evaluated for accuracy and validity. Qualitative researchers require meaningful judgements or strategies to determine the sample size and therefore can be overly complex (Patton, 1990). According to Patton (1990), the process of determining sample size depends on the nature of research rather than standard rules or procedures. Further, the research objectives, research problems, available time and cost, etc., also play a crucial role in determining the sample size. Leavy (2014), claimed that deeper insights into a research phenomenon can be obtained through relatively smaller sample size, as compared to generalizing theories with larger samples. Sandelowski (2008), argues that qualitative research with smaller sample size can be justified through data saturation. Charmaz (2011), claims that most researchers agree with smaller sample sizes and argues that multiple interviews do not necessarily prove to be meaningful. Cooper *et al* (2006), in their research journal stated 32 interviews to be realistic and minimal to attain data saturation where no added information could be retrieved. Most researchers agree to this number as the minimum interviews needed (Etikan *et al*, 2016; Saunders, 2011; Walker, 2012; Boddy, 2016; Saunders *et al*, 2018). According to Guest *et al* (2006), 15 to 40 interviews can be the average for qualitative research sample size whereas few claim that 10 would be more than sufficient for in-depth understanding (Hair *et al*, 2015; Saunders and Townsend, 2016). This research chooses sample size of 34 including both 20 semi-structured interviews and 2 focus groups with 7 each, which can strongly support this research.

3.8.9 JUSTIFICATION FOR THE SAMPLE SIZE

With data saturation in mind and the recommended number of samples for qualitative researchers, this research selects 20 samples from the population and 2 focus groups including 7 samples each. Although multiple studies have been done on IT startups, there are limited researchers who have tried to relate agile and Indian IT startups and therefore, 20 interview samples and 14 focus samples accounting to 34 in total would prove enough and reliable to represent the population chosen. Moreover, the focus of this research to understand sustainability of IT startups in depth rather than merely generalizing a few theories based on agile methodologies justifies the choice of 34 participants. The semi-structured interviews and focus groups were conducted in sequential manner. The semi-structured interview aims to understand the startup founders' and entrepreneurs' point of view about the sustainability issues that exist within the IT startups in India.

Table 3. 7 Sampling techniques

QUALITATIVE METHOD	SAMPLE SIZE	PARTICIPANTS	QUALIFICATIONS EXPECTED
Semi-structured interviews	20	Startup Founders and Co-Founders	Proven experience as a founder or co-founder of a startup for 1 to 7 years. Excellent leadership and interpersonal skills. Understanding of Indian market dynamics and trends. Ability to thrive in a fast-paced and dynamic environment.
		Startup managers/lead developers	Proven experience in managing IT operations within a startup environment. In-depth knowledge of IT infrastructure, systems, and cybersecurity. Project management certification (e.g., PMP, Agile) is a plus.
		Startup entrepreneurs	Entrepreneurial mindset with a track record of innovation and problem-solving. Understanding of market dynamics and trends. Ability to thrive in a fast-paced and dynamic environment.
		Startup Consultants	Proven experience as an IT consultant, preferably with startups. Strong project management skills and experience overseeing IT projects. In-depth knowledge of cybersecurity, cloud computing, and infrastructure solutions. Familiarity with startup environments and dynamics.
Focus Group	14	Agile coaches	Certified ScrumMaster (CSM) or equivalent Agile certifications. Proven experience as an Agile Coach in a complex organizational setting. In-depth knowledge of Agile frameworks (Scrum, Kanban, etc.) and Agile practices. Experience with Agile scaling frameworks (SAFe, LeSS, etc.). Familiarity with software development processes and methodologies.
		Agile Practitioners	Agile certification (e.g., Certified ScrumMaster, PMI-ACP) or Experience with Agile tools and project management software. Proven experience in managing IT projects, including successful project delivery.
		Project Managers	Project Management Professional (PMP) or equivalent certification.

			Proven experience in managing IT projects, including successful project delivery. Strong technical understanding and familiarity with software development life cycle (SDLC) and IT infrastructure. Proficiency in project management tools and software (e.g., Microsoft Project, Jira).
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Source: Adapter from IBEF (2019)

The semi-structured interviews yielded two pivotal themes: sustainability factors and the perception of transformation methodologies. Beyond these critical aspects, the subsequent exploration in focus groups, comprising agile coaches, agile practitioners, and project managers, aims to delve deeper into the theoretical underpinnings of agile transformation and its potential resolutions to the identified issues. This strategic augmentation enriches the existing findings and serves as a robust mechanism to enhance the research's validity and reliability. The ultimate goal of formulating a novel agile startup sustainability framework for Indian IT startups stands to gain substantial strength through the invaluable insights and diverse perspectives derived from these focused group discussions.

For clarity, Table 3.7, as adapted from IBEF (2019), succinctly outlines the sample size and the specific categories of participants selected, underscoring the methodological rigor and comprehensive approach undertaken in this research endeavor. This table also provides detailed characteristics and proficiency that qualifies each participant in this research. One of the most common qualifications expected from focus groups participants is a strong technical understanding of project management tools, certifications and years of experience. On the other hand, semi-structured interview participants are expected to have familiarity with startup environments and dynamics, to contribute towards identifying sustainability factors.

3.9 DATA COLLECTION METHODS

Embracing its qualitative nature, this research deliberately opts for a smaller sample size of 34 participants, a decision validated in the previous section due to time and cost constraints and other factors as specified. Aligning with the principles outlined by Crewell (2003) and Saunders *et al.* (2018), the emphasis on rich and deep insights underscores the appropriateness of a smaller sample size for this study.

To harness these qualitative data effectively, this research strategically employs a combination of semi-structured interviews and focus groups, ensuring an optimal approach to achieving its research objectives with depth and richness.

3.9.1 INTERVIEWS

As many researchers argue, conversation with each participant can help gather resourceful information (Robson, 2007). According to Longhurst (2003) and Walker (2012), certain data required for research cannot be observed but understood through emotions and behaviors of participants. Saunders (2012), describe three types of interview patterns namely unstructured, structured and semi-structured depending on the rigidity, openness and scope of the questions.

3.9.2 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

This research employs semi-structured in specific. Kruger and Casey (2000), claim semi-structured interviews to be more informal, allowing more conversations to flow and soft in nature. Skop (2006) and Cachia and Millward. (2011), consider semi-structured interviews to be self-conscious and partially structured which allows more open-ended questions rather than objective questions to be included in the questionnaire. Sekaran and Bougie (2016) and Gioia *et al* (2012), claim that semi-structured interviews as compared to other types have more advantage of having both pre-determined questions and room for open-ended questions, extracting rich information and deeper insights. Although criticisms such as inaccuracy, bias and difficulty in comparing findings threaten the reliability and validity of semi-structured interviews, relatively easy and predetermined questions can help guide researchers and participants to stay on topic, which encourages two-way communication (Robson, 2007; Gioia *et al*, 2012).

An average of 25 minutes was chosen as the length of each semi-structured interview, keeping in mind the significance of ideal time to collect as much data as possible from the participant (Robson, 2007). The researcher excluded the idea of an hour's time for these interviews considering the busy schedule of the participants. A consent form as shown in Appendix 6 seeking complete trust and cooperation from the participants and participation information sheet as shown in Appendix 5 which gives a brief answer to all the possible questions that the participants could have, was given to the participants prior to the actual interview. More semi-structured interview questions have been attached in Appendix 2 which clearly relates it to the framework.

As this research focuses on startup founders and entrepreneurs for semi-structured interviews, the location must be decided in convenience with the participants to give comfortability and confidentiality to them (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Audio and video recording of the interviews has been consented with the participants prior to the actual meeting to make them comfortable and aware of the questions put forward (Guest *et al*, 2006; Saunders *et al*, 2009; Lewis, 2015). Most researchers also stress non-verbal body language in addition to the words as valuable to the understanding of the phenomena (Robson, 2007; Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). The semi-structured questions were arranged sequentially addressing each research objective in detail (Robson, 2007; Williams, 2007). The semi-structured nature of the interview questions also gives additional room along with structured questions that can best capture data from each participant.

3.9.3 SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW PROCESS

As this research topic aims to investigate the impact of agile transformation on the sustainability of Indian IT startups, it is much evident that the participants need to be from within India, predominantly from Tier 1 cities. Table 3.6 and 3.7 clearly state the qualifications and expectations of the interview participants wherein a rich understanding Indian IT startup market and trends is a necessity. Conducting a semi-structured interview involves careful planning and execution to gather meaningful and accurate data. Prior to the interview, the researcher established the research objectives and formulated 14 open-ended questions. Pilot testing helped refine questions and ensure clarity. Through CEO portals and IBEF websites, the researcher refined the participants to be selected for this research and sent formal emails, LinkedIn requests, and direct telephone calls.

With the complete assurance of availability and confidentiality, the participants were then asked to complete the consent forms and Participant Information Sheet. Due to COVID - 19 lockdown restrictions, voice over recordings and video recordings were preferred over face-to-face interview. The actual interview began with a formal introduction, establishing rapport and explaining the purpose of this research. Using a set of predetermined questions, the interviewer encouraged in-depth responses through active listening and probing. Flexibility was essential to explore unexpected topics. Recording methods, such as audio/video recording and manual notetaking were two reliable methods used. Closure involved summarizing key points and thanking the interviewee who participated.

An average of 25 - 35 minutes was chosen as the length of each semi-structured interview, keeping in mind the significance of ideal time to collect as much data as possible from the participant (Robson, 2007). The researcher excluded the idea of an hour's time for these interviews considering the busy schedule of the participants.

To enhance validity, questions were aligned with research objectives and to measure intended constructs accurately. Ensuring that researcher and the participants are well-trained on the research objectives, interview protocol, and techniques, developing a standardized interview protocol with a set of core questions to be asked in each interview, conducting a pilot test with a small sample of participants prior to actual interviews, using consistent recording methods, high-quality recording equipment and standard transcription procedures, assessing inter-rater reliability to ensure agreement of codes and themes developed, sharing preliminary findings or interpretations with participants to validate or correct the researcher's understanding and encouraging reflexivity on biases and assumptions were methods to ensure overall reliability of the data collected. Peer review, member checking, and reflexive considerations contributed to the overall rigor of the process, ensuring the collected data is valid and reliable for analysis.

3.9.4 FOCUS GROUPS

Focus groups, a type of interview, combines more than 8 participants to discuss and talk about a specific topic and gives freedom to the participants to share their perspectives about the research problem (Saunders *et al*, 2009). The conversational or interactive nature of focus groups helps every participant to freely engage (Cavana *et al*, 2001). Implementing focus group, although at the expense of bringing all the expertise together can provide clarity and in-depth understanding in the areas uncovered by the semi-structured interviews.

3.9.5 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING FOCUS GROUPS

The benefit of accommodating more than 1 participant at the same time helps the researcher to easily observe words and body language during the discussion when opposing views and opinions emerge. Most researchers argue that focus groups are more dynamic compared to interviews with individual participants (Krueger, 1994; Lewis, 2015).

Wilkinson (1998) and Sandelowski (2008), argue that focus groups contribute immensely towards enhancing the data, creating opportunities to explore theories in a collectively agreed language, giving space for participants to change the direction of data flow, deepening the understanding of the phenomena and observing the derivation of theories. Morgan (1997) and Cameron (2005), argue that focus groups can be focused on a topic yet non-directive, which allows room for exploration of the research phenomena in various angles. According to Goss and Leinback (1996), homogeneous samples form the best participants for focus groups, in this case, participants who are all well-versed in agile transformation and its impacts over wider IT industry. Guest *et al* (2006) and Hair *et al* (2015), argue an hour to be ideal for a focus group discussion, which can conveniently help researchers to settle with the phenomena. Sekaran and Bougie (2016), claims that homogeneous participants from the same level of knowledge and experience can best contribute to meaningful results. Lewis (2015) and Boddy (2016), argue that conflicting personalities can also contribute to a more unbiased and holistic view of research phenomena. Although differences of opinions can be inevitable, the researcher needs to take the responsibility to function between researcher and observer, avoiding conflicts and ensure that the research questions get answered (Ozuem *et al*, 2008). The focus group questions as shown in Appendix 3, complement the semi-structured questions but also help the Researcher gain understanding concepts uncovered in the interviews. The focus group must provide that space for participants to voice their opinions without biases.

3.9.6 FOCUS GROUP PROCESS

In accordance with the research topic, this research considers two focus group as a prominent necessity to further understand the phenomena of agile transformation in depth, and to initiate discussions about Indian IT startup sustainability and its correlation with agile transformation among agile coaches, practitioners and project managers, whose qualifications and expectation are as detailed in Table 3.6 and 3.7. To enhance the robustness of this research, the researcher deliberately incorporated an additional participant specifically chosen to represent the semi-structured interview samples. This meticulous inclusion, alongside the six focus group participants, serves as a strategic measure aimed at fortifying the validity, reliability and overall credibility of the research findings, and also raise difference of opinions for constructive discussions.

Conducting a focus group is a nuanced process requiring careful planning, skilled facilitation, and meticulous recording and therefore prior to the session, thorough preparation was made, involving the definition of research objectives, identification of target participants, and development of 8 open-ended, focus group questions as shown in Appendix 3. For the comfortability of the participants and adhering to COVID –19 lockdown restrictions, Microsoft Teams was used as the platform to conduct, record and transcribe the two focus group discussions. The researcher, the moderator of the group, begins discussions allowing respondents to construct a conversation and generate real time data. Participants were asked to raise their hand, to raise their opinion, whereby each individual participant was given equal opportunity to speak. Creating a conducive atmosphere and establishing ground rules, effective facilitation techniques, such as active listening and probing, encourages participant engagement and ensures the exploration of diverse perspectives. The researcher was also responsible for managing group dynamics and navigating through varying opinions, allowing and extracting participant thoughts and perceptions that were more than just socially acceptable and one-sided answers. The researcher also at instances had to stop a few participants from taking too long, make sure the conversations are on track and relevant to the questions, initiate a conflict opinion to avoid one-sidedness, etc., to make it an effective focus group discussion. In the light of employing triangulation method, the researcher also brings out the findings from semi-structured interviews to highly contribute towards the validation of the findings. The closure of the session involved summarizing key points and allowing participants to provide final thoughts, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

While initially planned for an hour, the discussion seamlessly extended for a few additional minutes, with the participant consent, to avoid abrupt conclusions and ensure a thorough exploration. Simultaneous to video recording, meticulous notes were taken on repeated words, themes, non-verbal cues, and deviations from the planned structure, enhancing the depth of analysis. These notes offer additional context, fostering a more comprehensive understanding. Rigorous adherence to consistent procedures, peer review of protocols and analyses, and systematic data analysis collectively fortify the reliability of the research, establishing a robust foundation for the research's outcomes.

3.9.7 TRANSCRIPTION METHODS

Transcription refers to the process of converting spoken language or audio content into written text. Qualitative approach employed in this research combines semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions which highly involves verbal communication and to transcribe this to written text can be crucial for analysis, decoding, creating themes and patterns, and interpreting the data for achieving the objectives of this research. Capturing words, nuances, and even non-verbal pauses or tones can be integral for the transcription process. Verbatim transcription allows even stutters and false starts to the transcription process, translating the content exactly as it was spoken, without any paraphrasing.

This research meticulously adheres to a verbatim transcription style by skillfully encapsulating the tone, emphasis, and nuanced emotions. Furthermore, it goes beyond literal translation, incorporating a profound interpretation that, while maintaining authenticity, strategically omits regional words or phrases to ensure a refined and universally translated rendition. As the qualitative interviews and focus groups were conducted mostly through Microsoft Teams, the live transcription feature was used to transcribe words as they were spoken, which helped maintain accuracy. Moreover, the recorded audios were run through a transcription software called Otter.AI to further validate the transcriptions. This ensures transparency, replicability and credibility of this research, wherein future researcher can use the same transcription software to obtain optimum results. In addition to this, the researcher's nationality, proficiency of regional languages, excellent attention to details, research skills, etc., furthermore, approve the accuracy and trust in the transcription of few spoken words which were in regional language such as Tamil and Hindi, although English was mostly maintained. Considerations like audio quality, familiarity with specific regional vocabulary or accents or emotions, and the nature of the content were critical in guiding the transcription process to yield reliable and meaningful results.

3.10 DATA ANALYSIS AND PLAN

Data collected through primary and secondary resources need final analysis, meaningful comprehension, and further creation of a hypothesis (Krauss, 2005). As qualitative approach achieves research objective of determining perception of managers about agile transformation on sustainability, recording patterns within this theme, in other words, find repeated information that carry significance within multiple interviews.

This can be achieved through thematic analysis, which will help organize interviews and their different methods in this research. NVivo as a most known software or manual word tree mapping for qualitative data analysis, will also prove advantageous for this research, following six stages to predominantly answer research questions and unify ideas regarding the phenomenon and overall reduce ambiguity, improve quality and rigor of thematic data analysis (Buetow, 2010). “Familiarization with data; generation of initial codes; searching for themes; reviewing themes, definition of themes; and report production” as procedures will be used for thematic data Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

3.10.1 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING THEMATIC DATA ANALYSIS APPROACH

Thematic data analysis method has been adopted for this research to interpret interview responses and focus group discussions into themes and codes that create repeated patterns which can bring meaningful data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Saunders, 2011). A more deductive thematic approach has been adopted by the researcher validating specific patterns and themes from data. Although few themes were decided based on previous models and literatures, few emerged as new themes from the primary data collection. As not much research has been done in the field of agile transformation for IT startup sustainability in the context of India, the researcher required more in-depth understanding from interviewees and discussion panels leaning towards an inductive approach. As per Boyatzis (1998), both inductive and deductive thematic approaches combined can benefit this research by addressing sustainability issues among IT startups.

Sustainability can be considered as a perceptual phenomenon and therefore 1) directly involves interviewees to share their experience and opinions 2) includes the researcher alongside the interview, guiding and accompanying them 3) combines both inductive and deductive thematic approaches to exclusively conduct field research (Braun and Clarke, 2006). In this research 1) participants related to startups and 2) participants related to agile were the two main classifications, both proving to be highly valuable to understand sustainability.

Repeated patterns and words were recorded as themes and codes interpreted from semi-structured interviews and focus groups. The data-driven approach has helped the researcher identify and draw relationships between the codes (Patton, 1990; Boyatzis, 1988). Braun and Clarke (2006) and Nowell *et al* (2017), propose the following guidelines 1) familiarizing with data 2) interpreting

transcripts and generating codes 3) searching themes 4) reviewing themes 5) naming themes 6) reporting. Literatures on agile transformation and sustainability were reviewed to validate the inclusion of each theme and moreover the transcripts were read multiple times to familiarize with data in sequential manner. Keywords and codes were developed through manual thematic analysis predominantly, transcribing all 20 interviews to understand in-depth and create new themes.

3.11 RESEARCH QUALITY

Shenton (2004), claims research quality to be integral for any research in parallel with sample size, deciding individual standards and selection parameters. The quality standards for quantitative research such as validity, generalizability and reliability cannot be applied to qualitative research as there exists dissimilarities and incompatibility issues. According to Golafshani (2003) and Shenton (2004), qualitative research can be of high quality when the research questions are well justified and clear, keeping the research relevant to the current scenario. Moreover, the conceptual framework developed as part of the research should align with the research design, questions, methodology and findings, which determine the quality of qualitative research (Saunders, 2011). Quantitative researchers use reliability to determine if the research can be replicated under similar circumstances to produce the same results on applying the same research method (Golfshani, 2003). Saunders (2011) claims that time relevance plays a key role in determining reliable findings and outcomes. These standards of reliability cannot be applied for qualitative research because qualitative researchers focus on exploring phenomena that can be understood (Stenbacka, 2001).

3.11.1 JUSTIFICATION OF TRUSTWORTHINESS

Qualitative researchers measure their research using trustworthiness rather than reliability under the sub-categories of credibility, dependability, confirmability, transferability and reflexivity as shown in Table 3.8. Seale (1999), states the openness and vulnerability of trustworthiness of qualitative research to be criticized and discussed with multiple researchers. According to Lewis (2015) and Bryman and Bell (2015), trustworthiness can improve the quality of this research.

This research has been compatible with the following regards of trustworthiness: 1) The research and ethics guidelines provided by The University of the West of Scotland have been strictly followed (UWS, 2021). Following this, the ethical issues have been addressed and approved prior to any form of data collection or pilot study (Saunders *et al*, 2009).

Table 3. 8 Various attributes of trustworthiness

CRITERIA	MEANING	REPRESENTATION
Credibility	Plausible and trustworthy findings	Alignment between all the elements of the research (Theory/framework/ methodology/strategy/sample size/findings)
Dependability	Replicability in similar scenarios	Sufficient data for future research to adopt same methodology and procedure to obtain different results
Confirmability	Strong relationship between data and findings	The detailed description and quotes project research findings in detail
Transferability	Ability to transfer this research findings to future research in different settings	The detailed description of context of research strategy and findings
Reflexivity	Reflection of one's own perception/ beliefs and judgments during research	The detailed explanation of reflection of researcher's ideology and beliefs employed within the research process

Source: Adapted from Denzin and Lincoln (2011)

2) The triangulation strategy employed in this research incorporated multiple techniques and tools to validate the research findings (Morse, 1994; Yin, 2009). The use of focus groups in addition to the semi-structured interviews can definitely provide value in understanding the phenomena in-depth; 3) The personal interests, career goals and educational background aligns with the research objectives proving the Researcher's potential and knowledge in this field.

Quantitative researchers correlate validity to the accuracy of the measurement which in the context of qualitative research cannot be achieved given the wider perspectives, opinions and views in social realism (Heale and Twycross, 2015; Altheide and Johnson, 2011). Also, credibility used by the quantitative researcher for assessing empirical evidence, significance of the phenomena, efforts undertaken by the researcher and the research sample can be interpreted as rigor in terms of qualitative research (Patton, 1999; Altheide and Johnson, 2011). Technical rigor considered as a criterion for assessing credibility has been achieved in this research by a detailed description of the research methodology and strategies in this Chapter. According to Patton (1999), triangulation and contextual data collection can also be criteria to assess quality of a qualitative research.

Quantitative research uses generalizability to determine the ability of a research to be extended for samples outside its scope which cannot be achieved in qualitative research given the judgements used by the researcher to include only selected participants (Hair *et al*, 2015). Crotty (1998) and Saunders (2011), argue generalizability to be the secondary concern of qualitative researchers wherein the future researchers can judge the results and findings contributing to the phenomena.

Eisenhardt (2007), states that the smaller sample size as compared to quantitative research in qualitative research, limits its scope of generalizability. Qualitative researchers can also generalize their findings and outcomes by extending them for international contexts although not in an empirical manner (Stake, 1978; Yin, 2009). The ability to generalize this research for any target sample based in India focusing on IT startups, proves the generalizability of this research under carefully considered judgements and criteria (Maxwell, 2013; Zikmund *et al*, 2013). The unnecessary of generalizing theories proves valuable for this research which focuses mainly on exploring the sustainability issues of IT startups in India.

3.12 RESEARCH ETHICS

Angrosino (2011), claims that any research should adhere to the rules and regulation of the University's academic ethics code which also values the business world. According to UWS (2021), this research questions, objectives, methodologies and ethics have been approved in advance to the data collection. As this research focuses mainly on startup founders, entrepreneurs and employees for the semi-structured interviews and agile coaches, practitioners and project managers for the focus groups, the research problem of sustainability has been the key topic driving the questionnaires for both. Although there were potential samples from overseas, startups in India were given most priority given the research scope and objectives. A brief introduction to the research was provided to the interviewees who were asked for further contentment and personal details to be recorded for the purpose of this research, after which they were interviewed.

The research purpose, aims and objectives were shared with the participants prior to the interview to provide clarity and set the right expectations from them. With complete freedom to withdraw at any point of research a participant feels uncomfortable or faces issues, proves that participants in their own interests and consent have agreed to this interview in the first place. Moreover, the secure maintenance of the confidentiality of the participants adds confidence and trustworthiness to this research, protecting their details and answers from being leaked to third parties or agencies. As per Saunders (2011), disclosure of any sensitive information of the participant can lead to ethics breach and violation of ethical conduct. The organizations under observation have been asked for approval prior to the actual interview. The intentions of this research have been clearly communicated ahead of the interview to ensure ambiguities, conflicts and controversies.

3.13 RESEARCH LIMITATION

Sample size of 20 interviews and 2 focus groups, given the time limit and access constraints especially during pandemic in 2021, can be limitations when conceptualizing the outcomes of this research for the entire IT Start-up population. The small sample size of 34 participants may limit the generalizability of findings to the diverse Indian IT startup landscape. Method triangulation, including semi-structured interviews and focus groups, was employed to gather rich information. Limitations associated with qualitative data, such as non-numeric nature and difficulty in quantification, pose challenges. Despite concerns about generalizability and subjectivity, the research addresses these limitations by ensuring trustworthiness and reliability, emphasizing participant selection and criteria. In this qualitative research, participant bias introduces potential distortions in data due to characteristics, attitudes, or behaviors. Despite efforts to establish a non-judgmental environment, biases, especially a pronounced developer-entrepreneur bias, can impact the accuracy of responses. Biases in terms of culture, sample profile and sampling methods might limit the data collection of this research. As perceptions of sustainability enablers are subjective, different project managers and employees may have different views considering their business model for start-ups. Client projects in the IT industry are diverse and therefore findings of factors affecting sustainability in this research may be subject to change in forthcoming years. These limitations can be initial steps for further scope for future researchers to focus on. Despite potential vulnerabilities to biases, purposeful sampling, triangulation, and methodological considerations enhance the robustness of the findings. Future research should expand the sample size for broader applicability. The research aimed to engage startup founders and entrepreneurs from Tier 1 cities in India, but COVID-19 restrictions limited data collection to a subset of cities. Expansion to include startup consultants introduced potential biases, but the findings correlate with literature and contribute valuable insights to agile transformation and sustainability. Employing a cross-sectional time horizon, this research provides a snapshot rather than tracking changes over time. The absence of longitudinal data limits insights into the dynamic nature of agile transformation and sustainability. Future research should consider follow-ups with respondents to observe trends and identify causal relationships, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the research phenomena. Chapter 6, Section 6.8 outlines the limitations inherent in this research, offering a thorough and comprehensive examination. Furthermore, it delves into potential strategies and methods aimed at overcoming these limitations.

3.14 CHAPTER CONCLUSION

This chapter highlighted the research paradigm, briefing about the different worldviews, further explaining how interpretivism can be justified for this research. Later, a comparison between the quantitative and qualitative approaches was drawn, defending the qualitative/inductive approach to be more ideal for this research. Further, the choice of triangulation for using more than one method to validate and choice of case study strategy to deeply understand the phenomena were discussed. The pilot study and the feedback that approached completion were also noted in this chapter. Further justifying the sample population, size and purposive strategy, this chapter further concluded semi-structured interviews and focus groups to be significant data collection methods. Finally, the research quality was justified, and ethical considerations were briefed. The next chapter will apply the research methodology discussed in this Chapter and formulate findings from the actual data collection.

CHAPTER 4 FINDINGS AND DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, insights derived from the qualitative research presented in Chapter 2 are meticulously examined and elucidated using relevant tables and figures to explicate the discoveries. The discussion begins by providing an overview of the word tree and themes in Section 4.2, followed by an in-depth analysis of both adopted themes such as identifications of sustainability factors, traditional methodologies, agile transformation and agile theory vs practice in Sections 4.3 and emergent themes in Section 4.4 from the research. Section 4.5 introduces new inferences derived from factual findings, particularly emphasizing the misconceptions surrounding agile principles, values, and practices correlating to the literature in Sub-Sections 4.3.3 to 4.4.3. Three essential prerequisites—agile mindset, agile culture, and stakeholder participation—are underscored as critical components.

Moreover, this chapter uncovers a significant misunderstanding of agile principles and practices, leading to the identification of pre-requisites in Sub-Sections 4.3.3 to 4.4.3, namely agile mindset, agile culture, and stakeholder participation. Sections 4.4.4 and 4.4.5 shed light on the profound impacts of increased visibility and optimized adaptability of resources on risk management and risk agility; influence of agile transformation on strategic management, addressing factors affecting sustainability such as strategic misalignment and unskilled labor in Sub-Sections 4.4.6 and 4.4.7; and relationships among communicating priorities, continuous learning, and the sustainability of agile transformation in Sub-Sections 4.4.8 and 4.4.9.

As detailed in the previous chapter, the 20 semi-structured interview questions and 2 focus groups discussions with 7 participants in each group have been conducted and the findings and corresponding thematic data analysis have been comprehended in this chapter. Moreover, the themes, codes and keywords generated will be compared and correlated with the literature review from Chapter 2. The ultimate aim of this chapter is to find answers to research questions in Chapter 1 and formulate new themes that emerged through the data collected. Collective responses will add value in understanding agile transformation for sustainability of Indian IT startups.

4.2 OVERVIEW OF THEMES GENERATED

As established in Chapter 3, Section 3.10, thematic analysis was justified as the effective data analysis technique, which can be done manually or using software like NVivo. Manual thematic analysis involves the researcher manually reviewing and decoding the information, identifying themes through a rigorous and iterative process, to obtain in-depth exploration of the subject phenomena. Despite being time-consuming and necessity for peer review and inter-rater reliability, this approach allows flexibility, detailed interpretation and subjective judgement to best answer the research questions. On the other hand, software-based approaches use algorithms to identify patterns and generate themes from the data collected. Although this approach is quicker, there's less room for flexibility and nuanced interpretation, also emphasizing the researcher's familiarity with software's functionalities and limitations. Understanding the nature of the research questions and the research goal to obtain in-depth exploration, this research opts for manual thematic analysis which can prove highly beneficial.

The researcher begins with thorough familiarization with raw data collected, such as transcripts or manual notes taken, to gain a comprehensive understanding. The analysis initiates with open coding to identify key concepts, followed by clustering to form preliminary themes. A rigorous review refines themes for accurate representation, maintaining clarity through clear definitions. Compiling data excerpts under each theme provides evidence for theme emergence. Exploring relationships between themes captures the complexity and interrelatedness within the data. Crafting a narrative summarizes findings, incorporating examples aligned with research objectives. Peer review enhances credibility. The analysis concludes by presenting themes, evidence, and quotes in a research report. Revisiting and refining the analysis can help delve deeper into the data. The meticulous approach ensures a robust qualitative analysis that aligns with the research's objectives, providing a nuanced understanding of the data.

According to Paaton (1990) and Braun and Clarke (2006), multiple codes from keywords were generated throughout the semi-structured interview and focus group data to form meaningful themes and patterns, balancing the homogeneity and external heterogeneity of the data. This helped the researcher maintain coherence of data and be able to distinguish one from another. The tone and choice of specific works were keenly observed to aid the researcher obtain deeper behavioral insight into the phenomenon of sustainability.

Table 4. 1 Overview of themes, definitions, codes and keywords generated

THEMES	DEFINITION	CODES	KEY WORDS
ADOPTED THEMES			
1. Sustainability factors	The factors that affect sustainability of Indian IT startups	1. Risk Factors	Ignored customer; customer behavior; unclear requirements; lack of funds; high competition
		2. Strategic factors	Misalignment; ineffective planning; unproductive culture; productivity; right team
		3. Performance factors	Quality; deliverables; failed business model; adoption challenges; skill development
2. Existing traditional methods	The understanding of existing transformation methodologies such as	1. Waterfall	Longer time to market; unaccommodated change; rigidity; more documentation; high re-engineering cost
		2. Iterative	Skilled workforce; no working models; product value; lack of increment; need high resource
		3. Spiral	Lack of team focus; mini waterfall; client uninvolved; optimum risk mitigation
3. Understanding agile transformation	The understanding of agile transformation from startup's perspective	1. Agile vs traditional	MVP; feedback; SCRUM; welcoming change; small teams; incremental requirement gathering
		2. Agile benefits	Reduced delivery time; improved quality; cost-effective; rapid prototyping; communication
		3. Agile theory vs practice	Documentation; agile practices; tools vs culture; need for agile; continuous learning
EMERGED THEMES			
1. Agile transformation pre-requisites	The pre-requisites for best impact of Agile transformation on sustainability	1. Agile mindset	Fixed mindset; misconceptions; unclear definition; true agility; service quality; failing fast; learning quick
		2. Agile culture	Employee focused; customer centricity; shared purpose; innovation; fear-driven behaviors; core values
		3. Stakeholder participation	Collaborative teams; self-organized individuals; customer satisfaction; shared goals
2. Agile transformation elements	The elements that help improve sustainability of agile startups	1. High visibility	Transparency; reduced project risk; quick adaptation; decision making; responsibility; product backlog
		2. Optimum resource allocation	Financial factors; human resources; technological advancements; unanticipated risks; workable software; milestones
		3. Strategic alignment	Vision and strategy; market strategy; strategic planning; developers' view; day-to-day activities; strategic direction; long-term growth

		4. Strategic sensitivity	Work environment; team motivation; innovativeness; awareness; engagement; learning and development
		5. Communicating priorities	Epics and story board; workflow; work not done; highest priority; less rework; maintained documents; reliability
		6. Continuous learning	Responsiveness: commitment to learning; high flexibility; cross-functional learning; upskilling; customer relationship

Table 4.1 clearly portrays both adopted and emerged themes from this research and highlights keywords from each code generated within each theme. Sustainability factors, traditional methodologies and agile transformation were adopted as themes from Chapter 2 literature and agile pre-requisites and agile elements were themes that emerged through the data collection and findings. Both adopted and emerged themes will be further discussed in the following sections.

4.3 DATA ANALYSIS OF ADOPTED THEMES

As stated earlier, sustainability factors, traditional methodologies and their failures and understanding of agile theory vs practice have been adopted from the literatures of specific themes from Chapter 2 and validated for data analysis in the following sections. This section will include both data collected from semi-structured interviews and focus groups.

4.3.1 SUSTAINABILITY FACTORS

Research question 1: What are the factors that influence sustainability in Indian IT start-ups, requires the understanding and identification of specific factors that affects the sustainability of Indian IT startups. The findings of this theme aim to answer this research question. As discussed in Chapter 2 Section 2.3, the phenomenon of sustainability includes elements that link to maintaining outcomes, thinking about the future risks and handling the resources that are available (Lindsey, 2011, Bolis *et al*, 2014). According to Ender and Remig (2015) and Yang (2019), there still exists vagueness in the concept of sustainability and how it fits a specific context. This section explores the idea of sustainability of Indian IT startups and the pain points that startup founders think has been the reason for startup failure.

A female startup project manager with 3 years of experience in IT industry responded to the question related to startup failures as follows:

“Specifically considering India, I believe startups are not able to grab what the market wants, and what the consumer is really asking for! Most instances, what I’ve seen is startups have a vague belief that their products will do well, but it doesn’t! Managers are stepping in with no clear understanding of the market value of their product or the consumer behavior, and so, their performance starts to dip. Another issue that I believe is the reason for startup failure is that startups think of profitability and forget the main problem that the startup intended to solve in the market. This pushes them to start making products that does not stand with their company’s vision and mission!”

The respondent seemed sensible when explaining about the startup failure reasons as she has been a part of the startup for 3 years. According to her, the startup failure rate of 67% is acceptable and is an ever-growing concern in the Indian startup ecosystem. According to her, startups fail due to the poor understanding of the market and the customer behavior, a vague belief in the product, not aligned to mission and vision and therefore decelerating performance and the heedful focus on profitability more than the process. This corresponds with Table 2.6 where product unwelcomed, no market needs, strategic misalignment, ignored customers, client management, etc., have been identified through literature as startup failure reasons.

Another male startup founder with 3 years of establishment was asked the same question on the reasons why startup fails to which he responded as follows:

“If you ask me, startups need to understand what their clients need and their methodology. They need to build that credibility and spend time on what the client needs to do, and that does not need to be agile. So, they need to deliver it by understanding what the clients need to do. Clear definition of the roles, process and milestones, sprints and the stakeholders is very important.”

In response to the highlighted importance of comprehending clients, there was a conspicuous acknowledgment of the significance of client management. Furthermore, the imperative to adeptly deliver to clients through robust requirements gathering techniques underscores the significance of employing a transformation methodology like agile. Establishing credibility with customers amplifies the necessity for active customer collaboration in innovating processes and strategic objectives for the startup. This cohesive approach not only solidifies client relationships but also strategically positions the startup for sustained success in the dynamic business landscape.

In comparison with Table 2.6, the ignored customers, customer satisfaction, defining deliverables, client management and product unwelcome can be considered as factors for startup failure. On asking a male startup entrepreneur who has just founded a startup but has years of experience working as a developer in the IT industry, he responded as follows:

“Firstly, finding the right developers has been a struggle as they are becoming very scarce. Many skilled developers are logging out of IT because of how they are being treated. The less people in IT... the demand increases. Finding projects is quite easy, getting the right people is hard. I feel like the IT companies need to be managed by IT skilled and proficient people. Managers with no or less experience in IT practices... How can they understand their developers? If the client is not good, I say to their face that it will not work. We can sustain indefinitely, as IT demand increases day by day, the only challenge is the quality of the service!”

This adds a different view to the previous two responses and brings out the need for the right developers, the way they are mistreated, the productivity of being transparent with the customers, entrepreneurs and startup founders to be sound in IT software development and processes and most importantly the quality of service, which alarms the startup founders.

This corresponds to Table 2.6, where team inefficiency, unproductive culture, ineffective planning, failed business models where focus should be on the quality, etc., has been highlighted. According to him the focus should be on the client and how to collaborate with them to bring quality products and services to the market, and ultimately satisfying them by meeting their expectations.

Given the same question in a focus group with 4 participants, one of the participants who has 18 years of experience working in IT industry under dissimilar roles such as technical support, senior developer and project manager exclaims as follows:

“See, startups are small scale, so the working capital is important... this decides the quality of your team, marketing, and the number of clients. Product research on the other hand helps to identify the customer's needs and demands. Next, the time that startups take to deliver the product to the market really matters, and startups with lack of funds really struggle in this aspect. Although finance is necessary, what I've experienced as a senior developer is that startups need to believe in the core product they are developing. If the product is unique and closer to usability to the customer needs, this automatically brings in profitability. Startups need to brainstorm on what must be their product. When that is not defined, there is no value being created.”

In addition to the factors already highlighted through semi-structured interviews, the sufficiency of funds has been identified as the major criteria for Indian startups regardless of industry to support the quality of team, process, deliverables, etc. This factor of lack of funds was agreed by another participant having similar experience in the IT industry who also added that pricing strategies as opposed to funds, can affect the profitability of startups as follows:

“I believe there’s a lack of clear pricing strategy amongst the startups which has challenged their sustainability within the high competition, prevalent in the Indian startup industries”

The relationship between funds, pricing strategy and sustainability within the high competition has been evident through this discussion. Although, there is an evident focus on the financial factors when asked another male senior consultant who consults for startups in India, he highlighted few more sustainability factors as follows:

“Most startups have clients who are outside India... There is this added pressure of their products to meet international standards. And when they don’t, usability and value creation become a big question mark. If customers are upset, startups lose their projects and their profit, which makes retrospection more expensive. So, startups are under the pressure of recruiting the right talent or equipping their employees with the right skills for their business, who can effectively translate the business problem into software that solves customer problems... Like it is intended to. Quality project managers overlook these factors and therefore the scrum team is not well developed. The user experience should be really good and that is not available in startups or the software they build.”

The idea that most startups have their headquarters or base overseas, having clients or customers outside India brings out the need for meeting international standards. It is quite different to having Indian customers, who have different expectations as compared to others. To meet these requirements, having the right team developed and monitored is equally important. Most startups fail to enrich their team with the right skillset to meet international standards which creates poor culture and therefore poor translation of business problems into the software.

Another male scrum master who works for a startup that has been in the market for 5 years claim the following sustainability factors for startups:

“We really need to redefine the culture in our startups. Are we truly addressing the real-life events and challenges that our team is facing? Is equipping our team been the top priority? Again, let’s not forget, if there’s no real purpose behind creating a product, it’s a

failure. If the customers don't need it, then why are we even making it, right? How quickly we turn our solution into products by adopting the right process is crucial for business growth. We've got to focus on the long-term goals and strategies, or we'll lose the advantage and fail. Startups are all about adapting to change. If we don't instill that into our work culture, we'll become irrelevant and eventually fail.”

According to him, startup culture has not been as productive and lucrative for the businesses to sustain and grow in the market which can be seen in Table 2.6 as the unproductive culture. Team inefficiency once again has been the emphasis when it comes to satisfying customers both international and Indian. As repeatedly argued by most interviewees, the need for a product or software in the market has been very unclear, which has questioned the business purpose for long term goals and sustainability. Moreover, he adheres to the fact that the startup fails to adhere to a dynamic and ever-changing ecosystem leading to quick failures.

The landscape of businesses underwent a seismic shift due to the transformative impact of COVID-19, reshaping their marketing strategies, operational structures, and customer perceptions. Against this backdrop of widespread business challenge, participants in the focus groups were strategically probed on the profound effects of the pandemic on their startups, yielding insightful responses as meticulously tabulated in Table 4.2. The comprehensive analysis of the integral theme of startup failures unveiled a diverse array of contributing factors. To fortify the robustness of these findings, a rigorous comparison was made with the existing literature in Chapter 2, Sections 2.2 and 2.3. Notably, the prevailing theme underscored unwelcome products and misaligned market needs as pivotal criteria, aligning with and reinforcing the broader narrative emerging from the pandemic-induced challenges faced by startups.

Only 9 responses were recorded for financial sustainability factors whereas ignored customer needs with 20 responses, ineffective planning with 21, strategic misalignment with 15, unproductive culture with 18, team inefficiency with 19 and quality of the product with 20 responses. This shows the dependency of non-financial factors as compared to financial factors for the sustainability of Indian IT startups. Cultural factors and people factors were predominantly raised as concerns for the sustainability crisis in the Indian startup ecosystem. The next section will discuss how traditional methods have attempted to overcome these challenges.

Table 4. 2 Focus group responses for the impact of global pandemic on their business

DESIGNATION	COMPANY AGE	RESPONSES
Business Consultant	53	<i>"Digital initiatives for increasing employee productivity and offering digital services to our clients"</i>
Solutions Architect (Developer)	50+	<i>"We are not able to meet the customers during the pandemic."</i>
Associate consultant	47	<i>"There has always been a plan B in the organization to leverage such issues"</i>
Project Manager	3	<i>"Addressing Client Business Continuity with the New Normal (Work from Home) was one of the critical challenges faced but adopting SOP and leveraging Best Practices these challenges got mitigated. "</i>
Programmer Analyst	28	<i>"Digital initiatives for increasing employee productivity and offering digital services to our clients "</i>
Business Analyst	50	<i>"Affect the risk management in our startup"</i>
Founder and Managing director	2	<i>"In comparison with other companies, the pandemic situation has made our business grow more as many of our clients move on from physical stores to digital stores. This made our growth in a short period."</i>

Sustainability Factors

Figure 4. 1 Data Analysis of factors affecting sustainability of Indian IT startups

4.3.2 EXISTING TRANSFORMATION METHODOLOGIES AND THEIR FAILURES

Research question 2: “Are existing management frameworks effective enough to support the sustainability of Indian start-ups? If yes, how? If not, why?”, requires the understanding and evaluation of existing transformation methodologies and their failure to support sustainability of Indian IT startups. The findings of this theme aim to answer this research question. As detailed in Chapter 2, Section 2.4, transformation methodology both directs and enables a business towards achieving targeted goals or change through concise relationships between significant management components (Rajagopalan and Mathew, 2016; Axel and Lars, 2016). Also, the link between IT SD methods that disrupt traditional practices and fundamental business processes can be transformation, which has been established in Sub-Section 2.4.2 (Immelt, 2017; Stephen, 2018; Geyi *et al*, 2020). Therefore, it is necessary to understand this relationship between traditional methods and sustainability failures within the context of Indian IT startups. A 17-year experience in IT business consultant who consults for startups exclaimed as follows:

“Traditional style... waterfall method... got the requirements, groomed it, went for the rigorous documentation, started development, went for testing, then independent testing, User acceptance testing, Integration testing, then rolled out... That’s time consuming.”

According to him, traditional waterfall methods follow a rigorous process which involves much time for each step from user requirement gathering to the release and development to the testing. This corresponds to the literature review in Sub-Section 2.5.2 and Table 2.7 where the rigorous process of Waterfall method has been detailed, creating a dependency on the previous step to proceed further. When asked about the major drawback of the method he further responded as follows:

“In my opinion, in traditional methods, you cannot change or alter the requirements during the middle of the process. First, it’s time-consuming... Second, it comes at a huge cost! This creates a huge space between the actual customer problems and the software solutions and makes sensitive product deliveries difficult”

The time insensitive deliveries and failure to actually meet customer requirements were two key drawbacks that the researcher could easily grasp from the respondent who further explained how Spiral managed to address this to a certain extent.

“Previously, companies took a long time to make their own successful product but now we get more changes every year because of competitor overload. Then they came up with the Spiral model... break the whole component into smaller modules... define requirements and

work on it and at that time they start working on other aspects of the software development, which gives them flexibility.”

The findings that the researcher could draw from this respondent is the need for flexibility in the processes to welcome change, which was lacking in the traditional transformational methods. The need to constantly update and be ahead of the competitors has put pressure on the IT businesses to perform more than expected. As a consultant, he suggests startups reconsider their processes for achieving flexibility. The appraisals and criticism, detailed in Table 2.7, can also be validated here, as he also highlights the need for flexibility in traditional methodologies.

Another male project manager who has worked for 10+ years in the IT industry claims as follows:

“There is a concept called time to market... At the end of the day, what is my MVP. MVP is Minimum Viable Product... What is the minimum valuable product that I can show my customer? MVP as a concept was totally unavailable in traditional methods. You know... Let’s say the customers are asking you to build a cat, at the end of the day it was a dog that they built! This became the scenario where people completely misinterpreted the requirements. Still, I’d say waterfall is the best methodology under the conditions of rigidity and the size of the project”

Another male startup founder with 3 years of experience considers rigidity as a bonus to the startup functioning as it reduces his risk. His response was as follows:

“If you ask me, compared to a well-planned waterfall approach, where what has been decided is completed in time, recent approaches or methods have only increased the risk of the work taking longer and not knowing the time when it can be finished”

This criticism from a startup founder has not only been shocking but also alarming in terms of the need for rigidity to some extent in new transformational methodologies. This also corresponds to the literature gap in Section 2.6 and Sub-Section 2.7.5, where the current agile frameworks have not considered the rigidity tolerance of agile practices and documentation levels. This corresponds to Table 2.15 in Chapter 2, Section 2.7 and Sub-Section 2.7.3, where the strengths and weaknesses of current agile frameworks have been tabulated. When discussed within the focus group one of the senior managers in a startup established for less than a year accepted how the waterfall method couldn’t help with their project as follows:

“We didn’t know the requirements clearly before we started the development, and it delayed the project. Even our clients were not able to clearly define and conceptualize their requirements initially... Or give any functional specifications. We as a company knew that it was a high-risk possibility... To an extent where we could lose this project!”

Another lead business analyst who has 12+ years of experience who was in the discussion also supported the above statement as follows:

“Although we had moved to Agile, years back it was just the waterfall method that was proven and tested! We had a project where the customer wanted to change functionalities within the product and so it took us months to re-engineer and accommodate those changes within the product development! That actually cost us a lot because that needed another skilled resource to be brought into the team!”

The tone in which he expressed his views clearly shows how much re-work went into the accommodation of change and defines the rigidity of this method. Another senior agile coach with 20+ years of experience in the discussion also explained the failures of other predominant traditional methods such as V-model and spiral models as follows:

“In the V-shaped model, the software is developed during the implementation phase, so no early prototypes of the software get developed. Changes that could happen in the midway needed strenuous test documents along with requirement documents which increased time to market, which is the money! With the Spiral model there was a substantial risk of not even meeting the scheduler or budget. It needed high risk expertise to be present and also, Spiral cannot work for smaller projects... documentation is hideous, too many demands... One good thing about Spiral though, it paved a way to breaking up larger work into smaller chunks!”

A semi-structured interview with one of the females leads developers who works for a startup also had the similar views as to this, where she explained:

“When you look at traditional models on the whole, it needed the requirements to be very clear right from the beginning. It was difficult to measure the progress within each phase, involved too much cost to get one change done within the development, involved high risk... needed expertise in the fields to be working. Some projects couldn't meet deadlines, leaving clients in the dark about the ongoing process... Most alarming issue, in my opinion, is that there's no room for changes, clients get no information except at the end and most importantly no working model until the end of the development phase!”

On complete analysis, the researcher could find out the gaps in these traditional methods that were critical for the Indian IT startups and it was so evident that without these factors being addressed, sustainability could not be achieved. Startup founders and managers accept that the dynamics have changed and the need for agility has accelerated over the years, even more so post-pandemic.

Drawbacks of Traditional Methods

Figure 4. 2 Data Analysis of drawbacks of traditional methods

As per the data collected the researcher developed a chart, Figure 4.2, that shows the percentage of sampling population that validates each drawback of the traditional methods. Out of 34 samples including semi-structured and focus groups, 87% respond as traditional methods taking longer time to market, 79% claim that there's no room for change during development which all the more supports the 68% of responses claiming traditional methods to be rigid and 50% of responses claiming that re-engineering costs is more.

The responses gathered, including significant factors like limited client involvement, challenges in visualizing progress, and the demand for a highly skilled workforce, directly align with and are reinforced by the insights presented in Table 2.7 in Section 2.4.5 and Table 2.9 in Section 2.5.4. These tables meticulously outline the criticisms directed at traditional methodologies, particularly in contrast to agile methodology. This convergence of real-world responses and established criticisms underscores the rationale for a paradigm shift towards more agile-based concepts to ensure the sustained viability of Indian IT startups. It not only validates the challenges faced by startups but also advocates for a strategic embrace of agile methodologies as a transformative solution in navigating the dynamic and demanding landscape of the IT industry.

4.3.3 UNDERSTANDING OF AGILE TRANSFORMATION

Research question 3: “How Indian IT startups adapt to agile transformation in both theory and practice?” requires a prior understanding of what agile transformation means to the Indian IT startups, and if agile is necessary for the contribution towards the sustainability of Indian IT startups. The findings in this theme will address this research question. As detailed in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.5.1, agility, the ability to change or think fast and act quickly was considered as one of the key characteristics that IT MNCs and startups lacked (Collier, 2012; Measey, 2015; Dikert *et al*, 2016). This section scrutinizes the theme of agile transformation and how managers perceive it for their startups and businesses.

A female startup developer responded to her understanding of agile as follows:

“What I think agile is, it is a sort of isolated process. So, in our company, to address big process of development tasks, what we just do is divide it into smaller tasks that are executable modules. In that way we create milestones for all entire project and target one milestone at a sprint so that basically your advantage is focusing that task on mind, so that the efficiency increases, and the process will be carried out seamlessly. By doing this, flexibility increases... on the development side they are more focused and the task in their hand is very well defined on what they need to achieve and also... on the deliverable side on what the customer is asking for... that can be delivered in the project anytime.”

According to her, agile means to split big processes into smaller executable tasks which can help achieve incremental milestones increasing efficiency and focus. This has been one of the biggest challenges in traditional waterfall and other transformational approaches as detailed in Section 2.4. As she’s a developer, she expressed her concern for unclear deliverables and undefined goals within the processes that needed to be targeted. To further strengthen this thought from a more managerial point of view, a male business consultant who has consulted for multiple startups was asked about his understanding of agile transformation and he responded as follows:

“You know, agile was initially brought in for those big tech giants like Google and Microsoft. The whole idea was about continuous product delivery and manufacturing. In my experience in Microsoft, we design a core product in Windows version, and then someone asks for a Mac version, so we dive into that. It's like this continuous development loop. We developed a Core Platform first and then kept adding features seamlessly! And in Agile, you've got all these functionalities, each handled by different teams. It's pretty efficient, cuts down a lot of time, but it's all about these teams interacting with each other. The planning for each release is crucial too. We decide what improvements and features

we're bringing in. But here's the twist... not every release churns out the final product! Sometimes it's about delivering a core functionality first, followed by working on additional features in parallel. And it really depends on how quickly you want those product features out there. But, interestingly, not all forms of Agile are used in every scenario. There's this scaled agile thing now. So, Agile is like this game-changer, shaking up the traditional approach to development, making things more flexible and collaborative.”

As someone who has worked for Microsoft as support engineer and developed larger platforms for major clients since 2004, this participant seemed to know more about the domain and has now moved into business consulting to provide real time solutions for IT startups in India. He used the term continuous product delivery to define agile, where a core product gets developed and then features get added onto the core product, saving cost and money without compromising the quality of the product. He also added on the information about scaled agile for startups which has gained much attention in recent years. Having worked with other transformational methodologies, he finds it agile to be less time-consuming, that clearly defines short-term goals. This corresponds to the comparison between agile and non-agile benefits drawn in Table 2.9, where agile methods, by reducing the re-engineering cost have made changes easier to accommodate during the process, making it less time-consuming.

Another male startup founder who has had years of experience as a developer had a different view to agile and his response was as follows:

“All companies in India are for money. They treat people as cattle and find ways to get more money from them and we don't want to do that. On methodologies if you treat people well it does not matter. As these things are created, we use it to show it to the customers about the progress in work. Agile is just a tool to satisfy the client. Getting more feedback, a working software is Agile.”

The developer turned founder seemed to be more reluctant and resistant to the idea of agile right from the beginning of the interview. The researcher, in aim to avoid self-biases about agile transformation, wanted to welcome the interviewee’s criticism on agile transformation and therefore wanted to know why he didn’t think agile is necessary to which he replied:

“See... employees do not care about the process they need to follow. All they care about is their work and the kind of environment they need to work in. The company needs to respond to change no matter what methodology is being followed and I personally do not believe in Agile methods as the ultimate solution.”

His statement seems contradictory in the sense that he believes startups need to adapt to change but also doesn't believe in agile while agile primarily focuses on welcoming change. His idea about the emphasis of the work environment and culture can be a theme that can be further analyzed in the following sections. This corresponds to Table 2.11, where the focus has been shifted away from the agile factors that can promote effective implementation.

Nevertheless, another male startup founder with 5 years of experience views agile to be as follows:

“The platform was developed in terms of sprints with a shorter period of time. Small features delivered in a small period of time... Agile methodology.”

One thing that could be easily analyzed through the responses was the immediate association of agile with sprint and scrum. This has been identified through the literature as a common misconception in Table 2.12. Further another male startup scrum master with 3 years of experience explained about his understanding of agile as follows:

“When we're looking at startups, you know, startups are like the youngsters of the business world. They might not have all the methodologies down, but their inexperience can be a blessing. They don't need to unlearn anything. Agile is becoming the norm. But if you're transitioning from other methodologies, it's a whole different ball game! The challenge is in how the platform is executed, delivered on time, and how quickly it can adapt. Failing fast and continuous updating are key factors, especially for startups. But they're struggling with the transformation process. It's a tough gig. The market and customer experience are evolving rapidly, not just in India but globally. To keep up, you really need to embrace Agile. The agility to adapt to change is crucial, especially for startups navigating this dynamic landscape.”

As a scrum master who manages agile teams, he could've been biased about agile having a positive impact, yet he openly explained how there are startups who don't even find the need for any transformation methodology to be followed. Nevertheless, he emphasized the actual phenomenon of agile which allows startups to fail fast and continuously update to perform well. Throughout the interview with him, it was evident that his views on agile were more than a mere project management tool point of view.

When the researcher asked the same question in the focus group, participants had varied opinions and understanding about agile. One of the responses from interviewees with at least 20+ years of experience was as follows:

“I'm already working in Agile. We call it the scrum. It has existed for years now... The need for Agile actually depends on the nature of the project. The primary reason we adopt Agile

is to deliver results speedily and with good quality. Agile is suitable when you have a dependent delivery schedule. Each task is divided into micro levels, so you will know what must be done and the level of complexity will be reduced. You will be able to know where the dependency needs to be implemented. So, the work can go flawlessly.”

Another participant in the focus group which had agile consultant and coaches with 20+ years of experience in consulting leading banking clients explains agile as follows:

“In software development, it feels like sometimes we forget about the customers, who are essentially the soul of the project. Customer collaboration often takes a back seat. There are fewer ways it's evident in the project sometimes. Especially for startups in India, understanding the client's requirements is crucial. It's not just about getting feedback; it's about altering things along the way. That adaptability is key. And you know what's great about agile? We get more detailed wireframes and understanding compared to other methodologies. Agile emphasizes keeping the customer in the loop and ensuring their needs are met throughout the development process.”

Clarity in terms of requirements gathering and customer feedback has been evidently improved through agile transformation methodology according to these consultants. They have been in the transformation process for banking companies and so they also explained about the challenges in adopting agile which will be discussed in the following sections.

Criticisms were also evident through focus group discussions where one of the startup founders who has previously worked for IT companies exclaims as follows:

“I work in agile development, but I strongly feel that it is not suitable for software development as there are so many dependencies. Also, we can't release, and the customer can't realize the output when 10% to 30% of the work is done, which is again the case in traditional methodologies right! I believe agile is mostly suitable for manufacturing industries”

The key factor that defines agile is the working software which allows customers to actually know what the developers are building. This response from him shows that there is still an unawareness or vagueness about the definition of agile. Nevertheless, it is his opinion about agile transformation and how software development cannot adopt it. A co-founder for a startup that has been there in the market for less than 5 years argues that regardless of the transformation methodology adopted the following seems more significant:

“Speed, efficiency and quality in every function within a startup in India is the mantra and meticulously adopting them is crucial”

Now, if there exists a need for startups to provide speed, efficiency and quality in every aspect of business function, then there is a need to scrutinize agile transformation for its ability to provide all these for a startup. This is in accordance with the literature reviewed in Chapter 2, Section 2.5, Sub-Section 2.5.5.2, Figure 2.15, where these factors have been identified to be integral for an agile transformation. This further adheres to the necessity of agile transformation in Indian IT startups. To support this question, another startup managing director with 3 years of experience explains as follows:

“In my opinion, agile methods will help all businesses to grow healthy from the initial stage of organizational strategy to the final delivery of the product to clients. The majority of startups will learn agile methodologies later as at the initial stage they concentrate on the business and later they look into agile.”

This statement also poses a serious question if agile is suitable only for startups who have gone past the seed or initial stage or if agile is still relevant for a startup that has just been established. This needs to be scrutinized as different research which can differentiate startups for their stages of growth and individually analyze the impact of agile for each of them.

On complete analysis of all the responses about the understanding of agile transformation there is an evident need for agile to be implemented in Indian IT startups with the context of dynamic environment. Few interviewees suggested agile as a necessity for IT startups in India.

Table 4. 3 Perceived understanding of Agile transformation

PERCEIVED UNDERSTANDING OF AGILE	FREQUENCY OF RESPONSES
Breaking down large volume of data into smaller tasks	22
Create milestones as sprints	7
Increased flexibility to accommodate change	26
Companies need transparency	18
Continuous delivery of working software for client to get feedback	24
Gets the product to market in less time	20
When the requirements are not very clear	21
Failing fast to learn quick	11
Agile is a principle and more of a mindset	4

From the data collected the researcher tabulated the frequency of responses and certain keywords that kept repeating in Table 4.3. This includes semi-structured interviews and focus group responses with a total of 30 respondents. 26 out of 30 interviewees believed that agile methods are implemented in IT companies because it increases flexibility to accommodate change even in the development phase. 24 out of 30 interviewees stated that continuous delivery of working software was the key to implementing agile transformation to get more feedback from the customers. 22 participants believed that agile methods break down larger volumes of data into smaller working software. Surprisingly, only 4 interviewees stated that agile is a principle and more of a mindset rather than a tool which shows the lack of understanding of agile transformation among MNCs and IT startups implementing agile. This corresponds and proves that misconceptions of agile transformation as drawn out in Table 2.12, still threatens IT startups to migrate towards more agile methods or enhance their current practice of agile. The next section will scrutinize the differences between theory and actual practice of agile transformation as the fundamentals are wrong.

4.3.4 AGILE TRANSFORMATION THEORY VS PRACTICE

Research Question 3: “How Indian IT startups adapt to agile transformation in both theory and practice?” requires a further insight and clear differentiation between how Agile transformation is preached and how it’s practiced. The findings in this theme will address this research question. As detailed in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.6.6 as implementation challenges of agile transformation, there always exists a disambiguation between a theory that is explained in books and the same being implemented in an industrial point of view (Ghani *et al*, 2015; Kamei *et al*, 2017). Therefore, there is a need to find the difference between the theory of agile as explained in western cultures and the way it has been practiced within the context of Indian IT startups and IT MNCs.

In order to understand if agile can actually help startups, the researcher first tried to find out how larger MNCs view agile to be in practice. The response from a female developer who works for an IT MNC for 6 years explains as follows:

“I came across a work where I had the role of facing customers... and they were Agile based, and they used to have regular catch ups twice in a day and I had to update on what is going on and there were sprints to make sure the works are completed before the deadline. I used to say that my team was agile, and it was never agile!”

This female developer had learnt from scratch the technology and software development processes but was fairly introduced to agile transformation although she works in agile. The tone that she set in is that she was forced to implement agile and call their team agile but, she recalls agile principles and exclaims that her team was never agile. Chapter 2, Section 2.5, Sub-Section 2.5.6, explains this critical situation where even MNCs that claim to be agile are not truly agile. To support this statement, another response from a male senior project manager in the focus group, who has hired many newcomers into his company was recorded and his response was as follows:

“Agile is a principle and not a technology. It can be used in any business section of the IT industry or any other industry. Agile has helped us a lot in terms of achieving confidence with the customers and building MVPs seamlessly! It does provide a lot of flexibility to change features and processes... Even till the last step of deployment. Getting the big tasks into smaller chunks is agile. This understanding is lacking heavily in freshers. They just read it as a theory. For them, it’s just a tool they use!”

Having asked why he thinks his company couldn’t educate these freshers about agile transformation; he explained as follows:

“There is really not much time when there’s pressure to perform and build confidence with the customers. Employees just view these principles purely in the view of getting promotion. But how many actually learn agile the right way... It is a serious question!”

As the researcher expected, there is still unawareness of the actual concept of agile transformation and therefore managers and employees tend to blindly follow the agile practices in a bookish manner. This has caused friction for startups who try to imitate MNCs. This has also been highlighted as a literature gap in Chapter 2, Section 2.6, which even more supports the need for an agile startup sustainability framework that provides implementation guidance so that startup CEOs and entrepreneurs can understand the principle, educate their employees and then implement it to their context.

A startup co-founder who has been managing his startup for 5 years explains as follows:

“I strongly feel that startup decision makers should educate the need and impact of agile transformation before the actual transformation within the company! Why's that? Well, understanding the principles and impact of agile is crucial. It's not just about changing processes; it's a cultural shift. Employees need to be aware of the limitations of traditional approaches, how agile addresses those issues, and the potential benefits... quicker iterations, better customer satisfaction. Only then, it sets expectations and gets everyone on board with the mindset.”

Any transformation or change management should communicate the need for transformation and the impact it'll have on the company prior to the actual transition putting the company at risk. This response from him confirms that education on the need for actual transformation is necessary for startups as compared to larger MNCs. To critique this statement another startup manager who has 8 years of experience working in the IT field exclaims as follows:

"We follow methodologies based on our own needs and requirements, some of our practices may fall under agile, also we need to tailor our practices according to prevailing need and situation. You cannot overthrow all non-agile methods."

This argument shows that even agile practices can fail if they are not tailored for the needs and requirements of the startup it is applied on. This perspective from him actually requires agile to be defined by more than just merely agile practices written as theory. Another respondent from the focus group, when asked if this was true, added to this point that making the entire team believe in agile and its benefits can be a challenge, and his response was follows:

"Absolutely! The primary challenge is making the entire team believe and work with your processes. You can't keep on changing or evolving month by month as it may reduce the focus, passion and confidence inside the team. This can even lead to project failure, which no one wants right."

The sad reality in today's IT startups is the fact that they need to prove to customers through agile, making them sound more professional. A senior developer when asked explained as follows:

"End of the day, see if you want to implement agile or anything... The baseline should be very clear. What am I supposed to achieve? What is my end target? If the process I follow doesn't work, what is it that I really need to try out? All these need to be planned before a startup can adapt agile principles and policies. But people, management or companies these days are like... I need to implement agile, let me go with agile! What is my roadmap, what is that I'm looking for? Look, there are also hybrid models which can serve the purpose, like the BEAM model!"

Looking at this perspective from a senior developer, it seems like the strategic roadmap is missing within Indian startups who try to blindly implement agile. This could be a cultural disability where startups try to westernize yet miss the whole point of agile transformation and its benefits. On complete analysis of all the data collected in this theme the researcher tabulated the following factors how startup founders and entrepreneurs misunderstand agile practices in Table 4.4. Comparing Table 4.4 and Table 2.12 in Chapter 2, it is evident that these misconceptions are valid and much relevant to the case of Indian IT startups.

Table 4. 4 Perceived misunderstandings of agile transformation

NATURE OF INTERVIEWEES	PERCEIVED MISUNDERSTANDINGS OF AGILE	NUMBER OF RESPONSES
Startups founders who have previous experience as senior developers in the IT industry	Agile is just a tool to satisfy client and gain confidence with customers	3
	Startups don't need to emphasize on process, it's all about the software development	
Startup founders who have previous experience of working as senior project managers in the IT industry	Agile is for big giants not startups	9
	No fixed budget estimates as process keeps changing	
	Well-funded startups can only implement Agile	
Entrepreneurs who have just established their startups	Works well for MNCs so it should work for startups	3
	No documentation needed	

The data from 9 startup founders and co-founders who have had previous experience as managers have different perspectives to 3 founders who have just worked as developers. Researchers think that the way these developers were treated in their previous companies could have a serious impact on the company culture and the way they perceive processes. Moreover, 3 entrepreneurs who have just established startups have this idea that agile works well for MNCs so it should work for them. 9 Startups founders who have previously been senior managers think agile is for giant companies and not for startups and focus on financial factors.

4.4 EMERGED THEMES

Research Question 4: “How effective are current agile transformation frameworks in managing sustainability of Indian IT start-ups?”, requires a prior understanding of what needs to be altered or elements to be considered beyond existing agile frameworks and adoption methods, to contribute towards sustainability of Indian IT startups. There were various themes discussed over the previous sections in the context of agile transformation for the sustainability of Indian IT startups. Some of the themes evolved as being ineffectively practiced or misinterpreted within the Indian startup ecosystem and therefore has forced them to rethink their business.

For example, when asked about the understanding of agile, even the experienced agile scrum masters and project managers for larger MNCs tend to have only a vague idea of agile. This shows that there exists a need for proper definition of agile. Moreover, the efforts to find agile in actual practice displayed the ignorance of companies to educate their employees about agile. There was also a strong imitation from startups to implement agile without knowing the need and impact it has on their startups. A clear definition of their target and also their strategic roadmap needs to be made prior to the actual transformation. Three new keywords that emerged in accordance with the research are the agile mindset, agile culture and stakeholder participation, and these themes will address the Research Question 4. Furthermore, six elements namely visibility, resource allocation, strategic alignment, strategic sensitivity, communicating priorities and continuous learning as agile elements that could impact sustainability of Indian IT startups have emerged. These emerging themes will be discussed in the next section.

4.4.1 AGILE MINDSET

Agile transformation, as highlighted by Burnette *et al.* (2013), intricately centers on a profound mindset shift that specifically aims at fostering the growth and sustainability of both individuals and businesses. This pivotal theme, extracted from responses pertaining to the understanding of agile practices, not only surfaced consistently but also demonstrated a recurrent pattern and a major literature gap as highlighted in Chapter 2, Section 2.6, thereby earning its unequivocal inclusion in this section. Each startup has its own strategic vision and mission which represents the mindset of startup stakeholders and directs the organization's processes and operations. Chapter 2, Section 2.5, revealed the vagueness and ambiguity in the term agile and agile mindset, which further raised concerns about the common misconceptions and implementational challenges of agile. Considering the difference of opinion about agile transformation amongst startups as revealed in Section 4.3.3, only 14 respondents were asked about their entrepreneurial mindset as opposed to using the term agile mindset. As discussed in Chapter 2, Section 2.7, Sub-Section 2.7.4 and 2.7.6, where the new framework to be developed aims to achieve overall sustainability, there needs to be a linkage between the startup vision and the agile transformation. Table 4.5, meticulously presents the collated responses from startup founders, entrepreneurs and managers, providing a structured insight into the driving forces shaping their entrepreneurial journey.

Table 4. 5 Understanding strategic vision of Indian IT startups

INTERVIEWEE	STARTUP AGE (YR)	RESPONSE
Startup founder	3	<i>"To provide IT services and develop software products"</i>
Entrepreneur	3 months	<i>"To Help Students who needs Guidance to get good grades on exams through best tutors by our App Product"</i>
Startup co-founder	5	<i>"To deliver domestically assembled computer systems within India"</i>
Entrepreneur	6 months	<i>"To implement innovation in businesses and adapt automation to reduce cost and resource"</i>
Startup founder	5	<i>"To provide IT services"</i>
Startup founder	5	<i>"To provide innovative technology solutions and consulting"</i>
Startup co-founder	2	<i>"The motive was to achieve excellence in technology and using that we intend to provide best quality service for our customers."</i>
Startup manager	6	<i>"Best service at the right budget."</i>
Startup CEO	5	<i>"To provide IT services"</i>
Entrepreneur	7 months	<i>"In order to create the best services for their customer"</i>
Startup co-founder	3	<i>"Enable clients drive digital transformation and IT Spend Optimization, while creating sustainable business value leveraging IT and Trends Effectively (Levitare)"</i>
Startup CEO	5	<i>"I think the world keeps on moving to science with advanced technology and I am also sure that all those technologies will play a vital role, so I would like to be a part of that growth"</i>
Startup Manager	5	<i>"To provide excellent service in the field of medical billing and scheduling to the providers"</i>
Entrepreneur	1	<i>"I know the end to end application journey. So I thought of starting a consulting business. I also love teaching so started an academy for salesforce training as well"</i>

Understanding the motives behind and strategic vision for establishing a startup or being a part of it can help understand how far these startup stakeholders are inherently agile and can align with the agile mindset. On analysis of the strategic visions of these startups, it can be noted that providing best and quality services was a repeated theme. Although innovation, excellence and being updated with advanced technologies were also recorded as recurring patterns, one interesting response was the need to create sustainable business value.

As this research aims to understand the impact of agile transformation on the sustainability of Indian IT startups, it is necessary to examine how engraved sustainability is, in the mindset of startup founders, entrepreneurs and managers. Shockingly only 1 out of 14 participants emphasized the need for sustainability as part of the strategic vision and agile mindset, which symbolizes the failure of agile transformation with respect to mindset transformation. When asked about agile mindset by a senior developer in a MNC in one of the focus groups he explained as follows:

“How can I deliver value to the customers? Typically, the industry works on research and if some concept appears to be fancy in the eyes of the customers, then that is used. The whole process is questionable. People don't implement the process properly and that does not make it agile. The industry requires a mindset change to start updating the process to deliver a product. Agile is a catchy phrase and people are willing to get there.”

The tone that he set for this question shows how much he emphasized the need for the mindset change for successful software development. According to him most IT companies have shifted to agile without this mindset change and therefore he claims that they cannot be called agile because they blindly follow agile practices. This is in accordance with the literature reviewed in Chapter 2, Section 2.5, Sub-Section 2.5.6, where migrating to agile without knowing the need and benefits of agile transformation can cause serious implementation aftereffects. Another lead developer who has worked for 20+ years in the IT industry explains as follows:

“Agile isn't just a methodology... it's a set of principles that can be applied in various situations. Take roadwork, for example. You can break down large tasks into smaller, more manageable chunks using agile principles. You may think, isn't Agile mostly for software development? Nope, it's more versatile than that. Even the development of COVID vaccines has embraced Agile transformation.”

This shows that the core principles of Agile are adaptable and beneficial in navigating complex challenges across different domains, even to non-IT businesses, but it all depends on the mind change. According to him, breaking volumes of data into workable processes can effectively increase agility. When discussed in one of the focus groups about the mindset of startups in India, a female senior scrum master with 10+ years of explained as follows:

“I have worked and consulted many startups in India but then, one major drawback that I see is the prevalent fixed mindset as compared to Agile mindset. When you bring new methodologies or tools, you also need to adapt to the new mindset that's needed to work on it. You cannot work with the same mindset and call that transformation!”

She used an extremely critical term transformation to explain how startups transforming into agile needs transformation in all areas including the mindset. Although, this is not explicitly provided in the existing literatures, this highly corresponds to the agile principle as shown in Chapter 2, Section 2.5, Figure 2.12, which corresponds to the literature gap of agile mindset transformation as a pre-requisite for agile practices. Moreover, a senior agile coach who has consulted many IT MNCs responded as follows:

“Startups need to understand why they need Agile and evaluate if their startup actually needs Agile because the Agile method cannot be suitable for all nature of projects. If the requirements are not rapidly changing or if your customers are unwilling to participate in your process or if there’s less uniqueness and research needed for software development, don’t go for Agile! As an Agile coach I have seen startups struggle with this aspect where they transform to Agile but still practice mini waterfall inside their sprints, where they never needed Agile in the first place!”

According to him, startups have failed to understand the need for agile in their startups and therefore try to apply agile for projects that don’t need agile. In a way, this approach of identifying the need before actually applying it, is also agility and agile mindset as he claims.

To further this the researcher asked a male startup founder established for 3 years what he perceives about agile mindset and what he thinks as necessary elements for it; his response was as follows:

“If you ask me, Agile mindset is not just for the management but also for the team members and it’s all about emphasizing the customer needs and having that accountability and respect, while also focusing on building the right team with the right skills. How having the agile mindset has helped my startup is the way we face challenges, have a can-do attitude and that space to innovate and learn while embracing mistakes. This has helped us get more projects recently and be profitable as a company!”

This interviewee expressed his thoughts on agile mindset very clearly, highlighting the need for agile mindset in all levels of management from bottom to top and also emphasized customer satisfaction and team building at the heart of it. His startup has had a turnover of 1million in a year and shows how much value the agile mindset has had over their success. Further his tone set the ability of agile managers to guide the team and influence high productivity within projects.

Hence, we can see this theme as one of the crucial factors that can impact sustainability as a whole and adhere to effective agile transformation in all levels of management. The infusion of an agile mindset not only fosters innovation but also redirects focus towards customer-centric approaches, particularly towards to the context of Indian IT startups. Entrepreneurs in the Indian landscape must embrace the synergistic principles of sustainability and an agile mindset, creating the ability to retain customers and build teams. Furthermore, the nexus between the right mindset and profitability, as evident from participant responses, amplifies the significance of cultivating an agile mindset. The subsequent section will delve into the intricacies of fostering an agile culture.

4.4.2 AGILE CULTURE

Culture considered as an intangible asset for a company can be a crucial element for the way processes and tools are employed within the company to ensure its sustainability and growth (Tolfo *et al*, 2011). The value of agile manifesto and its benefits needs to be incorporated within the culture and only then can the startup realize potential benefits from agile practices.

Table 4. 6 Interviewee responses for the significance of culture

INTERVIEWEE	RESPONSES	FOCUS
Startup founder	<i>"Flat organization with less or no hierarchy, teams are empowered for taking decisions to speed up the execution"</i>	EMPLOYEE
Entrepreneur	<i>"We focus on VISION, PASSION, HONESTY, TRUST. We work 6 days a week and take vacations for a complete week once every 3 months"</i>	CUSTOMER/EMPLOYEE
Startup co-founder	<i>"Relaxed culture with decent employee benefits. This is good learning for me."</i>	EMPLOYEE
Entrepreneur	<i>"Our management primarily focuses on the ideas of the client. However any reality changes that could bring out better version of the called product will be suggested at times"</i>	CUSTOMER
Startup founder	<i>"Work life balance is good"</i>	EMPLOYEE
Startup founder	<i>"Work while you work and chill as you do"</i>	EMPLOYEE
Startup co-founder	<i>"The company provides the best training, exposure and freedom to our employees which results in superior knowledge and skills, this directly satisfies our core motive and also benefits"</i>	CUSTOMER/EMPLOYEE
Startup manager	<i>"Sharing the actual possibilities to fulfill the client's needs at given time and cost."</i>	CUSTOMER
Startup CEO	<i>"Employee centric company that give priority to the employees and their benefits"</i>	EMPLOYEE
Entrepreneur	<i>"Company work culture is to help and meet the customer's needs . Understands the needs of the employees "</i>	CUSTOMER/EMPLOYEE
Startup co-founder	<i>"Speed + Efficiency + Quality are the Key Dimensions and Critical Success Factors. Most Importantly, Enablement, Empowerment, Autonomy provided to the team to get abridged with the Latest Trends in Business & Technology and continuously strive to innovate and add value to clients business."</i>	CUSTOMER
Startup CEO	<i>"Employee satisfaction is more important as this leads to more productivity, so we provide monthly allowances like mobile recharges, surprise gifts, unplanned trips, remote work, flexible working shifts, This makes our company grow healthy and unique."</i>	EMPLOYEE
Startup Manager	<i>"We value the young talents to reach different heights in their careers".</i>	EMPLOYEE
Entrepreneur	<i>"Since it is started new, We are forming a culture with friendly environment with more learning"</i>	EMPLOYEE

Agile transformation in the context of India requires the understanding of Indian culture and the way startups perceive culture and its significance. The responses from the interviewees to highlight the significance of culture for the success of the startups have been tabulated in Table 4.6. The responses from the startups founders were named under the focus of employees, customers and both together and the results showed that 11 out of 15 startups signified culture to be employee centric which shows how much culture impacts team building.

When a female lead developer who has been in the company for 3 years was asked about the agile culture her response was as follows:

“I guess so... They should believe in a certain methodology: out of five people, if four are working in an Agile manner and the one is not speaking up and standing, the team's efficiency is at stake. So, if a culture is present and everybody follows that Agile culture so that the end result is aligned with what they actually started for.”

Although the tone that she was explaining depicted that she wasn't sure in the beginning she strongly believes that an agile culture can build team efficiency and moreover the strategic alignment of vision and goals. When scrutinizing the sustainability factors, this research found out that unproductive culture played a key role in the failure of startups and therefore this response from her truly supports it.

When discussed within the focus group a senior project manager who has worked for 5+ years explained as follows:

“Have you noticed how businesses practicing agile development seem to struggle with transformation? Why do you think that is? Well, a lot of the failures are tied to culture and resistance to change. People think it's just about adopting new practices. It's more than that. Agile is about fostering a collaborative and adaptive culture. But there's often resistance because it means shifting established norms. Sounds more like it's not just a process change but a whole cultural shift isn't it.”

This shows that the resistance to change has been the biggest hurdle for successful adoption of agile practices. He also added that:

“You see, continuous learning and cross-functional training are just as crucial as the Agile transformation itself. Think about it... you cannot afford to be outdated when the world around you is constantly evolving. Adopting Agile doesn't stop at initial stages, it's about nurturing an agile mindset over time. This is why... regular training sessions are needed for teams to be well-versed in the latest practices, fostering adaptability and knowledge-sharing. It's like an ongoing investment into continuous learning”

According to him, continuously learning from failures and making cross-functional training available for the entire team can equip them with the latest agile principles and practices. The tone which he said, proves the urgency of this to be implemented for company success. When a startup founder who was in the discussion with other managers and senior scrum masters raised a question asking the culture of less documentation, as agile prioritizes interactions over documentations, and one of the senior managers who has had 15+ year of experience explained as follows:

“Adopting Agile doesn’t mean there’s no documentation at all! I see a lot of project managers in startups who get confused with this fact. It just prioritizes customer feedback, internal and external communication over the strenuous documentation phase. As I already mentioned the rigidity in traditional methods, Agile tries to strike a balance between documenting enough to allow for future knowledge transfer while keeping unnecessary work to a minimum. This can be one of the trickiest parts of implementing an agile process in a startup!”

This explains the documentation crisis explained in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.5.5 where we discussed the implementation challenges of agile in reality. This also adds to the implementation challenges presented in Table 2.11, where culture transformation in people aspect can be crucial for the effective implementation of agile transformation. According to him, striking a balance between documentation and customer communication can be the key factor for IT startup sustainability in India. Moreover, another startup founder in a semi-structured interview stated these factors that affected his startup culture as follows:

“Transforming the culture and ways of working was our biggest challenge to date although we had adopted Agile practices and ceremonies. You see... technologies can be learnt, but culture cannot be achieved in a day!”

This emphasis on culture transformation prior to technology change can be seen as the ultimate people dimension of challenge. Transforming cultures isn’t quantifiable or easily achievable as he said, it needs dedicated efforts from the leadership and management to develop that unique culture to enhance decision making, personal transformation, etc. One of the agile scrum masters in a focus group claimed as follows:

“I strongly believe that changing the culture in a startup essentially means altering attitudes and behaviors when faced with challenges. Now, how do we go about that? Startup founders in India should articulate a culture that embodies willingness, commitment, respect, communication, collaboration, transparency... continuous

inspection, and adaptation. It needs to be a strategic goal for startup transformation. It can sound a bit comprehensive but wait, it doesn't end there... Leadership needs to step-up. Instead of just extracting work, they should make efforts to train and educate the team with Agile principles, values, practices, and frameworks. Simply pushing for results won't cut it in the long run, benefiting neither the startup nor the team.”

She has worked for multiple teams and various projects offshore and understands that culture should be considered in strategic direction and planning. According to her, the leadership and management should make ample efforts to educate and train the team. She also added key principles of agile as the ultimate cultural goals for a startup in India. Upon comprehensive analysis, it becomes evident that Indian startups face a critical imperative to confront and rectify the pervasive culture of resistance. Leadership must unequivocally take ownership and exert efforts to educate and train employees, instilling agile values and principles. A pivotal shift necessitates the realignment of metrics to accentuate value addition. Emphasized in Sub-Section 2.7.5, it is crucial to acknowledge that culture is not built overnight but through the consistent cultivation of desirable behaviors in daily activities. This underscores the magnitude of sustained efforts required to transform the organizational culture, making it conducive to the successful implementation of agile methodologies and fostering an environment of continuous improvement and adaptability.

4.4.3 STAKEHOLDER PARTICIPATION

According to Abrahamsson *et al* (2002) and Aguanno (2004), stakeholder participation includes processes that enables stakeholders such as the customer, team, leadership, public, etc., to understand and influence processes that may benefit or affect them. At its core, involvement and engagement emerge as pivotal descriptors compiling the essence of stakeholder participation. This section is aimed to unravel the fundamental importance of stakeholder participation in ensuring the triumph of agile transformation. The inquiry commences by collecting insights from startup founders, probing into their strategies for stakeholder participation and retention. The ensuing responses and strategies are systematically compiled and dissected in Table 4.7, charting a course towards a nuanced understanding of how effective stakeholder engagement propels the success of agile transformations in the startup landscape.

On analyzing the responses from the startup founders, co-founders, CEOs and entrepreneurs, the word customer satisfaction and employee retention were used multiple times alongside words like trust, relationship and innovation. One of the issues highlighted in Chapter 1, Section 1.3, Table 1.2, is the ineffective stakeholder management, where it is evident that startups struggle to retain skilled workforce which undermines the ecosystem for Indian IT startups.

Table 4. 7 Stakeholder participation strategy in place

INTERVIEWEE	RESPONSES	STRATEGY IN PLACE
Startup founder	<i>"Challenging work assignments, technology training and creating a trustable environment"</i>	<i>"Prioritizing and aligning to customer needs"</i>
Entrepreneur	<i>"By setting targets that brings more revenue so they can get their Hike on Money to buy what they dream about"</i>	<i>"Innovation behind the product, we keep on innovating and trying out first"</i>
Startup co-founder	<i>"With competitive pricing"</i>	<i>"Employee retention without scare of job loss"</i>
Entrepreneur	<i>"I believe, a friendly environment and punctual services brings out the goodness of a firm"</i>	<i>"The shared experiences of my mentors are the major supplement to survive the initial periods."</i>
Startup founder	<i>"Maintain a cordial relationship with the employees"</i>	<i>"Trust"</i>
Startup founder	<i>"Customer satisfaction and focus with remuneration as per industry standards"</i>	<i>"Growth and significance in challenging times and importance to emerging technologies"</i>
Startup co-founder	<i>"Our project success rate has been 99% which results in our customer retention for years together. Our company provides massive knowledge that makes the employees stick."</i>	<i>"Our unique approach, best practices, thirst for excellence, innovative methodologies and simplistic processes contribute greatly ."</i>
Startup manager	<i>"Explaining the client - the possibility to achieve their need, guiding the client with new ways, minimizing the allotted budget, sharing simple, understandable reports and best service on time"</i>	<i>"Explaining how it works; Need vs budget vs output"</i>
Startup CEO	<i>"Provide benefits, good care, reasonable & allowed work hours to employees. For customer providing the best quality IT services with reasonable cost and be transparent with them"</i>	<i>"Make your internal customers (Employees) happy and they bring business"</i>
Entrepreneur	<i>"By meeting their needs by having proper delivery as well by encouraging the employees for their commitment"</i>	<i>"Commitment and prompt delivery"</i>

Startup co-founder	<i>"Understanding the pain points and motivators of our stakeholders (Clients, Trusted Partners and our employees/team) as our pain motivators and addressing them at Warp Speed in a continuous and consistent fashion..."</i>	<i>"Speed + Efficiency & Quality + Competitive Pricing. Effective Pains, Needs, Threats, Opportunities Analysis and Solutions. "</i>
Startup CEO	<i>"At present we are gaining clients by reference from word of mouth and sometimes, from internet sources like google, bing."</i>	<i>"We provide quality service to clients at an affordable price and if they have zero knowledge in this field we will help them in all aspects, for example, Web Development (We take care of complete SEO, hosting, domain, website security, etc.) these types of all in one support makes our client happier by comparing with other vendors."</i>
Startup Manager	<i>"By providing skilled and efficient work "</i>	<i>"Client satisfaction is the main factor "</i>
Entrepreneur	<i>"Encouraging our employees, periodical appreciations"</i>	<i>"We take personal care of the trainees who enrolled with our academy. We value the relationship rather than amount for business clients"</i>

Researchers over the years have tapped into the field of stakeholder management but very few are in the context of Indian IT startups and therefore the researcher asked one of the senior managers in an MNC and he explained as follows:

"Participation in startups means that all your customers and you as company share a common understanding and involvement in decision making, relationship building and so on. It can ultimately lead to skill empowerment, better decision making, and collective interest being met"

According to him, there's a strong relationship between stakeholder participation and effective decision making which means the goals are of collective interests. As we already discussed in earlier section, ignored customers was one of the major challenges in the startup ecosystem of India and by addressing stakeholder participation it can be possible to address this issue. When asked a startup co-founder who has worked for a startup for 1 month his response was as follows:

"We believe in trusting our employees for greater success of our startup. Our recent XP to Windows 10 migration project for a large client which normally would take a year to complete took us less than 8 months just in time for their cyber security check with the trust that our employees could deliver on time... That actually gave us confidence with the customers and has gained us more projects within our pipeline for the next 5 years"

He has been working in a larger MNC for years and decided to shift to a startup with the intention of learning and being part of a startup process shaping the company's culture and performance. His views about trust can be resonated with responses many other startup founders and senior project managers where trust increases accountability, ownership and transparency. When asked by a senior manager on measures for employee retention in a focus group he explained as follows:

“Employees have the liberty to switch or leave a startup because they might get paid more or they might get more benefits from MNCs. To be fair, it's their call! This can be a serious risk for startups who are completely dependent on their smaller team to deliver and therefore retaining their employees is as important as running their businesses. Startups need to invest in training and development, add more rewards and recognitions, offer personal growth opportunities and provide them a friendly balanced environment.”

According to her, training and development, reward techniques, work environment and personal growth can be crucial for startups in India to address the employee turnover. Although these responses address employee retention, customer satisfaction also plays a key role. When asked a startup founder in a focus group discussion about ways to do so, his response was as follows:

“When a customer trusts us with a consecutive project, I consider that as customer satisfaction because, I know as a company we've provided the best quality service! This will give me and team the confidence to attract new customers to my project profile without having the need to advertise more”

His views about customer retention are backed up with previous researcher in the literature who associate it with brand loyalty, increased marketing and perception about the company. The correlation between customer retention and less advertising can be one of the major findings for this research.

The overall analysis further underscores the significance of factors like customer collaboration within the realm of agile transformation, highlighting its profound impact on customer retention and satisfaction. Beyond this, recommendations gleaned from focus group discussions, such as the implementation of regular surveys to comprehend customer behavior and the adoption of effective team-building techniques to retain employees, emerge as invaluable considerations for startups. These insights not only illuminate the path towards enhanced customer satisfaction but also present actionable strategies for startups to fortify their customer relationships and improve internal team cohesion, aligning with the broader objectives of sustainable growth and success in a dynamic business environment.

4.4.4 HIGH VISIBILITY

In a way to engage startup founders, co-founders and entrepreneurs, the researcher asked them to rate their own startup in terms of their visibility with the customers and its risk management. Visibility here can be seen as the ability to be transparent and collaborative with customers at every stage of the process to maintain a long-term relationship with them. Out of 20 interviewees, 15 were startup founders and the rating they gave for their startup is as shown in Figure 4.3.

We can see that 48.7% of the founders think their startup is highly visible with the customers. We also see a major lack where 46.7% of startups think they aren't visible with the customers giving themselves a rating of 3 and 4, which shows the lack of visibility amongst Indian IT startups.

Figure 4.3 Data Analysis of visibility ratings for startups

When a startup founder was asked if he thinks agile can improve visibility with customers and thereby affect sustainability, his response was as follows:

“It does, there is a to and fro communication in agile in development and I think I see that as an advantage for any startup be IT or non-IT.”

When asked how this helps build visibility with customers, he further explains that:

“Certainly! You will get help from your team when something does not go well, and it builds that level of trust in the customer that even if they've missed any notable points, team members will bring them out because there's better transparency. That gives the confidence that next time the customer demands for the same team member or a particular team to develop their product”

This shows that the level of trust increases when startups become more transparent with their process and practices with their customers. According to him, customers collaborate with the startup to add in more benefits to the software development process. Moreover, transparency has built some strong relationships with his team and customers so that they want to retain the same team for future projects. When asked in a focus group about the benefit of being transparent with customers, an agile coach with 20+ years of experience explained as follows:

“Look... transparency with customers isn't just about sharing information; it's about delivering working software early on so they can make quick changes. Imagine setting a deadline together, and as we develop, the customer is fully aware of the issues raised during software development. It provides room for changes and adjustments based on their feedback. It's not just about updates; it's about involving them early in the process. This becomes a proactive approach! Early involvement and constant communication help us meet their expectations and respond swiftly to any modifications they want to make. Transparency in action not only builds trust but also ensures that the end product aligns closely with the customer's vision.”

The way he drew a relationship between prototyping and transparency shows the impact of Agile transformation towards a startup's sustainability. Moreover, he claims that transparency in software development methods ensure that the end product aligns with the customer's vision which ultimately addresses the ignored customer needs as a sustainability factor highlighted in literature in Chapter 2 and findings in Chapter 4. Although, most researchers have already studied about the relationship between Agility and transparency, within the context of India, there needs to be drawn a tolerance level. A response from a developer turned startup founder as follows:

“I know I'm going to be controversial but look... startups need to be transparent yes and Agile does help them in that aspect of being open with the customers, making them see and verify performance in every sprint. Being transparent also reduces the risk of producing poor quality and low value work at very early stages. Yet... startups also need to be aware of patent protection and rights to safeguard themselves from imitators and competitors. You cannot just be transparent about everything!”

The need to put boundaries for transparency and tolerance has been highlighted by this developer turned startup founder who believes that software code is the core of the company and protecting it against fraudulent imitation can also be a struggle for Indian IT startups. This seems to adhere to the literature gap as to setting the tolerance level for transparency in the frameworks.

Although the research emerged with the element of visibility, the remains a need to relate it to the sustainability challenge which is the ignored customer needs. To understand this, a startup co-founder with 5 years of establishment in a focus group explained as follows:

“Agile allows startups to make changes in development quickly and ship them to customers on time. It also incrementally tests the processes, gathers customer feedback, and improves them over time. It provides customers with the highest value possible with each sprint. This can be used to their advantage by bringing products to market quickly or helping to overcome business challenges quickly, even if incrementally in all disciplines.”

Incremental software development is seen as the value for agile startups to be sustainable and be transparent with the customers. According to him, applying transparency in all levels of management and employees can impact sustainability of Indian IT startups. This corresponds to Figure 2.16 in Chapter 2, Section 2.5, where agile methodologies can aid startups to improve visibility and thereby reduce risk, which furthermore aligns with the risk agility. Analysis of visibility element of agile, risk identification in terms of external stakeholder such as the customers and clients can be crucial for creating a robust risk mitigation. The next section will scrutinize the optimum resource allocation for achieving sustainability in Indian IT startups.

4.4.5 OPTIMUM RESOURCE ALLOCATION

Optimum resource allocation here can be seen as the measures towards effective strategic planning to obtain quick feedback and optimize resource allocation. We have seen in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.3.4, how resource allocation impacts risk management of IT startups which shows its significance towards achieving sustainability. In a way to engage and obtain relevant results, as shown in Figure 4.4, 15 startup founders, co-founders and entrepreneurs were asked to rate the importance of optimum resource allocation for sustaining their startups and 46.7% voted for 4 rating, 33.3% voting for 5 rating and 13.3% voted for 3 rating. This shows that almost 80% of the startups believe that resource allocation is necessary for startups.

Figure 4. 4 Data Analysis of resource allocation ratings for startups

When further asked a senior manager who has 10+ years of experience in the IT industry about the impact of agile transformation on resource allocation, his response was as follows:

“Have you ever thought about how the software realm is evolving into this dynamic, ever-changing environment? It's starting to resemble a complex adaptive system. And you know, the way resources are allocated in agile is a game-changer compared to traditional methods. In traditional approaches, resource allocation tends to be static, fixed. But in agile, it's way more dynamic, adapting to the needs of the project as it unfolds. Projects

adopting Agile are getting more flexible and responsive to the changes that are inherent in the software landscape. Dynamic resource allocation in agile allows us to navigate the rapid shifts and inventions in the software world more effectively. Now that's something that all Agile frameworks should aim to implement!"

This shows that the complexity of software projects in recent years has increased leading to a dynamic resource allocation method. According to him agile as compared to traditional methods can address this ambiguity. There's also a stress on the factor that dynamic resource allocation needs to be an unavoidable element in any Agile startup framework. Although there were multiple responses that agreed with this statement, a few senior project managers in the focus group stated as follows:

"When there's not enough information on the story board, it becomes difficult to initially do resource planning in Agile. Budget estimation is fixed in Waterfall and therefore the customer knows what to expect in terms of cost."

This argument from a senior project manager was kept as a discussion in another focus group where one of the senior agile scrum masters who has worked for 10+ years stated as follows:

"In my experience, Agile teams learn early what works and what doesn't! As the project is done in cycles of sprints, the funds are released in the beginning of a sprint keeping managers and the team well informed for decision making and potentially reduce overall spending. And in Agile, you're not wasting time and efforts on building something that the customer doesn't need and therefore re-engineering cost gets reduced whereas in Waterfall, it's huge!"

According to her, incremental software releases and accommodation of errors in the early stages drastically reduces re-engineering costs in agile methods as compared to rigid traditional methods. From the tone she set, she was confident that customers aren't always aware of their needs and therefore that requires dynamic resource allocation methods. On asking a startup founder, the practical challenges of resource allocation in his startup, he explained as follows:

"Because we're an emerging startup, it's highly difficult to find the right people with the required skill set. More goes into training them and that challenges the funds that we have. Sometimes, we'd have to depend on a few of our senior developers for multiple projects who eventually get burnt out. It's mostly out of force because we're left with no choice. Also, when a customer suggests a change, you also need to have available resources in your team. It can be human skills, technological advancements, management skills, training needed, etc. All play a major part in resource allocation"

As stated, finding the right team has been a challenge for most startups and the findings have proved that to be true. Burning out senior developers and highly skilled employees not only drains them but also might lead to employee turnover at some point. According to him, accommodating change is one thing, but making sure the resources are available to accommodate them is another.

When asked an agile coach in a focus group with 20+ years of experience about the possible steps that Indian IT startups could take to overcome this resource allocation barrier, he claimed that:

“Agile involves less rigorous planning compared to traditional methods. It's more about adaptability. You may immediately ask... doesn't that make resource allocation less predictable? Yes... It does introduce some unpredictability, but Agile offers resource management practices like resource leveling, where we identify and establish resources before taking on a project. Interesting isn't it! It involves effective forecasting techniques and the use of automated resource allocation software. It makes task and project allocation more flexible, especially in the challenging environment of the Indian startup system. So, I would say... it's a trade-off between adaptability and predictability where a balance is maintained by providing flexibility in resource handling while maintaining effective resource management practices.”

This shows how good agile practices such as resource levelling, automated resource allocation and forecasting techniques can actually lead to optimum resource allocation. The word flexibility that he used can be taken as agility here and therefore resource agility can be significant for agile transformation. To finally know the impact of resource agility on sustainability and risk management, one of the senior managers from focus group responded as follows:

“Startups need to develop that agility to regularly confirm and adjust requirements according to ongoing communication with the customer. They should be able to deliver fully functional and tested software features so that technical risks can be identified early and mitigated throughout the process. So yes... resource agility does impact risk management and can have a direct effect on sustainability.”

This response where the idea of customer collaboration reduces technical risks early in the development phase can be accredited to the success of agile transformation in providing risk agility in businesses, having a direct influence of the sustainability of Indian IT startups. Overall analysis proves that optimum resource allocation can have a direct impact on the sustainability of Indian IT startups moreover, they consider the human resource risks and improve their forecasting, resource levelling and communication skills to adhere to the changes. This link strengthens the need for agile in Indian IT startups. The next section will discuss more on strategic alignment.

4.4.6 STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT

According to Gopagani and Sabbella (2020), misalignment of strategic goals has been critical for failure in IT startups where the project doesn't reach the intended goals and objectives. As shown in Figure 4.5, startup founders, co-founders and entrepreneurs were asked to rate the importance of agile in strategic alignment for their startup and almost 46.7% of the responses gave 4 stars whereas 40% gave 5 stars, 86.7% collectively believe that agile improves strategic alignment.

Figure 4. 5 Data Analysis of strategic alignment ratings for startups

The responses frequently used the strategic alignment with vision and goals of the startup as one of the key challenges for most startups. When a senior project manager with 10+ years of experience was asked about his views on strategic alignment, he explained as follows:

“Strategic planning executed with an agile mindset can yield a transformational shift in an organization committed to scaling agile. Then only will they be able to see improved operational effectiveness through the continuous alignment of business and technology teams. The learning and development plan with the business plan should be put in place properly to align/achieve the strategic business mission, vision, strategy and goals.”

This view about strategic planning with agile transformation emphasizes the need for strategic alignment of business mission, vision, strategy and goals with the technology teams and activities. Also, the word continuous alignment sets the tone of urgency and significance in a startup.

When asked a startup founder with 3 years of establishment about the impact of agile on strategic alignment in his startup, his response was as follows:

“Aligning departmental goals towards the ultimate mission of our startup to provide excellent and best quality IT services has been the key and Agile... in a way has helped us get that clear and visible with our customers”

Agile has helped him align his departmental goals with that of the startups vision and goals wherein customer satisfaction has improved establishing the link between customer relationship and strategic alignment. Another startup founder with 2 years of establishment claimed that:

“In my opinion... the entire team needs to know the context in which they’re working and the impact of every activity they do towards achieving the vision and goals of the startup. Then there’s no point, isn’t it? Now with Agile... the results are evident, and outcomes are highly transparent and visible with both the management and the customers. In that way we don’t have to constantly supervise them... all we need to do is make them aware of their responsibilities and trust them”

Working without context can be one of the possible failure reasons for strategic misalignment of goals and daily activities where the employees are unaware of their contribution towards success. According to him, being highly transparent with outcomes and results rather than extracting work from a team, inspecting and supervising them, makes them aware of their responsibilities and duties, which creates a healthy working environment. This correlates with Table 2.10 in Chapter 2, where agile is seen to encourage leadership and employee collaboration, which in turn encourages employees to be self-organized and maintain minimum dependency on leadership.

When a senior consultant who has consulted multiple startups for 10+ years was asked about his views if agile can impact strategic alignment and thereby increase opportunities for sustainability, he explained as follows:

“Agile has really improved decision-making across all levels, from bottom-tier employees to top management. It's making a big impact on aligning our vision and goals strategically. agile's transparency and collaboration make decision-making more inclusive and informed. It's been crucial in ensuring everyone works towards the same strategic objectives. And when a startup's strategic direction aligns with its goals, there's a significant improvement in overall performance and sustainability, right?”

The correlation between strategic alignment, overall performance and sustainability has been literature gaps discussed in Chapter 2. This brings out another aspect of improved decision making in agile transformation for the effective strategic alignment which in turn impacts sustainability of the IT startups in India.

4.4.7 STRATEGIC SENSITIVITY

Most of the responses for agile theory vs practice them stated that the employees weren't provided with a sensitive work environment where they felt motivated, appreciated or contributing towards meeting customer requirements. This emerged as a theme for further discussion where we asked startup founders, co-founders and entrepreneurs to rate the significance of having a strategic sensitive environment for a sustainable startup and 53.3% voted for strongly agree and 26.7% for agree which collectively shows that 80% of Indian startups believe that strategic sensitivity can enable sustainability in their startups, as shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4. 6 Data analysis of strategic sensitivity ratings for startups

An entrepreneur who has just established his startup for a year responded to the question of how agile transformation improves strategic sensitivity as follows:

“One of the Agile principles focuses on the project team and emphasizes the importance of trust, support and motivation. It increases productivity and profits for the startup”

Again, the word ‘trust’ has been used frequently when it comes to sensitive work environment which directly increases productivity and profitability of the startup. When asked another female startup CEO, she responded as follows:

“What I’ve seen in my experience is... Agile enables transparent communication with customers and employees, engages the team and empowers them and builds strategic partnerships. This creates agility even within the lowest level of management where employees also become more agile!”

Ensuring agility within employees can be a takeaway for startups wishing to improve strategic sensitivity within the startups. According to her, building agility from lower levels of management can impact the startup for a bigger picture. This corresponds to Table 2.9 in Chapter 2, Section 2.5, where agile transformation is seen to facilitate organic structure within an organization, wherein it encourages flexible and participative work environment. Another senior manager with 10+ years of experience was asked about employees getting burnt out in startups, he responded as follows:

“Agile provides strategic benefits... focus on the highest-priority features, ongoing risk management and producing substantially higher-quality outputs... Now, all this together can result in significantly more effective use of staff time. This means that your department can produce more business value for the same level of effort, and within the same timeframe and budget. Higher levels of productivity during standard working hours also minimizes the need for last-minute fighting and overtime!”

Here, the senior manager who has worked for multiple projects highlighted the frequent problem of employees having the need to work overtime. He further suggested that agile can actually standardize the working hours yet produce better results and increased profits. Another senior consultant who has worked for 10+ years, in a focus group explained as follows:

“Have you noticed how Agile makes work feel so much more rewarding? The quick results we get are way more satisfying than drowning in piles of paperwork. Not just that, we deliver top-notch software, making us feel proud of what we do. It's a win-win! Plus... it seems like this whole concept... kind of... boosts employee morale, making them stick around. That's got to be good for the team and the company. Overall, this can result in an environment of greater employee retention, with the corresponding benefits of reducing the department's overheads by replacing staff and preserving corporate memory.”

In the previous section where stakeholder participation was considered as a significant prerequisite for agile transformation, here we see that creating a sensitive work environment can target employee retention. Also, the ability of agile transformation to value and celebrate employees and their success can further enable employee satisfaction. Another agile scrum master in a focus group furthered the discussion as follows:

“An environment that fosters the rapid delivery of tangible outcomes, the production of substantially higher-quality outputs and responsiveness to business change requires staff to be creative in the design of their solutions to ensure that delivered functionality and underlying technical platforms are readily adaptable in the future. This can often lead to innovative solutions to address the challenges of ensuring both utility and extensibility in delivered capabilities.”

Innovation, as significant for sustainability, needs to be inculcated within the sensitive work environment where everyone feels the need to adapt to futuristic technologies and advancements. According to her, Agile transformation can highly influence innovation with technologies, engineering practices and cutting-edge solutions which can definitely impact sustainability of Indian IT startups. Moreover, the focus on employee retention and satisfaction can be evident through the responses obtained.

4.4.8 COMMUNICATING PRIORITIES

According to Jedynak (2015), reducing the amount of work not done can be one of the implementation challenges for MNC and startups. In India, as discussed in previous sections, the miscommunication of priorities has led to the poor quality and inconsistent deliverables, one of the themes that emerged from the discussion of agile theory vs practice. To understand more about the relationship between agile communication of priorities and sustainability, the researcher asked startups to rate this and only 27% were confident and 46% stated maybe compared to 27% stating no, collectively voting 73% favoring agile for communicating priorities.

When a senior project manager was asked in a focus group about the significance of communicating priorities over sustainability, his response was as follows:

“Yes... product owners and scrum masters based on product owner’s input have the authority to command the prioritization of day-to-day work. Communication of priorities based on business changes is more effective in agile compared to traditional methods as it comes via an only source of POC!”

As a project manager who has worked with traditional and agile methodologies, he points out the prioritization of day-to-day work and communication of priorities has been effective in agile methods compared to traditional methods. In a focus group discussion, a startup co-founder also expressed similar views and added to this point as follows:

“Agile is all about keeping that communication flowing smoothly. It’s not a one-and-done deal. You communicate regularly checking in with the customer. The project team works hand-in-hand with them to make sure what you’re doing aligns with the organization’s latest priorities. It’s like... a constant feedback loop to make sure you’re on the right track. So, instead of just sticking to a plan, you’re always adapting based on the current priorities! Responsive to change!”

According to him, adapting to changing priorities can also be a challenge for Indian IT startups and their sustainability. Another senior agile coach who has been part of larger and smaller companies and responsible for agile transformation explains as follows:

“The rapid delivery of tangible outcomes as part of ongoing risk management compels staff to regularly produce fully functional and fully tested features. Building these functional capabilities requires working system components, such as an established architecture, a live database, and a functional integration platform... all of which can help with the identification of technical risks for isolated features for solution issues.”

The technical aspects that he mentioned of functional integration and architecture can be seen as highest priorities when considering technical risks that might arise during software development. These can be taken as critical for IT startups in India as they have been a major risk for larger companies as well. Another startup founder who has had previous experience of working in larger companies, when asked about the significance of communicating priorities stated as follows:

“The strong alignment with business requirements, focus on the highest-priority features, and responsiveness to business change...underpins Agile approaches at a strategic level also serve to focus staff on consistently producing capabilities that the business actually needs with features that are usable... and used... by the customer. Not only does this create a stronger working relationship with the customer or more positive feedback about a specific department throughout the organization, but it also means that customers are less likely to urgently need critical features added to a delivered system.”

The initial concern raised about cost effectiveness and late deliverables were identified through this response. According to him, startups build product features that are not of highest priority, making employees lose focus of producing capabilities that businesses need. The feedback mechanism of agile communication can build stronger working relationships with customers and produce deliverable at the right time. This adheres to Table 2.10, where agile promotes continuous planning and adaptability, informal and more people-oriented communication which makes priorities easier to be communicated with employees and leadership.

Another senior consultant for startups responded as follows:

“In my years of experience... I believe... startups in India need to quickly learn to trust the process and the team to deliver capabilities that meet their requirements, rather than rely upon pre-defined documentation as a safety net to ensure that their needs will be met. To add to this... transparency in status tracking means that the department will be less dependent upon detailed upfront project plans... this ensures that work stays on track to deliver agreed outcomes.”

The resounding tone in his response accentuates the systemic failure among Indian IT startups, placing undue emphasis on pre-defined documentation rather than cultivating trust in the team and the iterative process, which corresponds to the agile literature and manifesto value in Chapter 2, Section 2.5. This illustration vividly underscores the critical importance of prioritizing agility over inflexible processes.

An overall examination of these insights unveils a compelling narrative: startups that adeptly communicate priorities are better at delivering agreed outcomes with diminished reliance on cumbersome documentation and tracking measures. The responses compellingly establish a robust correlation, asserting that effective communication of priorities forms the base connecting sustainability and agile transformation. This linkage signifies that a strategic shift towards prioritization and clear communication is pivotal for startups seeking sustained success in the competitive IT landscape.

4.4.9 CONTINUOUS LEARNING

Another concern raised during discussion from sustainability factors affecting Indian startups was the team inefficiencies and quality of product. The emerged theme from this discussion was the learning culture in Indian startups where startups continuously learn from every project they take over. The extent to which agile transformation can impact continuous learning was asked and more than 80% of the startup founders, entrepreneurs and managers believed that agile actually promotes learning and development.

A startup founder who recently did a new project for a well-known customer stated as follows:

“Learning happens all the time, during a project. Leaders who recognize this and give employees the space... either physical, virtual or XR... the capacity, which is time to learn... and personalized or engaging experiences, will drive enthusiasm and curiosity to learn, which in turn sets a solid foundation for a culture of learning.”

He further credited his startup’s learning culture for the phenomenal turnover that they made for their new project. The emphasis that he put on leadership shows the significance and the urgency for managers to implement this as part of the culture. Furthermore, another senior manager in a focus group responded as follows:

“Workforces with a continuous learning mindset and high digital readiness can adapt more swiftly to the next unknown. Organizations that are highly collaborative and use agile learning strategies... in my opinion... will be better positioned to reskill and upskill their workforces to meet these future challenges. Teams should learn continuously through daily collaboration and problem solving. Events such as team retrospectives and inspect and adapt will automatically support this. SAFe model, a recently booming agile model, provides regular dedicated time and space for learning through the innovation and planning iteration that occurs in every program increment in a sprint.”

The link between agile mindset and agile culture and the successful agile transformation can further be empirically proved through this response. Moreover, he draws a direct relationship between continuous learning and ability to adapt to uncertainty. Reskilling and upskilling are two strategies that he proposed for successful learning culture. Another senior agile scrum master with 10+ years of experience, suggested another aspect of agile learning culture as follows:

“Agile methods through continuous retrospective feedback and project review meetings contribute towards driving innovation. Not only for the managers but also for the employees who want to grow and outperform their past achievements should continuously update, innovate and compete. The management should be responsible for such motivational measures to incorporate learning and development. This can actually help startups grow and sustain in the market”

This response shows how continuous learning contributes to innovation, personal growth, development, startup’s growth and sustainability. The direct difference between these elements has been evident with all the other responses. This corresponds to Table 2.9 and Table 2.10 which highlights the continuous learning and upskilling aspects of agile transformation for the sustainability of Indian IT startups. A holistic analysis predominantly directs managers to prioritize a robust culture of continuous learning, fostering it systematically through project retrospect and reviews to propel sustained success in the dynamic and competitive Indian startup landscape.

4.5 AGILE TRANSFORMATION ON SUSTAINABILITY: NEW INFERENCES

The impacts of agile transformation on the sustainability of IT startups have been the soul of this research as shown in Chapter 1, Section 1.7 and this section brings out the actual opinion and views of the interviewees within the context of India. Research Question 4: “How effective are current agile transformation frameworks in managing sustainability of Indian IT start-ups?”, requires a holistic view of how agile frameworks support sustainability of Indian IT startups and how effectively do existing frameworks capture its elements. The findings in this theme address this research question. While addressing the adopted themes such as sustainability, traditional and agile implementational challenges, three new themes such as agile mindset, agile culture and stakeholder participation as pre-requisites and six new themes under agile elements emerged which startup founders, co-founder, entrepreneurs and managers consider as critical for the sustainability of Indian IT startups. To get more clarity, they were subdivided to understand agile for three disciplines of management namely, risk, strategy and performance.

When asked about the impact of agile elements spanning from Sub-Section 4.4.1 to Sub-Section 4.4.9 on the sustainability of Indian IT startups, responses were categorized into yes, no, maybe, and not sure. The conclusive findings, as illustrated in Figure 4.7, resounds an assertive 53.3% of startup founders, co-founders, and managers unequivocally expressing a strong yes. This statistical majority underscores a compelling consensus, signifying a prevailing belief among over half of the sampled participants that these agile transformation elements wield a direct and affirmative influence on the sustainability of their startups.

Figure 4. 7 Data Analysis of Impacts of Agile transformation on sustainability

23.3% strongly stated that agile does not impact sustainability in any form through these elements. 16.7% stated that these agile elements alongside few other critical management elements could bring more clarity and effect into sustainability of startups. 6.7% were unsure of the idea of agile transformation and its direct impacts on sustainability. On analysis we can collectively see that 76.6% including both yes and maybe believe that these above elements can have direct impact on the sustainability of Indian IT startups for long-term.

The discussion of sustainability factors suggested that team inefficiencies, untimely deliverables and quality of the product as predominant factors affecting Indian startup sustainability. To understand deeper about the direct impacts of agile transformation on sustainability for the context of Indian IT startups, the researcher further questioned startups founders and managers, and one of them responded as follows:

“I would say... the best process for a start-up is one which allows room for quick decisions, streamlines workflow, and consensus on how things should be done. As the business scales, it would also be convenient to have a process that can easily be reproduced for each new team. Agile transformation... on the whole helps achieve this for startup sustainability”

This response highlights the strategic and operational agility through agile transformation for sustainability of Indian IT startups. Further, another senior consultant who analyzes the financial status of startups, stated as follows:

“One of the most desirable benefits of Agile transformation is the higher return on investment. Agile organizations are more efficient and focuses only on projects that deliver ROI. They constantly measure performance and reassess projects, eliminating any that do not offer real value. This can give an advantage over competitors”

The financial concern of the startup sustainability can also be addressed through agile transformation and provide competitive advantage over competitors. Although the financial theme has been further recommended for future research, the link between agile transformation and sustainability to provide competitive advantage has been established through this response.

Another senior manager in a focus group provided practical guidelines to achieve strategic agility through agile transformation practices as follows:

“IT startup founders and managers in India are in a unique position to align the day-to-day work that is done by their staff with the overarching strategic objectives and guidelines of the organization. This combined role can often be a balancing act of juggling executive demands along with the practical challenges of delivering effective technological solutions. However, it also provides an opportunity for IT directors to double the benefits that they can receive from the use of Agile approaches in their department by leveraging both the strategic and tactical advantages that they deliver.”

According to him, there is an urgent need to align day-to-day activities with the overall strategic management of the Indian IT startups. He further emphasizes the need for agile towards effective technological solutions and tactical advantages. This corresponds to Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.5.3 and 2.5.4, Figure 2.12 and Figure 2.13 which highlights the benefits of agile transformation and its significant manifesto values.

Finally, another senior consultant who has consulted for various IT startups in India, when asked about the overall impacts of agile transformation on startups, explained as follows:

“As a consultant, I’ve experienced the magnitude in which Agile really helps startups cut down on software costs. It’s all about aligning with what the business really needs and focusing on the top-priority features. But how does that impact the overall costs? When we’re in sync with business requirements and keep our focus sharp, it means fewer headaches down the road. Agile is all about delivering the best quality products that stand the test of time. But you know... nothing’s perfect. Does it mean our solutions are error-free? No... Incremental testing doesn’t guarantee perfection, but it sure does catch a lot of

issues early on. It's all about quality control throughout the Agile process. Let me keep it simple... Agile is built for change. It embraces evolving business demands and ensures our solutions can adapt. So, it's not just about now; it's about being ready for what's coming. We're not just minimizing costs now but also future proofing solutions. It's like an investment in efficiency.”

According to him agile brings more than just process innovation but also impacts positively over the overall cost effectiveness, giving the competitive advantage needed. This aspect of sustainability provides the impact of agile sustainability to bring organizational agility within the startups to further enhance the scope of agile transformation. He further highlights the strategic, risk and operational agility combined to provide sustainability of Indian IT startups. Overall analysis shows the strong relationship between agile transformation and IT sustainability.

4.6 CHAPTER CONCLUSION

This chapter drew inferences from the qualitative research in Chapter 2 and used appropriate table and figures to explain the findings. The overview of the word tree and themes were presented earlier in this chapter followed by detailed analysis of adopted and emerged themes from this research. Finally, new inferences from the factual findings have been stated in Section 4.5. As per the findings from Sub-Sections 4.3.3 to 4.4.3 there has been a clear misunderstanding of agile principles, values and practices and therefore, three pre-requisites such as agile mindset, agile culture and stakeholder participation have been highlighted. As per the findings in Sub-Sections 4.4.4 and 4.4.5 the Researcher found out that the increased visibility and optimized adaptability of resources have had impacts over risk management and risk agility. The idea of agile for risk management has been there in literatures for recent years but not empirically proved but with findings it could be seen that there Another theme that emerged from the adopted discussion was the impact of agile transformation on strategic management when discussion about the factors affecting sustainability such as the strategic misalignment and unskilled labor in Sub-Sections 4.4.6 and 4.4.7. The themes that emerged through the findings in Sub-Sections 4.4.8 and 4.4.9 were the relationship between communicating priorities, continuous learning and agile transformation sustainability. The final theme from Section 4.5, shows how sustainability in Indian IT startups can give competitive advantage and organizational agility for a long-term. The next chapter will further discuss these findings with various literatures in the research field and further validate them with the framework developed in Chapter 2, Figure 2.22.

CHAPTER 5 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

5.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, we delve into the intricacies of both adopted and emerged themes gleaned from the preceding chapter's findings, evaluating and analyzing them with the insights of various authors in the field of agile transformation. Despite the growing interest and contributions of numerous researchers in this domain, the current discourse encapsulates explicitly articulated information within its dedicated sections. Additionally, we revisit and refine the proposed framework introduced in Chapter 2, aligning it with the emergent themes to bridge gaps in literature and framework understanding, and generate new hypotheses.

The discussion in this chapter primarily extends to the impact of agile transformation on both project and overall startup sustainability, drawing relationships between literature review in Chapter 2 and findings in Chapter 4, validating the similarities and highlighting the differences. The data analysis, particularly focused on IT startups in India, underscores the pivotal role of establishing an agile mindset, fostering an agile culture, and ensuring stakeholder participation for the success of agile transformation. The framework illustrated in Figure 5.8 emphasizes targeting agile practices and tools to attain sustainability, addressing a notable gap in existing frameworks that fail to cater specifically to Indian IT startups.

This chapter further elucidates emerged findings from the research, the significance of agile transformation in bolstering sustainability within key management disciplines, namely risk, strategy, and performance management, and practical strategies for mitigating risks, aligning agile practices with the startup's vision, and fostering a motivated workforce committed to continuous learning. A comprehensive exploration of the step-by-step implementation guidance, along with an analysis of the strengths and limitations of the framework, is also presented in this chapter.

5.2 KEY SUSTAINABILITY FACTORS AND PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The researcher through data analysis of semi-structured interviews and focus groups accumulated both literature findings and empirical investigation related to the Indian IT startup ecosystem to bring out the following key themes that have significant impact on the successful implementation of the conceptual framework and their interaction with each other.

The idea of agile transformation for macro-management of IT companies has picked up interest in recent years where a shift towards implementing this agile transformation for startups has been influenced by sustainability factors that have affected them. Chapter 2, Section 2.6, disclosed that silo/traditional software development and management overlooked the importance of strategic alignment of IT processes and management for agile adoption.

Both academic publication and industry reviews proposed challenges to agile adoption and implementation which affected risk, strategy and performance. Findings from data collection showed that the dynamic nature of IT startups in India has forced and or encouraged them to re-evaluate their software development process and management. Literature reveals the increase in the exit rate of startups as one of the internal drivers that has scrutinized IT processes. Although these have been driving forces for entrepreneurs, startup founders and project managers to adopt agile, the failure to address existing structure, silo cultural risks, change resistance, etc., have all the more stagnated startups from growing. Core organization aspects such as risk, strategy and performance have been a major concern for startups founders identified in Chapter 2, Section 2.2.

Researchers have tabulated the need for a sustainable framework that helps foster cost-effective, timely and quality delivery of software whereby the management should supervise software development processes and factors that affect the business. As detailed in Chapter 2, Section 2.6, Table 2.13 and Appendix 3, the four-quadrant framework helped categorize literatures based on their source, purpose, results and relevance to this research. Most research done in the context of agile transformation and sustainability has been visionary and more descriptive in nature leaving a void in the actual prescriptive literatures. While some have focused on sustainability in different perspectives and agile transformation for larger companies linking few of the elements, only few exist in the fourth quadrant where a framework has been developed and its implementation guidance has been provided, which has been the main focus of this research.

Figure 5.1 compiles the research findings of sustainability factors that affect sustainability of Indian IT startups from Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1. In Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.2.3 and Sub-Section 2.2.4, we identified multiple factors from academic and industrial literatures that affected the sustainability of Indian IT startups in these disciplines.

Although academic literatures from Crittenden *et al* (2011), Savitz and Weber (2007), Bocken *et al* (2014) and Orsato *et al* (2015), in Sub-Section 2.2.3.1, Table 2.3, identified strategic factors such as ineffective planning, poor requirement management, misaligned road maps, pre-mature scaling and failed business model, factors such as strategic misalignment and unproductive culture were relevant and more significant for the sustainability of Indian IT startups as found out in Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1.

Figure 5. 1 Discussion on sustainability factors on research findings

According to Morioka and Carvalho (2016), Bansal and Roth (2000), Silvius and Tharp (2013), Zheng (2013) and Paulraj *et al* (2017), performance factors such as poor financials, team inefficiency, stagnant learning and unsatisfied customers were identified as integral factors that affect sustainability of startups in Sub-Section 2.2.3.2, Table 2.4. Through interviews and focus group discussion the researcher found out that the two significant factors are team inefficiency and poor quality of deliverables in Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1. According to Winnall (2013), Silvius *et al* (2012), Hijazi *et al* (2012), Purvis *et al* (2019) and Noshir *et al* (2019), in Sub-Section 2.2.3.3, risk factors such as high uncertainty, legal compliance, lack of innovation, poor resource management and miscommunication were identified to affect sustainability. Findings from Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1, showed that two significant factors such as ignored customer needs and ineffective planning is considered significant risk factors to affect sustainability within the context of Indian IT startups.

The literature supports the view that sustainability factors can be unique to demographic regions and therefore the identification of these unique factors have added insight into the sustainability literature in the context of Indian IT startups. The results in line with the Section 2.2.5, Table 2.6, accumulating all the factors from multiple literatures in addition with industrial publications such as Statista (2019), Forbes (2019), CB Insights (2019) and Failory (2020), have been validated in findings and unique factors within the context has been identified.

5.3 TRADITIONAL METHODOLOGIES FAILURES

Literatures from Reiffer (2002) and Fowler (2004), in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.4.1, defined the scope of traditional methodologies for the sustainability of startups. Three major methods such as the waterfall in Sub-Section 2.4.2, Iterative in Sub-Section 2.4.3 and Spiral model in Sub-Section 2.4.4 were scrutinized and discussed. Munassar and Govardhan (2011), Bassil (2012) and Vaishnavi *et al* (2014), highlighted the ignored customer communication, no for change during software development, substantial risk, uncertainty, unsuitability for smaller project, ineffective measurement and tracking and untimely deliver as failures of waterfall method. Moreover, Nabil *et al* (2010), Munassar and Govardhan (2011), Ahimbisibwe *et al* (2015), Budi *et al* (2016) and Adel and Abdullah (2015), stated that Iterative methods required more resources and constant management, issues with foreseeing design changes, unsuitability for smaller projects, unidentified risks and requirement of highly skilled expertise for risk analysis as failures of this model in Sub-Section 2.4.3.

Richard *et al* (2015), Khan *et al* (2013), Leasu *et al* (2012) and Mahalakshmi and Sundararajan (2013), proposed factors such as cost ineffectiveness, requirement of highly skilled employees, ineffective for small projects, mini-waterfall methods, no accommodation for change, chances to exceed deadlines as failures of Spiral methods. Chapter 2, Table 2.7 compares all the traditional methodologies by scrutinizing their appraisals and criticism, where the impacts of traditional methods on sustainability can be seen. To support the literatures of Stocia *et al* (2013), Olszewska *et al* (2016), Berglund *et al* (2018) and Dean (2020), the Table 5.1 compares the factors from existing literatures and factors unique to Indian IT startups.

Table 5. 1 Comparison of literature and findings for failures of traditional methods

LITERATURE REVIEW (Section 2.4, Table 2.7)	RESEARCH FINDINGS (Section 4.3.2, Fig 4.2)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High risk and uncertainty involved • No room for change during development process • Not suitable for complex and object oriented projects • Progress measurement is difficult • Skilled expertise required • Poor risk identification techniques • Ineffective and unsuitable for smaller projects • Expensive and cost-ineffective • High re-engineering cost • Rigorous level of documentation • Highly rigid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer time to market • No room for change during development • No working model till end of deployment • High Rigidity • Difficult to measure progress • Requires highly skilled workforce • More documentation • Client not involved • Re-engineering costs more • Difficult to visualize progress • Lack of focus towards team handling and culture

In Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.3.2, Figure 4.2, the reasons why traditional methodologies cannot meet the sustainability requirements have been identified as failure factors through research findings from both focus groups and semi-structured interviews. According to findings, there were two critical concerns that contradicted the literatures and provided new insights within the context of sustainability of Indian IT startups. As detailed in Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.3.2, almost 90% of the responses criticized traditional methods to take longer time to reach the market. The second focus is team handling, which has been completely ignored by traditional methods as 30% of the responses voted for team inefficiency in them. This shows that the research findings support the literature but also adds two key major findings within the context such as the longer time and team inefficiency. Analyzing both these factors can empirically and academically prove that traditional methodologies cannot impact sustainability of Indian IT startups as detailed in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.4.5. This also supports the literature of Geyi *et al* (2020) and Dean and Marc (2020), where there remains a need for more agile methods to support sustainability of IT startups.

5.4 AGILE TRANSFORMATION ON SUSTAINABILITY FACTORS

Literatures from Cohen *et al* (2004), Collier (2012), Reis (2011), Measey (2015) and Campanelli and Parreiras (2015), in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.5.1, defined the agile transformation along with its manifesto values in Sub-Section 2.5.2, followed by the benefits of agile transformation in Section 2.5.3.

According to Dikert *et al* (2016), Ghani and Bello (2015) and Kamei *et al* (2017), agile transformation has direct impact on the process and can improve efficiency and effectiveness in the management. Although multiple literatures in Sub-Section 2.5.4 such as Balaji and Sundararajan (2012), Leau *et al* (2012), Stocia *et al* (2013) and Sanchez and Connor (2016) have compared traditional methods and Agile methods, there exists the literature gap in the linking between these elements and sustainability as detailed in Section 2.6. Sub-Section 2.5.6 scrutinized the literature of agile adoption challenges in practice to understand the misconceptions and misinterpretations of agile transformation. According to Chow and Cao (2008), Sharma *et al* (2012), Kamei *et al* (2017), Ghani *et al* (2015) and Alsahli *et al* (2017), agile transformation has not been tailored, well-defined and properly provided with guidelines as mentioned in Section 2.6. As detailed in Chapter2, Table 2.14, there is a lack of a fully dynamic and holistic sustainable transformation method framework which considers factors such as mindset, culture, silo sustainability practices, custom define sustainability, and good understanding of agile transformation and key factors affecting sustainability. To understand the startup managers and founders' perspective on agile transformation, this research implemented semi-structured interviews with 15 startup executives and 5 senior manager and consultant who have had experience with startups and focus groups with both categories mixed as detailed in Section 3.8.

The findings in Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.3.3, Table 4.3 and Table 4.4, support the literature review Table 2.12 to confirm that there exists an unclear understanding of agile transformation. 26 out of 30 interviewees correlate agile to breaking down of large volume of data into workable software. This supports the literature from Ghani *et al* (2015) and Kamei *et al* (2017), where the benefits of agile transformation have been provided. Also, the perception that agile is just a tool to satisfy clients, agile is not for startups, no fixed budgeting, agile doesn't require documentation, agile is proven and needs no tailoring are few misconceptions that findings from Chapter 4, Table 4.4 Sub-Section 4.3.4 comprehend. In addition, the findings suggested that the startup founders who have had previous experience as developers in MNCs have different views than startup founders as managers, which contradicts the literature about the development team.

Although most of the findings supported the literatures from Chapter2, section 2.5 and accredited the literature gaps from Section 2.6 where the literature gaps have been tabulated, there were 9 themes that emerged under two main themes such as the agile pre-requisites including agile

mindset in Sub-Section 4.4.1, agile culture in Sub-Section 4.4.2 and stakeholder participation in Sub-Section 4.4.3. and agile sustainability elements such as high visibility in Sub-Section 4.4.4, optimum resource allocation in Sub-Section 4.4.5, strategic alignment in Sub-Section 4.4.6, strategic sensitivity in Sub-Section 4.4.7, communicating priorities in Sub-Section 4.4.8 and continuous learning in Sub-Section 4.4.9. The emerging themes have further been discussed under three management disciplines such as risk, strategic and performance to achieve the alignment of organizational objectives with the agile transformation goals and sustainability elements.

5.4.1 AGILE MINDSET

In Chapter 2, Section 2.6, literature gap such as the silo sustainability management mentality and maturity practices, weak understanding of how-to custom defines sustainability for Indian IT startups, failure to foresee risks, not embedding sustainability into the startup management and lack of understanding of key sustainability factors were identified.

From Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.4.1. We can see that the findings from data collected show that agile mindset helps in creating innovative environment and shifts focus on customer satisfaction which can enhance sustainability. Dweck (2006) and Broza (2015), indirectly point out the difference between fixed and growth mindset psychology relating agile mindset to creativity and innovation. The findings support the literature from Burnette *et al* (2013), where agile mindset can accommodate failures, believing in the possibility of continuous development and perceiving failures as lesson rather than diagnosis.

Another key finding from the data analysis in Sub-Section 4.4.1 is the perceived misunderstandings of agile and the basic understanding of the need for agile in startups. Heidemeyer (2020), argues that agile transformation allows managers and team members to embrace challenges, deal with obstacles and learn together through feedback to be successful rather being competent and threatening. Gannod *et al* (2018), Miler and Gaida (2020) and Heidemeyer (2020), propose elements of agile mindset and competences for agile teams and evaluate the importance of agile mindset from 52 agile practitioners and evaluate 26 elements for its effectiveness. Startup founders and managers need to identify which of these elements of agile mindset can best provide effective solutions for their startup sustainability.

Table 5. 2 Difference between fixed mindset and Agile mindset

FACTORS	FIXED MINDSET	AGILE MINDSET	LITERATURE
BELIEFS	Creativity and intelligence is static	Creativity and intelligence is dynamic	Dweck (2006) Broza (2015) Burnette et al (2013) Gannod (2019) Miler and Gaida (2020) Heidemeyer (2020)
CHALLENGES	Avoids	Embrace	
OBSTACLES	Gives up	Deals with	
EFFORTS	Not seen as value-addition	Seen as necessary for value-addition	
FEEDBACK	Considered as deadline	Considered as learning outcome	
SUCCESS OF OTHERS	Felt threatened	Inspired	
GOALS	Real limit missing out on potential	Reaching more than their capabilities and potential	

Table 5.2 brings out the differences between fixed mindset and agile mindset, where fixed mindset can be associated with traditional mindset and methods that have failed to be dynamic in terms of learning and growth, being threatened by success of other (Broza, 2015; Miler and Gaida, 2020).

5.4.2 AGILE CULTURE

In Chapter 2, Section 2.6, literature gaps such as the resistance culture, closed and distrust within employees leading to unproductive culture. From Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.4.2, there has been a lack of agile culture and high resistance amidst management and employees to transform. These findings have been backed up by evidence from previous literature where culture, although ambiguous and vague, plays a significant role in differentiating a company's beliefs, assumptions and values from others (Tolfo *et al*, 2011). Gelmis *et al* (2022), recently conducted as research to study the impact of Turkish national culture on agile software development in Turkey, which points out that countries like India and China suffer cultural risks such as hierarchical power distance, improper communication, formalization level, poor leadership styles, poor decision making, interaction manners and business motivation. Moreover, Gelmis *et al* (2022), argues that cultural transformation plays a key role in agile transformation, bringing success to companies by promoting employee performance and retention which has been the repeated pattern observed from the findings in Sub-Section 4.4.2. Dennison (1990), Johnson (1999) and Schein (1999), have been early contributors to the literature of culture and its levels, seeking to achieve goals throughout artifacts, espoused values and basic underlying assumption. Literatures from Lindvall *et al* (2002), Cockburn (2006) and Derby (2006), support the findings that agile culture needs to incorporate principles, manifestos and beliefs into the organizational culture, emphasizing flexibility.

Rosenberg (2015), within the context of Israel, brings out significance of organization culture aspect of an agile transformation rather than just learning and implementing new methods and practices. Findings from this research showed that management and team lacked this psychological transformation which can enhance the performance with innovation rather than fear of survival. Although many IT startups in India have understood the benefits of agile transformation, they have failed to operate cultural change as compared to agile tools and practices which they worship predominantly (Hussman and Putman, 2004; Rosenberg, 2015). Findings in Sub-Section 4.4.2 show that agile daily standup which allows team to express their values and opinions, have only been paid lip service and merely considered as team attendance imposing an immediate need to quantize and measure the intangible cultural transformation. Indian IT startups yet to implement agile or who have already implemented agile need to begin or refocus agile transformation to frame agile as cultural transformation rather than technical transformation. Survey from Gupta *et al* (2019) and Bastiaansen and Wilderom (2021), focuses on the correlation of IT department culture and agile practices to quantify cultural improvement which can identify behavioral engagement, team retention, peer accountability, positive responsiveness, etc., towards startup sustainability.

5.4.3 STAKEHOLDER PARTICIPATION

In Chapter 2, Section 2.6, literature gaps such as lack of involvement from senior management levels to identify, plan and effectively capitalize customer collaboration and employee engagement, lead to the question of how stakeholder participation can impact the success of agile transformation. Findings from Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.4.3 showed that increased stakeholder participation can improve brand loyalty, increase marketing and perception about the startup and customer collaboration contributes towards customer retention and a higher satisfaction rate. Previous literature has researched the relationship between stakeholder participation and agile transformation. Recently, Abirami *et al* (2021), surveyed 292 agile projects to cross examine the impact of stakeholder participation on achieving agility. Conforto *et al* (2014), claims that critical agile practices such as the collaboration of teams and customers promoting shared responsibility has higher impact on project sustainability which in turn can impact sustainability. Uludag *et al* (2019), although in the context of retail, has explored that stakeholder participation achieves increased commitment, builds long-term relationship, customer involves and change tolerance in co-located smaller teams, which can apply to the sustainability of Indian IT startups.

In Sub-Section 2.5.2, we have seen that one of the key manifestos of agile is to prioritize customer interaction to get quicker feedback, something that has been lacking in traditional methods. Findings in Section 4.4.3 show that more than 60% of agile teams with varied expertise, experiences, skills and domain knowledge collaborative with clients who have requirements for a software to be built, can help faster innovation and higher adaptability to change.

Figure 5. 2 Impacts of team characteristics and client collaboration on Agility

Source: Abirami *et al* (2021)

Narayanan *et al* (2015), Tam *et al* (2020) and Abirami *et al* (2021), are few of the recent research that argue the need for self-organized teams, healthy customer relationships and continuous interaction in agile transformation to be successful (See Figure 5.2). This customer collaboration has been completely limited to initial gathering of requirements and then feedback towards the end of the project in traditional methodologies as seen in Section 2.4. Findings contradict the literatures showing that although agile transformation claims to be collaborated with customers, in reality the lack of customer involvement due to skepticism and hype, distance factor, time commitment, larger customers, negotiating and ineffective customer have been challenging.

5.4.4 RISK AGILITY

In Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.5.5.3, impacts of agile transformation on risk management were reviewed through literatures and identified failure to identify potential risks to sustainability, lack of compliance governance leading to risks, failure to identify and capitalize resources available, ignorance of capability building and unproductive efforts as literature gaps in Table 2.14.

Findings from Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1, and Figure 5.1, shows that ignored customer needs and ineffective planning as risk factors unique to Indian IT startups. Interviewees were asked if and how agile can address these issues and the responses in Sub-Section 4.3.1, agile visibility and optimum resource allocation can be tools to overcome these challenges.

Figure 5. 3 Agile transformation and Risk Agility

5.4.4.1 VISIBILITY

Findings from Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.4.4, showed that agile transformation enables openness with customers, continuously interacts, welcomes change, visualizes results, tracks progress and feedbacks quickness, to improve visibility with the customers and thereby recognize customer needs early, which has been a major challenge for sustainability of Indian IT startups, See Figure 5.3. Literatures have also supported that visibility with customers can improve time to market, structures information, enhances opportunities for supervision, increases degree of customer confidence and trust with the company (Robson, 2013; Noteboom *et al*, 2021). As reviewed in Sub-Section 2.4.5 and Table 5.1, the linear traditional methods have been formal and rigid with customers, involving documentation and contract negotiations as the only means of communication. Hammad *et al* (2019) and Heikkila *et al* (2015), survey how agile transformation focuses on face-to-face communication for startups to reduce heavy documentation.

Recent research from Zieni *et al* (2021), argues that companies need to be transparent yet limited to preserve patent rights and GDPR. Sverrisdottir *et al* (2014), suggested skilled product owners for this purpose to handle multiple agile teams reasonably and effectively. Findings in Sub-Section 4.4.4 show that visibility when tolerated with vulnerability of imitation of ideas, patent regulations etc., improves quality of work and predominantly reduces project risks. Indian IT startups with lack of visibility end up building poor quality software which then delays the customers or even loses them for not delivering the product on time or delivering exactly what the customer needs. Effective feedback and communication practices can enhance their decision making and risk management (Kautz *et al*, 2017). Agile can be transparent in terms of planning work that needs to be done, reviews about the current sprint or iteration cycle and retrospective of team insights about productivity and quality (Betta and Boronina, 2018). The relationship between agile visibility and risk management can be established through the fact that customers who know more about the process and output, the quality and value are determinable which ends up with customers trusting the company with future projects and building long term relationships.

5.4.4.2 RESOURCE ALLOCATION

According to Stettina and Hörz (2015), resource allocation refers to the process of assigning and managing the available assets including both tangible software, technology and engineering practices and intangible assets such as human capital. In Chapter 2, Section 2.6, the failure to identify and capitalize resource available was raised as a literature gap and on analyzing data in Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.4.5, findings show that Indian IT startups with respect to human allocation have suffered internal politics, favoritism, etc., which have all the more failed to determine tasks that need to be assigned to each team member has led to individuals burning out as their capabilities could not be maximized. According to Alami (2016) and Albarqi and Qureshi (2018), ineffective resource allocation has led to inadequate planning posing serious threat to risk management in startups. Roque *et al* (2016) argues that uncertainty can largely affect resource allocation process and can further impose significant risks where the company ends up using deteriorated models in asset management. Optimum resource allocation can only be achieved through identification of resource's relevance and usefulness for the specific project and resource building factors like priority, integration of tasks, time and space complexities foster the enhancement of project planning (Guan *et al*, 2019).

As detailed in Sub-Section 2.5.3, in agile transformation, the final product gets broken down into smaller MVPs that get released in an incremental and iterative way following a series of cycles (Hussain *et al*, 2009; Rodriguez *et al*, 2009; Hoda and Murugesan, 2016; Dikert *et al*, 2016). Resource allocation gets done in every sprint cycle where the features are selected, and the software gets implemented. Incremental releases that provide working software for the customers in every sprint cycle have had adverse effects with the productivity of developers and the tasks that have been similar. Optimum resource allocation can help effectively realize the releases' tasks and follow the plan and help Indian startups achieve risk agility.

5.4.5 STRATEGIC AGILITY

In Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.5.5.1, the impacts of agile transformation on sustainability of startups in terms of strategic management had been scrutinized from literatures such as Rand and Eckfeldt (2004), Hock *et al* (2016), Daneva *et al* (2013) and Kaufmann *et al* (2020), to propose that agile transformation provides strategic alignment of vision and mission. Findings from Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1 and Figure 5.1, shows strategic misalignment and unproductivity as strategic factors unique to Indian IT startups. Therefore, to address these issues, interviewees were asked if and how agile can address these issues and the responses in Section 4.4, agile strategic alignment and strategic sensitivity can be tools to overcome these challenges as shown in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5. 4 Agile transformation and Strategic Agility

5.4.5.1 STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT

The significance of strategic alignment of the internal project objectives with the broader strategic objectives of the company has been recognized for years including micro and macro-economics, corporate and project and personnel levels and dimension such as social and intellectual to provide a disciplined way of thought process and team working (Reich and Benbasat, 2000; Chan and Chang, 2002; Hales and Gooch, 2004). As highlighted in Section 2.6, strategic misalignment with management discipline has been a key literature gap identified in this research. Findings in Sections 4.3 and 4.4.6 have shown that most IT startups in India struggle to align operational initiatives with strategic objectives of the company, which has led to poor resource allocation, structure and complete disaster of strategic, structural, tactical and operational levels. Recent research from Nguyen (2021), studied the significance of agile transformation for strategic alignment in FinTech startups to improve project success rates and increase customer satisfaction. Petit and Marnewick (2021), another recent researcher in agile literature supports this with a relationship model between customers and startups by shaping strategic goals and objectives to align with departmental goals. According to Chikhale and Mansouri (2015), a collaborative agile framework can enhance strategic alignment and ensure overall governance. According to Crick and Chew (2017), most startups suffer from the artificial gap that has been created between strategies in paper and reality, making processes rigid and static. Therefore, startups in India need to prepare teams to act appropriately during challenges and the phases unexpected, which requires strategies to be clear to everyone and also relevant to day-to-day work of agile practices. As detailed in Sub-Section 2.5.4, Table 2.9, traditional methods have failed to create this strategic alignment and close this strategy-practice gap due to the need for well-defined top-down process for setting objectives, sophisticated rules to calculate status with customers and architect a KPI that took hours to be built (Balaji and Sundararajan, 2012; Tayloer *et al*, 2008; Gregory *et al*, 2015). Agile transformation can integrate the actual process of business, enrich two-way collaboration and tighten the relationship between financial decisions and operational decisions.

5.4.5.2 STRATEGIC SENSITIVITY

Doz (2020), proposed the significant relationship between strategic agility and strategic sensitivity that results from the behaviors and skills of the leaders and managers to implement strategic actions and directions, and take strategic decisions which supports the findings from Sub-Section 4.4.7.

Strategic sensitivity requires both sharpness of perception and the ability to evolve and identify strategic situations that can possibly occur in the future, providing the basis for strategic sense making (Brannen, 2004; Bower, 2007; Thomas, 2016). Findings from Sub-Section 4.4.1 showed that agile mindset enables strategic sensitivity as it increases mindful awareness of the futuristic challenges and the willingness to develop intellectual boundaries for the growth of the startup. As highlighted in literature gaps Section 2.6, unproductive work environment has been a challenge for most startups in India. According to Doz (2020), dedicating time, being intellectually curious, engaging in innovative practices, cultivating contextual awareness and completely eliminating the need to reach quick judgements, ensures strategic sensitivity (See Figure 5.5).

Figure 5. 5 Enablers of Strategic Sensitivity

Source: Yves Doz (2020)

Findings from Chapter 4, Section 4.3 showed how agile has been misunderstood for SCRUM or SPRINT techniques which don't hold the central weight of the agile transformation approach. In support with this, Melo and Kon (2011), Vidgen *et al* (2017) and Badampudi *et al* (2013), in agile conferences proposed that team interaction, team dialogic process, handling conflicting ideas, freedom to blow whistle, question management and process, etc., hold higher impact on the success of agile transformation. Moreover, literature that supports team motivation towards motivating the team to ask questions and admit faults, provides room for exploring wild ideas and most importantly allowing them to challenge the status quo or existing practices.

According to Unterkalmsteiner *et al* (2016), an Indian IT startup can stop being agile if this very factor gets neglected. Larger companies have been trapped by the politics of personal biases in terms of candidate hiring, individual appraisals and rewards, where the vulnerability gets punished, and the team feels discouraged and silenced to an extent where the trust eventually breaks.

5.4.6 PERFORMANCE AGILITY

In Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.5.5.2, literature showed that agile transformation improves performance management (Stare, 2014; Moran, 2015; Santos *et al*, 2013; Dohe and Pike, 2018). The literature further showed how traditional methodologies failed to accommodate changes which kept the performance static (Fagerholm *et al*, 2015; Cappelli and Tavis, 2016; Winter, 2015; Malik *et al*, 2021). Findings from Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1 and Figure 5.1, shows poor deliverable quality and team inefficiency as two primary risks costing Indian IT startups their sustainability. Therefore, to address these issues, interviewees were asked if and how agile can address these issues and the responses in Chapter 4, Section 4.4, where agile communication of priorities and continuous learning were suggested as tools to overcome these challenges and the same has been represented in Figure 5.6 and its associated agile practices.

Figure 5. 6 Agile transformation and Operational Agility

5.4.6.1 COMMUNICATING PRIORITIES

According to Aalst *et al* (2003) and Daneva *et al* (2013), workflow includes the sequence of tasks from a software at its birth stage to its development, that needs to be completed sequentially or in parallel to achieve the collective business outcome, also detailed in Chapter 2 Sub-Section 2.3.2. As highlighted in literature gaps Section 2.6, lack of agility in workflow, overlooking change of priorities with changing customer requirements and agile-scrum driven biases have challenged the sustainability of Indian IT startups (Immelt, 2017; Ahimbisibwe *et al*, 2015; Denning, 2019). Findings from interviews and focus groups on Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.4.8 showed that poor communication of highest priorities with peers and customers has affected cost, value proposition, skill management of IT startups in India. In support with this, literatures show how release priorities and backlogs in agile transformation can actively monitor priorities to eliminate waste, also keeping in mind the need to avoid neglect of lower priorities as it can also impact the quality of the final product (Mikulenias and Kapocius, 2011; Sachdeva, 2017). Mougouei *et al* (2015), proposed a model for prioritizing factors and to quantify them to be fuzzed, linking cost, risk and impact as prioritization factors to prioritize a certain task and select it for implementation during each release sprint. Recent research from Loiro *et al* (2019), supports the findings by showing how communication of priorities hold equal weightage to identifying priorities while reducing the number of neglected requirements to meet time and budget constraints and achieve strategic goals. Common communication challenges that Indian IT startups need to be aware of are the miscommunication, poorly organized interactions, inadequate documentation, tolerance of changing requirements, inability to foster co-location due to pandemic, lack of commitment from the team, etc. as in Sub-Section 4.3.1 (Balaji *et al*, 2015; Vaishnavi *et al*, 2014). Scheduling daily or weekly meetings, usage of burn down charts, sprint backlogs, task boards or KANBAN boards and prioritizing sprint reviews at the end of releases can be best agile practices that can enable effective communication of priorities within Indian IT startups.

5.4.6.2 CONTINUOUS LEARNING

Remaining competitive as a company requires constant improvement of skill sets and removal of the need to complete skills. One of the key reasons for companies to adopt agile is to welcome change and if the team isn't equipped enough to tackle those scenarios, the efficiency becomes questionable, moreover the survivability and existence (Avolio *et al*, 2009; Babb *et al*, 2014).

As detailed in Section 2.6, Table 2.14, inadequate cross-functional skill set, lack of continuous learning and innovation, lack of continuous learning from every project to develop unique and profitable business model as critical literature gaps (Anseel, 2017; Asghar *et al*, 2017; Jain *et al*, 2018; Noguera *et al*, 2018). Findings in Sub-Section 4.4.9 shows how with traditional economies being overtaken by digital economies, Indian IT startups have struggled immensely to shift from static, formulaic and process-driven learning and development strategies which have become outdated and clearly unsuccessful for creating high quality and highly skilled teams. In support with this, research from Armanious and Padgett (2021), proposes five integrated elements of agile learning strategies that include agile leadership styles, changing the culture to embrace learning, knowledge capturing and sharing and focus on emerging or futuristic trends in engineering practices and developments. Another recent research from Annosi *et al* (2020), recognizes the serious lack of agile companies to research and learn self-management and team-based approaches at key levels of the company, as shown in Figure 5.7.

Figure 5. 7 Organizational learning constructs with levels of management

Source: Annosi *et al* (2020)

In any agile company, the individuals and the company itself should evolve and develop through continuous learning by receiving feedback and being exposed to development opportunities (Schatz and Abdelshafi, 2005; Rerup and Feldman, 2011). This characteristic of feedback that was predominantly overlooked by traditional methods in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.4.5, Table 2.7 has been the heartbeat of agile teams and its culture were taking risks, failing fast and pursuing continuous development have had certain impacts. Findings from Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.4.9 shows how IT Startups in India have failed to encourage employees to ask for and give feedback about the process which all the more has been more inclined towards the traditional approach. The inability to continuously learn can be considered as a mindset lack or capability barrier where the feedback has been formal in terms of reporting, documentations and retrospect whereas in true agile companies, feedback doesn't necessarily have to follow a hierarchy (Annosi and Brunetta, 2017). According to Dean and Marc (2020) and Renzi *et al* (2021), this creates the need for disciplined rituals or strategic activities that can effectively gather feedback and evaluate performance. Also, findings show how line managers in traditional methods have failed to allow team members to actively share feedback, status of development, employee information, etc., through hierarchical barriers at every stage of the process. IT startups in India needs to be aware of challenges in individual appraisals where agile requires individuals to work in a team, adopting best practices to differentiation between individual performances based on the individual's contribution towards desired behavioral values and willingness to continuously learn.

5.5 VALIDATION OF THE AGILE STARTUP SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

The main aim of this section is to embed empirical research findings into the theoretical agile startup sustainability framework developed at the end of Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.7.6. The researcher performed semi-structured interviews and focus groups and finally used thematic analysis to verify the various themes adopted in the framework. This section, alongside findings and literature, provides practical guidelines to provide validation for the framework.

The framework presented in Chapter 2, Figure 2.22 was derived from key findings from both academic and industrial literatures with the primary aim of addressing literature gaps presented in section 2.6, Table, that provides rationale for strategic alignment of management disciplines with agile transformation. Therefore, the research first identified sustainability factors affecting risk, strategic and performance management and linked it to the agile transformation in Section 2.5.

The empirical evidence provided in Chapter 4, validated the importance of aligning these factors and also suggested agile elements to target sustainability of Indian IT startups. The last step is to provide implementation guidelines for agile practitioners, startup founders and managers. The framework presented in Section 2.7, Figure 2.22, was developed around four pillars namely the agile pre-requisites, agile transformation, startup foundation and external sustainability. The agile pre-requisites included the agile mindset, agile culture and stakeholder participation. Agile transformation includes agile practices, process, values and principles. The management disciplines included risk, strategy and performance management where agility in each discipline was the ultimate goal.

Figure 5. 8 Agile Startups Sustainability Framework

Having outlined the four key pillars of agile startup sustainability framework, the researcher investigated the sample population to validate these pillars and add more input to the final framework. Figure 5.8 shows the agile startup sustainability framework with some emerged findings from Chapter 4, Section 4.4. added on to the framework in Chapter 2, Figure 2.22. It also depicts the addition of specific agile elements such as visibility, resource allocation, strategic alignment, strategic sensitivity, communication of priorities and continuous learning. Another addition has been drawn into the pillar of agile pre-requisites, namely the agile mindset, agile culture and stakeholder participation. All the significant changes to the theoretical framework are highlighted in red. Number 1-6 refer to the implementation guidance steps in Section 5.6.

Comparing Figure 2.22 and Figure 5.8, shows how risk, strategy and management pillar have included findings from Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1, where the key sustainability factors that are unique and relevant to Indian IT startups have been identified. The risk agility section is shown to have included two key components, namely the high visibility and optimum resource allocation which has been discussed in Sub-Sections 5.4.4.1 and 5.4.4.2. The inclusion of these components targets agile practices towards two major risks namely the ignored customer needs and ineffective planning, as shown in Figure 5.1, to increase the risk agility of Indian IT startups to be sustainable.

Another change to the strategic management discipline is the inclusion of two new components, namely strategic alignment and strategic sensitivity. Findings from Sub-Section 4.4.6 and 4.4.7, and discussion in Chapter 5, Sub-Section 5.4.5.1 and Sub-Section 5.4.5.2, show the significance of these two components to address strategic misalignment and unproductive culture of the Indian IT startups as shown in Figure 4.1, to improve strategic agility to ensure overall sustainability.

Another change to the performance management discipline is the inclusion of two new components, namely the communication of priorities and continuous learning. Findings from Sub-Section 4.4.8 and Sub-Section 4.4.9, and discussion in Sub-Section 5.4.6.1 and Sub-Section 5.4.6.2, shows the significance of these two components to address poor deliverable quality and team inefficiency if the Indian IT startups as shown in Figure 4.1, to achieve operational agility, towards effective performance management.

Another key realignment as shown in Figure 5.8, shows the inclusion of agile mindset as discussion in Sub-Section 5.4.1, agile culture as discussed in Sub-Section 5.4.2 and stakeholder participation as discussed in Sub-Section 5.4.3. From the empirical findings it was evident that although agile transformation could effectively provide sustainability, pre-requisites such as these 3 elements shows utmost urgency and significance as pre-requisites for agile transformation to be successfully adopted within the context of Indian IT startups ensuring sustainability.

As stated in Chapters 4, responses from semi-structured interviews and focus groups shows how the responsibility and the accountability lies with the senior management, founders and entrepreneurs to identify sustainability factors unique to their startup and target agile transformation practices towards their sustainability as these cannot be universal. Having discussed and analyzed the results in Chapters 4 and 5, the research determined that the following elements should be considered throughout the implementation efforts:

- Develop agile mindset, build agile culture and increase stakeholder participation to achieve successful agile transformation;
- Target agile practices and tools towards increasing visibility and optimizing resource allocation to achieve risk agility;
- Target agile practices and tools towards aligning strategic goals with day-to-day activities and increasing productivity to achieve strategic agility;
- Target agile practices and tools towards communicating priorities and improving team efficiency to achieve operational agility;
- Agility in risk, strategic and performance management should directly impact sustainability to achieve competitive advantage and organization agility.

The factors such as agile mindset and agile culture has been constantly voiced by the interviewees as significant factors for the success of agile transformation as misunderstandings and misinterpretation of agile tools and practices have led to IT companies failing even with agile transformation. This shows how even agile transformation, adopted and implemented in the wrong way can impact sustainability in a negative manner. Managers and startup founders need to understand agile for its benefits and uniqueness to provide sustainability for their startups where collaboration with customers and employees, breakdown of hierarchies, continuous learning culture should be signified. The next section offers implementation guidance for the validated agile startup sustainability framework.

5.6 IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES FOR AGILE STARTUP SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

This section proposes guidelines for the right implementation of the agile startup sustainability framework, derived through literature and empirical investigation. Most researchers argue that situation analysis that determines current practices, standards, etc., comes prior to any transformation. Some startups can be implementing agile in a failuristic way and others may not be having any processes or other methodologies, and therefore a clear analysis of Agility check needs to be done before implementing agile startup sustainability framework. Researcher recommends the following questions be asked to startup managers and founders wishing to implement agile framework:

- What is the current process and how sustainability factors foster the need for agile practices to be embedded within a startup?
- What benefits can agile transformation adoption bring to the startup?
- How can stakeholders be influenced to support agile transformation?
- How to align agile transformation methodology with 3 pillars of risk, strategy and performance?
- How to define elements such as transparency, resource optimization, strategic alignment, strategic sensitivity, communicating priorities and continuous learning for the startup?
- How to develop an agile mindset and agile culture within the startup to support the framework?
- How to achieve sustainability and thereby competitive advantage and organizational agility through the framework?

The researcher recommends these questions as mandatory for the framework validation and the implementation guidelines. Understanding and defining the process that is unique to a startup can actually help identify the actual need for agile practices in these areas, allowing stakeholders to embed them into current processes. Startups need to be aware of the benefits of agile transformation which needs to be communicated throughout the levels of management, wherein everyone knows the strategic direction and objectives of this transformation. Considering the following steps can help foster the right implementation.

Step 1) Define the external and internal dynamism in the market environment

Step 2) Establish current processes and pain points that affect sustainability

Step 3) Educate with agile transformation for startup sustainability

- a. Agile mindset
- b. Agile culture
- c. Stakeholder participation

Step 4) Introduce change through framework in an incremental way

- d. Transparency
- e. Optimum resource allocation
- f. Strategic alignment
- g. Strategic sensitivity
- h. Communicating priorities
- i. Continuous learning

Step 5) Monitor outputs through well-defined and customized KSIs

- j. Competitive advantage
- k. Organizational agility

Step 6) Feedback and retrospect learning outcomes into the framework

As these above steps are followed through the implementation the following action plan as shown in Figure 5.9, can be considered at the end of every stage:

Figure 5. 9 Action Plan

5.6.1 DEFINE

IT startups in India operate in a competitive and highly dynamic ecosystem, exposed to internal and external dynamics. The researcher recommends that defining external sustainability factors such as ignored customer needs, poor quality deliverables and strategic misalignment and internal factors such as ineffective resource allocation, unproductive culture and team inefficiency must be the initial step for startup founders and managers. Startups in India involve macro and micro levels of changes and not identifying these dynamics can result in management losing control over performance, strategic ability and risk mitigation. Tools like PESTEL and SWOT can be used by senior management to identify such external factors. Managers and the team collaboratively need to be involved in identifying internal dynamics and the expected tools and technologies that can satisfy customer expectations and behaviors. Projects can be unique in terms of the required resources, skills, management abilities and team efficiency. These can lead to clear setting of strategic objectives and strategic goals in alignment with external and internal dynamics.

5.6.2 ESTABLISH

Having established the strategic objectives and goals to be achieved, the researcher recommends managers and founders to work towards establishing current practices and pain points with the way the startup works. Identifying available resources, current strategies and tools adapted, current nature of the projects handled, current practices for client management, current practices for learning and feedback and listing out the lags and deficiencies is the integral step towards reaching those goals listed in the previous step. Geyi *et al* (2020) and Dean and Marc (2020), have been influential with the literature of agile practices and sustainability, proposing the need to establish current practices to achieve sustainability.

Table 5. 3 Tools to define and establish sustainability factors and current practices

TOOLS	EXAMPLES
IDENTIFICATION OF SUSTAINABILITY FACTORS	Brainstorming Interviews and surveys PESTEL & SWOT Analysis Porter's Five Forces 5C Analysis VRIO Analysis
CHECKLIST FOR SUSTAINABILITY FACTOR IDENTIFICATION	Risk Factors Strategic Factors Performance Factors Financial Factors
ESTABLISH CURRENT PRACTICES AND STRATEGIES	SWOT Analysis Flow diagrams and Process Naos Agile Fluency Model Stakeholder Analysis Culture Mapping
BUSINESS IMPROVEMENT	Gap Analysis Root cause analysis Plan-Do-Study-Act Force Field Analysis Just In Time and Sig Sigma
CHANGE MANAGEMENT	Kotter's 8 step Change Model Lewin's Change model McKinsey 7S Model Kubler-Ross Change Framework ADKAR Analysis

Table 5.3 combines the tools for startups founders and managers to identify sustainability factors, checklist for categorizing factors under the management disciplines of financial and non-financial factors, tools to establish current practices and strategies, business improvement tools to find gaps between expected results and current achievements and finally change management models to understand the need for change and requirements.

5.6.3 EDUCATE

The researcher then recommends startups to educate the need for agile transformation and inculcate three major elements such as the agile mindset, agile culture and stakeholder participation of agile prior to introducing agile tools and practices for improvement and growth. IT startups in India have been facing this crisis where the copy culture of western practices have led to new practices and tools being incorporated without understanding the need for it. IT startups in India need to accept the fact that agile can also not work on the following scenarios:

1. Implementing agile without believing in its core value and principles can all the more degrade performance of startups implementing agile practices.
2. Startups implementing mini-waterfall or existing transformational practices and techniques within agile transformation approach cannot provide the ultimate benefit of agile.
3. When the requirements are clearly stated and not subject to change over a span of weeks or months, the probability of dynamic changes seems minimal. Therefore, startups trying to overwork themselves with agile principles and sprint tools can only burden and burn out the team rather aiding them towards sustainability.
4. Startups with clearly mentioned requirements and adequate amount of expertise can implement traditional transformation methodologies and still be sustainable yet given the lack of pool of skilled workforce, this has been a challenge for startups (Geyi *et al*, 2020).
5. When customers are unwilling to participate or collaborate with startups to know the outcome or value on every step of the process, satisfying them becomes a challenge and priority for most Indian IT startups affecting work culture and process methods.
6. Projects without noticeable complexities, urgency and uniqueness where nothing new gets built or has a minimum innovation index.
7. Teams which have not prioritized self-organization cannot implement agile transformation given the high dependency of hierarchy and management.
8. When startups do not invest in cross-functionality where individuals work as a team to complement each other with adequate investment of money and time on research and development of good engineering practices.

The above scenarios need to be considered for effectiveness and suitability of agile transformation for the sustainability of Indian IT startups. Moreover, communication of gaps between expected and achieved results within all management levels needs to be implemented.

5.6.4 INTRODUCE

Only after educating agile at all levels of management and team does the research recommends introducing best agile practices to achieve the intended agile elements and goals. There are multiple agile practices and agile methods to select from such as SCRUM, KANBAN, DEVOPS, CRYSTAL, XP, etc., yet targeting agile practices from hybrid models can achieve sustainability for the startups in India. The list of best practices has been tabulated below in Table 5.4.

Table 5. 4 Best Agile practices to achieve Agile elements

AGILE ELEMENTS	AGILE PRACTICES
HIGH VISIBILITY	Iterative development KANBAN board Sprint demo meetings
OPTIMUM RESOURCE ALLOCATION	Scrum meetings Daily standups Value Stream Analysis Planning Poker or Scrum Poker
STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT	Agile role clarity Test driven development Clear communication rules
STRATEGIC SENSITIVITY	Time boxing Release planning Agile workspace
COMMUNICATION OF PRIORITIES	Product and Sprint backlog User stories Requirement prioritization Quick rebuilding and reformatting
CONTINUOUS LEARNING	Feedback Retrospect Review meetings Learning and development

Signoretta *et al* (2019), Oliva and Kotabe (2019), Dean and Marc (2020), Diego *et al* (2020) and Geyi *et al* (2020), are few of the researchers who have developed frameworks in the quadrant relating agile transformation and sustainability in Chapter 2, Table 2.14. Any agile framework, practice and tools are subject to the implementation methods and therefore managers need to select appropriate practices from Table 5.4, instead of copying from western cultures. Moreover, the practices adopted must directly address the sustainability factors identified in the first step, if not the practices have not been effectively implemented. According to recent literature, agile transformation must never be prescribed but encouraged within the team, introducing iteration in every startup process, bridging the gaps found in step 3, synchronized but never be caught up with agile ceremonies. Following agile practices with rigidity can result in another traditional method.

5.6.5 MONITOR

One of the key findings from this research is the failure of even larger IT MNCs in India to stay truly agile and many reasons have been accounted. One of the primary reasons for agile methods not delivering their best ability is the failure of startup founders and managers to monitor results and track when changes become integrated. Evaluating the quality of results helps to forecast future needs, risks, strategic objectives and skill requirements. Managers and founders on implementing the tools and practices mentioned in the previous section should then monitor the results for achieving competitive advantage and organizational agility, the two integral contributions of sustainability in IT startups.

Table 5. 5 List of software for Agile monitoring

LIST OF SOFTWARE TO MONITOR AGILE			
Proof Hub	Agilean	JIRA	Kantree
Wrike	Version One	Axosoft	Notion
Smartsheet	Binfire	Pivotal tracker	Hitask
Active Collab	LeankitKanban	MeisterTask	Basecamp
Asana	DailyScrum	Taiga	

As tabulated in Table 5.5, startup managers can also software developed methods of agile monitoring which automatically tracks progress, visually represents results and sprint demos. One of the most used software tools is the JIRA which tracks bugs, improves project management, sets priorities, captures and assigns tasks helping startups achieve long-term goals.

5.6.6 FEEDBACK

One of the strengths of adopting agile transformation is the feedback mechanism of taking lessons, failures, challenges and obstacles from current project into new projects, whereby following steps 1 to 5 again. The failure to feedback the results of each intended agile element can make startups settle for short term wins and lose long-term objectives and goals. Moreover, the hierarchical barriers highlighted through research findings need to be constructively developed to effectively input feedback from all levels of management and not just from the top to bottom. Continuous development of startup processes and personal growth can be impacted through feedback of thoughts, views and opinions, communicated between the managers and employees. Researcher recommends that startup managers and founders continuously follow steps 1-6 to continually define external and internal factors to align agile tools for sustainability.

5.7 STRENGTHS OF THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

As detailed in Chapter 2 and earlier sections, the complex and dynamic nature of startup sustainability has challenged researchers to develop a framework that captures relevant agile elements that prove critical to startup sustainability in India (Mensah and Enu-Kwesi, 2018; Victor, 2019; Vinit and Joakim, 2019). The hypotheses generated in the end of Chapter 4 and the discussion in Chapter 5 highlight the changes needed to the current agile frameworks to achieve the integral aim of this research. The proposed framework intended as an implementation tool for IT startups aims to improve understanding of sustainability factors, agile transformation elements and their targeted benefits to improve competitive advantage and organizational agility. The strengths of this framework are as follows:

1. Linking academic and industrial literature

One of the key research problems identified was the lack of conceptualization and categorization of sustainability within the context of Indian IT startups. The framework successfully defines sustainability for Indian IT startups in the context of choosing the right transformation method that influences risk agility, strategic agility and operational agility, which previous researchers have overlooked (Bolis *et al*, 2014; Thomas, 2015; Yang, 2019). The factors affecting sustainability were identified both from academic and industry-based literatures and were compared and discussed with the empirical findings of research participants (Santisteban and David, 2017; Marcio, 2018; IBEF, 2019; Statista, 2019). The six factors included in the framework reflects the specific factors that affect the sustainability of Indian IT startups from the startup managers, entrepreneurs and founders' perspective. The proposed framework combines both literature themes adopted in Chapter 2 and empirical findings in Chapter 4 to provide startups the credibility and confidence to use this framework at management levels.

2. Addressing major sustainability issues in Indian IT startups

As highlighted in Chapter 1 and Chapter 2, the factors that affect sustainability depend on the context of industry and demography at which it is applied (Ejermo and Xiao, 2014; Hyder and Lussier, 2016). The major sustainability issues with respect to Indian IT startups have been identified both in literatures in Chapter 2, Section 2.2, Sub-Section 2.2.3 and in the findings in Chapter 4, Section 4.3, Sub-Section 4.3.1, Figure 4.1., and finally drawn in Chapter 5, Section 5.2, Figure 5.1 as ignored customer needs,

ineffective planning, strategic misalignment, unproductive culture, poor deliverables and quality, and team inefficiency. Agile transformation has been directed and targeted to addressing each individual sustainability factor to further ensure risk, strategy and performance agility, through specific agile elements such as visibility, resource allocation, strategic alignment, sensitivity, communicating priorities and continuous learning, and finally contribute towards the sustainability of Indian IT startups.

3. Customizable to the specific startup

The sustainability challenges are subject to change, given the uncertainties, instability and rapid innovation in the Indian IT startup landscape and therefore, there is an evident risk that factors targeted in the developed framework may get outdated (Santisteban and Mauricio, 2017; Niazi *et al*, 2016; Oliva and Kotabe, 2019). Unlike current frameworks from El-Khalil and Mezher (2020), Geyi *et al* (2020), Dean and Marc (2020) and Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020), the agile startup sustainability framework in Figure 5.8 provides room for more sustainability factors to be included and customized according to specific startup as depicted in Chapter 5, Section 5.6, Sub-Section 5.6.2, where the sustainability factors are advised to be established and defined prior to agile transformation. Therefore, this framework evolves dynamically to the changes in the sustainability factors.

4. Aligned with key management disciplines

One of the major literature gaps as highlighted in Chapter 2, Section 2.6 is the unclear conceptualization of sustainability and misalignment of transformation methods with overall sustainability of the startups, which has also been pointed out in the beginning of this research in Chapter 1, Section 1.4 (Subbarao and Rani, 2015; Lonkar and Gupte, 2017). This has been addressed in this research in Chapter 2, Section 2.2, where project sustainability has been linked to overall holistic sustainability of the Indian IT startups by ensuring risk, strategy and performance agility (Santiago and Emre, 2017; Yang, 2019; Denning, 2019). While critical management disciplines such as risk, strategy and performance have been established as key pillars for Indian IT startups, the agile startup sustainability framework in Chapter 5, Figure 5.8, effectively links project and overall sustainability.

5. Expanded scope of agile transformation

The benefits of agile transformation have been established in numerous instances throughout this research, Chapter 2, Section 2.5 and Chapter 4, Section 4.3. Flexibility, adaptability, customer-centricity, early and continuous delivery, faster time to market, iterative improvement, adaptive planning, enhanced communication and collaboration, improved customer and employee engagement levels, embracing change, etc., have been confined to the scope of effective project management (Paternoster, 2014; Ghani *et al*, 2015; Kamei *et al*, 2017; Alsahli *et al*, 2017). Despite this, agile transformation that does not consider transformation at macro-level in these disciplines can only end up as mere project management tool (Geyi *et al*, 2020). The developed agile startup sustainability framework expands the scope of agile transformation from just ensuring project success to now influencing the holistic sustainability of Indian IT startups.

6. Recognizing intangible factors limiting sustainability

Chapter 2, Section 2.7, Sub-Section 2.7.3 and Chapter 4, Section 4.4, highlighted emerged themes that needed attention while considering implementational challenges of agile transformation frameworks. Intangible factors such as agile mindset, agile culture and stakeholder participation have not been included as part of the transformation criteria in previous literatures and current agile frameworks (Miler and Gaida, 2020; Abirami *et al*, 2021; Gelmis *et al*, 2022). The developed framework includes these factors into consideration while implementing agile transformation which can largely impact Indian IT startup sustainability.

The formulation of the agile startup sustainability framework injects a robust vitality into startup sustainability practices, fostering a dynamic synergy between agile methodologies and sustainable practices. This research asserts that the conceptual model introduced holds the transformative potential to harmonize agile practices and tools, steering them toward the ultimate goal of achieving holistic sustainability. The envisioned outcome is a substantial enhancement in the agility of startups concerning risk management, strategic initiatives, and overall performance. By striving for these improvements, startups can secure a competitive advantage and improve their organizational agility, propelling them towards a more resilient and enduring position in the dynamic business landscape.

5.8 LIMITATIONS OF THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The use of only three elements of business sustainability, which is the risk, strategy and performance, can be a limiting factor for this framework as sustainability of a business involves much more than these three elements. Based on the Indian IT startup context, these three elements can be sufficient yet be subjective to additional elements of concern. Nevertheless, future researchers and practitioners can add on to the values and benefits that this proposed framework intends to provide. The generalizability of this framework for IT startups across different regions within India can be challenging as India in itself is a multi-cultured country that houses different management disciplines and practices. Although the researcher has gained extensive knowledge about the agile transformation and sustainability literature, practical inexperience and unawareness of actual processes and technicalities can limit the researcher to deepen and confidently validate the solution provided.

5.9 CHAPTER CONCLUSION

This chapter discussed both the adopted themes and the emerged themes from the findings in the previous chapter with the work of various authors in the field. Many researchers have gained more interest in this field, and many have contributed towards the agile transformation literature, yet the current information obtained from this discussion has been clearly stated and mentioned within the respective sections. Further the proposed framework in chapter 2 was altered and validated with findings to include emerged themes and fill literature and framework gaps. The step-by-step implementation guidance, strengths and limitations of the framework was also discussed.

According to Cho (2008) and Measey (2015), agility is the ability to welcome and adapt to change which means it applies for management disciplines within the organization. As per Geyi *et al* (2020), agile transformation does not only impact project sustainability but also startup sustainability by effectively improving practices and goals. In the case of IT startups in India, the data analysis concluded that establishing the agile mindset, agile culture and stakeholder participation plays a key role in the success of agile transformation. Alongside these pre-requisites, targeting agile practices and tools to achieve sustainability has been emphasized through the framework in Figure 5.8. Although there are 12 principles of agile and multiple benefits, none of the current frameworks were targeted for the sustainability of Indian IT startups and therefore the following points briefly explains the emerged findings from the research:

- Having the agile mindset, developing the right culture and ensuring complete stakeholder participation are considered as vital factors for the Indian IT startups since the entrepreneurs, founders and managers have a vague understanding of agile and blindly follow its practices from books. The results tend to emerge from a focus group of agile coaches, project managers and senior consultants who have worked for years in the industry and believe this lack to be the cause of early failures and exit rates;
- The role of agile transformation in bringing sustainability within the key management disciplines also plays a significant role in ensuring sustainability of the startup. Analyzing three prime disciplines such as risk, strategy and performance management can open opportunities to bring processes targeted to increase growth and ensure sustainability;
- Considering the research findings through semi-structured interviews and focus groups, risk management in Indian IT startups can be targeted for high visibility and optimum resource allocation to achieve sustainability within the startup. Strategic misalignment found out to be one of the key issues for failures of Indian IT startups can focus on getting agile practices aligned with the vision and mission of the startup and to achieve this, the workforce needs to be motivated and appraised. Communicating priorities and continuously learning from every project can improve performance of the startups to achieve sustainability;
- Considering the higher competition of IT startups in India and the increasing need for organization agility, having the right mindset, culture and stakeholder participation to steer agile transformation towards achieving transparency, optimum resource allocation, strategic alignment, strategic sensitivity, communication priorities and continuous learning can ultimately bring sustainability in startups bring value among competitors and within the startup.

Having summarized the key emerged findings, discussed and validated with literature from various researchers, the following Chapter 6 will conclude this research and explain how the aims and objectives of this research have been met and intended contributions have been, along with further recommendations for startup managers and academic researcher.

CHAPTER 6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 CONCLUSION

This Chapter considers the research contributions, validates the aims and objectives and how they've been achieved, evaluates the answers for the research questions, takes out conclusions from research findings, thereby resonating the value of this research for the sustainability of Indian IT startups and to fill the research gaps in Chapter 2, Section 2.6, Table 2.14.

On discussing the research aims, objectives and questions, this chapter will also highlight the limitations of this research thereby offering recommendations for future research drawing conclusions from research findings to contribute both academically and practically. This section concludes and summarizes key takeaways from this research. This research has highlighted the lack of in-depth academic research in the field of Indian IT startups within the context of agile transformation for sustainability where prior research has only been more generic and non-relative of agile and sustainability concepts in Chapter 2, Table 2.14.

The research has identified the unclear and vague definitions of agile transformation and its practices to be the biggest challenge for its effective implementation. Entrepreneurs, startups founders, project managers, developers and agile practitioners realize agile as difficult and good in books rather than being practical and integrating it within the existing organization process, and thereby inculcating the agile mindset and culture to support sustainable IT startups by tailoring best-fit practices and targeting agile ceremonies that add meaning and value.

The traditional mindset of the IT process as revealed in this research has been the biggest challenge for Indian IT startups to be sustainable. Chapter 2, Section 2.4 and Chapter 4, Sub-Section 4.3.2 highlights the significance of breaking these traditional software development processes, practices and functionalities to a wider perspective of startup transformation and sustainability.

This research to its best ability has identified gaps in the agile sustainability literature and has developed agile startup sustainability framework considering both tangible and intangible elements of a sustainable startup in India and recommends collaborating and evaluating both financial and non-financial factors for other industries as well. The academic and practitioner gap has also been addressed in this research where the understanding of agile transformation to drive long term sustainability has been provided in Chapters 2, Section 2.6.

This research has developed a framework considering the ever-prevalent challenges for the right implementation and adoption of agile transformation. As most research is focused on either agile as a tool and sustainability as concepts, this research has bridged two wider perspectives and has united them as the solution for sustainability of Indian IT startups. The researcher understands the dynamic and ever-changing IT needs that can highly affect the startup processes and believes that there exists a rationale for a new and relevant conceptual framework to be updated. The researcher also finds startup founders and agile practitioners to be unaware of the actual agile concepts who rather misconnect it as merely a tool that replaces traditional methodologies. This research further emphasizes agile transformation as a macro-management principle that potentially impacts strategy and optimize performance, through cost-effective processes, highly collaborative customers and motivated workforce.

Another major gap in the literature that this research revealed in Chapter 2, Section 2.6, is the lack of significance of sustainability as a major challenge in the Indian IT startup ecosystem. Data collected from interviewees revealed their unawareness of the high failure rate prevalent in the market leading to undefined processes and radical innovation which does not support the startup overall. Another vital conclusion from this research is the importance of an agile culture, mindset and all stakeholder participation which rather precedes any transformation within a startup. If the culture and the entrepreneurial mindset does not support agile transformation, even under best practices and methods, agile can fail miserably. Closed mindset and distrust within employees have also been identified in Chapter 2 as major gaps in literature and in industry.

Chapter 2, 4 and 5 also enlighten failure to identify and capitalize resources available, ignorance of capacity building, wasting time building unproductive software, lack of strategic alignment of agile processes with vision and mission, lack of continuous learning, lack of a fully dynamic and holistic sustainability framework, overlooking internal and external environment, inconsistent methods and procedures, lack of visibility within projects, lack of sustainability measures within the startup, resistance to change or rather unwillingness to learn, division between academics and practitioners adoption methods, etc., as key takeaways that startups can be aware. Thus, defining and customizing agile rather than blindly following it is a major recommendation from this research as discussed. Moreover, future researchers can further enhance this research by extending this concept to other sectors and other countries, generalizing and validating the framework.

Establishing the right mindset and culture with all stakeholders can improve the effectiveness of agile transformation methodologies bringing agility in three aspects such as risk, strategy and performance of a startup. Another key observation in this research is the need for continuous embedding of agile principles and values into the startup vision and mission to fail quick and learn fast to enhance decision making and strategic growth. These factors were further added to the theoretical framework in Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.7.6 and was finalized in Chapter 5, Section 5.5.

The interviewees for this research also posed a major threat of agile being misguided and followed from books without being customized and tailored to meet a startup's need. On analyzing data collected from agile coaches, managers and expertise through focus groups, even larger MNCs have transformed to agile without effectively communicating the change within the company, leading to merely role changes rather than change of culture and mindset. This can be taken as a major recommendation where startups need to hire agile coaches who can educate employees and managers in a more practical and relevant means that will add meaning to the startup.

Interviewees also admit the lack of clear agile implementation guidance that has led to inadequate resource allocation creating sustainability issues. Although agile as a principle has grown immensely over the years, it still seems to be at its earlier stage with startup sustainability and growth. This all the more concludes this research by recommending startups to develop an agile mindset and culture that support agile transformation both top and bottom level of management focusing more on communication of priorities, transparency, resource optimization, strategic alignment, sensitive workforce and continuous learning. This research encourages future researchers to bring out more sustainability factors such as financial and legal compliance issues and figure out if agile can address these. Increased interest in startup growth in India can not only help them sustain in the market but also impact India's economy to a greater extent.

6.2 ACHIEVING RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To show evidence of research aims being achieved, we review the aim of this research as detailed in Chapter 1, Section 1.7:

1. To investigate agile Transformation and sustainability of IT businesses
2. To develop an agile Transformation sustainability framework for Indian IT start-ups, supported with implementational guidance.

Aim 1 has been achieved through Chapter 2 and 5, where extensive critical literature review on agile transformation and sustainability of IT businesses have highlighted key factors within the Indian startup ecosystem. This paved the way for developing a conceptual framework developed by the researcher backed up with theory and empirical evidence which augments the literature gaps, thereby achieving Aim 2. In addition, Chapter 5 also provides incremental steps for the right implementation of the agile startup sustainability framework, thereby validating Aim 2.

The objectives of this research as detailed in Chapter 1, Section 1.8:

1. To identify the factors that foster sustainability in IT start-ups in India;
2. To evaluate literature on existing transformation methodologies on Indian IT start-ups;
3. To analyze Managers' perception of agile transformation and its applications within context;
4. To evaluate current agile sustainability frameworks and develop a new framework

Chapter 2 identified specific key factors related to risk, strategy and performance in Sub-Section 2.2.3, wherein Sub-Section 2.2.5 summarized those factors scrutinized under academic and industrial literature within process related sustainability factors, achieving Objective 1.

Chapter 2 linked the transformation methodologies and sustainability factors in Sub-Section 2.3.4, reviewed existing methodologies through Sections 2.4 to 2.5, to differentiate the impacts of agile transformation on Indian IT startups from the rest, thereby achieving Objective 2.

Chapter 2 highlighted implementation challenges that differentiated theory and practice of agile transformation to understand the managers' perception of agile transformation and its applications through Sub-Sections 2.5.6 and 2.6, signifying the literature gaps to be filled, thereby achieving Objective 3. Moreover, Chapter 4 and Chapter 5 validated and discussed the literature review through data collection from targeted samples and recent literature.

Chapter 2 brought out the literature gaps and Chapter 5 formulates empirical evidence that led to the evolution of the conceptual framework by carefully evaluating both the values and deficits of existing agile sustainability frameworks in practice, achieving Objective 4.

Therefore, all the aims and objectives of this research as described in Chapter 1, Section 1.7 and Section 1.8 have been achieved successfully.

6.3 ACHIEVING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This section addresses each research question in Chapter 1, Section 1.9, individually explaining how this research has achieved in answering them.

1. What are the factors that influence sustainability in Indian IT start-ups?

In Chapter 2, Sub-Section 2.2.3, factors affecting the sustainability of the Indian IT startups were scrutinized under three categories namely risk, strategy and performance. Savitz and Weber (2007) and Crittenden *et al* (2011), set the tone for achieving sustainability, the process needs to be aligned with the goals of the startups. Many academic and industrial literatures were reviewed to bring both factors in theory and practice to light. Table 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5 scrutinized individual factors and tabulated them from different research papers and industrial articles. Ineffective planning, poor requirement management, misaligned strategic goals, premature scaling, and failed business models were categorized as sustainability factors under strategic management (Orsato *et al*, 2015; KPMG, 2019; NASSCOM, 2019). Poor financials, team inefficiencies, stagnant learning and ignoring customers were identified as sustainability factors under the category of performance (Chen *et al*, 2017; Circcullo *et al*, 2018). High uncertainty, sub-standard governance and compliance, lack of innovation, poor resource management and poor communication were highlighted as crucial sustainability factors under risk management (Purvis *et al*, 2019; Dutta *et al*, 2020). All these literatures that identified factors that affect sustainability were further scrutinized through 20 semi-structured interviews and a focus group of 8 members that asked interviewees their opinion on the top 3 pain points that affect startup sustainability.

After analysis, it was found out that most startup founders and entrepreneurs responded with the product being mismatched with customer requirements as predominant concern. Moreover, the researcher could identify non-financial or process-oriented sustainability factors to be of much concern than the financial risks for a startup. This research took all the viewpoints of startup founders and project managers who work in MNCs, where even business consultants who have experience of 20+ years concord with the factors mentioned in the literature. On overall analysis, to answer the first question, factors such as ignored customer needs, ineffective planning, strategic misalignment, unproductive culture, team inefficiency, deliverables and quality of the product to be critical factors within the context of Indian IT startups.

2. Are existing management frameworks effective enough to support the sustainability of Indian start-ups? If yes, how? If not, why?

To answer this question, the literature based on existing methodologies such as the waterfall, iterative, V-shaped, parallel and spiral methods were compared for their benefits and criticisms in Chapter 2, Section 2.4. Table 2.7 compared existing methodologies to best give the failure factors that need to be addressed. Collectively grouped as traditional transformational methodologies or non-agile methodologies, they argued that rigorous documentation and planning is the key for a project's sustainability and therefore customer retention. When asked about the traditional methodologies, senior project manager and lead developers, although didn't completely critique on them, they categorized such heavyweight, plan-driven and process focused methodology to be suitable for larger sizes and rigid nature of the project. Most startup founders given the dynamic nature of the startup ecosystem and customer base, argued non-agile traditional methodologies to be too rigid for startup, costing their ability to be flexible to changes, adapting to innovative technologies along the way and also motivating the team. When asked in the focus group discussion of 8 people, 6 out of 8 interviewees responded that non-agile methodologies to be irrelevant for startups taking much time to deliver to the market. Therefore, the answer to the question from both the literature and data collection is that the traditional non-agile methodologies are ineffective especially within the context of Indian IT startups.

3. How Indian IT startups adapt to agile Transformation in both theory and practice?

This research approached this question with the ambiguity that any theory can be good in books but can have practical implementation challenges when put to practice. So, the first part of the question, which is the understanding of agile as a theory, was reviewed in Chapter 2, Section 2.5, where the agile philosophy, manifesto and principles were introduced. Agile as opposed to traditional methodologies was found out to be lightweight, focusing on people interactions more than processes and tools, aiming to achieve a working software rather than comprehensive documentation, collaborate with customers than a rigid contract negotiation and finally respond and welcome at any stage of development rather than blindly just following a plan. Further the understanding of agile from the startup founders and manager's perspective were highlighted through semi-structured interviews and focus groups of 8. The research through their responses found out that agile has not been clearly termed and defined for it really is.

There exists an unawareness within the startup founders who blindly follow agile practices and call themselves agile. The culture of copying from the western practices has demotivated and further decelerated the growth of Indian IT startups. In reality, agile has been practiced for all the more wrong reasons as analyzed from interview responses to predominantly gain customer confidence but it has rather affected the confidence of developers and testers who work for the startup, burning them out of their time and energy. Furthermore, this research scrutinized agile for its 6 main promises that can impact management disciplines namely the visibility, resource allocation, strategic alignment, strategic sensitivity, communicating priorities and continuous learning. These elements of agile transformation were further scrutinized for theory vs practice and the analysis proved that less than 40% of the companies that practice agile implement agile practices and see the positive impacts of it in their process and management and the rest have practical challenges in achieving these agile goals.

4. How effective are current agile Transformation frameworks in managing sustainability of Indian IT start-ups?

One of the main aims of this research was to develop a new conceptual framework that addresses the sustainability issue in the context of Indian IT startups. The first part of the question is to evaluate current agile frameworks in managing sustainability. El-Khalil and Mezher (2020) developed a conceptual framework that linked agility and operational performance in the context of sustainability. This conceptual framework lacked customer collaboration and strategic alignment as key sustainability factors in the context of Indian IT startups. Geyi *et al* (2020), proposed a conceptual model that explored the interaction between agility, sustainability and performance. Here the customer collaboration has been included but the resource optimization, which is also a major criterion, has been overlooked. Moreover, the emphasis is on agile practices rather than sustainability outputs. Conceptual frameworks from Ghezzi and Cavallo (2020) and Dean and Marc (2020), linked business models and agile approach taking agile more than a mere tool to a management principle to monitor a company. Again, these agile frameworks listed in Chapter 2, Section 2.7, were not targeted for the startups and especially not for the Indian IT startups. Therefore, the evaluation of these conceptual frameworks proved the need for another new framework that links the major disciplines such as risk, performance and strategy, together with agile transformation and further linked it to the sustainability of the startups.

After analysis, it was found that Indian startup founders largely lacked the agile mindset, culture and stakeholder collaboration or participation that needed to steer a successful agile transformation. This conceptual framework focuses on the need for the awareness of agile transformation and its impact on the sustainability of Indian IT startups even before applying any of its practices. Consequently, to answer this question, the current frameworks, although effective in terms of best practices and linking agile with sustainability, are ineffective in terms of establishing the clear definition of what agile means to the startup. This framework believes that agile that does not achieve sustainability should be revisited for their implementation.

6.4 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

On complete in-depth analysis of the research findings, comparison with previous studies and new findings, the agile transformation and its impact on sustainability of Indian IT startups were studied. A summary of all the findings is as follows.

1. There are financial and non-financial factors that affect the sustainability of Indian IT startups, where non-financial factors account for 70% of failure rate.
2. Most startups struggle with understanding customer needs and fail to collaboratively work with them to adapt to changes.
3. Ineffective planning, strategic misalignment, unproductive culture, team inefficiency, poor deliverables and low-quality product/service have largely impacted sustainability of Indian IT startups as compared to other factors.
4. Most IT startups in India consider traditional or non-agile transformation methodologies to be rigid, time-consuming, plan-driven and heavyweight to be relevant for today's dynamic market.
5. Transforming to agile doesn't necessarily mean eradicating non-agile practices but rather tailoring it to the needs and requirements of the specific IT startup in India.
6. Non-agile transformation methodologies can arguably be effective in terms of planning but not effective enough to sustain IT startups in India today.
7. Agile transformation as a philosophy has been vaguely understood and mostly misinterpreted among larger and smaller IT companies.
8. Many larger MNCs that call themselves agile to gain confidence among customers, do not truly follow agile to address the sustainability crisis.

9. Having the agile mindset, building the agile culture and ensuring absolute stakeholder participation prior to the actual agile transformation can steer the startup towards achieving sustainability.
10. Targeting agile transformation to empower risk, strategy and performance can ultimately impact sustainability.
11. Risk management in Indian IT startups lack visibility with the customer and optimum resource allocation leading to ignored customer needs and ineffective planning of product/service software development.
12. Strategic management in Indian IT startups are ineffective in aligning processes with strategic vision and direction which fail to enrich the team with the best skills and competences needed to achieve the process.
13. Improving communication of priorities and thereby continuously learning from failures can impact on the performance management of Indian IT startups
14. Agile transformation, when done right and tailored in relevance to the startups to achieve sustainability within risk, strategy and performance management disciplines can positively impact India IT startups to achieve competitive advantage among competitors and organizational agility within the startup.

6.5 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION

6.5.1 CONTRIBUTION TO THEORY

This research through an in-depth review that critically analyzes literature and practices about agile transformation, contributes immensely towards the academic knowledge and practitioner guidance. The identification of sustainability factors in Chapter 2 can help startup founders be aware of the external and internal challenges that need to be addressed early in their startup career. This research further differentiates itself from other studies within the context of Indian IT startups.

While exploring solutions to sustain IT startups, changes in the processes over the decade have also been reviewed as no other research paper. Chapter 2, Section 2.6 identifies unique literature gaps that have not been addressed in previous research. The development of a new agile startup sustainability framework, Figure 5.8 will be one of its kind for Indian IT startups that not only implements agile with the right mindset, culture and stakeholder participation but also provides risk, strategy and performance agility to influence competitive edge and organizational agility.

Table 6. 1 Summary of the research contributions to the theory

CONTRIBUTIONS	DESCRIPTION	CHAPTER/FIGURE
Industry background	Descriptive analysis of Indian IT startup ecosystem	Chapter 1
Literature review	Evaluation of sustainability factors	Chapters 2
	Evaluation of traditional transformation methodologies	Chapters 2
	Evaluation of Agile transformation methodology	Chapters 2
	Evaluation of academic and industry contribution	Chapters 2
	Literature gaps	Chapters 2
Development of Agile startup sustainability framework	Evaluation of current sustainability frameworks	Chapters 2
	Rationale for Agile startup sustainability framework	Chapters 2
	Derivation of the framework	Chapters 2
	Elements of the framework	Chapters 2
Research methodology	Multi-method research design	Chapters 3
Empirical findings	Qualitative: Semi-structured interviews	Chapter 3,4
	Qualitative: Focus groups	Chapter 3,4
Validation of the Agile startup sustainability framework	Agile startup sustainability framework	Chapter 5
Practical guidelines	Implementation of the Agile startup sustainability framework	Chapter 5

Table 6.1 summarizes the research contributions to literature and agile theories, highlighting the selective sections from each chapter. Candidates selected as target interviewees for this research had immense knowledge and years of experience in the IT industry to contribute towards this research. The findings of these interviews were validated through two focus groups that voiced multiple opinions about agile, both pros and cons, that no other research can provide. The need for high visibility, optimum resource allocation, strategic alignment, strategic sensitivity, communication of priorities and continuous learning for a startup to be sustainable has been both reviewed in Chapter 2 through the literature and also through empirical evidence from interviews as recorded in Chapter 4. Significant impacts of agile transformation on sustainability of IT startups have been best evaluated through this research. By identifying and addressing each sustainability factor, this research offers practical guidance for any IT startup in India.

Moreover, the detailed behavioral and cultural viewpoints that were collected as data from interviewees elevate the richness of this research by being more relevant and reliable for startups in the IT industry. The methodological approach that combines both literature from recent years and practical evidence can prove as key contributions towards the success of this research.

6.5.2 CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE PRACTICE

The major contribution to practice is the agile startup sustainability framework developed in Chapter 5, Figure 5.8 which needs to be implemented under the guidelines and action plan provided in Section 5.6, Figure 5.9. India has taken multiple efforts recently to support startups financially, yet a larger volume of IT startup exits has opened opportunities for research and development of new models to address this sustainability crisis. Meanwhile, the rate of IT startups being established in a year is incredibly increasing in recent years which has all the more turned attention towards IT startups in India and their sustainability.

Accordingly, the need to counteract this issue has given a boost to the practitioner community, industry consultants and academic researchers. This is the first research that contributes towards the understanding of the relationship between agile transformation and startup sustainability and the need for targeted agile elements to compete in the Indian startup ecosystem. Young startup entrepreneurs, founders who have had experience working in larger MNCs, project managers, agile scrum masters, coaches and practitioners can be best benefited through this research. This research contributes to these individuals as follows:

1. There could be multiple reasons why startups can fail but in context with Indian IT startups, process-oriented factors have been highlighted more than the financial factors. This shows that startup founders and managers who are much focused on getting returns on investment, profitability, etc., need to focus on primarily improving the quality of the product/service/software that forms the core of the startup. Ignoring customers by not collaborating with them right from early stages has reduced customer visibility and therefore affected customer confidence. The management of startups need to first identify the key factors that are affecting their sustainability or pain points that might affect in the future. Therefore, this research that has collectively identified key factors through literature and data analysis can help startups identify futuristic risks.

2. Traditional non-agile transformational methodologies have been identified as ineffective in achieving sustainability within the context of Indian IT startups given their rigidity and heavyweight planning. This has given managers the need to transform into agile, mostly due to customer pressure, increased sales opportunities, improved performance, etc. But, this research found out that this transformation from traditional to agile hasn't been done with the right mindset, culture and stakeholder participation and has not impacted startups. Managers and startup founders need to first understand the need for agile and not just transform with the intention of copying western practices and culture. Moreover, the vague understanding of agile even among senior managers and employees in larger MNCs, as highlighted in this research, is an alarming factor. Startup founders need to invest more time and money on educating employees about agile rather than just making them blindly follow Agile practices and ceremonies, making it another tradition.
3. The relationship between the key management disciplines and the actual process of SD needs to be established and only then, agile transformation can largely benefit startup founders by targeting agile practices to achieve sustainability. As per the data analysis in this research, 6 major strategies or elements were identified. Ensuring high visibility or transparency with the customers can help understand the requirements better, making the process more collaborative as compared to being authoritative. Allocating the right resource to build MVPs can first boost confidence with the customers and drive the sprints. Aligning all processes with the strategic vision and direction of the startup can help startup project managers and founders understand the lack of training, skills and competencies needed in the team. Managers should communicate priorities within projects and learn from failures as early as they can to build a flexible and more dynamic startup team.
4. Agile done right has been one of the phrases that has been constantly repeated throughout the data analysis. This shows how agile transformation as a philosophy and principle has been misled and misused by startup managers. Therefore, agile practices need to be tailored and made relevant to ultimately achieve sustainability. Sustainability has various dimensions, and this research focuses on the two pillars of sustaining competition and internal agility. If agile transformation is not targeted for achieving sustainability in these two areas, then the startup has to check their Agility and the impacts it has had over the startup. These are research findings that consultants can achieve through their models.

6.6 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ACADEMICS AND PRACTITIONERS

As discussed in Chapter 5, Section 5.5, Figure 5.8, where the framework was validated, startup founders, managers and entrepreneurs must implement the framework in their startup to achieve business sustainability amidst external and internal challenges and barriers. The following Table 6.2 provides practical implications through a strategic road map.

Table 6. 2 Agile startup strategic road map

AGILE STARTUP TRANSFORMATION ROADMAP					
VISION					
To be sustainable as a startup in the Indian startup ecosystem					
MISSION					
To incorporate Agile into risk, strategy and performance management of the startup					
CATEGORY			TAGLINE		
IT product and service based software development startups			Flexible, Agile and Sustainable startups		
RISK AGILITY		STRATEGIC AGILITY		OPERATIONAL AGILITY	
High Visibility	Optimum resource allocation	Strategic alignment	Strategic sensitivity	Communicating priorities	Continuous learning
<i>Pricing, Time to market, Quality, Team availability, Responsiveness, transparency in practices</i>	<i>Building MVPs Incremental planning, Daily standups & meetings</i>	<i>Product visions, Sprint planning, burn down chart, Milestones & short term goals</i>	<i>Upskilling, Innovation, Continuous Interaction, insight & foresight practices</i>	<i>Product backlog, User stories, Communication guide, Requirement priority, Visualizing workflows with agile software</i>	<i>Feedback monitoring, review-retrospect, continuous improvement, learn & develop, learning culture</i>
Customer Benefit	Customer Benefit	Customer Benefit	Customer Benefit	Customer Benefit	Customer Benefit
<i>Help distinguish startups from competitors,</i>	<i>Building trust & accountability</i>	<i>Strategic customer development; Increased</i>	<i>Price sensitivity, Breaking hierarchies for effective</i>	<i>High probability of achieving objectives; High flexibility towards</i>	<i>Improved customer service; Higher productivity;</i>

<i>gain confidence about process, personal relationship with startup</i>	<i>Reducing cost, time and increasing value</i>	<i>project success rate; Secure the PMO</i>	<i>management, increased customer satisfaction</i>	<i>change; flexibility in resource allocation and increased efficiency.</i>	<i>High quality products and services; Faster delivery; Decreased cost</i>
Company Benefit	Company Benefit	Company Benefit	Company Benefit	Company Benefit	Company Benefit
<i>Unifies business disciplines, improve risk mitigation and identification, boost sales and increased brand value and loyalty; strengthens relationships</i>	<i>Reducing waste and maximizing efforts taken; Effective planning of strategic decisions; assigning best team for job; optimize work</i>	<i>Prioritizing strategies and tactic for; capability development; Clear resource allocation decisions; Team focus</i>	<i>Self-organized teams; breaking hierarchies; motivated individuals; skill development; provide ability to predict customer's needs and movement of competitors</i>	<i>Easier task handling; gives a clear vision of short-term and long-term goals; Less stress and less likely to burn out; Effectively manage project deadlines; Urgency & important tasks easily identified</i>	<i>Greater employee engagement; reduced self-turnover; Lower error rate; Increased individual efficiency & productivity; Employee satisfaction</i>
MANAGER'S ROLE					
DEFINE	ESTABLISH	EDUCATE	INTRODUCE	MONITOR	FEEDBACK
<i>Define the external and internal dynamism in the market environment</i>	<i>Establish current process and pain points that affect sustainability</i>	<i>Educate with Agile transformation for startup sustainability Agile mindset, Agile culture, Stakeholder participation</i>	<i>Introduce change through framework in an incremental way to achieve risk, strategic and operational agility</i>	<i>Monitor outputs through well-defined and customized KSIs, Competitive advantage, Organizational agility</i>	<i>Feedback and retrospect learning outcomes into the framework</i>
SUSTAINABILITY					
<p>More profitable, reduced business costs, more innovative strategies, improved reputation, addition of new customer, strong customer relationship, achieving intended strategic goals, meeting changing customer demands, create talent & opportunities, strong presence in the Indian startup ecosystem</p>					
COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE & ORGANIZATIONAL AGILITY					
<p>Providing high quality & well priced services than others, increased customer base and brand loyalty, higher edge over competitors, adaptable to external and internal changes, rapidly meeting customer demands and expectations, lead change by improving culture, practices and outcomes, empowered and highly productive teams</p>					

6.7 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Most research that has been conducted within the context of agile transformation and Indian IT startups have not been properly backed up with empirical evidence which has been the major motivation towards this research. Most prior research lacks practical evidence to prove the impact of agile transformation on sustainability of IT startups; necessity of agile mindset, culture and stakeholder participation; agility in risk, performance and strategy leading to sustainability; agile transformation for competitive advantage and organizational agility. The research findings can be exploratory for future researchers who wish to build upon the themes and topics covered in this research beyond the scope of IT startups. This research limits itself to non-financial factors that only target process-oriented issues and therefore the first recommendation would be to investigate this framework for financial sustainability factors that have been primarily neglected. This can further elevate the idea of agile transformation for the entire startup process eliminating the need for complex business models. Moreover, the scope of this research can be further diversified for other industries such as agriculture, pharma, e-commerce, etc., which also contributes immensely towards India's GDP. As culture, mindset and stakeholder participation have been identified as elements, a clear definition of each element in context with Indian IT startups, needs to be identified through future research. As agile transformation is dynamic and evolving in nature in terms of tools and practices, there's always room for customization of the conceptual framework as proposed in this research. The inability to quantify intangible elements of this framework can be addressed in future research and more targeted practices can be provided. The methodologies used for future research on sustainability of Indian IT startups can target more samples and wider demography extending to major tier cities of India and other countries affected by sustainability factors adding to the generalization of this research findings and framework validation. Keeping everything in mind, future researchers can aim to provide valuable practical guidance for Indian IT startups and thereby impact the economy of India.

6.8 LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

Considering all the sections this research has covered, including the conceptual framework, research methodologies, research sampling, data collection, data analysis, access to data, availability of resources, etc., this section aims to identify potential limitations that can alarm future researchers and make them aware. The limitations of this research are as follows:

1. The emphasis behind the agile startup sustainability framework, Chapter 5, Figure 5.8

As established earlier as a research problem in Section 1.4, there's evident scarcity of Agile startup frameworks in the context of Indian IT startups which poses a significant challenge to the industry's adaptability and sustainability. Through responses from semi-structured interviews and focus groups in Chapter 4, Section 4.3, it was clear that there's a lack of awareness and understanding among Indian IT startups regarding the benefits and implementation of Agile practices, a culture resistance and deeply ingrained traditional approaches, hierarchies and structures resisting transition to Agile, budget constraints and skill-workforce demand, and in addition the competitive nature of the Indian IT industry which corresponds to the literature review in Chapter 2, Section 2.. Although, these can be limitations for the emphasis behind the agile startup sustainability framework, this research can be the starting point for IT startup founders, entrepreneurs and managers in their seed stage of startup to educate themselves with process management techniques based on agile transformation more than just instinctive behavior and radical innovation.

2. Potential bias of the respondents

Participant bias in this qualitative research introduces potential distortions in data due to participants' characteristics, attitudes, or behaviors. The sub consciousness of providing socially acceptable responses rather than genuine perspectives and thoughts, can impact and alter the accuracy of the responses. While the researcher meticulously established a non-judgmental environment, clearly communicating the research purpose and obtaining consent before interviews and focus groups, it is crucial to acknowledge that even with these rigorous measures, potential biases can inevitably permeate qualitative research. This research also uncovered a profound developer-entrepreneur bias, depicting a contrast in perspectives between developers possessing extensive IT process knowledge and entrepreneurial experience versus entrepreneurs with a managerial background. Those developers who have initiated their own companies exhibit a distinct viewpoint on agile transformation and its practices, perceiving them through a lens shaped by their hands-on involvement in software development. In contrast, entrepreneurs primarily rooted in management view agile not as a burden but as a strategic advantage, illuminating the significant impact of this developer-entrepreneur bias on perceptions within the realm of

agile methodologies. This research has allowed and recorded both opinions and perspectives to best capture the study of the phenomena.

3. Difference between financial and non-financial factors

As part of this research, sustainability factors were identified through literature and interviews. Although agile proves beneficial it cannot address finance related issues or has not been identified for startups which also plays a significant role in startups sustainability in India, posing this as another limitation for the framework. This can limit this research aiming to provide a holistic approach for Indian IT startup management.

4. High dependency on Qualitative strategy

Although method triangulation including semi-structured interviews and focus groups, were used to foster rich information, limitations that pertain to any qualitative strategies applies to this research. The non-numeric nature of qualitative data also makes quantification and statistical analysis challenging, restricting the ability to draw numerical conclusions. Nevertheless, an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon has been achieved, which has been the primary concern of this exploratory research. Although qualitative research raises concern around limited generalizability, inherent subjectivity, and difficulty in replication, this research aims to address these limitations by ensuring trustworthiness and reliability as highlighted in Chapter 3, Section 3., making sure the selected participants, their selection criteria, and their inputs are reliable to the research topic and contribute to the academic literature.

5. The sampling inaccuracy

This research aimed to engage startup founders, entrepreneurs and project managers from a wider landscape of Tier 1 cities in India such as Bengaluru, Delhi, Chennai, Hyderabad, Mumbai, Pune, Kolkata, and Ahmedabad as mentioned in Chapter 3. However, the widespread impact of the COVID –19 pandemic limited data accessibility and movement between all these cities due to lockdown restrictions and therefore, the researcher could only collect data from cities like Chennai, Bengaluru, Hyderabad and Mumbai. Future researchers can further this research to other cities in India including Tier 2 cities. Startup founders and entrepreneurs who had strict confidentiality policies regarding the disclosure of company processes, a preference for voice recordings over video, time and budget constraints projected as limitations for data collection. Consequently, the research

expanded to include startup consultants with clients as Indian IT startups, who were later added to the selection criteria. While this broader scope offered valuable insights, it introduced a few inaccuracies due to participants' biases towards their clients and their operational perspectives, which has also been highlighted in Chapter 4. Nevertheless, the findings of this research correlate with literature and provide new insights about Agile transformation and sustainability and contribute immensely towards the research topic.

6. Small sample size and difficulty of generalizing the findings

A small sample size in qualitative research poses several limitations that can impact the depth and generalizability of the research's findings. Generalizing results to a wider population which is the Indian IT startup landscape can be a crucial challenge, as the selected sample size 34 participants, including semi-structured interviewees and focus group participants, may not adequately represent the diversity within the phenomenon under investigation, and lead to a potential compromise in the applicability of research findings to different contexts. As mentioned earlier, there is an increased vulnerability to respondent biases which can further set drawbacks. Moreover, establishing trustworthiness and ensuring reliability can be more complex with limited sample size. Despite these setbacks, this research enhances the robustness of the findings by employing purposeful sampling, where the selection criteria were effectively introduced, employing data and method triangulation to complete each other for its weaknesses and strengths, and transferability of the findings to different contexts to ensure generalizability. Future researchers can build on this research by expanding the sample size and applying the agile startup sustainability framework to more diverse demography and in different contexts.

7. The lack of longitudinal data

This research employs cross-sectional time horizon where data from research participants are collected at a single point in time, providing a snapshot of a population or a phenomenon at that specific moment. The absence of longitudinal data in this research can pose significant limitations, particularly in understanding and interpreting changes, patterns and developments of the research phenomena which is sustainability and agile transformation over time within the context of Indian IT startups. This restricts this research from tracking developments, observing trends, and identifying causal relationships between highly dynamic subject phenomena, agile transformation and

sustainability, which limits the in-depth insight. Future research can involve following up with the respondents to examine the trajectory of behaviors, change in the perspective of the phenomena, etc., which could be integral to this research topic, and largely overcome this limitation.

To ensure the validity and reliability of this research, multiple qualitative methods were used which has been highlighted in Chapter 3. A strong literature base for the interview questions set the right spirit amongst the targeted samples for interviews to be conducted and results to be verified. This has furthermore increased the research credibility. Purposive sampling used to identify potential target samples to get both reliable and relevant information for this research, proved valid and credible to achieve a meaningful qualitative analysis, giving the internal validity for the findings. While accepting the need for the emphasis of the framework before applying it, IT startups especially in India have a greater willingness and utmost ability to experiment and innovate for profitable results. This potential opportunity can bring the Agile startup framework as the solution for process-oriented sustainability issues pertaining to the market. The scope of this framework (if implemented with the right mindset and customized to meet specific needs) expands to startups other than the IT industry which has IT services and solutions as part of their business operations.

6.9 RESEARCHER PERSONAL REFLECTION

The decision to do this research was challenging and difficult to convince my peers, friends and family especially the need to choose Indian IT startups. As detailed in Chapter 1, the key motivation for the researcher is to contribute towards the country where the researcher has had experience and also to achieve greater insights into business consulting in the field of IT.

Firstly, with the engineering background of study, family and friends were much worried about the researcher's ability to tap into the field of IT startups where the researcher has zero experience. Furthermore, the choice of qualitative methodology to interview startup founders, managers, entrepreneurs and agile coaches was much of a concern as the researcher had limited access to these contacts. Only halfway through the research was the contribution towards theory and practice evident which furthermore gained confidence among supervisors and peers. The positive paradigm, as opposed to interpretivism approach, although provides empirical evidence quantitatively, the research understood the need to explore the concept of agile transformation.

With the questions of whys and how's, it was beneficial to gain better insight into the phenomenon of sustainability using a more qualitative approach. This raised the confidence of the researcher to further provide valuable, credible, trustworthy and reliable results and findings. As a researcher, this has developed interview skills, understanding manager's perspectives, comparing responses and analysis techniques, compiling business reports, management skills, time management skills and also rich understanding of agile transformation.

To support the research, the researcher had to first pilot study with senior agile scrum masters and a pool of project managers to initially educate with the concept of agile transformation. Communicating with multiple IT employees and gaining their experience had personally helped the researcher gain confidence in this research. The practical problems from a few of the startup founders and managers inspired the researcher to potentially tap into the sustainability factors. Gaining interest, the researcher then reviewed other research studies in this field and identified the literature gap where there were no research papers explaining the relationship between the agile transformation process and sustainability.

Self-reflection was implemented at every stage of the research to avoid self-biases, validate findings, gain trustworthiness of the empirical evidence and append self-understanding into the areas needed. The researcher's transparency and credibility can be judged by readers.

6.10 RESEARCH CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Sustainability as a broad concept was conceptualized and categorized within the context of Indian IT startups to better contribute to the target industry and provide practical solutions. This research emerged with the intention of addressing the reasons why Indian IT startups struggle to sustain for longer term, and successfully identified specific factors that affects sustainability in the context of Indian IT startups. While Agile methodologies have gained prominence globally for their flexibility and responsiveness, there is a notable gap in their systematic implementation within the Indian startup ecosystem. Agile transformation, which has predominantly been misunderstood and ill-treated, was analyzed and compared with traditional methodologies in the light of risk, strategy and performance, to evaluate its contribution to the sustainability of Indian IT startups. The scope of Agile transformation has been extended from mere project management tool to a radical mindset and culture that can influence startups holistically.

In conclusion, the integration of agile transformation and sustainability within the context of IT startups holds significant implications for both academic understanding and practical applications. This research offers a valuable framework that not only aids startups in navigating uncertainties and optimizing their operations but also contributes to broader societal benefits.

From an academic perspective, this research enriches the understanding of the intricate relationship between risk, strategy, and performance management in the dynamic context of IT startups. It provides a nuanced perspective on how these elements interact within the unique sustainability challenges and opportunities presented by the Indian IT startup ecosystem. Scholars and researchers can leverage these insights to further refine theoretical models and contribute to the evolving discourse on sustainable business practices. Practically, the developed framework equips IT startups with a strategic approach to achieve a holistic agile management that aligns seamlessly with sustainability goals. Limited awareness, cultural resistance, and resource constraints impede Agile adoption among Indian IT startups. Many lack an understanding of Agile's benefits, hindering its potential in product development and market adaptation. Cultural resistance, hierarchical structures, and traditional project management approaches pose challenges. Resource constraints limit investment in necessary training and infrastructure, acting as a deterrent. Competitive pressures may lead startups to prioritize short-term gains over long-term Agile benefits, perpetuating its scarcity. By implementing this framework, startups can enhance their resilience, competitive advantage, and ultimately overall performance. The positive outcomes extend beyond the organizational level, with potential ripple effects on the economy, environment, and society at large.

On an economic level, startups that effectively integrate sustainability practices are better positioned to attract investment and foster long-term growth. The efficient allocation of resources and a focus on high-impact activities contribute to economic stability and job creation within the startup sector. Additionally, the positive environmental impact of sustainable practices aligns with global efforts of the IT industry. Furthermore, the societal implications of this research are substantial. IT startups that prioritize sustainability not only contribute to a more environmentally conscious business landscape but also foster social responsibility and ethical business practices. This, in turn, can lead to increased trust from consumers, improved community relations, and a positive influence on corporate culture.

In summary, this research on the integration of agile transformation and sustainability in IT startups not only advances academic knowledge but also provides a practical and actionable framework with far-reaching implications. By enabling startups to navigate risks and pursue sustainability, this research contributes to a more resilient, responsible, and sustainable business ecosystem, ultimately benefiting society by fostering economic growth, environmental stewardship, and socially responsible entrepreneurship.

Government of India, IT industry stakeholders, educational institutions, and Indian IT MNCs and startups can play a pivotal role in furthering this research by promoting the understanding and adoption of Agile transformation for young entrepreneurs and emerging companies to best capitalize its sustainability benefits. The agile startup sustainability framework developed in this research can be the starting point for creating awareness for the urgency of sustainability measures to be incorporated early in the startup stages. The development and dissemination of case studies showcasing successful Agile transformations within the Indian context can also serve as valuable resources for startups looking to overcome the scarcity and harness the potential of Agile frameworks. Sustainable startups mean increased job creation, robust economy, economic growth, technological innovation, community engagement, informed and resilient management, emphasis on long-term value creation, enhanced corporate reputations, and creating an overall positive and lasting impact on India's startup landscape and reputation.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Aalst, V. D. Weske, W.M., M. and Wirtz, G., (2003) Advanced topics in workflow management: Issues, requirements, and solutions. Journal of Integrated Design and Process Science, Vol: 7(3), pp.49-77.
2. Abdelmaboud, A., Jawawi, D.N., Ghani, I., Elsafi, A. and Kitchenham, B., (2015). Quality of service approaches in cloud computing: A systematic mapping study. Journal of Systems and Software, Vol: 101, pp.159-179.
3. Abirami R., Jigish, Z., Dessa, D., John, S. D., (2021) The impact of project team characteristics and client collaboration on project agility and project success: An empirical study, European Management Journal, ISSN 0263-2373, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2021.09.011>.
4. Abrahamsson, P., Salo, O., Ronkainen, J. and Warsta, J., (2017). Agile software development methods: Review and analysis. arXiv preprint Available: arXiv:1709.08439.
5. Adel, A., Abdullah, B., (2015) A Comparison Between Three SDLC Models Waterfall Model, Spiral Model, and Incremental/Iterative Model International Journal of Computer Science Issues Vol: 12(1).
6. Adetokumbo, A., A., Basirat, A., A., (2013) Software Engineering Methodologies: A review of the Waterfall Model and Object-oriented Approach International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research Vol: 4(7) pp 427-430.
7. Agrawal, A., DeFries, R.S., Ellis, E.C., Chapin III, F.S., Matson, P.A., Turner, B.L., Crutzen, P.J., Field, C., Gleick, P., Kareiva, P.M. and Lambin, E., (2012). Planetary opportunities: a social contract for global change science to contribute to a sustainable future. BioScience, Vol: 62(6), pp.603-606.
8. Ahimbisibwe, A., Cavana, R.Y. and Daellenbach, U. (2015), A contingency fit model of critical success factors for software development projects: A comparison of agile and traditional plan-based methodologies, Journal of Enterprise Information Management, Vol: 28(1), pp. 7-33. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-08-2013-0060>.
9. Ahimbisibwe, A., Daellenbach, U. and Cavana, R., (2017). Empirical comparison of traditional plan-based and agile methodologies. Journal of Enterprise Information Management, Vol: 30(3), pp.400-453.
10. Ahmed, A.R., Tayyab, M., Bhatti, S.N., Alzahrani, A.J. and Babar, M.I., (2017). Impact of story point estimation on product using metrics in scrum development process. International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol: 8(4), pp.385-391.
11. Alami, A., (2016). Why do information technology projects fail? Procedia Computer Science, Vol: 100, pp.62-71.
12. Albarqi, A.A. and Qureshi, R., (2018). The proposed L-Scrumban methodology to improve the efficiency of agile software development. International Journal of Information Engineering and Electronic Business, Vol: 11(3), p.23.
13. Allan, D. S., Srivastava and Rajendra K. (1991) Brand Equity: A Perspective on its Meaning and Measurement. Cambridge Mass: Marketing Science Institute.
14. Alsahli, A., Khan, H. and Alyahya, S., (2017). Agile development overcomes GSD challenges: a systematic literature review. International Journal of Computer Science and Software Engineering, Vol: 6(1), p.7.
15. Altheide, D.L. and Johnson, J.M., (2011). Reflections on interpretive adequacy in qualitative research. The SAGE handbook of qualitative research, 4, pp.581-594.

16. M. Amini, C.C. Bienstock (2014) Corporate sustainability: an integrative definition and framework to evaluate corporate practice and guide academic research, Journal on Clean. Prod., Vol: 76, pp. 12-19, 10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.02.01
17. Anderson, D.J., Concas, G., Lunesu, M.I., Marchesi, M. and Zhang, H., (2012), A comparative study of Scrum and Kanban approaches on a real case study using simulation. In International Conference on Agile Software Development (pp. 123-137). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
18. Andrews, T. (2012). What is social constructionism? The Grounded Theory Review, Vol: 11(1), pp 39-46.
19. Angrosino, M. (2011). Recontextualizing observation: ethnography, pedagogy, and the prospects for a progressive political agenda. In N. Denzin & Y. Lincoln (Eds.), The SAGE handbook of qualitative research (Vol. 3, pp. 729-745). Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Angrosino, M. and Rosenberg, J., 2011. Observations on observation. The Sage handbook of qualitative research, 4, pp.467-478.
20. Annosi, M.C. and Brunetta, F., (2017). Linking Organizational Controls and Organizational Learning: Research Approach and Methodology. In New Organizational Forms, Controls, and Institutions (pp. 111-137). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
21. Annosi, M.C., Martini, A., Brunetta, F. and Marchegiani, L., (2020). Learning in an agile setting: A multilevel research study on the evolution of organizational routines. Journal of Business Research, 110, pp.554-566.
22. Anseel, F., (2017). Agile learning strategies for sustainable careers: a review and integrated model of feedback-seeking behavior and reflection. Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability, Vol: 28, pp.51-57.
23. Anthony, (2016) Green Information Systems Integration in Information Technology Based Organizations: An Academic Literature Review Journal of soft computing and decision support systems, Vol: 3(6).
24. Armanious, M. and Padgett, J.D. (2021), Agile learning strategies to compete in an uncertain business environment, Journal of Workplace Learning, Vol: 33(8), pp. 635-647, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JWL-11-2020-0181>.
25. Asghar, A.R., Tabassum, A., Bhatti, S.N. and Jadi, A.M., (2017), Impact and challenges of requirements elicitation & prioritization in quality to agile process: Scrum as a case scenario. In 2017 International Conference on Communication Technologies (ComTech) (pp. 50-55). IEEE. Available: doi: 10.1109/COMTECH.2017.8065749.
26. Aslam, T., and Linnéusson, G., Ng, A.H. (2018) Quantitative analysis of a conceptual system dynamics maintenance performance model using multi-objective optimisation. Journal of Simulation, Vol: 12(2), pp.171-189.
27. Avolio, B.J. Walumbwa, F.O. Weber T.J. (2009) Leadership: Current theories, research, and future directions Annual Review of Psychology, Vol: 60, pp. 421-449
28. Babb, J., Hoda, R. and Nørbjerg, J., (2014). Embedding reflection and learning into agile software development. IEEE software, Vol: 31(4), pp.51-57.
29. Babbie, E and Mouton, J (2004) The Practice of Social Research, OUP: Cape Town.
30. Bäcklander, G. (2019) - Doing complexity leadership theory: How agile coaches at Spotify practise enabling leadership, Creativity and Innovation Management, Vol: 28(1) p. 42-60, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1111/caim.12303>.
31. Badampudi, D., Fricker, S.A. and Moreno, A.M., (2013), Perspectives on productivity and delays in large-scale agile projects. In International Conference on Agile Software Development Vol: 149 (pp. 180-194). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

32. Bajwa, S., Wang, X., Duc, A., Chanin, R., Prikladnicki, R., Pompermaier, L. and Abrahamsson, P., (2017). Start-Ups Must Be Ready to Pivot. IEEE Software, Vol: 34(3), pp.18-22.
33. Baker S. W. and Thomas, J. C. (2007) Agile Principles as a Leadership Value System: How Agile Memes Survive and Thrive in a Corporate IT Culture, (AGILE 2007), pp. 415-420, Available: doi: 10.1109/AGILE.2007.10.
34. Balaji M., Velmurugan V., Subashree C. (2015). TADS: An assessment methodology for agile supply chains Journal of applied research and technology, Vol: 13 (5) pp. 504-509.
35. Balaji, S. and Sundararajan, M.M., (2012). Waterfall vs. V-Model vs. Agile: A comparative study on SDLC. International Journal of Information Technology and Business Management, Vol: 2(1), pp.26-30.
36. Balboni, B. and Bortoluzzi, G., (2015). Business Model Adaptation and the Success of New Ventures. Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Innovation, Vol: 11(1), pp.119-140.
37. Bartlett, J.E., Kotrlik, J.W., and Higgins, C.C. (2001). Organizational Research: Determining Appropriate Sample Size in Survey Research Information Technology, Learning, and Performance Journal, Vol: 19(1), pp 43-50.
38. Basiago, A. (1999). Economic, social, and environmental sustainability in development theory and urban planning practice, The Environmentalist, Vol: 19, 145–6.
39. Bassil, Y., (2012). A simulation model for the waterfall software development life cycle. arXiv preprint arXiv:1205.6904.
40. Bastiaansen, C.A.J. and Wilderom, C.P.M. (2021), Agile and generic work values of British Vs Indian IT workers: a culture-clash case, Journal of Strategy and Management, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSMA-03-2021-0071>.
41. Bell E., Bryman A., and Harley B. (2018) Business Research Methods; 5th Edition. Pub: Oxford University Press.
42. Benmoussa, R., Abdelkadir, C., Abd, A. and Hassou, M. (2015), Capability/maturity based model for logistics processes assessment: Application to distribution processes, International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management, Vol: 64(1), pp. 28-51. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-08-2012-0084>.
43. Berger, P., & Luckmann, T. (1966). The social construction of reality: A treatise in the sociology of knowledge. New York: Doubleday Dell.
44. Berglund A. F. Gong, L., LI, D. (2018) Testing and validating Extended Reality (xR) technologies in manufacturing Procedia Manufacturing, Vol: 25 pp. 31-38
45. Beske-Janssen, P., Johnson, M.P. and Schaltegger, S., (2015). 20 years of performance measurement in sustainable supply chain management–what has been achieved? Supply chain management: An international Journal, Vol: 20(6), pp 664-680.
46. Betta, J. and Boronina, L., (2018). Transparency in Project Management–from Traditional to Agile. Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research, Vol: 56, pp.446-449.
47. Bhatti, S.N., Tabassum, A., Asghar, A.R., and Jadi, A.M., (2017), Impact and challenges of requirements elicitation & prioritization in quality to agile process: Scrum as a case scenario. In 2017 International Conference on Communication Technologies (ComTech) (pp. 50-55). IEEE.
48. Biesta, G. (2010). Pragmatism and the philosophical foundations of mixed methods research. In A. Tashakkori & C. Teddlie (Eds.), Sage handbook of mixed methods in social & behavioral research (2nd ed., pp. 95-118). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

49. Biloslavo, R., Bagnoli, C. and Edgar, D., (2018). An eco-critical perspective on business models: The value triangle as an approach to closing the sustainability gap. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 174, pp.746-762.
50. Björk, J., Frishammar, J., Richtnér, A., Brattström, A., Magnusson, M. (2019). Opportunities and challenges in the new innovation landscape: Implications for innovation auditing and innovation management. European Management Journal, Vol: 37(2), pp.151-164.
51. Blank, S. (2007). The Four Steps to the Epiphany – Successful Strategies for Products that Win. Raleigh, NC: Lulu Enterprises.
52. Blank, S. and Euchner, J., (2018). The genesis and future of Lean Startup: An interview with Steve Blank. Research-Technology Management, Vol: 61(5), pp.15-21.
53. Blome, C., Schoenherr, T. and Rexhausen, D., (2013). Antecedents and enablers of supply chain agility and its effect on performance: a dynamic capabilities perspective. International Journal of Production Research, Vol: 51(4), pp.1295-1318.
54. Bocken, N., (2015). Sustainable venture capital – catalyst for sustainable start-up success? Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 108, pp.647-658.
55. Bocken, N., Short, S., Rana, P. and Evans, S., (2014). A literature and practice review to develop sustainable business model archetypes. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 65, pp.42-56.
56. Boddy, C.R., (2016). Sample size for qualitative research. Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal, Vol: 19(4) pp. 426-432.
57. Boehm, B., (1988). A spiral model of software development and enhancement. Computer, Vol: 21(5), pp.61-72.
58. Bolis, I., Brunoro, C. and Sznclwar, L., (2014). Mapping the relationships between work and sustainability and the opportunities for ergonomic action. Applied Ergonomics, Vol: 45(4), pp.1225-1239.
59. Bos-Brouwers, H., (2009). Corporate sustainability and innovation in SMEs: evidence of themes and activities in practice. Business Strategy and the Environment, p.n/a-n/a.
60. Bower J. (2007) The CEO within: Why inside outsiders are the key to succession planning Harvard Business School Press, Boston.
61. Boyatzis, R. (1998). Transforming qualitative information. Thousand Oaks: Sage
62. Brannen M.Y. When Mickey loses face: Recontextualization, semantic fit, and the semiotics of foreignness Academy of Management Review, Vol: 29, pp. 593-616.
63. Braun, M.T., (2013). Obstacles to social networking website use among older adults. Computers in human behavior, Vol: 29(3), pp.673-680.
64. Braun, V. and Clarke, V., (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. Qualitative research in psychology, Vol: 3(2), pp.77-101.
65. Brereton, P., Kitchenham, B., Budgen, D., Turner, M. and Khalil, M., (2007). Lessons from applying the systematic literature review process within the software engineering domain. Journal of Systems and Software, Vol: 80(4), pp.571-583.
66. Briassoulis, H., (2001). Sustainable Development and its Indicators: Through a (Planner's) Glass Darkly. Journal of Environmental Planning and Management, Vol: 44(3), pp.409-427.
67. Brookman, F., Smit, J. and Silvius, A.J., (2012). Perception of information technology enablers for effective supply chain management. Communications of the IIMA, Vol: 12(2), p.4.
68. Brown, C.A., Hansen, H.N., Jiang, X.J., Blateyron, F., Berglund, J., Senin, N., Bartkowiak, T., Dixon, B., Le Goic, G., Quinsat, Y. and Stemp, W.J., (2018). Multiscale analyses and characterizations of surface topographies. CIRP annals, Vol: 67(2), pp.839-862.

69. Broy, M., (2006), Challenges in automotive software engineering. In Proceedings of the 28th international conference on Software engineering (pp. 33-42).
70. Broza, G. (2015) The Agile Mind-Set Making Agile Processes Work Pub: CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform
71. Brundtland (1987) Report of the world commission on environment and development: our common future Available: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/5987our-common-future.pdf>. [Accessed on 16th April 2019]
72. Bryman, A. and Bell, E., (2015). Business research methods. Oxford University Press, USA
73. Bryman, A. and Burgess, R.G. (1994). Analyzing qualitative data, Vol: 11, London: Routledge.
74. Budi, D.S. and Abijono, H., (2016). Analisis Pemilihan Penerapan Proyek Metodologi Pengembangan Rekayasa Perangkat Lunak. Teknika, Vol: 5(1), pp.24-31.
75. Budsaratagoon, P. and Jitmaneroj, B., (2019). Measuring causal relations and identifying critical drivers for corporate sustainability: the quadruple bottom line approach. Measuring Business Excellence, Vol: 23(3), pp.292-316.
76. Buetow, S., (2010). Thematic analysis and its reconceptualization as ‘saliency analysis’. Journal of health services research & policy, Vol: 15(2), pp.123-125.
77. Burnette, JL, O; Boyle, EH, VanEpps, EM, Pollack, JM & Finkel, EJ (2013). Mind-sets matter: A meta-analytic review of implicit theories and self-regulation. Psychological Bulletin, Vol: 139(3), 655-701.
78. Cachia, M. and Millward, L. (2011), The telephone medium and semi-structured interviews: a complementary fit, Qualitative Research in Organizations and Management, Vol: 6(3), pp. 265-277. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/17465641111188420>.
79. Calero, C., Moraga, M. and Bertoa, M.F., (2013). Towards a software product sustainability model. arXiv preprint arXiv:1309.1640.
80. Cameron, J., (2005). Focusing on the focus group. Qualitative research methods in human geography, Vol: 2(8), pp.116-132.
81. Campanelli, A.S. and Parreiras, F.S., (2015). Agile methods tailoring—A systematic literature review. Journal of Systems and Software, Vol: 110, pp.85-100.
82. Cappelli, P. and Tavis, A., (2016). The performance management revolution. Harvard Business Review, Vol: 94(10), pp.58-67.
83. Caracelli, V.J. and Greene, J.C., (1993). Data analysis strategies for mixed-method evaluation designs. Educational evaluation and policy analysis, Vol: 15(2), pp.195-207.
84. Caroline, P., Brenda, M., David, S. (2008) An Elaboration of Critical Success Factors for Rural ICT Project Sustainability in Developing Countries: Exploring the DWESA Case, Journal of Information Technology Case and Application Research, Vol: 10(4), pp. 32-55, Available: DOI: 10.1080/15228053.2008.10856146.
85. Carsten, K., Kock, A. and Gemünden, H.G., (2020). Emerging strategy recognition in agile portfolios. International Journal of Project Management, Vol: 38(7), pp.429-440.
86. Carvalho, E.L. Cheiran, J.F.P., de M. Rodrigues, E., de S. and da Silva, J.P.S., (2017). Problem-based learning to align theory and practice in software testing teaching. In Proceedings of the 31st Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering (pp. 328-337).
87. Cavana, R.Y., Delahaye, B.L. and Sekaran, U., (2001). Applied business research: Qualitative and quantitative methods. John Wiley & Sons Australia.
88. CB Insights (2019) Startup Failure Post-Mortems CB Insights [Online] Available: www.cbinsights.com [Accessed: 20 January 2020]

89. Ceasar, N. and Page, N., (2013). A time and place for sustainability. Journal of Management Development, Vol: 32(3), pp.268-276.
90. Cervone, H.F., (2011). Understanding agile project management methods using Scrum. OCLC Systems & Services: International digital library perspectives. Vol: 27(1), pp. 18-22.
91. Chan, F.T.S. and Zhang, J., (2002). A multi-agent-based agile shop floor control system. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, Vol: 19(10), pp.764-774.
92. Chander, M., Jain, S. and Shankar, R., (2013). Modeling of information security management parameters in Indian organizations using ISM and MICMAC approach. Journal of Modelling in Management, Vol: 8(2), pp.171-189.
93. Charmaz, K. (2011). Constructing grounded theory. A practical guide through qualitative analysis (Vol. 3). London: Sage.
94. Chen, Y., Wang, Y., Nevo, S., Benitez, J. and Kou, G., (2017). Improving Strategic Flexibility with Information Technologies: Insights for Firm Performance in an Emerging Economy. Journal of Information Technology, Vol: 32(1), pp.10-25.
95. Chigona, W., Roode, D., Nabeel, N. and Pinnock, B., (2010). Investigating the impact of stakeholder management on the implementation of a public access project: The case of Smart Cape. South African Journal of Business Management, Vol: 41(2), pp.39-49.
96. Chikhale, M.M. and Mansouri, M., (2015). An agile and collaborative framework for effective governance to enhance management in large-scale enterprise business systems: The case of Apple Inc. Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management, Vol: 16(3), pp.283-293.
97. Chiu, C. and Yang, C., (2019). Competitive advantage and simultaneous mutual influences between information technology adoption and service innovation: Moderating effects of environmental factors. Structural Change and Economic Dynamics, Vol: 49, pp.192-205.
98. Cho, J., (2008). Issues and Challenges of agile software development with SCRUM. Issues in Information Systems, Vol: 9(2), pp.188-195.
99. Cho, Y. and McLean, G., (2009). Leading Asian countries' HRD practices in the IT industry: a comparative study of South Korea and India. Human Resource Development International, Vol: 12(3), pp.313-331.
100. Chow, T. and Cao, D.B., (2008). A survey study of critical success factors in agile software projects. Journal of systems and software, Vol: 81(6), pp.961-971.
101. Choy, K., Gunasekaran, A., Lam, H., Chow, K., Tsim, Y., Ng, T., Tse, Y. and Lu, X., (2014). Impact of information technology on the performance of logistics industry: the case of Hong Kong and Pearl Delta region. Journal of the Operational Research Society, Vol: 65(6), pp.904-916.
102. Ciccullo, F., Pero, M., Caridi, M., Gosling, J. and Purvis, L., (2018). Integrating the environmental and social sustainability pillars into the lean and agile supply chain management paradigms: A literature review and future research directions. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 172, pp.2336-2350.
103. Ciric, D., Gracanin, D., Lalic, B., Tasic, N., Delic, M. and Medic, N., (2019). Agile vs. Traditional Approach in Project Management: Strategies, Challenges and Reasons to Introduce Agile. Procedia Manufacturing, Vol: 39, pp.1407-1414.
104. Clarke, P. and O'Connor, R., (2012). The situational factors that affect the software development process: Towards a comprehensive reference framework. Information and Software Technology, Vol: 54(5), pp.433-447.
105. Cobb, C.G., (2011). Making sense of agile project management: balancing control and agility. John Wiley & Sons.

106. Cocco, L., Mannaro, K., Concas, G. and Marchesi, M., (2011), Simulating Kanban and scrum vs. waterfall with system dynamics. In International conference on agile software development Vol: 77, pp. 117-131. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
107. Cockburn, A. (2006) Agile software development: The cooperative game. Pub: Pearson Education
108. Cockburn, A. and Highsmith, J., (2001). Agile software development, the people factor. Computer, Vol: 34(11), pp.131-133.
109. Cohen, B. and Winn, M., (2007). Market imperfections, opportunity and sustainable entrepreneurship. Journal of Business Venturing, Vol: 22(1), pp.29-49.
110. Cohen, D., Lindvall, M. and Costa, P., (2004). An introduction to agile methods. Advanced Computing, Vol: 62(3), pp.1-66.
111. Coleman, G. and O'Connor, R., (2006). Software process in practice: A grounded theory of the Irish software industry. In European Conference on Software Process Improvement (pp. 28-39). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
112. Collier, K., (2012). Agile analytics: A value-driven approach to business intelligence and data warehousing. Addison-Wesley.
113. Collis, J. and Hussey, R. (2003), Business Research: A Practical Guide for Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students, Palgrave Macmillan, Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire.
114. Colombo, M. and Grilli, L., (2005). Founders' human capital and the growth of new technology-based firms: A competence-based view. Research Policy, Vol: 34(6), pp.795-816.
115. CompTIA (2020) 2020 IT (Information Technology) Industry trend analysis [Online] Available: <https://www.comptia.org/content/research/it-industry-outlook-2020> [Accessed: 17 December 2020].
116. Conboy, K. and Carroll, N., (2019). Implementing large-scale agile frameworks: challenges and recommendations. IEEE Software, Vol: 36(2), pp.44-50.
117. Conforto, E.C. Salum, F. Amaral, D.C. da Silva, S.L. de Almeida L.F.M. (2014) Can agile project management be adopted by industries other than software development? Project Management Journal, Vol: 45(3), pp. 21-34.
118. Cooper, D.R., Schindler, P.S. and Sun, J., (2006). Business research methods (Vol. 9). New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin
119. Cooper, R.G. and Sommer, A.F., (2016). The agile–stage-gate hybrid model: a promising new approach and a new research opportunity. Journal of Product Innovation Management, Vol: 33(5), pp.513-526.
120. Cowling M. Fryges H. Licht G. Murray G.C. (2006) Survival of New Technology Based Firms in the UK and Germany Babson College Entrepreneurship Research Conference (BCERC) 2006 Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research 2006.
121. Creswell, J. W. (1998). Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions. Sage Publications, Inc.
122. Creswell, J. W. (2003). Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
123. Creswell, J. W. (2013). Qualitative Inquiry and research design choosing among five approaches (3rd Ed). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
124. Creswell, J.W., (1999). Mixed-method research: Introduction and application. In Handbook of educational policy (pp. 455-472). Pub: Academic press.
125. Creswell, J.W., (2011). Controversies in mixed methods research. The Sage handbook of qualitative research, Vol: 4(1), pp.269-284.

126. Crick, C. and Chew, E.K., (2017). Business processes in the agile organization: a socio-technical perspective. Software & Systems Modeling, Vol: 16(3), pp.631-648.
127. Crittenden, V.L., Crittenden, W.F., Ferrell, L.K., Ferrell, O.C. and Pinney, C.C., (2011). Market-oriented sustainability: a conceptual framework and propositions. Journal of the academy of marketing science, Vol: 39(1), pp.71-85.
128. Crotty, M. (1998). The foundations of social research. London: Sage.
129. Crowne, M., (2002). Why software product startups fail and what to do about it. Evolution of software product development in startup companies. In IEEE International Engineering Management Conference (Vol. 1, pp. 338-343). IEEE.
130. Cunliffe, A.L. (2008). Orientations to Social Constructionism: Relationally Responsive Social Constructionism and its Implications for Knowledge and Learning. Management Learning, Vol: 39(2), pp. 123-139.
131. Czibula, I.G., Czibula, G., Marian, Z. and Ionescu, V.S., (2016). A novel approach using fuzzy self-organizing maps for detecting software faults. Studies in Informatics and Control, Vol: 25(2), pp.207-216.
132. Damanpour, F. and Aravind, D., (2012). Managerial innovation: Conceptions, processes and antecedents. Management and organization review, Vol: 8(2), pp.423-454.
133. Daneva, M., Van Der Veen, E., Amrit, C., Ghaisas, S., Sikkil, K., Kumar, R., Ajmeri, N., Ramteerthkar, U. and Wieringa, R., (2013). Agile requirements prioritization in large-scale outsourced system projects: An empirical study. Journal of systems and software, Vol: 86(5), pp.1333-1353.
134. Daniel, C. Fabio. K., (2018) A maturity model for software startup ecosystems. Journal of Innovation Entrepreneurship, Vol: 7(14), Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-018-0091-6>.
135. Daniel, P.S. and Sam, A.G., (2011). Research methodology. Gyan Publishing House.
136. Davcik, N., Vinhas da Silva, R. and Hair, J., (2015). Towards a unified theory of brand equity: conceptualizations, taxonomy and avenues for future research. Journal of Product and Brand Management, Vol: 24(1), pp.3-17.
137. David, D., Gopalan, S. and Ramachandran, S., (2021). The startup environment and funding activity in India. In Investment in Startups and Small Business Financing pp. 193-232.
138. de Burgos Jiménez, J. and Céspedes Lorente, J., (2001). Environmental performance as an operations objective. International Journal of Operations & Production Management, Vol: 21(12), pp.1553-1572.
139. Dean A. S. and Marc, G. (2020) The lean startup framework: Closing the academic–practitioner divide. Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice, Vol: 45(5), pp.967-998.
140. Dean, T. and McMullen, J., (2007). Toward a theory of sustainable entrepreneurship: Reducing environmental degradation through entrepreneurial action. Journal of Business Venturing, Vol: 22(1), pp.50-76.
141. Denning, S. (2019), Lessons learned from mapping successful and unsuccessful Agile transformation journeys, Strategy & Leadership, Vol: 47(4), pp. 3-11. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/SL-04-2019-0052>.
142. Dennison DR. (1990). Corporate Culture and Organizational Effectiveness. Wiley: New York.
143. Denzin, N., & Lincoln, Y. (2011). The SAGE Handbook of qualitative research (Vol. 4). Thousand Oaks: SAGE.

144. Derby, E., (2006). Observations on corporate culture and agile methods adoption/adaptation.
145. Dey I. (1993) Qualitative Data Analysis. A User-Friendly Guide for Social Scientists. Routledge, London.
146. Diego S. S., Ghezzi, A., Aguiar, R.B.D., Cortimiglia, M.N. and ten Caten, C.S. (2020), Lean Startup, Agile Methodologies and Customer Development for business model innovation: A systematic review and research agenda, International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research, Vol: 26(4), pp. 595-628. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEBr-07-2019-0425>.
147. Diego, M.F. Méndez, E. R. González-Ladrón-De-Guevara, F. Abrahão S. and Insfran, E. (2020). An Update on Effort Estimation in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review, in IEEE Access, Vol: 8, pp. 166768-166800, Available: doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3021664.
148. Dikert, K., Paasivaara, M. and Lassenius, C., (2016). Challenges and success factors for large-scale agile transformations: A systematic literature review. Journal of Systems and Software, Vol: 119, pp.87-108.
149. Dinesh, K. and Sushil, N., (2019). Strategic innovation factors in startups: results of a cross-case analysis of Indian startups. Journal for Global Business Advancement, Vol: 12(3), p.449.
150. do Rosário Cabrita, M., Duarte, S., Carvalho, H. and Cruz-Machado, V., (2016). Integration of lean, agile, resilient and green paradigms in a business model perspective: theoretical foundations. IFAC-PapersOnLine, Vol: 49(12), pp.1306-1311.
151. Dohe, K. and Pike, R. (2018), Integration of Project Management Techniques in Digital Projects, Project Management in the Library Workplace (Advances in Library Administration and Organization, Vol. 38), Emerald Publishing Limited, Bingley, pp. 151-166.
152. Donalek, J.G., (2005). The interview in qualitative research. Urologic Nursing, Vol: 25(2), pp.124-125.
153. Dooley, K.E., (2007). Viewing Agricultural Education Research through a Qualitative Lens. Journal of Agricultural Education, Vol: 48(4), pp.32-42.
154. Doz, Y., (2020). Fostering strategic agility: How individual executives and human resource practices contribute. Human Resource Management Review, Vol: 30(1), p.100693.
155. Doz, Y.L. and Kosonen, M., (2010). Embedding strategic agility: A leadership agenda for accelerating business model renewal. Long range planning, Vol: 43(2-3), pp.370-382.
156. Duc, A.N. and Abrahamsson, P., (2016), May. Minimum viable product or multiple facet product? The role of MVP in software startups. In International Conference on Agile Software Development (pp. 118-130). Springer, Cham.
157. Dudovskiy, J., (2016). The Ultimate Guide to Writing a Dissertation in Business Studies: A step-by-step Assistance, July edition, eBook Journal of Mixed Methods Research, Vol: 4(1). pp. 6-16.
158. Dutta, D., Sukumar, A., Jafari-Sadeghi, V., and Garcia-Perez, A., (2020). The potential link between corporate innovations and corporate competitiveness: evidence from IT firms in the UK. Journal of Knowledge Management, Vol: 24(5), pp.965-983.
159. Dweck, CS (2006). Mindset: The new psychology of success. New York: Random House.

160. Dyllick, T. and Muff, K., (2016). Clarifying the meaning of sustainable business: Introducing a typology from business-as-usual to true business sustainability. Organization & Environment, Vol: 29(2), pp.156-174.
161. Ebert, C. and Paasivaara, M., (2017). Scaling agile. Ieee Software, Vol: 34(6), pp.98-103.
162. Eid, M. (2009) Sustainable Development & Project Management, Lambert Academic Publishing, Cologne.
163. Eisenhardt, K. (2007). Theory building from cases: opportunities and challenges, Academy of Management Journal, Vol: 50(1), 25-32.
164. Eisenhardt, K.M. and Graebner, M.E., (2007). Theory building from cases: Opportunities and challenges. Academy of management journal, Vol: 50(1), pp.25-32.
165. Ejermo, O. and Xiao, J., (2014). Entrepreneurship and survival over the business cycle: how do new technology-based firms differ? Small Business Economics, Vol: 43(2), pp.411-426.
166. Elfil, M. and Negida, A., (2017). Sampling methods in clinical research; an educational review. Emergency, Vol: 5(1).
167. El-Khalil, R. and Mezher, M.A., (2020). The mediating impact of sustainability on the relationship between agility and operational performance. Operations Research Perspectives, Vol: 7, p.100171.
168. J. Elkington (1998) Partnerships from cannibals with forks: the triple bottom line of 21st-century business Environ. Qual. Manag. Vol: 6, pp. 37-51, 10.1002/tqem.3310080106.
169. Eloranta, V. and Koskimies, K., (2014). Lightweight Architecture Knowledge Management for Agile Software Development, In Agile Software Architecture (pp. 189-213). Morgan Kaufmann.
170. Enders, J.C. and Remig, M. eds., (2015). Theories of sustainable development (Vol. 52). London: Routledge.
171. Esfahbodi, A., Zhang, Y., Watson, G. and Zhang, T., (2017). Governance pressures and performance outcomes of sustainable supply chain management – An empirical analysis of UK manufacturing industry. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 155, pp.66-78.
172. Esubalew T.W., (2018). Software Development Methodologies and Practices in Startups-Systematic Literature. Submitted for University of Oulu.
173. Etikan, I., Alkassim, R. and Abubakar, S., (2016). Comparison of snowball sampling and sequential sampling technique. Biometrics and Biostatistics International Journal, Vol: 3(1), p.55.
174. Eyisi D. (2016) The Usefulness of Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches and Methods in Researching Problem-Solving Ability in Science Education Curriculum. Journal of Education and Practice, Vol: 7(15), 91-100.
175. Ezzy, D., (2013). Qualitative analysis. Pub: Routledge.
176. Fadhel K. (2002), Positivist and Hermeneutic Paradigm, A Critical Evaluation under their Structure of Scientific Practice, The Sosland Journal, pp. 21-28.
177. Fagerholm, F., Ikonen, M., Kettunen, P., Münch, J., Roto, V. and Abrahamsson, P., (2015). Performance Alignment Work: How software developers experience the continuous adaptation of team performance in Lean and Agile environments. Information and Software Technology, Vol: 64, pp.132-147.
178. Failory (2020) - Startup Failure Rate: How Many Startups Fail and Why? Failory [Online] January 9 Available: <https://www.failory.com/> [Accessed: 15 November 2020].

179. Fang, X., Misra, S., Xue, G. and Yang, D., (2012). Managing smart grid information in the cloud: opportunities, model, and applications. IEEE Network, Vol: 26(4), pp.32-38.
180. Fangmann, J., Looks, H., Thomaschewski, J. and Schön, E.M., (2020). Agile transformation in e-government projects. In 2020 15th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI) (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
181. Fatemi, A. and Fooladi, I., (2013). Sustainable finance: A new paradigm. Global Finance Journal, Vol: 24(2), pp.101-113.
182. Felin, T., Gambardella, A., Stern, S. and Zenger, T., (2019). Lean startup and the business model: Experimentation revisited. Forthcoming in Long Range Planning (Open Access).
183. Flint, D.J. and Golicic, S.L. (2009), Searching for competitive advantage through sustainability: A qualitative study in the New Zealand wine industry, International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol: 39(10), pp. 841-860, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09600030911011441>.
184. Forbes (2019) Startups Don't Need More Money— They Need More Customer Insights Forbes [Online] Available: forbes.com [Accessed: 14 March 2020].
185. Foss, N.J. and Saebi, T., (2018). Business models and business model innovation: Between wicked and paradigmatic problems. Long range planning, Vol: 51(1), pp.9-21.
186. Fowler, M. and Highsmith, J., (2001). The agile manifesto. Software development, Vol: 9(8), pp.28-35.
187. Fowler, M., (2004). UML distilled: a brief guide to the standard object modeling language. Addison-Wesley Professional.
188. Friess, E., (2018). Filling to Capacity: An Exploratory Study of Project Management Language in Agile Scrum Teams. Technical Communication, Vol: 65(2), pp.169-180.
189. Fuchs, C. and Hess, T., (2018). Becoming agile in the digital transformation: The process of a large-scale agile transformation.
190. Gandomani, T. J. and Ziaei Nafchi, M., (2016). Agile transition and adoption human-related challenges and issues: A Grounded Theory approach. Computers in Human Behavior, Vol: 62, pp.257-266.
191. Gandomani, T., Zulzalil, H., Javanmardi, A., Ghani, A., Sultan, A., Nafchi, M. (2013) How pre-start up assessment helps software companies in Agile Transition Science International, Vol: 25(1) pp. 1125-1130.
192. Gannod, G. C., Eberle, W. F., Talbert, D. A., Cooke, R. A., Kathy, H., Kathy, O., Jasmin, B., (2018). Establishing an Agile Mindset and Culture for Workforce Preparedness: A Baseline Study, 2018 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE), pp. 1-9, Available: doi: 10.1109/FIE.2018.8658712.
193. Gareis, R. Huemann, M. Martinuzzi, R-A. Weninger C. and Sedlacko, M. (2013) Project Management & Sustainable Development Principles, Project Management Institute, Newtown Square, PA, USA.
194. Gaurav, K. Pradeep B.K., (2012). Impact of agile methodology on software development process. International Journal of Computer Technology and Electronics Engineering (IJCTEE), Vol: 2(4), pp.46-50.
195. Gelmis, A., Ozkan, N., Ahmad, A.J., Guler, M.G. (2022). Impact of Turkish National Culture on Agile Software Development in Turkey. In: Przybyłek, A., Jarzębowski, A., Luković, I., Ng, Y.Y. (eds) Lean and Agile Software Development. LASD 2022. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, vol 438. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-94238-0_5.

196. GEM (2018) Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Reports [Online] Available: <https://www.gemconsortium.org/> [Accessed: 20 September 2018].
197. Gerster, D., Dremel, C., Brenner, W. and Kelker, P., (2020). How enterprises adopt agile forms of organizational design: A multiple-case study. ACM SIGMIS Database: The Database for Advances in Information Systems, Vol: 51(1), pp.84-103.
198. Geyi, W., El-Khalil, R. and Mezher, M., (2020). The mediating impact of sustainability on the relationship between agility and operational performance. Operations Research Perspectives, Vol: 7, p.100171.
199. Ghani, I. and Bello, M., (2015). Agile adoption in IT organizations. KSII Transactions on Internet and Information Systems (TIIS), Vol: 9(8), pp.3231-3248.
200. Ghani, I., Bello, M. and Bagiwa, I.L., (2015). A survey-based analysis of agile adoption on performances of IT organizations. Journal of Internet Computing and Services, Vol: 16(5), pp.87-92.
201. Ghauri, P., (2004). Designing and conducting case studies in international business research. Handbook of qualitative research methods for international business, pp.109-124.
202. Ghaziri, H. and Awad, E., (2005). Is there a future for knowledge management? Journal of Information Technology Management, Vol: 16(1), pp.31-38.
203. Ghezzi, A., & Cavallo, A. (2020). Agile business model innovation in digital entrepreneurship: Lean startup approaches. Journal of Business Research, Vol: 110, pp. 519–537.
204. Giannakis, M. and Papadopoulos, T., (2016). Supply chain sustainability: A risk management approach. International Journal of Production Economics, Vol: 171, pp.455-470.
205. Giardino, C., Wang, X. and Abrahamsson, P., (2014). Why early-stage software startups fail: a behavioral framework. In International conference of software business (pp. 27-41). Springer, Cham.
206. Gioia, D. A., Corley, K. G., and Hamilton, A. L. (2012). Seeking qualitative rigor in inductive research: notes on the Gioia methodology. Organizational Research Methods, Vol: 16(1), 15-31.
207. Golafshani, N. (2003). Understanding reliability and validity in qualitative research. The Qualitative Report, Vol: 8, pp. 597-607.
208. Golicic, S. and Smith, C., (2013). A Meta-Analysis of Environmentally Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices and Firm Performance. Journal of Supply Chain Management, Vol: 49(2), pp.78-95.
209. Gopaldas P., (2018). Evaluating market opportunity and delivering a successful product New Trends in Business Management, p.1. Zenon Academic Publishing.
210. Goss, J.D. and Leinbach, T.R., (1996). Focus groups as alternative research practice: experience with transmigrants in Indonesia. Area, pp.115-123.
211. Govardhan S. and Dr. Jeyakumaran, M. (2018) Business Incubator for startup India International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews, Vol: 5, Special Issue, E-ISSN 2348 –1269, Print ISSN 2349-5138.
212. Govindan, K, Lalmazloumian, M., Wong, K.Y., and Kannan, D., (2016). A robust optimization model for agile and build-to-order supply chain planning under uncertainties. Annals of Operations Research, Vol: 240(2), pp. 435-470.
213. Graue, C., (2015). Qualitative data analysis. International Journal of Sales, Retailing & Marketing, Vol: 4(9), pp. 183.

214. Gregory, P., Barroca, L., Taylor, K., Salah, D. and Sharp, H., (2015). Agile challenges in practice: a thematic analysis. In International Conference on Agile Software Development (pp. 64-80). Springer, Cham.
215. Gruber, M., MacMillan, I.C. and Thompson, J.D., (2008). Look before you leap: Market opportunity identification in emerging technology firms. Management science, Vol: 54(9), pp.1652-1665.
216. Gruber, M., Tal, S., (2017). Where to play. FT Publishing International.
217. Guba, E. G. & Lincoln, Y. S. (1994). Competing paradigms in qualitative research. In Denzin, N.K. & Lincoln, Y.S. Handbook of qualitative research, 3rd Edition. (pp. 105 – 117). California: Sage.
218. Guest, G., Bunce, A. and Johnson, L., (2006). How many interviews are enough? An experiment with data saturation and variability. Field methods, Vol: 18(1), pp. 59-82.
219. Gunasekaran, A., Yusuf, Y.Y., Adeleye, E.O., Papadopoulos, T., Kovvuri, D. and Geyi, D.A.G., (2019). Agile manufacturing: an evolutionary review of practices. International Journal of Production Research, Vol: 57(15-16), pp. 5154-5174.
220. Gupta, M., George J. F., Xia, W., (2019). Relationships between IT department culture and agile software development practices: An empirical investigation, International Journal of Information Management, Vol: 44, pp. 13-24, ISSN 0268-4012, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2018.09.006>.
221. Hahn, R. and Kühnen, M., (2013). Determinants of sustainability reporting: a review of results, trends, theory, and opportunities in an expanding field of research. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 59, pp. 5-21.
222. Hair, J.F., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M., Sarstedt, M. (2015) A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS–SEM). Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.
223. Hales, C. and Gooch, S., (2004). The Project Context. In Managing Engineering Design (pp. 23-51). Springer, London.
224. Hammad, M. Inayat I. and Zahid, M. (2019). Risk Management in Agile Software Development: A Survey, International Conference on Frontiers of Information Technology (FIT), pp. 162-1624, Available: doi: 10.1109/FIT47737.2019.00039.
225. Heale, R. and Forbes, D., (2013). Understanding triangulation in research. Evidence-based nursing, Vol: 16(4), pp. 98-98.
226. Heale, R. and Twycross, A., (2015). Validity and reliability in quantitative studies. Evidence-based nursing, Vol: 18(3), pp. 66-67.
227. Healy, M. and Perry, C., (2000). Comprehensive criteria to judge validity and reliability of qualitative research within the realism paradigm. Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal, Vol: 3(3), pp. 118-126.
228. Heidemeyer, C., (2020). The Agile Mindset: 11 tips for everyday life (part 3/3). [Online] June 9, Available: <https://echometerapp.com/en/agile-mindset-5/>.
229. Heikkilä, V.T., Paasivaara, M., Rautiainen, K., Lassenius, C., Toivola, T. and Järvinen, J., (2015). Operational release planning in large-scale Scrum with multiple stakeholders—A longitudinal case study at F-Secure Corporation. Information and Software Technology, Vol: 57, pp. 116-140.
230. Henderson S., B. Gill, A.Q., and Niazi, M., (2018). Scaling for agility: A reference model for hybrid traditional-agile software development methodologies. Information Systems Frontiers, Vol: 20(2), pp. 315-341.

231. Hess, D. and Warren, D.E., (2008). The meaning and meaningfulness of corporate social initiatives. Business and Society review, Vol: 113(2), pp. 163-197.
232. Hesse-Biber, S.N. and Leavy, P.L., (2004). Qualitative Research. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
233. Hijazi, H., Khmour, T. and Alarabeyyat, A., (2012). A review of risk management in different software development methodologies. International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol: 45(7), pp. 8-12.
234. Hirner, A., Esch, T., Asamer, H., Bachofer, F., Balhar, J., Boettcher, M., Boissier, E., d' Angelo, P., Gevaert, C., Jupova, K., Kurz, F., Kwarteng, A., Mathot, E., Marconcini, M., Marin, A., Metz-Marconcini, A., Pacini, F., Paganini, M., Permana, H., Soukup, T., Uereyen, S., Small, C., Svaton, V. and Zeidler, J., (2018). Digital world meets urban planet – new prospects for evidence-based urban studies arising from joint exploitation of big earth data, information technology and shared knowledge. International Journal of Digital Earth, Vol: 13(1), pp. 136-157.
235. Hock, M., Clauss, T. and Schulz, E., (2016). The impact of organizational culture on a firm's capability to innovate the business model. R&d Management, Vol: 46(3), pp.433-450.
236. Hoda, R. and Murugesan, L.K., (2016). Multi-level agile project management challenges: A self-organizing team perspective. Journal of Systems and Software, Vol: 117, pp.245-257.
237. Hoda, S., Hoeve, W.J.V. and Hooker, J.N., (2010). A systematic approach to MDD-based constraint programming. In International Conference on Principles and Practice of Constraint Programming (pp. 266-280). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
238. Hohl, P., Klünder, J., van Bennekum, A., Lockard, R., Gifford, J., Münch, J., Stupperich, M. and Schneider, K., (2018). Back to the future: origins and directions of the “Agile Manifesto”–views of the originators. Journal of Software Engineering Research and Development, Vol: 6(1), pp. 1-27.
239. Hörisch, J., Freeman, R. and Schaltegger, S., (2014). Applying Stakeholder Theory in Sustainability Management. Organization & Environment, Vol: 27(4), pp. 328-346.
240. Hu, Y., Zhang, X., Sun, X., Liu, M. and Du, J., (2009). An intelligent model for software project risk prediction. In 2009 International Conference on Information Management, Innovation Management and Industrial Engineering (Vol. 1, pp. 629-632). IEEE.
241. Hughes, J., & Sharrock, W. (1997). The philosophy of social research (3rd ed.). London: Longman.
242. Hussain, Z., Slany, W. and Holzinger, A., (2009). Investigating agile user-centered design in practice: A grounded theory perspective. In Symposium of the Austrian HCI and Usability Engineering Group (pp. 279-289). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
243. Hussey, J. and Hussey, R. (1997) Business research: a practical guide for undergraduate and postgraduate students. Basingstoke: Macmillan.
244. Hussman, D., Putman, D. (2004). How to Maintain and Promote Healthy Agile Culture. In: Eckstein, J., Baumeister, H. (eds) Extreme Programming and Agile Processes in Software Engineering. XP 2004. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 3092. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-24853-8_53.
245. Hyder, S. and Lussier, R.N. (2016), Why businesses succeed or fail: a study on small businesses in Pakistan, Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies, Vol: 8(1), pp. 82-100. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEEE-03-2015-0020>.

246. IBEF (2019) India Brand Equity Foundation: Information Technology IT and ITeS Industry Statistics in India [Online] Available: <https://www.ibef.org/> [Accessed: 10 October 2019].
247. Immelt, J. (2017), Inside GE's Transformation, Harvard Business Review, Available: <https://hbr.org/2017/09/inside-ge-transformation>.
248. Iosif, A., Koussouris, S., Papaspyros, D., Arvanitakis, E., Mouzakitis, S., Franken, S., Kolvenbach, S. and Prinz, W., (2016). User involvement in software development processes. Procedia Computer Science, Vol: 97, pp. 73-83.
249. Isomursu, M., Sirotkin, A., Voltti, P. and Halonen, M., (2012). User experience design goes agile in lean transformation--A Case Study. In 2012 Agile Conference (pp. 1-10). IEEE.
250. Jackson, S.E. and Ruderman, M.N., (1995). Diversity in work teams: Research paradigms for a changing workplace (pp. xv-271). American Psychological Association.
251. Jain, P., Sharma, A. and Ahuja, L., (2018). Software Maintainability Estimation in Agile Software Development. International Journal of Open Source Software and Processes (IJOSSP), Vol: 9(4), pp. 65-78.
252. Jeff. S. and Matt, R. S. (2013). The Agile start-up: Quick and dirty lessons every entrepreneur should know. John Wiley & Sons.
253. Jeffrey H. Dyer, H. S., Hesterly W. S. (2018). The relational view revisited: A dynamic perspective on value creation and value capture Strategic Management Journal, Vol: 39(12) pp. 3140-3162.
254. John, J. (2017) Lean or Agile: Lessons Learned from a Tech Startup PM World Journal [Online] Vol: 6(8) pp 1-20 Available: Research gate [Accessed: 22nd October 2018].
255. Johnson, KW. (1999). The role of culture in achieving organizational integrity and managing conflicts between cultures. Available: www.ethicaledge.com/quest_5.html.
256. Johnson, R.B. and Onwuegbuzie, A.J. (2004) Mixed Methods Research: A Research Paradigm Whose Time Has Come. Educational Researcher, Vol: 33, pp. 14-26.
257. Judith, B. G., Robert, N. L. (2015). Success Factors for Small Businesses in Guanajuato, Mexico International Journal of Business and Social Science, Vol: 6(11).
258. Jurca, G., Hellmann, T.D. and Maurer, F., (2014). Integrating agile and user-centered design: A systematic mapping and review of evaluation and validation studies of agile-UX. In 2014 Agile conference (pp. 24-32). IEEE.
259. Kalenda, M., Hyna, P. and Rossi, B., (2018). Scaling agile in large organizations: Practices, challenges, and success factors. Journal of Software: Evolution and Process, Vol: 30(10), p. 1954.
260. Kamei, F., Pinto, G., Cartaxo, B. and Vasconcelos, A., (2017). On the benefits/limitations of agile software development: an interview study with Brazilian companies. In Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software engineering (pp. 154-159).
261. Kaufmann, C., Kock, A. and Gemünden, H.G., (2020). Emerging strategy recognition in agile portfolios. International Journal of Project Management, Vol: 38(7), pp. 429-440.
262. Kautz, K., Johansen, T.H. and Uldahl, A., (2017). The perceived impact of the agile development and project management method scrum on process transparency in information systems development. In Complexity in Information Systems Development Vol: 22 (pp. 237-253). Springer, Cham.

263. Kelley, D. and Nakosteen, R., (2005). Technology Resources, Alliances, and Sustained Growth in New, Technology-Based Firms. IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management, Vol: 52(3), pp.292-300.
264. Khalifeh, A., Farrell, P., Alrousan, M., Alwardat, S. and Faisal, M. (2020), "Incorporating sustainability into software projects: a conceptual framework", International Journal of Managing Projects in Business, Vol. 13 No. 6, pp. 1339-1361. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMPB-12-2019-0289>
265. Khalil, C., & Khalil, S. (2016) A governance framework for adopting Agile Methodologies International Journal of e-Education, e-Business, e-Management and e-Learning, Vol: 6(2), pp. 111-119.
266. Khan, M., F., Khurram, A., Q., Ali, K., S., (2013). Performance Evaluation of Software Development Models Software Engineering Journal, Vol: 3(1), pp. 1-4.
267. Kim, B. (2001). Social constructivism. Emerging perspectives on learning, teaching, and technology, Vol: 1(1), p. 16.
268. Kim, S., Lee, H., Kwon, Y., Yu, M. and Jo, H., (2016). Our journey to becoming agile: Experiences with agile transformation in Samsung electronics. In 2016 23rd Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference (APSEC) (pp. 377-380). IEEE.
269. Korreck, S., (2019). The Indian startup ecosystem: Drivers, challenges and pillars of support. ORF Occasional Paper, (210).
270. Koziolk, H., (2011). Sustainability evaluation of software architectures, Proceedings of the joint ACM SIGSOFT conference -- QoSA and ACM SIGSOFT symposium -- ISARCS on Quality of software architectures -- QoSA and architecting critical systems -- ISARCS. [online] ACM Conferences. Available: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2000259.2000263> [Accessed 26 March 2022].
271. KPMG (2019), Agile or irrelevant: Redefining resilience KPMG [Online] Available: www.kpmg.org [Accessed: 29 January 2020].
272. Krauss, S.E., (2005). Research paradigms and meaning making: A primer. The qualitative report, Vol: 10(4), pp. 758-770.
273. Krishna, S., Ojha, A.K. and Barrett, M., (2017). Competitive advantage in the software industry: an analysis of the Indian experience. In Information technology in context (pp. 182-197). Routledge.
274. Krishnan, R. and Prashantham, S., (2019). Innovation in and from India: The who, where, what, and when. Global Strategy Journal, Vol: 9(3), pp. 357-377.
275. Krueger, R. (1994). Focus groups (Vol. 2). Thousand Oaks: Sage.
276. Krueger, R.A., Casey, M.A. (2000). Focus groups. A practical guide for applied research (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
277. Kuhn, T.S. (1962). The structure of scientific revolutions. Chicago Uni. Chicago Press.
278. Kuhrmann, M., Diebold, P., Münch, J., Tell, P., Garousi, V., Felderer, M., Trektere, K., McCaffery, F., Linssen, O., Hanser, E. and Prause, C.R., (2017). Hybrid software and system development in practice: waterfall, scrum, and beyond. In Proceedings of the 2017 International Conference on Software and System Process (pp. 30-39).
279. Labuschagne, C. and Brent, A., 2007. Sustainability assessment criteria for projects and technologies: Judgements of industry managers, The South African Journal of Industrial Engineering, Vol: 18(1).

280. Lahti, T., Wincent, J. and Parida, V., (2018). A Definition and Theoretical Review of the Circular Economy, Value Creation, and Sustainable Business Models: Where Are We Now and Where Should Research Move in the Future? Sustainability, Vol: 10(8), p. 2799.
281. Lan, Y. Unhelkar, B. (2005) Global Enterprise Transitions, Hershey, PA, USA: IGI Global.
282. Lappi, T., Karvonen, T., Lwakatare, L.E., Aaltonen, K. and Kuvaja, P., (2018). Toward an improved understanding of agile project governance: A systematic literature review. Project Management Journal, Vol: 49(6), pp. 39-63.
283. Lather, P. (1986). Research as praxis. Harvard Educational Review, Vol: 56(3), pp. 257-277.
284. Leasu, B., Y., Loo, K., W., Tham, Y., W., Tan, F., S., (2012) Software Development Life Cycle Agile Vs Traditional Approaches International Conference on Information and Network Technology, Vol: 37(1) pp. 162-166.
285. Leavy, P. (2014). Writing up qualitative research. In J. Gilgun (Ed.), The Oxford Handbook of Qualitative Research Oxford: Oxford University Press.
286. Lee, A. and Baskerville, R., (2003). Generalizing Generalizability in Information Systems Research. Information Systems Research, Vol: 14(3), pp.221-243.
287. Lee, S. and Yong, H.S., (2010). Distributed agile: project management in a global environment. Empirical software engineering, Vol: 15(2), pp. 204-217.
288. Leedy, P.D. and Ormrod, J.E., (2019). Practical research: Planning and design. Pearson. One Lake Street, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey 07458.
289. Lei, H., Ganjezadeh, F., Jayachandran, P.K. and Ozcan, P., (2017). A statistical analysis of the effects of Scrum and Kanban on software development projects. Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing, Vol: 43, pp. 59-67.
290. Lewis S., (2015). Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches. Health Promotion Practice, Vol: 16(4) pp. 473-475.
291. Li, L., Guan, Q., Jin, L. and Guo, M., (2019). Resource allocation and task offloading for heterogeneous real-time tasks with uncertain duration time in a fog queueing system. IEEE Access, Vol: 7, pp. 9912-9925.
292. Lieblich, A., Tuval-Mashiach, R., and Zilber, T. (1998). Narrative analysis: Reading, analysis, and interpretation. New Delhi, India: Sage Publications.
293. Lin, C.T., Chiu, H. and Tseng, Y.H., (2006). Agility evaluation using fuzzy logic. International Journal of Production Economics, Vol: 101(2), pp.353-368.
294. Lindsey, T.C., (2011). Sustainable principles: common values for achieving sustainability. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 19(5), pp. 561-565.
295. Lindvall, M., Basili, V., Boehm, B., Costa, P., Dangle, K. Shull, F. (2002), Empirical findings in agile methods, extreme programming and agile methods, Proceedings of the Second XP Universe and First Agile Universe Conference on Extreme Programming and Agile Methods – XP/Agile Universe, London, pp. 81-92, Springer, Available: www.cs.umd.edu/~mvz/pub/agile.pdf [Accessed: 10 March 2020].
296. Loiro, C., Castro, H., Ávila, P., Cruz-Cunha, M.M., Putnik, G.D. and Ferreira, L., (2019). Agile project management: A communicational workflow proposal. Procedia Computer Science, Vol: 164, pp. 485-490.
297. Longhurst, R., (2003). Semi-structured interviews and focus groups. Key methods in geography, Vol: 3(2), pp. 143-156.

298. Lonkar, S. and Gupte, R., (2017). New Product Development and Innovation for Sustainable Profitable Businesses of Indian Small and Medium Scale Industries (SMEs) and Startups. Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development, Vol: 8(4), p. 993.
299. Lopez-Valeiras, E., Gomez-Conde, J. and Naranjo-Gil, D., (2015). Sustainable Innovation, Management Accounting and Control Systems, and International Performance. Sustainability, Vol: 7(3), pp. 3479-3492.
300. Lucas, Jr., H., Agarwal, R., Clemons, E., El Sawy, O. and Weber, B., (2013). Impactful Research on Transformational Information Technology: An Opportunity to Inform New Audiences. MIS Quarterly, Vol: 37(2), pp. 371-382.
301. Lüdeke-Freund, F. and Boons, F., (2013). Business models for sustainable innovation: state-of-the-art and steps towards a research agenda. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 45, pp. 9-19.
302. Mahalakshmi, M., Sundararajan, M. (2013) Traditional SDLC Vs Scrum Methodology – A Comparative Study International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering [Online] Vol: 3(6), pp. 192-196, Available: www.ijetae.com [Accessed: 12 November 2019]
303. Mahaux, M., Heymans, P. and Saval, G., (2011). Discovering sustainability requirements: an experience report. In International Working Conference on Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality (pp. 19-33). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
304. Mali, S. and Ananth, S. (2012). Understanding post-adoptive agile usage: An exploratory cross-case analysis. Journal of Systems and Software, Vol: 85(6), pp. 1255-1268.
305. Malik, M., Sarwar, S. and Orr, S., (2021). Agile practices and performance: Examining the role of psychological empowerment. International Journal of Project Management, Vol: 39(1), pp. 10-20.
306. Mamaghani, E.J. and Medini, K., (2021). Resilience, agility and risk management in production ramp-up. Procedia CIRP, Vol: 103, pp. 37-41.
307. Manuel, K., (2012) A critical investigation of the merits and drawbacks of in-depth interviews 1st ed Pub: GRIN Verlag
308. Marçal, A.S.C., Soares, F.S.F., de Freitas, B.C.C. and Belchior, A.D., (2007). Mapping CMMI project management process areas to SCRUM practices. In 31st IEEE Software Engineering Workshop (SEW 2007) (pp. 13-22). IEEE.
309. Maria, V. Palacin-Silva, Ahmed, S., Jari, P., (2018) Infusing sustainability into software engineering education: Lessons learned from capstone projects, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 172, pp. 4338-4347, ISSN 0959-6526, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.06.078>.
310. Marian, S., Bogedan, G., Marinela, M., Cristian, U., (2016) Analyzing Agile development from Waterfall style to Scrumban Informatica Economica, Vol: 20(4), pp 5-14.
311. Marion, T.J., Friar, J.H. and Cullinane, T., (2012). A Multi-Disciplinary New Product Development Course for Technological Entrepreneurs. Journal of the Academy of Business Education, Vol: 13.
312. Marschan-Piekkari, R., Welch, C., (2004) Qualitative Research Methods in International Business: The State of the Art, in Marschan-Piekkari, R./ Welch, C. (eds.), Handbook of Qualitative Research Methods for International Business, Cheltenham: Edward Elgar 2004, pp. 5–24.

313. Marshall, S., Gupta, A., Calfas, K., Robinson, T., Rock, C., Huang, J., Epstein-Corbin, M., Servetas, C., Donohue, M., Norman, G., Raab, F., Merchant, G., Fowler, J., Griswold, W., Fogg, B. and Patrick, K., (2015). Clinical trial management of participant recruitment, enrollment, engagement, and retention in the SMART study using a Marketing and Information Technology (MARKIT) model. Contemporary Clinical Trials, Vol: 42, pp. 185-195.
314. Maslow A. H. (2013) Toward a Psychology of Being Pub: Simon and Schuster.
315. Mathiyazhagan, K. Agarwal, V. Appolloni, A. Saikouk, T Gnanavelbabu, A. (2021). Integrating lean and agile practices for achieving global sustainability goals in Indian manufacturing industries, Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Vol: 171, p. 120982, ISSN 0040-1625, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120982>.
316. Mathur J, D. and Khurana, R., (2013). Need for sustainable global business model in software outsourcing. Business Process Management Journal, Vol: 19(1), pp. 54-69.
317. Matt, M., (2018) STARTUP Statistics – The Number you need to Know Small Business Trends [Online] 15 May Available: Small Business Trends [Accessed: 01 October 2018]
318. Mawhinney, C., (2011). Information Systems Academic Program Assessment: A Comparison of Objective and Subjective Approaches. International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER), Vol: 1(9).
319. Maxwell, J. (2013). Qualitative Research Design: An Interactive Approach (Vol. 3). Thousand Oaks: Sage.
320. McAdam, M. and McAdam, R., (2008). High tech start-ups in University Science Park incubators: The relationship between the start-up's lifecycle progression and use of the incubator's resources. Technovation, Vol: 28(5), pp. 277-290.
321. McKeown, I. and Philip, G., (2003). Business transformation, information technology and competitive strategies: learning to fly. International Journal of Information Management, Vol: 23(1), pp. 3-24.
322. Measy, P., (2015). Agile Foundations: Principles, Practices and Framework. BCS Learning & Development.
323. Melo, C., Cruzes, D.S., Kon, F. and Conradi, R., (2011), August. Agile team perceptions of productivity factors. In 2011 Agile Conference (pp. 57-66). IEEE.
324. Melo, O C.D. and Kon, F., (2011), May. Empirical evaluation of agile practices impacts on team productivity. In International Conference on Agile Software Development, Vol: 77, pp. 322-323. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
325. Mensah, J. and Enu-Kwesi, F., (2019). Implications of environmental sanitation management for sustainable livelihoods in the catchment area of Benya Lagoon in Ghana. Journal of Integrative Environmental Sciences, Vol: 16(1), pp.23-43.
326. Michael J. Bianchi, Daniel C. Amaral, Edivandro C. Conforto, (2016). Diagnostic Techniques in Project Management pp. 749 - 757 Available DOI10.3233/978-1-61499-703-0-749, Series Advances in Transdisciplinary Engineering Ebook Vol: 4, Transdisciplinary Engineering: Crossing Boundaries
327. Micic, L. (2017) Agile methodology selection criteria: IT start-up case study Conference Proceedings of IOP Conference Series: Materials science and engineering Pub: Bosnia and Herzegovina
328. Middleton, P. and Sutton, J., (2005). Lean software strategies: proven techniques for managers and developers. CRC Press.

329. Mikhieieva, O. and Stephan, K., (2020). A Retrospective on Agile Transformations: Survey Results on Agility of German Organisations. In 2020 IEEE European Technology and Engineering Management Summit (E-TEMS) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
330. Mikulenas, G. and Kapocius, K., (2011). An approach for prioritizing agile practices for adaptation. In Information Systems Development (pp. 485-498). Springer, New York, NY. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-7355-9_41.
331. Miler, J. and Gaida, P., (2019). On the agile mindset of an effective team—an industrial opinion survey. In 2019 federated conference on computer science and information systems (fedcsis) (pp. 841-849). IEEE.
332. Miler, J., Gaida, P. (2020). Identification of the Agile Mindset and Its Comparison to the Competencies of Selected Agile Roles. In: Przybyłek, A., Morales-Trujillo, M. (eds) Advances in Agile and User-Centred Software Engineering. LASD MIDI 2019. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, Vol: 376. Springer, Cham. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37534-8_3.
333. Mill, G.A., (2006). The financial performance of a socially responsible investment over time and a possible link with corporate social responsibility. Journal of Business Ethics, Vol: 63(2), pp. 131-148.
334. Milne, M.J. and Gray, R., (2013). W (h)ither ecology? The triple bottom line, the global reporting initiative, and corporate sustainability reporting. Journal of business ethics, Vol: 118(1), pp. 13-29.
335. Moran, A., (2015). Managing agile. Strategy, implementation, organization and People. Cham: Springer.
336. Moravcová, B. and Legény, F., (2016). Agile Adoption in IT Companies-Building a Change Capability by Qualitative Description of Agile Implementation in Different Companies. In International Conference on Exploring Services Science (pp. 251-262). Springer, Cham.
337. Morgan, D.L., (1997). Planning and research design for focus groups. Focus groups as qualitative research, Vol: 16(10.4135), p.9781412984287.
338. Morgan, R. and Page, K., (2008). Managing business transformation to deliver strategic agility. Strategic Change, Vol: 17(5-6), pp. 155-168.
339. Morioka, S.N. and de Carvalho, M.M., 2016. A systematic literature review towards a conceptual framework for integrating sustainability performance into business. Journal of Cleaner Production, 136, pp.134-146.
340. Morse, J. M. (1994). Designing funded qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), Handbook of Qualitative Research (pp. 220-235). Thousand Oaks: Sage.
341. Mougouei, D., Shen, H. and Babar, M.A., (2015). Partial selection of agile software requirements. International Journal of Software Engineering and Its Applications, Vol: 9(1), pp. 113-126.
342. Mueller, S., Volery, T. and Von Siemens, B., 2012. What do entrepreneurs actually do? An observational study of entrepreneurs' everyday behavior in the start-up and growth stages. Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice, 36(5), pp.995-1017.
343. Müller, R.M. and Thoring, K., (2012). Design thinking vs. lean startup: A comparison of two user-driven innovation strategies. Leading through design, Vol: 151, pp. 91-106.
344. Nabil, M., Ali, M., Govardhan, A., (2010) A Comparison Between Five Models of Software Engineering IJCSI International Journal of Computer Science Issues, Vol: 7(5), pp. 94 – 101.

345. Narayanan, S., Ram, N., Tobias, S., (2015). Assessing the contingent effects of collaboration on agility performance in buyer–supplier relationships, Journal of Operations Management, Vol: 33–34, pp. 140-154, ISSN 0272-6963, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2014.11.004>.
346. NASSCOM (2017) Indian Start-up Ecosystem – Traversing the Maturity cycle NASSCOM [Online] Available: <https://nasscom.in/> [Accessed: 01 November 2018].
347. NASSCOM (2019) Annual Report 2017-18: IT-BPM start-up sector in India NASSCOM [Online] Available: <https://nasscom.in/> [Accessed: 14 October 2019].
348. Nath, U.K., Jagadev, A.K. and Pattnaik, P.K., 2021. An efficient model of schedule accuracy using PAS agile simulation model. Materials Today: Proceedings.
349. Naumann, S., Kern, E., Dick, M. and Johann, T., (2015). Sustainable software engineering: Process and quality models, life cycle, and social aspects. In ICT Innovations for Sustainability (pp. 191-205). Springer, Cham.
350. Nerur, S., Mahapatra, R. and Mangalaraj, G., (2005). Challenges of migrating to agile methodologies. Communications of the ACM, Vol: 48(5), pp. 72-78.
351. Nguyen, V.H., (2021). Towards an Agile Quality Management Model for Microservice Architecture in FinTech. In Proceedings of the Future Technologies Conference (pp. 471-485). Springer, Cham.
352. Niazi, M., Mahmood, S., Alshayeb, M., Qureshi, A.M., Faisal, K. and Cerpa, N., (2016). Toward successful project management in global software development. International Journal of Project Management, Vol: 34(8), pp. 1553-1567.
353. Nicholas, W. (2005) Your Research Project: A Step-by-step Guide for the First-time Researcher, Sage Publications.
354. Nidumolu, R., Prahalad, C.K. and Rangaswami, M.R., (2009). Why sustainability is now the key driver of innovation. Harvard business review, Vol: 87(9), pp. 56-64.
355. Noguera, I., Guerrero-Roldán, A.E. and Masó, R., (2018). Collaborative agile learning in online environments: Strategies for improving team regulation and project management. Computers & Education, Vol: 116, pp. 110-129.
356. Nomi, B., (2015). Requirement management in agile software environment. Procedia Computer Science, Vol: 62, pp. 81-83.
357. Noshir, C. Satyam, M., Huang, Y., Neidhardt, J., Uzzi, B., (2019). Prior shared success predicts victory in team competitions. Nature Human Behaviour, Vol: 3(1), pp. 74-81.
358. Noteboom, C., Ofori, M., Sutrave, K. and El-Gayar, O., (2021). Agile project management: a systematic literature review of adoption drivers and critical success factors. In Proceedings of the 54th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (p. 6775).
359. Nowell, L.S., Norris, J.M., White, D.E. and Moules, N.J., (2017). Thematic analysis: Striving to meet the trustworthiness criteria. International journal of qualitative methods, Vol: 16(1), p.1609406917733847.
360. Ofer, Z., Raghuvar, D. P., Gurmeet, S., Shamsuddin, A., The moderating effect of risk on the relationship between planning and success, International Journal of Project Management, Vol: 32(3), pp. 435-441, ISSN 0263-7863, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2013.07.002>.
361. Olawale, F. and Garwe, D., (2010). Obstacles to the growth of new SMEs in South Africa: A principal component analysis approach. African journal of Business management, Vol: 4(5), pp. 729-738.

362. Oliva, F. and Kotabe, M., (2019). Barriers, practices, methods and knowledge management tools in startups. Journal of Knowledge Management, Vol: 23(9), pp. 1838-1856, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-06-2018-0361>.
363. Oliva, F., Kotabe, M., Teberga, P., Testi, L., Giudice, M., Kelle, P. and Cunha, M., (2022). Risks and critical success factors in the internationalization of born global startups of industry 4.0: A social, environmental, economic, and institutional analysis. Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Vol: 175, p. 121346.
364. Olszewska (née Płaska), M., Heidenberg, J., Weijola, M., Mikkonen, K. and Porres, I., (2016). Quantitatively measuring a large-scale agile transformation. Journal of Systems and Software, Vol: 117, pp. 258-273.
365. Omair, A., (2014). Sample size estimation and sampling techniques for selecting a representative sample. Journal of Health specialties, Vol: 2(4), p. 142.
366. Onwuegbuzie, A.J., Dickinson, W.B., Leech, N.L., and Zoran, A.G. (2009). A Qualitative Framework for Collecting and Analyzing Data in Focus Group Research, International Journal of Qualitative Methods, Vol: 8(3), pp. 1-21.
367. Orsato, R.J., Garcia, A., Mendes-Da-Silva, W., Simonetti, R. and Monzoni, M., (2015). Sustainability indexes: why join in? A study of the 'Corporate Sustainability Index (ISE)' in Brazil. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 96, pp. 161-170.
368. Osterwalder, A. and Pigneur, Y., (2010). Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers, (Vol. 1). John Wiley & Sons.
369. Ozuem, W., Howell, K. E., & Lancaster, G. (2008). Communicating in the new interactive marketplace. European Journal of Marketing, Vol: 42(9/10), pp. 1059-1083.
370. Pandita, R. and Singh, S., (2017). Doctoral Theses Awarded in Library and Information Science in India during 2010-2014: A Study. DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology, Vol: 37(6), p. 379.
371. Paternoster, N., Giardino, C., Unterkalmsteiner, M., Gorschek, T. and Abrahamsson, P., (2014). Software development in startup companies: A systematic mapping study. Information and Software Technology, Vol: 56(10), pp. 1200-1218.
372. Patton, M. (1990). Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods. Beverly Hills: Sage.
373. Patton, M.Q., (1999). Enhancing the quality and credibility of qualitative analysis. Health services research, Vol: 34(5 Pt 2), p. 1189.
374. Patton, M.Q., (2002). Two decades of developments in qualitative inquiry: A personal, experiential perspective. Qualitative social work, Vol: 1(3), pp. 261-283.
375. Paulraj, A., Chen, I.J. and Blome, C. (2017) Motives and Performance Outcomes of Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices: A Multi-Theoretical Perspective. Journal in Business Ethics, Vol: 145, pp. 239–258. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-015-2857-0>.
376. Pedro, S. and Jeffrey, P.K., (2015). Does Agile work? A quantitative analysis of agile project success. International journal of project management, Vol: 33(5), pp. 1040-1051.
377. Pekrun, R., Goetz, T., Titz, W. and Perry, R.P., (2002). Academic emotions in students' self-regulated learning and achievement: A program of qualitative and quantitative research. Educational psychologist, Vol: 37(2), pp. 91-105.
378. Penzenstadler, B. and Femmer, H., (2013). A generic model for sustainability with process- and product-specific instances. In Proceedings of the 2013 workshop on Green in/by software engineering (pp. 3-8).

379. Petit, Y. and Marnewick, C., (2021). Strategic alignment of information technology initiatives in a scaled agile environment. *The Journal of Modern Project Management*, 8(3).
380. Petrillo, A., Di Bona, G., Forcina, A. and Silvestri, A., 2018. Building excellence through the Agile Reengineering Performance Model (ARPM). *Business Process Management Journal*, Vol: 24(1), pp. 128-157.
381. Pfleeger, S.L. and Atlee, J., (2006). *Software Engineering: Theory and Practice*. Pub: Pearson International edition
382. Philipp, P., Uludag, Ö., Putta, A., Paasivaara, M., Lassenius, C. and Matthes, F., (2020). Revealing the state-of-the-art in large-scale agile development: A systematic mapping study. [arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.05578](https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.05578).
383. Piaget, J. (1967). *Biologie et connaissance (Biology and knowledge)*, Paris, Gallimard.
384. Pirolo, L. and Presutti, M., (2010). The impact of social capital on the start-ups' performance growth. *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol: 48(2), pp. 197-227.
385. Porter, M.E. and Kramer, M.R., (2011). Creating shared value: Redefining capitalism and the role of the corporation in society. *Harvard Business Review*, Vol: 89(1/2), pp. 62-77.
386. Potter, J. and Wetherell, M., (1994). Analyzing discourse. *Analyzing qualitative data*, pp. 47-66.
387. Preisendörfer, P., Bitz, A. and Bezuidenhout, F.J., (2012). Business start-ups and their prospects of success in South African townships. *South African Review of Sociology*, Vol: 43(3), pp. 3-23.
388. Pressman, R.S., (2005). *Software engineering: a practitioner's approach*. Palgrave Macmillan.
389. Prochazka, J., (2011). Agile support and Maintenance of IT services. *In Information Systems Development* (pp. 597-609). Springer, New York, NY.
390. Purvis, B., Mao, Y. and Robinson, D., (2019). Three pillars of sustainability: in search of conceptual origins. *Sustainability science*, Vol: 14(3), pp. 681-695.
391. PwC (2017). *Agile Project Delivery Confidence: Mitigate project risks and deliver value to your business* PwC [Online] Available: PwC [Accessed: 12 November 2018]
392. Qumer, A. and Henderson-Sellers, B., (2008). A framework to support the evaluation, adoption and improvement of agile methods in practice. *Journal of Systems and Software*, Vol: 81(11), pp. 1899-1919.
393. Qureshi, M.R.J., (2012). Agile software development methodology for medium and large projects. *IET software*, Vol: 6(4), pp. 358-363.
394. Radha, R. and Ilankumaran, G., (2018). Indian startups – Issues, challenges and opportunities, *Advance and Innovative Research*, p.109.
395. Rahayu, P., Sensuse, D.I., Purwandari, B., Budi, I. and Zulkarnaim, N., (2016). Review on e-Portfolio definition, model, type and system. *In 2016 International Conference on Information Technology Systems and Innovation (ICITSI)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
396. Rajagopalan, S. and Mathew, S.K., (2016). Choice of agile methodologies in software development: a vendor perspective. *Journal of International Technology and Information Management*, Vol: 25(1), p. 3.
397. Rajesh, R. and Ravi, V., (2015). Supplier selection in resilient supply chains: a grey relational analysis approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol: 86, pp. 343-359.
398. Rand, C. and Eckfeldt, B., (2004). Aligning strategic planning with agile development: Extending agile thinking to business improvement. *In Agile Development Conference* (pp. 78-82). IEEE.

399. Reich, B.H. and Benbasat, I., (2000). Factors that influence the social dimension of alignment between business and information technology objectives. MIS quarterly, pp. 81-113.
400. Reifer, D.J., (2002). How good are agile methods? IEEE software, Vol: 19(4), pp. 16-18.
401. Reim, W., Parida, V. and Örtqvist, D., (2015). Product–Service Systems (PSS) business models and tactics—a systematic literature review. Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol: 97, pp. 61-75.
402. Renzl, B., Mahringer, C.A., Rost, M. and Scheible, L., (2021). Organizational Agility: Current Challenges and Future Opportunities. Journal of Competences, Vol: 11, pp. 1-10.
403. Rerup, C. and Feldman, M.S., (2011). Routines as a source of change in organizational schemata: The role of trial-and-error learning. Academy of Management Journal, Vol: 54(3), pp. 577-610.
404. Richard, A., Sally, J., John, B., David, D., Patrick, O. (2015). Sustainability-oriented Innovation: A Systematic Review International Journal of Management Reviews, Vol: 18(2) p. 180-205, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijmr.12068>.
405. Richard, L., Coder, R., and Holzinger, M., (2014). Improved models for attitude estimation of agile space objects. Advanced Maui Optical and Space Surveillance Technologies (AMOS), pp. 15-231.
406. Ries, E., (2011). The lean startup: How today's entrepreneurs use continuous innovation to create radically successful businesses. Currency.
407. Rigby, P.C., Zhu, Y.C., Donadelli, S.M. and Mockus, A., (2016). Quantifying and mitigating turnover-induced knowledge loss: case studies of Chrome and a project at Avaya. In 2016 IEEE/ACM 38th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE) (pp. 1006-1016). IEEE.
408. Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., Nicholls, C. M., & Ormston, R. (2013). Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers. Sage.
409. Roberto, P., Guido, B., Marco, B. (2022). What drives the growth of start-up firms? A tool for mapping the state-of-the-art of the empirical literature European Journal of Innovation Management, Vol: 25(6), pp. 242-272, Emerald Publishing Limited 1460-1060 DOI 10.1108/EJIM-03-2021-0163.
410. Robson, C. (2007). Real World Research (Vol. 2). Chichester: Blackwell.
411. Robson, S., (2013). Agile SAP: introducing flexibility, transparency and speed to SAP implementations. IT Governance Ltd.
412. Rodríguez, P., Yagüe, A., Alarcón, P.P. and Garbajosa, J., (2009). Some findings concerning requirements in agile methodologies. In International Conference on Product-Focused Software Process Improvement (pp. 171-184). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
413. Roque, L., Araújo, A.A., Dantas, A., Saraiva, R. and Souza, J., (2016). Human resource allocation in agile software projects based on task similarities. In International Symposium on Search Based Software Engineering, Vol: 9962, pp. 291-297. Springer, Cham.
414. Rosenberg, S. (2015). Organizational Culture Aspects of an Agile Transformation. In: Lassenius, C., Dingsøyr, T., Paasivaara, M. (eds) Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming. XP 2015. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, vol 212. Springer, Cham. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-18612-2_28.
415. Rossman, G.B., Rallis, S.F. and Rossman, G.B., (1998). The researcher as learner. Learning in the field: an introduction to qualitative research Pub: Sage.

416. Sachdeva, V., (2017). Requirements Prioritization in Agile: Use of Planning Poker for Maximizing Return. In Information Technology-New Generations: 14th International Conference on Information Technology (Vol. 558, p. 403). Springer.
417. Sahil, B., Ankur, S., Usha, R. (2017) A detailed study of Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) Models International Journal of Engineering and Computer Science Vol: 6(7), pp. 22097-22100.
418. Sánchez-Gordón, M.L. and O'Connor, R.V., (2016). Understanding the gap between software process practices and actual practice in very small companies. Software Quality Journal, Vol: 24(3), pp. 549-570.
419. Sandelewski, M., (2000). Combining qualitative and quantitative sampling, data collection, and analysis techniques in mixed-method studies. Research in nursing & health, Vol: 23(3), pp.246-255.
420. Sandelowski, M., (2008). Reading, writing and systematic review. Journal of advanced nursing, Vol: 64(1), pp. 104-110.
421. Santiago, O., Emre, E., (2017) The Agile transition in software development companies: The most common barriers and how to overcome them Business and Management Research [Online] Vol: 6(4), pp. 40-53 Available: bmr.sciedupress.com [Accessed: 15th October 2018].
422. Santisteban, J. and David, M., (2017). Systematic literature review of critical success factors of Information Technology startups, Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal, Vol: 23(2) pp. 1-23 [Accessed 6 March 2022].
423. Santisteban, J. and Mauricio, D., (2017). Systematic literature review of critical success factors of information technology startups. Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal, Vol: 23(2), pp. 1-23.
424. Santos, M.D.A., Bermejo, P.H.D.S., de Oliveira, M.S., Tonelli, A.O. and Seidel, E.J., (2013). Improving the management of cost and scope in software projects using agile practices. International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT) Vol: 5(1), pp. 47-64, DOI: 10.5121/ijcsit.2013.5104.
425. Sara, A., Arif, B., Waleed, R. (2015) - A Survivability Model for Saudi ICT Start-ups AIRCC's International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, Vol: 7(2), pp. 145-157.
426. Sarantakos, S., (1998). Varieties of social research. In Social research (pp. 31-71). Palgrave, London.
427. Satar, M. and John, S., (2016). A conceptual model of critical success factors for Indian social enterprises. World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development, Vol: 12(2).
428. Saunders, B., Sim, J., Kingstone, T., Baker, S., Waterfield, J., Bartlam, B., Burroughs, H. and Jinks, C., (2018). Saturation in qualitative research: exploring its conceptualization and operationalization. Quality & quantity, Vol: 52(4), pp. 1893-1907.
429. Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2009) Research Methods for Business Students. Pearson, New York.
430. Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2012) Research Methods for Business Students. Pearson Education Ltd., Harlow.
431. Saunders, M.N. and Townsend, K., (2016). Reporting and justifying the number of interview participants in organization and workplace research. British Journal of Management, Vol: 27(4), pp. 836-852.

432. Savitz, A.W. and Weber, K., (2007). The sustainability sweet spot. Environmental quality management, Vol: 17(2), pp. 17-28.
433. Schaltegger, S., (2002). The link between 'green' and economic success: environmental management as the crucial trigger between environmental and economic performance. Journal of Environmental Management, Vol: 65(4), pp. 339-346.
434. Schaltegger, S., Beckmann, M. and Hansen, E.G., (2013). Transdisciplinarity in corporate sustainability: Mapping the field. Business Strategy and the Environment, Vol: 22(4), pp. 219-229.
435. Schatz, B. and Abdelshafi, I., (2005). Primavera gets agile: a successful transition to agile development. IEEE software, Vol: 22(3), pp. 36-42.
436. Schein EH. (1999). The Corporate Culture Survival Guide. Jossey-Bass: San Francisco, CA.
437. Schlauderer, S. and Overhage, S., (2013). Exploring the customer perspective of agile development: Acceptance factors and on-site customer perceptions in scrum projects.
438. Schneider, S. and Spieth, P., (2013). Business model innovation: Towards an integrated future research agenda. International Journal of Innovation Management, Vol: 17(1), p. 1340001.
439. Schwandt, T.A., (2001). Dictionary of qualitative research. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
440. Schwartz, SH and Bilsky, W. (1987), Toward a universal structure of human values, Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, Vol: 53, pp. 550-562.
441. Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R., (2016). Research methods for business: A skill building approach. John Wiley & Sons.
442. Shanmugasundaram, S., (2019). Internationalization and governance of Indian family-owned business groups. Journal of Family Business Management.
443. Sharma, S., Sarkar, D. and Gupta, D., (2012). Agile processes and methodologies: A conceptual study. International journal on computer science and Engineering, Vol: 4(5), p. 892.
444. Shenton, A. (2004). Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects. Education for Information, Vol: 22, pp. 63-75.
445. Shorten, A. and Moorley, C., (2014). Selecting the sample. Evidence-based nursing, Vol: 17(2), pp. 32-33.
446. Shrivastava, R., Hota, C. and Shrivastava, P., (2017). Protection against code exploitation using ROP and check-summing in IoT environment. In 2017 5th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoIC7) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
447. Signoretti, I. Marczak, S. Salerno, L. Lara A. d.and Bastos, R. (2019) Boosting Agile by Using User-Centered Design and Lean Startup: A Case Study of the Adoption of the Combined Approach in Software Development, ACM/IEEE International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement (ESEM), pp. 1-6, Available: doi: 10.1109/ESEM.2019.8870154.
448. Silva, H., Silveira, D., Dornelas, J. and Ferreira, H., (2019). Information Technology Governance in Small and Medium Enterprises - a Systematic Mapping, Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management, Vol: 17, pp.1-16.
449. Silverman, D., (1998). Qualitative research: meanings or practices? Information systems journal, Vol: 8(1), pp. 3-20.
450. Silvius, G. and Tharp, J., (2013). Sustainability integration for effective project management. Hershey, Pa.: IGI Global.

451. Singh, B., Nair, J., and Chellasamy, A. (2019). Readiness factors for information technology adoption in SMEs: testing an exploratory model in an Indian context. Journal of Asia Business Studies, Vol: 13(4), pp. 694-718.
452. Singh, I. and Kaur, N., 2017. Contribution of information technology in growth of Indian economy, International Journal of Research, Vol: 5(6), pp. 1-9.
453. Skop, E., (2006). The methodological potential of focus groups in population geography. Population, space and place, Vol: 12(2), pp. 113-124.
454. Soeken, M., Wille, R. and Drechsler, R., (2012). Assisted behavior driven development using natural language processing. In International Conference on Modelling Techniques and Tools for Computer Performance Evaluation (pp. 269-287). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
455. Spiegel, O., Abbassi, P., Zylka, M.P., Schlagwein, D., Fischbach, K. and Schoder, D., (2016). Business model development, founders' social capital and the success of early stage internet start-ups: a mixed-method study. Information Systems Journal, Vol: 26(5), pp. 421-449.
456. Srinivas, Subbarao, P., Suseela Rani, P. (2015). Strategies to Adopt Information Technology in SMEs Encyclopedia of Information Science and Technology, Third Edition DOI: 10.4018/978-1-4666-5888-2.ch659.
457. Srivastava, A., Bhardwaj, S. and Saraswat, S., (2017). SCRUM model for agile methodology. In 2017 International Conference on Computing, Communication and Automation (ICCCA) (pp. 864-869). IEEE.
458. Stake, R. (1978). The case study method in social inquiry. Educational Researcher, Vol: 7, pp. 5-8.
459. Stare, A., (2014). Agile project management in product development projects. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences, Vol: 119, pp. 295-304.
460. Statista (2019) Volume of startup exits worldwide from 2011 to 2018 Statista [Online] Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/885810/global-startup-exits/> [Accessed: 20 April 2020].
461. Stefan, K. and Turk, G., (2011). Human resource related problems in agile and traditional software project process models. International Journal of Information Technology Project Management (IJITPM), Vol: 2(2), pp. 1-13.
462. Stenbacka, C. (2001). Qualitative research requires quality concepts of its own. Management Decision, Vol: 39(7), pp. 551-555.
463. Stephen, D. (2016) How to make the whole organization “Agile” Journal on Strategy & Leadership, Vol: 44(4), pp. 10-17.
464. Stephen, D. (2018). How major corporations are making sense of Agile, Strategy & Leadership, Vol: 46(1), pp. 3-9.
465. Stettina, C.J. and Hörz, J., (2015). Agile portfolio management: An empirical perspective on the practice in use. International Journal of Project Management, Vol: 33(1), pp. 140-152.
466. Stoddart, M.C., (2011). If we wanted to be environmentally sustainable, we'd take the bus: Skiing, mobility and the irony of climate change. Human Ecology Review, pp. 19-29.
467. Stoica, I., Xin, R.S., Rosen, J., Franklin, M.J., Shenker, S. and Zaharia, M., (2013). Shark: SQL and rich analytics at scale. In Proceedings of the 2013 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of data (pp. 13-24).
468. Strauss, A. and Corbin, J., (1998). Basics of qualitative research techniques. Pub: Sage.

469. Strauss, A., and Corbin, J. (1990). Basics of Qualitative Research: Grounded Theory Procedures and Techniques. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
470. Sukamolson, S., (2007). Fundamentals of quantitative research. Language Institute Chulalongkorn University, Vol: 1(3), pp. 1-20.
471. Sulayman, M., Mendes, E., Urquhart, C., Riaz, M. and Tempero, E., (2014). Towards a theoretical framework of SPI success factors for small and medium web companies. Information and Software Technology, Vol: 56(7), pp. 807-820.
472. Sushil, (2017). Multi-criteria valuation of flexibility initiatives using integrated TISM – IRP with a big data framework, Production Planning & Control, Vol: 28(11-12), pp. 999-1010, DOI: 10.1080/09537287.2017.1336794.
473. Sutherland, J. and Tabaka, J., (2007). Incorporating Lean Development Practices into Agile Software Development. In 2007 40th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS'07) (pp. 273-273). IEEE.
474. Sverrisdottir, H.S., Ingason, H.T. and Jonasson, H.I., (2014). The role of the product owner in scrum-comparison between theory and practices. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences, Vol: 119, pp. 257-267.
475. Sweetman, R., Conboy, K. (2018) Portfolios of Agile Projects: A Complex Adaptive Systems' Agent Perspective Project Management Journal, Vol: 49(6), pp. 18-38, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/8756972818802712>.
476. Szekely, F. and Strebel, H., (2013). Incremental, radical and game-changing: strategic innovation for sustainability. Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society, Vol: 13(5), pp. 467-481.
477. Tam, C. E. Moura, J.D.C., Oliveira, T. Varajão, J. (2020) The factors influencing the success of on-going agile software development projects International Journal of Project Management, Vol: 38, pp. 165-178.
478. Tarhini, A., Al-Henzab, J., and Obeidat, B.Y., (2018). The associations among market orientation, technology orientation, entrepreneurial orientation and organizational performance. Benchmarking: An International Journal.
479. Tashakkori, A., & Teddlie, C. (2003). Handbook of mixed methods in social and behavioral research. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
480. Taylor, P.S., Greer, D., Coleman, G., McDaid, K. and Keenan, F., (2008). Preparing small software companies for tailored agile method adoption: Minimally intrusive risk assessment. Software Process: Improvement and Practice, Vol: 13(5), pp. 421-437.
481. Thomas, B., F., (2013). What Pragmatism was 1st ed Pub: Indiana University Press.
482. Thomas, D. (2016) The multicultural mind. Unleashing the hidden force for innovation in your organization Berrett-Koehler Publishers, Oakland.
483. Thomas, J., (2015). Exploring Strategies for Retaining Information Technology Professionals: A Case Study, Doctoral dissertation, Walden University.
484. Thurmond, V.A. (2001). The Point of Triangulation. Journal of Nursing Scholarship, Vol: 33(3), pp. 253-258.
485. Ticehurst, G. W. and Veal, A. J. (2000). Business Research Methods: a managerial approach, Longman, Pearson Education Pty Limited.
486. Tjarve, B. and Zemite, I., (2016). The Role of Cultural Activities in Community Development. Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis, Vol: 64(6), pp. 2151-2160.

487. Tolfo, C., Raul, S., Wazlawick, Marcelo, G. Gomes, Ferreira, F. Antonio F. (2011). Agile methods and organizational culture: reflections about cultural levels, Journal of Software Maintenance and Evolution: Research and Practice, Vol: 23(6), pp. 423-441, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1002/smr.483>.
488. Towey, D., Walker, J. and Ng, R., (2019). Embracing ambiguity. Interactive Technology and Smart Education, Vol: 16(2), pp.143-158.
489. Tyrer, S. and Heyman, B., (2016). Sampling in epidemiological research: issues, hazards and pitfalls. BJPsych bulletin, Vol: 40(2), pp. 57-60.
490. Ugah, J.O. and Ajah, A., (2013). A model of authoring system for e-learning courses. West African Journal of Industrial and Academic Research, Vol: 9(1), pp. 54-69.
491. Uhl, A. and Alexander Gollenia, L., (2016). A Handbook of Business Transformation Management Methodology, Pub: Routledge.
492. Uludağ, Ö., Kleehaus, M., Erçelik, S., Matthes, F. (2019). Using Social Network Analysis to Investigate the Collaboration Between Architects and Agile Teams: A Case Study of a Large-Scale Agile Development Program in a German Consumer Electronics Company. In: Kruchten, P., Fraser, S., Coallier, F. (eds) Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming. XP 2019. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, vol 355. Springer, Cham. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-19034-7_9.
493. University of the West of Scotland, UWS (2021). Research ethics: a handbook of principles and procedures. UWS [Online] Available: uws.ac.uk [Accessed: 25 August 2021].
494. Unterkalmsteiner, M., Abrahamsson, P., Wang, X., Nguyen-Duc, A., Shah, S.Q., Bajwa, S.S., Baltés, G.H., Conboy, K., Cullina, E., Dennehy, D. and Edison, H., (2016). Software startups—a research agenda. e-Informatica Software Engineering Journal Vol: 10(1) pp 89-123.
495. Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F.D., (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. Management science, Vol: 46(2), pp. 186-204.
496. Venters, C.C., Jay, C., Lau, L.M.S., Griffiths, M.K., Holmes, V., Ward, R.R., Austin, J., Dibsedale, C.E. and Xu, J., (2014). Software sustainability: The modern tower of babel. In CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Vol: 1216, pp. 7-12. CEUR.
497. Verma, J., P., (2012) Data Analysis in Management with SPSS Software 1st ed Pub: Springer Science & Business Media: Leandre and Duane, 2012.
498. Verma, S., Jain, V. and Majumdar, A., (2012). Modeling an agile supply chain: Research challenges and future directions. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Soft Computing for Problem Solving (SocProS 2011) (pp. 277-285). Springer, New Delhi.
499. Vicente-Oliva, S., Martínez-Sánchez, Á. and Berges-Muro, L., (2015). Research and development project management best practices and absorptive capacity: Empirical evidence from Spanish firms. International Journal of Project Management, Vol: 33(8), pp. 1704-1716.
500. Vidgen, R., Shaw, S. and Grant, D.B., (2017). Management challenges in creating value from business analytics. European Journal of Operational Research, Vol: 261(2), pp. 626-639.
501. Vinay, V. and Saleeshya, P.G., (2019). Manufacturing system sustainability through lean and agile initiatives. International Journal of Sustainable Engineering, Vol: 12(3), pp. 159-173.
502. Vygotsky LS. (1978). Mind in society. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
503. Waardenburg, V. G. and Vliet, V. H., (2013). When agile meets the enterprise. Information and Software Technology, Vol: 55(12), pp. 2154-2171.
504. Walker, J.L., (2012). Research column. The Use of Saturation in Qualitative Research. Canadian journal of cardiovascular nursing, Vol: 22(2).

505. Wan Ahmad, W.F., Butt, S.M. and Rahim, L., (2013), November. Usability evaluation of the agile software process. In International Visual Informatics Conference (pp. 640-651). Springer, Cham.
506. Wang, X., Hawkins, C. and Berman, E., (2014). Financing Sustainability and Stakeholder Engagement. Urban Affairs Review, Vol: 50(6), pp. 806-834.
507. Warner, M. and Zheng, L., (2013). Business Incentive Adoption in the Recession. Economic Development Quarterly, Vol: 27(2), pp. 90-101.
508. Weill, P. Vitale, M. (2013). Place to space: Migrating to ebusiness models Harvard Business Press, p. 372.
509. Welman, C., Kruger, F., & Mitchell, B. (2005) Research Methodology. New York: Wiley, pp. 45-87.
510. Wigger, K. A., Shepherd, D. A. (2019). We're All in the Same Boat: A Collective Model of Preserving and Accessing Nature-Based Opportunities. Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice, Vol: 302(5652), 104225871983401.
511. Wilkinson, A., Hill, M. and Gollan, P., (2001). The sustainability debate, International Journal of Operations and Production Management, Vol: 21(12), pp. 1492-1502.
512. Wilkinson, S. (1998). Focus groups in health research: exploring the meaning of health and illness. Journal of Health Psychology, Vol: 33, pp. 329-348.
513. Williams, C., (2007). Research methods. Journal of Business & Economic Research, Vol: 5(3), pp.65-72.
514. Williams, L. and Cockburn, A., (2003). Guest Editors' Introduction: Agile Software Development: It's about Feedback and Change. Computer, Vol: 36(6), pp. 39-43.
515. Wilshusen, P. and MacDonald, K., (2017). Fields of green: Corporate sustainability and the production of economic environmental governance. Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space, Vol: 49(8), pp. 1824-1845.
516. Winnall, J.L., (2013). Social sustainability to social benefit: Creating positive outcomes through a social risk-based approach. In Sustainability Integration for Effective Project Management (pp. 95-105). IGI Global.
517. Winter, B., (2015). Agile performance improvement. In Agile Performance Improvement (pp. 149-171). Apress, Berkeley, CA.
518. Wixom, Barbara H. and A. Todd Peter, (2005). A Theoretical Integration of User Satisfaction and Technology Acceptance, Information Systems Research, Vol: 16(1), pp. 85-102.
519. Wry, T. and Zhao, E.Y., (2018). Taking trade-offs seriously: Examining the contextually contingent relationship between social outreach intensity and financial sustainability in global microfinance. Organization Science, Vol: 29(3), pp. 507-528.
520. Yang, X. Sun, S.L. Zhao X. (2018) Search and execution: Examining the entrepreneurial cognitions behind the lean startup model Small Business Economics, pp. 1-13.
521. Yazici, H., (2020). An exploratory analysis of the project management and corporate sustainability capabilities for organizational success. International Journal of Managing Projects in Business, Vol: 13(4), pp. 793-817.
522. Yin, R.K., (2009). Case study research: Design and methods (Vol. 5). Pub: Sage.
523. Yoo, Choi, Lee, (2010). The Impact of Information Technology and Transactive Memory Systems on Knowledge Sharing, Application, and Team Performance: A Field Study. MIS Quarterly, Vol: 34(4), p. 855.

524. Young, D.S. and Casey, E.A., (2019). An examination of the sufficiency of small qualitative samples. Social Work Research, Vol: 43(1), pp. 53-58.
525. Young, R. A., & Collin, A. (2004). Introduction: Constructivism and social constructionism in the career field. Journal of Vocational Behavior, Vol: 64, pp. 373–388.
526. Yusuf, Y., Menhat, M.S., Abubakar, T. and Ogbuke, N.J., (2020). Agile capabilities as necessary conditions for maximising sustainable supply chain performance: An empirical investigation. International Journal of Production Economics, Vol: 222, p. 107501.
527. Yusuf, Y.Y., Musa, A., Dauda, M., El-Berishy, N., Kovvuri, D. and Abubakar, T., (2014). A study of the diffusion of agility and cluster competitiveness in the oil and gas supply chains. International Journal of Production Economics, Vol: 147, pp. 498-513.
528. Yvonne Feilzer, M., (2010). Doing mixed methods research pragmatically: Implications for the rediscovery of pragmatism as a research paradigm. Journal of mixed methods research, Vol: 4(1), pp. 6-16.
529. Yvonne, H. (2014). Software Engineering Team Project 2019-2020: Introduction and Start Up.
530. Zieni, B., Spagnuolo, D., Heckel, R. (2021). Transparency by Default: GDPR Patterns for Agile Development. In: Kö, A., Francesconi, E., Kotsis, G., Tjoa, A.M., Khalil, I. (eds) Electronic Government and the Information Systems Perspective. EGOVIS 2021. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol: 12926. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86611-2_7.
531. Zikmund, W.G., Babin, B.J., Carr, J.C. and Griffin, M., (2013). Business research methods. Cengage Learning
532. Žukauskas, P., Vveinhardt, J. and Andriukaitienė, R., (2018). Philosophy and paradigm of scientific research. Management culture and corporate social responsibility, Vol: 121.

LIST OF APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: PROPOSED FRAMEWORK WITH QUESTIONS

APPENDIX 2: SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Introduction: Introduction: This is Researcher currently pursuing my Doctorate in Business Administration in the University of the West of Scotland. I'm researching on the Impacts of Agile transformation on sustainability of Indian IT startups, mainly focusing on the need for Agile in today's dynamic environment. 70% startup failure rate and IT startup sector with 63% failure has been the driving motive for this research aiming to refocus Agile more than just a methodology and diffuse it into the working culture and entrepreneurial mindset. Collecting your views and opinions as a startup founder or manager can contribute immensely to this research and also share knowledge with young startup society. You will be given a consent form and Participant Information Sheet for further enquiries about the research and its validity.

Contact Details Required

Name: _____

Company Location: _____

Company age: _____

Designation: _____

Questions related to Process Inputs

Q1: What was the motive behind the business idea on which your company was started?

Q2: What is your company's work culture and how does it align with your motives?

Q3: How do you manage to retain your customers and employees?

Questions related to External Inputs

Q4: What are the differentiating factors that has helped you survive and sustain as a startup in the market since your establishment?

Q5: How has the global pandemic challenged your company's performance, strategic thinking and risk mitigation?

Questions related to Management Disciplines

Keeping in mind the process / methodology that you are currently adopting, rate the following characteristics for your startup

Q6: How transparent and collaborative are you with your customers at every stage of the process and does it help you maintain a long term relationship with them?

Q7: How do you satisfy customers through early and continuous delivery of working software / MVPs to get quick feedback and to optimize our resource allocation?

Q8: Do you think continuous monitoring and adjusting the company's strategic direction in alignment with the process is needed to develop innovative ways to create value?

Q9: How do you emphasize on creating a strategically sensitive work environment where everybody feels motivated, appreciated and contributing towards meeting customer requirements?

Q10: How do you maximize the amount of work not done (aligning value-producing resources and people with products and services) by effectively communicating priorities to keep the workflow and final solution more cost-efficient?

Q11: How significant is flexibility for adapting to emerging changes in the process and continuously learn from every project you take over?

Q12: Do you feel these characteristics are necessary for your startup to be sustainable? If so what are the practical challenges in implementing them?

Questions related to Process Inputs and Outputs

Q13: What is your understanding of Agile transformation? Is it necessary for your startup?

Q14: Do you think Agile transformation can impact your sustainability by giving your startup a competitive edge and an organizational agility? If so how?

Please render your valuable suggestions and feedback on the scope of this research for the startup community

APPENDIX 3: FOCUS GROUP QUESTIONS

Introduction: This is Researcher currently pursuing my Doctorate in Business Administration in the University of the west of Scotland. I'm researching on the Impacts of Agile transformation on sustainability of Indian IT startups, mainly focusing on 63% failure has been the driving motive for this research aiming to refocus Agile more than just a methodology and diffuse it into the working culture and entrepreneurial mindset. Collecting your views and opinions as a startup founder or manager can contribute immensely to this research and also share knowledge with young startup society.

Q1: What are the key sustainability factors that affect Indian IT startups? How has the pandemic challenged business sustainability and growth operations?

Q2: What have been the key drawback or failures of waterfall, parallel, V model and spiral (traditional methods) to support sustainability of Indian IT startups?

Q3: What is your understanding of agile transformation? How is Agile in practice within the context of Indian IT startups in contrast with Agile in theory?

Q4: What does it mean to have an agile mindset, culture and stakeholder collaboration as part of implementation methods and how significant is it for a successful agile transformation?

Q5: Can Agile increase visibility with customers and optimize resource allocation and thereby impact sustainability through effective risk agility?

Q6: Can Agile enhance strategic alignment with vision and mission and motivate the workforce to strategically perform better and thereby impact sustainability through strategic agility?

Q7: Can agile improve communication of priorities within a project and enrich flexibility through continuous learning and thereby impact sustainability through operational agility?

Q8: If a startup works on these aspects, can it have better chances at sustainability? If so, how do you draw a conclusion?

APPENDIX 4: ACADEMIC LITERATURE FINDINGS TABLE

Year	Author	Research Topic	Potential Outcome/Benefits	Limitations	Type
2012	Sven, O. and Sebastian, S.	How sustainable are Agile methodologies? Acceptance factors and developer perceptions in Scrum Projects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Use of agile methodologies beyond the adoption stage 2) Methodological triangulation to validate the results (quantitative and qualitative methods) 3) Scrum brings relative advantages and is more compatible with the way developers prefer to work, developers perceived the complexity of Scrum to be higher than that of traditional methodologies 4) Defines aspects of complexities in sustainability to ensure that developers remain committed and actively support agile principles 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) While the presented findings outline a framework of concrete factors, they are just an initial step that ought to be re-evaluated in other contexts 2) Other agile methodologies have not been compared to abstract the discussion of acceptance factors to a more general concept of agility 3) Strategies not developed to overcome identified causes of threats to the acceptance of agile methodologies 4) The distinct factors of acceptance of agile methodologies have not been quantified 	III
2012	Mali, S. and Ananth, S.	Understanding post-adoptive agile usage: An exploratory cross-case analysis	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Agile innovation factors (relative advantage, compatibility) 2) Sociological factors (experience level, Knowledge/expertise) 3) Technological factors (agile practices, tool support) 4) Team factors (team management, team leadership) 5) Organizational factors (top management support, method champion) influenced effective postadoption usage of agile practices 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Relationship between agile usage and agile effectiveness i.e., usage as a factor affecting effectiveness, has been omitted 2) Implementational guidelines have not been specified 	II
2013	Jeff, S. and Matt, R.	The Agile Start-Up: Quick and Dirty Lessons Every Entrepreneur Should Know	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 170 Step by step lessons for creating a startup that is agile 2) Targeted for entrepreneurs to provide core concepts and benefits of Agile 3) Reducing risk makes the organization agile and sustainable 4) Team building as a significant factor for agile teams 5) Getting business model right to avoid early scaling 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of academic references to back up few claims 2) Sustainability factor is not given much significance 3) Does not follow a framework or a blueprint 	IV
2014	Mario, S.	Mixed Agile/Traditional Project Management Method – Reality or Illusion?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Project management approach and project management method are somehow defined in separate ways 2) Both traditional and agile approaches have their advantages and disadvantages, if compared to different project characteristics 3) It is possible to combine both approaches for the single project and within single method 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The challenge is to define which project characteristics are important for choosing the right method and approach 2) Does not discuss how to build method with method elements based on different approaches 3) Does not define level of details needed from method element to build method 	II
2015	Georgios, P.	Moving from Traditional to Agile Software Development Methodologies Also on Large, Distributed Projects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Adopting the agile framework on large, distributed projects improves quality, allows for requirement changes and additions throughout the project and improves employee satisfaction while building the end product 2) Comparative case study to validate specific agile features on both agile and traditional teams 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Failure to provide action plan for transition from traditional to agile 2) Challenges of adopting Agile on projects not defined 3) Combating the time to adopt agile culture and embracing agile practice 	I
2015	Pedro, S. and Jeffrey, K., P.,	Does Agile work? — A quantitative analysis of agile project success	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Comprehensive and large-scale empirical analysis to explore efficacy of Agile projects 2) Linkage to efficiency, stakeholder satisfaction and performance for Agile method 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Regression analysis used to calculate efficacy 2) High dependency on surveys with participant errors 	II

			3) Quality of strategic vision as direct variable for sustainability	3) No unambiguous evidence of significance and relevance of relationships	
2015	Nomi, B.	Requirement Management in Agile Software Environment	1) Quality requirement management practices 2) Change is a requirement as a prominent factor for determining Agile method over others	1) No empirical evidence 2) Lacking industrial implementational guidance 3) Solely Academic and not for practitioner	I
2016	Xiaofeng, W., Henry, E. Sohaib, S. B. Carmine, G. and Pekka A.	Key Challenges in Software Startups Across Life Cycle Stages	1) Software engineering challenges are building software products, defining minimum viable product and building entrepreneurial team, while considering contextual factors, e.g., the product development stages and learning stages. 2) Misalignment of learning and product development stages and startup failure	1) Findings are not consistent with the generally innovative nature of software startups who are often chasing new technological changes and disrupting the software industry 2) The challenges were obtained through searching various online entrepreneurship forums and so need scientific evidence to support their validity	III
2016	Ilka, W.	Business experimentation for sustainability	1) Radical innovation led to sustainability 2) Relationship between sustainability and Strategy, Risk and Performance metrics 3) Collection of sustainable theories and combining academic and practitioner frameworks	1) Limited clarity of the research problem where the gap is between current speed and urgency of sustainability 2) Lack of peer reviewed knowledge 3) Transformational learning was not achieved while doing research and therefore prescriptive but with no practical experience	IV
2016	Yngve, L., Dag I., K., S., Torgeir, D., Gunnar, R., B. and Tore, D.	Teamwork quality and project success in software development: A survey of agile development teams	1) Quality of teamwork is a major factor in improving performance 2) Strong relationship between teamwork and team performance 3) Communication, coordination, balance of member contribution, mutual support, effort, and cohesion identified as factors affecting performance further benefiting work satisfaction and learning	1) Team performance is defined in terms of both product quality and project quality which are often negatively related in a trade-off function 2) Refinement and simplification of some of the constructs in the survey needed 3) TWQ have a dubious linear relation to project quality and, thus, team performance	II
2016	Oktay, T., Igor, S. and Jos, J., M., T.	Assessing the adoption level of scaled agile development: a maturity model for Scaled Agile Framework	1) Proposes a maturity model that can be used as a guideline by organizations to adopt SAFe and assess the success level of SAFe adoption 2) Prioritizes the improvement actions in adopting agile and SAFe practices 3) SAFe Maturity Model framework provides a structured approach to assess how well agile companies perform and their maturity	1) Limited participants to validate maturity model in the case company 2) Lower external validity of the empirical study and cannot be generalized 3) Assessment of utility, completeness, and validity of the maturity model needs to be quantified	IV
2016	Kim, D., Maria, P. and Casper, L.	Challenges and success factors for large-scale agile transformations: A systematic literature review	1) Presents a systematic literature review of empirical studies and experience reports on large-scale agile transformations 2) Choosing and customizing the agile approach, management support, mindset and alignment, and training and coaching as salient factors affecting agile transformation	1) Few papers linking agile and transformation to support literature 2) Results would be distorted heavily, and many valuable studies would be left out if a strict quality assessment were part of the inclusion criteria 3) Many primary studies were openly pro-agile, without giving a solid motivation for the standpoint	III
2016	Sania, N., V., Della S. and Matteo, M., S.	Extensive Literature Review to Investigate the Dimensions of Business Sustainability	1) Business sustainability factors identified as 1) economical, 2) social, and 3) environmental feature 2) To obtain sustainability, business still needs an answer to the question that why they need to	1) Ethical perspective, time factor and culture are limited factors and there are furthermore 2) Integration among the systems and dimensions are also important to get the benefits of sustainability	II

			incur some cost to become sustainable	3) Investigation of sustainability knowledge and practices in corporate world needed	
2017	Micic, L.	Agile method selection criteria: IT start-up case study	1) More companies recognize SCRUM's quality and usefulness in the application 2) Introduction of agile methodologies does not guarantee the success of the process and work of the organization itself	1) Elements of management, organization, management of human resources and technical quality of work are overlooked 2) Limited to only one case study and therefore no generalization of findings	I
2017	Santiago, O. and Emre, E.	Agile Transition in Software Development Companies: The Most Common Barriers and How to Overcome Them	1) Agile methods put more emphasis on people, interaction, working software, customer collaboration, and change, rather than on procedures, tools, contracts, and plans. 2) Selection of the project approach depends on each software development company and their organizational characteristics 3) Explores means to overcome all the barriers that companies have to deal with to become an Agile organization 4) Supplies the motivation and rationale for a new Agile framework to be developed	1) National culture may be a relevant characteristic as changing to different methodologies may come across different barriers within cultural settings 2) Organization size has been neglected as a factor while considering overcoming transition barriers 3) Based on the assumption that project managers and software developers are not misled with Agile	I
2017	Santisteban, J. and David, M.	Systematic Literature Review of Critical Success Factors of Information Technology Startups	1) Startups at their early stages of development demand proper management rather than profitability 2) Lack of effective strategic plan for innovation can doom startups 3) Government policies and financing can largely impact startups	1) No real agreement in literature about success factors 2) Organization, individual and external dimensions of factors does not clarify 3) Only few reliable factors to Indian IT Startups	II
2018	Marcio, A. D. L.	Sustainability-inspired business startups (SiBS): An exploratory study of early-stage UK companies from the creative industry	1) Startups process: Idea, Plan and execution, team, growth, timing, avoiding liquidation, contributing to the society 2) Startup drivers towards sustainability also depend on agile leadership 3) Business Model canvas can aid design thinking and business model innovation 4) Market and customer segment, customer and supplier relationship, human resources, product design, R&D innovation, and strategy for next 5 years as factors for sustainability	1) The research is indicative and exploratory, not representative 2) Limited number of business startups investigated 3) Data limited to British startups 4) Sector addressed are unrelated to Information Technology systems	III
2018	Eriks K. Michael U. Tony G.	Software engineering in start-up companies: An analysis of 88 experienced reports	Inadequacies in engineering requirements hinder other engineering activities and might lead to unwanted technical debt, poor product quality, and wasted resources on building irrelevant features 1) Software design knowledge must support the fast evolution of product prototypes, used to gather customer requirements, to a robust solution for easy maintenance	1) Minimum details on how start-ups manage software maintenance 2) Risks in supporting software are related to creating technical debt and shorter time to market	III
2018	Philipp, H., Jil, K. Arie, v., B., RyanL., JamesG.J	Back to the future: origins and directions of the "Agile Manifesto" – views of the originators	1) Survey and an interview study in collaboration with the original contributors of the manifesto for agile software development. 2) Focuses on the origins of the manifesto, the contributors' views	1) No guidelines for overcoming Agile misconceptions 2) No framework developed to address the issue of Agile mindset 3) No industrial references so therefore more academic rather	I

	ürgeM MichaelS , Kurt, S.		<p>from today’s perspective, and their outlook on future directions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3) Trending Agile misconceptions & commercialization discussed 4) Agile not a silver bullet but because of careful consideration of management requirement 		
2018	Gerard, W., SietseO. Garm L. Sjaak B. & Kurt, S.	Working software over comprehensive documentation – Rationales of agile teams for artefacts usage	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Adoption of Agile Software Development leads to agile artifacts 2) Team-internal communication leads to functional and technical design artefacts 3) Quality assurance leads to test-related artefacts 4) Agile teams impose governance on their own activities 5) External influences impose user-related material 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Exploratory multiple case study 2) Exclusion of pre-development artefacts, especially the ones which are associated with requirements in one or another format 	II
2018	Lappi, T., Karvone n, T., Lucy, E., L., Kirsi,A. Pasi, K.	Toward an improved Understanding of Agile project governance: A systematic literature review	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 6 dimensional frameworks that prioritize project governance in Agile teams 2) Lack of project governance can affect agile project performance 3) Structured literature review including recent conference papers 4) Goal setting, Appraisals, monitoring, coordination, decision making, capability building as factors affecting project governance 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No empirical evidence 2) Limited resources available on Agile transformation and research bias 3) Limited to Information and Software development context 	III
2018	Abdullah , M. A.	A review on the critical success factors of Agile software development: An empirical study	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Critical success factors for any Agile management: Delivery strategy, team capability and training, top management support, agile software development techniques, customer involvement, project management approach, organizational culture, and communication 2) Investigates the relationship between progress of the agile project and the importance of the success factor 3) Validating evaluation techniques for success of agile management 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Survey of 131 responses for data collection of CSF of Agile development 2) Use of Likert scale to analyze survey data 3) Use of cross sectional rather than longitudinal strategy 4) Only addressed to Saudi Arabia 	IV
2018	Julio, C. P. Rosaria, de F. S. M. R.	Design Thinking Integrated in Agile software development: A systematic literature review	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Agile enable software delivery, manages priorities changes, and increases productivity 2) Design thinking approach enhances customer need understanding: Empathy, definition, and fast prototyping 3) Scrum is the best ASD framework for improving quality and usability 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Mostly academic and therefore disconnect with practitioners 2) No empirical evidence 3) No implementational guidance 4) Neglects team size and challenges in terms of startups and sustainability 	I
2018	Antonio, G. and Angelo, C.	Agile Business Model Innovation in Digital Entrepreneurship: Lean Startup Approaches	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Main dimensions for considering Agile startups: Value capture, Value delivery, value creation, experimenting and Testing, Operational Agility and entrepreneurship and innovation culture 2) Lean and Agile principles combined can help high flexibility and agility in the organization 3) Co-relation between Agility and strategy 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Only targets digital startups at their first stages thereby neglecting sustainability 2) The unified framework of Business model innovation, Lean Scales Agile and Agile development are based on theoretical foundations and there is a disconnect with practitioners 	I
2018	Esubale w, W. T.	Software Development Methodologies and Practices in Startups	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Agile and lean startup methodologies as predominantly used method frameworks 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Validity threats are one of the major factors that influence the accuracy of research negatively. 	IV

		- Systematic Literature Review	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2) Startups do not strictly follow method principles, due to limited resource and time pressure 3) Software development methodologies in startups are informal, tailored and noticeably light 4) Existing literature on engineering practices in startups is not transferable to practitioners 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2) More empirical studies are needed to strengthen the results of this study 3) It is needed to evaluate the effectiveness and suitability of each development method and practice for different software startup situations 	
2019	Linda, H	Designing sustainably agile and resilient organizations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Rigid, bureaucratic, cultural practices and routines, inflexible, complicated governance can be barriers for complete and true agility 2) Learning and experimenting impact sustainability 3) Mindset is the biggest barrier 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Does not mention the motivation and the right time to scale up 2) Does not propose a framework that links agile concepts to sustainability 3) There exists a strategic implementational gap 	I
2019	Sabrina, K.	The Indian startup ecosystem: drivers, challengers, and pillars of support	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Discusses scope and characteristics of the Indian market, technology change, open innovation 2) Building and scaling, diversity and digital divide market orientation team skills identified as challenges for start ups 3) Indian start up ecosystem does not exist in silos, but are part of the broader economy 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The challenges are subject to change given the cultural challenges and negative stereotypes 2) More descriptive rather prescriptive although addressing industrial challenge 	III
2019	Woogon, S. and Seok-Won, L.	An agile approach for managing requirements change to improve learning and adaptability	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Agile development has to accommodate continuous change, organize requirements better and efficiently accommodate changes 2) Existing Agile RE approaches could be suboptimal 3) Addresses Academic, Analysts, agile and lean community 4) Customer impact mapping in Kanban board 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Applications in the industry need to be named 2) Effectiveness of other practitioners should be validated 3) The whole process of the production is not revealed 4) More practical examples of the industry can refine proposed methods 	II
2019	Mairon, K.	The Agile Model – Driven Method	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Combines both agile working techniques and development approach of model driven development 2) Case studies were used to confirm findings 3) MIDAS framework supports continuous improvement 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Only applicable to small scale business where problem domain is well structured 2) Model-driven development is not completely agile 3) Scaling is difficult with this model when the focus is on sustainability 4) The role of a mediator is mandatory 	IV
2019	Martin, C, Alon, R.	ING's Agile Transformation – Teaching an elephant to race	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Organic Agile Breaking Silos through the ripple effect 2) ING's attempt towards Agile transformation is open, more about mindset and less about methods 3) Experimenting and learning rather than repeating procedures 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) There is a risk of replacing one set of processes with another 2) Does not mention transformation in each segment of management rather on the whole 3) Over structuring of agile can create new agile challenges 	II
2019	Martijn, R. Sabine, S., Peter, S.	Organizational Agility and Value creation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Linking Organizational agility to value creation through Value Driven Framework 2) Benefits of transforming completely to Agile directly aligning to the strategic goals or values 3) Leadership Agility as contributing to Agile mindset 4) Agile Strategic management can ensure sustainability and competitive advantage 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Prescriptive yet academic collection of agility frameworks 2) Lack of clear explanation of the process of transformation and challenges 3) Not a generalized strategy for all functionalities of management 	III
2019	Tom, H.	Application of Organizational Agility to enhance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Value creation depends on costs and customers 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Assumption that customers know what they want 	I

		the predictability of costs and increase the profitability of creating value	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2) The double of uncertainty visualizes the value creation in terms of costs 3) Agility can enhance predictability of costs 4) 1st version of Minimum Viable Product can save time 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2) Customer value is hard to measure and quantify 3) This research uses trial and error algorithm to formulate a framework 	
2019	Fabio, L. O. Masaaki K.	Barriers, practices, methods, and knowledge management tools in startups	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Agile transformation can produce tangible and intangible assets that generate value 2) Knowledge management can aid Agile transformation 3) Lack of open innovation can affect agile sustainability 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Startups cannot yet formulate guidelines when complying with open innovation 2) Limited to only Sao Paulo startups 3) Barriers are only restricted to knowledge management lacks 	I
2019	Victor, K., A.	Strategies for Small Business Sustainability	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 50% failure rate for startups 2) Lack of customer experience and behavior understanding can cost sustainability 3) Linking strategic management to sustainability 4) Outdated conceptual framework of Ward and Dubos (1972) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Accuracy and bias of information collection through surveys 2) Collected within 5 years of study so further investigation can be updated 3) Only 5 interviews from within 1 geographical subdivision 	III
2019	Vinit, P., and Joakim, W.	Why and how to compete through sustainability: a review and outline of trends influencing firm and network-level transformation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Discusses impacts of transformation trends such as digitization, circular economy and servitization that affect sustainability 2) Emerging trends supply opportunities for sustainability 3) Startups have a leading edge in incorporating sustainability measures 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No empirical evidence to confirm literature in industry 2) Diminishes culture as factor towards sustainability 3) Does not supply framework for combating transformation challenges 	I
2020	Dean, A Marc, G	The lean startup Framework: Closing the Academic – Practitioner Divide	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Development of Lean startup framework to close the academic-practitioner gap 2) Finding and prioritizing market opportunities in startups 3) Designing business models 4) Customer development 5) Building the smallest practical product 6) Preserve or pivot with course of action 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lacking implementational guidance for the building blocks 2) Performance metrics of each block undefined 3) Sustainability aspect not addressed 	IV
2020	Diego S. S. Antonio G. Rafael B. de A. Marcelo N. Carla S. C.	Lean Startup, Agile Methodologies and Customer Development for business model innovation: A systematic review and research agenda	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Initial attempt to provide practical guidance based on extant literature 2) After validating the initial MVP and reaching the stage in which the venture has the right product for the market (product-market fit), entrepreneurs should continue to adopt the BML approach 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Quality of resources 2) Limited research 3) No framework to address implementational challenges 	III

APPENDIX 5: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you make your decision, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take your time to read the following information carefully. You may contact us through email for further enquiries and clarity regarding the research and its conduct. Take time to decide whether you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

1. Research Project Title

Impacts of Agile Transformation on Sustainability of Information Technology Startups in India

2. What is the project's purpose?

Information Technology (IT) Start-ups in India on an alarming failure rate of 67% since 2011 emphasizes on securing sustainability. A major shift towards Agile Transformation from traditional methodologies in IT Industry, capitalized client database and projects contributing to India's economy yet depriving sustainability of Start-ups. Literatures concerning significance of Agile in context with India remains limited and therefore, this research attempts to evaluate impacts of Agile Transformation and formulates feasible guidelines for sustainability of start-ups.

3. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because as Agile consultant, Agile coach, Project Manager, Startup C-Executive or person in a similar role, you will have knowledge about Indian IT startups and impacts of Agile transformation towards its sustainability.

4. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be able to keep a copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement on the online consent form. You can still withdraw at any time. You do not have to give a reason.

5. What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to choose between a semi-structured interview that will take 25 minutes' maximum or a focus group which we estimate will take you 15 minutes. Participants willing to take part in the interview must show their willingness through a consent form.

6. *What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?*

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort. Prioritizing health and safety during COVID pandemic, trusted online conferencing applications have been promoted in case of participant's unwillingness to meet face to face.

7. *What are the possible benefits of taking part?*

Whilst there are no immediate benefits participants will have a beneficial impact on literatures of Agile transformation for startups and towards the development of Agile sustainability framework. Results will be shared with participants to inform them about their professional work.

8. *What if something goes wrong?*

If you have any complaints about the project in the first instance you can contact any member of the research team. If you feel your complaint has not been handled to your satisfaction, you can contact the University of the West of Scotland Administration to take your complaint further (see below).

9. *Will my taking part in this research be kept confidential?*

All the information that this research collects about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential. Data collected may be shared in an anonymized form to allow reuse by the research team and other third parties but will not allow any individuals or their institutions to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications.

10. *Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?*

You will not be recorded in any way other than your input to the questionnaire without separate permission being gained from you. If you are taking part in the interview, you will be recorded, still the choice will be given to keep your face anonymous. Voice recording will be mandated when under interview, but data will be kept confidential.

11. *What type of information will be sought from me and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?*

The questionnaire will ask you about your opinions and current practices in relation to Agile transformation and sustainability. Your views and experience are just what the project is interested in exploring.

12. What will happen to the results of the research project?

Results of the research will be published. You and your institution will not be identified in any report or publication. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please ask us to put you on our circulation list.

13. Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This project has been ethically approved and subsequently endorsed by the ethics procedures of University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Research Ethics Committee monitors the application and delivery of the University's Ethics Review Procedure across the University.

If you have considered the data on this sheet and are willing to participate in this research, please proceed to fill in your contact details below and further sign the consent form. This data will be documented individually from all other data.

Name: _____

Contact Details: _____

Thank you for taking part in this research

APPENDIX 6: CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: *IMPACTS OF AGILE TRANSFORMATION ON SUSTAINABILITY OF IT STARTUPS IN INDIA*

Name of Researcher: Adino Shapher John, DBA (UWS)

Please initial
box

- 1. I confirm that I have read the information sheet for the above research I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

- 2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason, without my legal rights being affected. Any information given, will then be deleted when notified.

- 3. I understand that the information collected about me will be used to support other research in the future and may be shared anonymously with other researchers and third parties.

- 4. I agree that the personal data recorded in this research will stay private and confidential and once published it will be deleted.

- 5. (If appropriate) I agree to video/audio recording as part of the semi-structured interview and the means of recording used.

- 6. I agree to take part in the above research.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

APPENDIX 7: SEMI-STRUCTURED RESPONDENT LIST

Respondent	Sex	Designation	Company Location	Company age
Respondent 1	Male	Startup Founder	Chennai, Bangalore	3 Years
Respondent 2	Male	Entrepreneur	Chennai	3 Months
Respondent 3	Male	Startup Co-Founder	Chennai	5 Years
Respondent 4	Female	Entrepreneur	Mumbai	6 Months
Respondent 5	Male	Startup Founder	Hyderabad	5 Years
Respondent 6	Male	Startup Founder	Bangalore	5 Years
Respondent 7	Female	Startup Co-Founder	Chennai	2 Years
Respondent 8	Male	Startup Manager	Chennai	6 Years
Respondent 9	Male	Startup CEO	Bangalore	5 Years
Respondent 10	Male	Entrepreneur	Mumbai	7 Months
Respondent 11	Female	Startup Co-Founder	Chennai	3 Years
Respondent 12	Male	Startup CEO	Chennai	5 Years
Respondent 13	Male	Startup Manager	Chennai	5 Years
Respondent 14	Male	Entrepreneur	Bangalore	1 Year
Respondent 15	Male	Startup Founder	Chennai	7 Years
Respondent 16	Female	Lead Developer	Bangalore	4 Years
Respondent 17	Male	Project Manager	All over India	10 Years
Respondent 18	Male	Startup Founder	Bangalore	2 Years
Respondent 19	Male	Lead Project Manager	All over India	12 Years
Respondent 20	Female	Lead Project Manager	All over India	10+ Years

APPENDIX 8: FOCUS GROUP RESPONDENTS

FOCUS GROUP 1				
Respondent	Sex	Designation	Company Location	Company age
Respondent 1	Male	Business Consultant	All over India	53
Respondent 2	Female	Solution Architect (Developer)	All over India	50+
Respondent 3	Male	Associate consultant	All over India	47
Respondent 4	Female	Project Manager	All over India	3 Years
Respondent 5	Male	Programmer Analyst	All over India	28 Years
Respondent 6	Male	Business Analyst	All over India	50 Years
Respondent 7	Female	Founder and Managing Director	Bangalore	2 Years

FOCUS GROUP 2				
Respondent	Sex	Designation	Company Location	Company age
Respondent 1	Male	Business Analyst	All over India	30
Respondent 2	Female	Agile scrum master	All over India	50+
Respondent 3	Female	Agile consultant	All over India	40+
Respondent 4	Female	Lead Automation Tester	All over India	50+ Years
Respondent 5	Male	Agile scrum master	All over India	24 Years
Respondent 6	Male	Senior agile coach	All over India	50+ Years
Respondent 7	Male	Senior manager	All over India	6 Years